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COOK EAT! EXPLORE, LEARN, ENJOY FROM FOODIES TO FOODIES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In today's interconnected world, Cook Eat! offers an innovative solution for culinary and cultural discovery through a community-driven mobile application. Far beyond being a repository of recipes, Cook Eat! serves as a dynamic bridge connecting people with unfamiliar food items they encounter in markets, local stalls, restaurants, and more. Users can take a picture or describe any unknown food product, and instantly access a wealth of information provided by a global community of food enthusiasts familiar with it. This crowdsourced knowledge is curated and reviewed by food experts, ensuring accurate and culturally rich insights into the origins, uses, and preparation methods of various food items. Cook Eat! fosters an interactive platform where users can share their culinary experiences, offer tips on how to cook or consume different foods, and go deep into the cultural context behind them. The app supports a global exchange of culinary know-how, taking advantage of technological connectivity and the innate human curiosity to explore new culinary frontiers, promoting inclusivity, authenticity, and creativity. This abstract outlines the strategic framework behind Cook Eat!, including its development guided by the Business Model Canvas, SWOT analysis, Porter's Five Forces, and PEST analysis. These tools collectively ensure that Cook Eat! not only addresses the needs of modern consumers eager to explore global foods but also positions itself as a leading resource for understanding and appreciating the diverse world of food.

Keywords: Technology, food, cultural , foodies, community.

INTRODUCTION

In a world in continuous transformation it has been quite impossible to avoid the fusion of cultures, in which everybody finds themselves interconnected through several different ways. This link has growth due to many factors, such as immigration, industrialization, technology development, among other. For instance, between 2000 and 2023, intercontinental emigration has grown significantly due to various factors, including globalization, economic opportunities, political instability, and environmental changes. According to the World Migration Report (WMR) the percentage of international migration has increased from 2.8% in 2000 to 3.6% in 2020. The number of international migrants has increased notably in Asia (from 48.2 million in 1990 to 85.6 million in 2020) and in Europe (from 49.6 million to 86.7 million in the same period). In general, International migrants across the globe amounted to 281 millions in 2020, and the number is destined to increase during the following years (WORLD MIGRATION REPORT, s.f.). Likewise, data collected by the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) has shown that the number of people traveling for tourism has been steadily increased. Tourist arrivals worldwide has rose from 211,716,851 in 2010 to 367,927,907 in 2019. On the other hand, it is not only people moving but also products of all kinds. The FAO (2020) has reported that global agri-food trade has more than doubled since 1995, amounting to \$1.5 trillion in 2018, with emerging and developing countries' exports on the rise and accounting for over one-third of the world's total. About one-third of global agricultural and food exports are traded within a global value chain and cross borders at least twice. The rise of global value chains is driven by income growth, lower trade barriers and technological advancements, which have transformed markets and trade processes, linking farmers to traders and consumers across regions and countries.

Emigration, tourism, global trade and industrialization have significantly impact on the integration of food and culture worldwide. This integration has been manifesting itself in different ways, such as the introduction of diverse food goods in the market, new recipes, the blending of cultural practices, the enrichment of local traditions and the interest of people to explore different food and culture. However, the immense amount of information

available out is not totally accurate or linked properly to the cultural value to truly enhance the culinary experience.

With this in mind, Cook Eat! was conceived as an application that promotes food exploration alongside cultural insights provided by foodies around the world who want to share their knowledge while learning from others. By curating a wealth of information and cultural insights from a global community of food enthusiasts, Cook Eat! aims to fill this gap and provide users with a more enriching and authentic culinary journey. Through collective knowledge sharing and community diversity, this platform serves as a gateway for meaningful connections and cross-cultural knowledge exchange, enriching lives and fostering a more connected world regarding food culture.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Human beings have the willingness to share knowledge, especially regarding their identity and culture. As Rizzo and Herrero (2024) stand, cultural heritage includes traditions that are passed down from generations to generations. Some of these traditions are closely linked to food. Expressing the core of a culture through different traditions leads to create an identity, bringing the past to the present. Using food as an expression of that statement leads create connections, fostering empathy, appreciation and mutual respect. Nowadays many application are available but no one with the aim of let cultures talk through food.

Cook Eat! is looking forward to take the best of human value and cultural heritage in order to promote authenticity, inclusivity and creativity though the exploration of food worldwide by the awakening and creation of a community that shares a same goal.

In order to achieve the correct and objective development of CookEat! As a business idea, various tools were used such as business model canvas, SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) analysis, PEST (political, economic, social and technological) analysis and Porter's 5 forces.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As the first tool used there is the Business Model Canvas (Figure 1, Annexes). This model serves as a strategic tool for developing Cook Eat! by providing a clear and structured framework to outline and align all essential components of the business. It helps identify key partners, resources, and activities necessary for

building the app, while also defining the value propositions towards diverse customer segments. By detailing customer relationships and channels, the canvas guides effective engagement and outreach strategies. Additionally, it highlights the cost structure and revenue streams, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the financial aspects and facilitating decision-making. This view enables Cook Eat! strategically integrating technology with culinary exploration, promoting cultural exchange and community involvement, ultimately driving the app's growth and sustainability.

Figure 2 SWOT Analysis for Cook Eat!

The SWOT analysis (Figure 2), functions as a crucial business tool for Cook Eat! by systematically evaluating the app's internal strengths and weaknesses, alongside external opportunities and threats. By recognizing strengths such as expert reviewed content and cultural authenticity, Cook Eat! can build a solid foundation of trustworthiness within the community network. Addressing weaknesses like the overload of content reviewing helps in consider key operations and managing resources effectively. Identifying opportunities, such as expanding into educational markets enables Cook Eat! to leverage its unique value propositions and drive growth. Understanding threats, including content approval delays, allows the app to develop proactive strategies and actions to mitigate risks. This assessment facilitates strategic planning, ensuring that Cook Eat! can effectively take advantage of its strengths, overcome challenges, and capitalize on market opportunities for sustainable development and user engagement (Benzaghta et al., 2021).

Using Strengths to Maximize Opportunities

- Maximize growing interest in global food goods through the content from the foodies community worldwide reviewed by experts can attract users interested in authentic global recipes with cultural insights.
- Offer a diverse range of recipes alongside cultural aspects allows users to explore and appreciate various culinary traditions, enhancing their culinary knowledge and satisfaction.

Using Strengths to Minimize Threats

- Expert validation ensures the accuracy and reliability of content, reducing the risk of misinformation.
- Active user participation helps maintain fresh and diverse content without just relying on complex technological solutions, ensuring continuous engagement.
- Foster a sense of community and transparency, Cook Eat! can build trust, encouraging users to share data and interact with the app.
- Reenforce the authentic content to reduce the probability of cultural misrepresentation, enhancing the app's credibility and user trust.
- Provide a comprehensive database which allows the app to continue offering valuable content while awaiting new contributions to be reviewed and approved.

Minimizing Weaknesses by Taking Advantage of Opportunities

- Develop partnerships and collaborations can provide financial support or shared resources, balancing the costs of maintaining the app.
- Take advantage of the trend towards global food exploration can motivate both the community and experts to contribute actively, ensuring a steady flow of content and engagement.

Minimizing Weaknesses by Avoiding Threats

- Organize the moderation process by involving multiple experts can help minimize delays, ensuring timely updates and maintaining user engagement.
- Establish clear guidelines and fostering a culture of authenticity can encourage community members to provide accurate information, reducing reliance on experts.

Another crucial step used to assess the potential of the business is the PEST analysis, a strategic business tool used to identify, analyze,

and monitor the external factors that could impact an organization. The acronym stands for Political, Economic, Social, and Technological factors. These factors are examined to understand their influence on the organization and to inform strategic planning and decision-making.

From a *political* standpoint, the situation analyzed is quite uncertain. The rise of nationalist ideas and governments around the world could lead to changes in the laws regulating the trade of food products. This could negatively impact the availability of products on the market, but this is a prediction that cannot be made with certainty.

The *economic* side of the analysis has been assessed as ranging from uncertain to positive. Higher tariffs on imported products and increased energy costs could affect the overall cost of food. However, as shown by the data collected from the 'Our World in Data' portal, there is a very positive global trend regarding the increase in GDP and food availability and Main sectors as agriculture, tourism. HoReCa may contribute to a robust increasing food culture.

Social factors have been labeled as favorable. Living standards, education and healthcare concerns are improving worldwide emphasizing quality of life including food choices and related content, culinary knowledge and experiences. The world is getting increasingly globalized. Everywhere there's people coming from all over the world. Room for cultural exchange. which increases the possibility for culture exchange. Understanding these social dynamics could allow the app to tailor its content, features, and marketing strategies to reach the target audience effectively.

Technological factor has also been labeled as favorable. Technological innovation will foster the trade of more and more products, and the creation of others. The development of artificial intelligence could represent an important opportunity to implement in the app's search system. Its use would make it easier to recognize recipes and food products.

To evaluate the business plan, a tool that plays a key role is the Porter's Five Forces, a framework for analyzing the competitive forces within an industry and understanding its attractiveness in terms of profitability. Developed by Michael E. Porter, it helps businesses identify the strengths and weaknesses in their competitive environment. In recent years, its validity has been questioned due to changing markets, with

the emergence of new forces and tools. According to a 2014 publication, Porter's Five Forces still analyzes many concepts that remain valid in today's market world. the Five Competitive Forces model cannot be considered as outdated. The Five Competitive Forces are still applicable, but it is necessary to know the limitations of the model. Globalization, Deregulation and Digitalization have an impact on the existing forces but they do not develop a new one (Goyal, 2020). The five forces analyzed are:

- 1- Competitive rivalry: this pressure has been assessed as minimal, since no other company is currently interested in providing a similar service.
- 2- Supplier power (or bargaining power of suppliers): minimal, the company is not selling any products, so the only input needed is labor force. The company can choose between many alternatives, so the force is low.
- 3- Buyer power: this force has been assessed as considerable, as the customer can uninstall the app or switch to another service at any time. The countermeasure for this problem is to apply an efficient marketing strategy and make the app's interface accessible and easy to use for everyone.
- 4- Threat of substitution: Considered high due to the risk of other companies with higher means entering the same market with an already expanded customer base. The actions to take to prevent this risk are again building a good app with a strong branding that can build trust in the users.
- 5- Threat of new entry: As well as the precedent, this force is considered considerable. The reason and the countermeasure actions are the same.

CONCLUSIONS

Cook Eat! successfully addresses the gap in tools for identifying and understanding unfamiliar food items by benefit from the power of community engagement and validation from experts in the field. The app offers a platform for users to explore diverse foods, understand their cultural significance, and share their culinary experiences with others through a community network. By integrating modern technology with a user focal design, Cook Eat! enhances global culinary exploration and fosters a deeper appreciation of the world's food cultures.

By taking advantage of technology advance and fostering an active user community,

Cook Eat! not only enhances the user's food knowledge but also strengthens cross cultural connections through food. The app's focus on authentic, expert reviewed content and a community interaction, positions it as a leading resource for those willing to explore and understand the richness of global food culture.

As Cook Eat! continues to evolve, it is poised to become an essential tool for culinary enthusiasts, travelers, and anyone interested in the cultural stories behind the foods they encounter, providing a unique and valuable resource for culinary exploration and cultural exchange. Through the strategic use of development frameworks and a solid community network management system it has resulted in an app idea that not only meets user needs but also positions itself as a leading resource for food and cultural discovery. It is positioned to capitalize on the growing interest in food and cultural exploration by offering a unique blend of expert reviewed content and community involve contributions.

The implementation of various business tools and methodologies provides insights into customer needs, market dynamics, and operational requirements. This ensures that Cook Eat! evolves in alignment with user expectations and market opportunities. The organizational recommendations focus on building a capable team, adopting agile practices, fostering community, forming strategic partnerships, and planning for scalability and risk management.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following aspects were not covered in the study: the appreciation of customers towards an application like Cook Eat!, alongside the market and financial situation. Potential tools for implementation include:

- Customer Development Framework, which enables the systematic understanding and validation of customers' needs, preferences and behaviours.
- Market Research and Analysis, which supports the understanding of the real target market size, trends, competition and user profile.
- Financial Modelling, which enables the forecasting of revenues, costs and financial viability.

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ANNEXES

Figure 1 Business Model Canvas for Cook Eat!

This Business Model Canvas outlines the strategic approach for Cook Eat!, focusing on leveraging technology to facilitate culinary exploration and cultural exchange, and capitalizing on the growing interest in diverse food experiences by creating a solid community.

R-TYPE COLONIES OF CLOSTRIDIUM DIFFICILE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

R-type colonies (resistance colonies) in C. difficile refer to bacteria that have developed resistance to certain antibiotics. In the case of C. difficile, resistance to antibiotics such as metronidazole, vancomycin, and fluoroquinolones has become an increasing problem in treating infections caused by this bacterium. R-type colonies can survive and multiply in the presence of these antibiotics, making the treatment of infections more difficult. Clostridium difficile (C. difficile) is a gram-positive anaerobic bacterium that can cause intestinal infections, including severe diarrhea and inflammation of the colon. This bacterium can exist in two main forms: the vegetative form and the spore form. When environmental conditions become unfavorable (for example, in the presence of antibiotics or in an environment that does not allow the survival of the bacterium), C. difficile can form spores to survive. Treatment of C. difficile infections can be challenging, and antibiotic resistance can exacerbate the situation. It is important for physicians to carefully monitor the evolution of antibiotic resistance and to try to limit the use of antibiotics responsibly to minimize the risk of selecting R-type colonies and to improve treatment effectiveness. Additionally, new therapeutic strategies are being developed to address this issue, such as microbiome therapies and monoclonal antibody therapies

Keywords: colonies, antibiotics, spore

INTRODUCTION

Clostridium difficile is a Gram-positive anaerobic bacterium, which can cause severe intestinal infections in humans. It is one of the most common causes of nosocomial infections, meaning infections acquired during hospitalization. C. difficile is naturally found in the surrounding environment, but it can become problematic when it overgrows in a person's large intestine.

The main cause of C. difficile infection is the use of antibiotics. When antibiotics destroy the normal intestinal flora, C. difficile can proliferate and cause infection. C. difficile bacteria produce toxins that cause inflammation in the colon, leading to severe diarrhea, abdominal pain, and other symptoms.

Infections with C. difficile range from mild forms of diarrhea to severe infections that can be life-threatening. Individuals at increased risk of C. difficile infections include those who are elderly, have chronic medical conditions, are hospitalized, or have recently been treated with antibiotics.

The diagnosis of C. difficile infection usually involves testing the stool for the presence of toxins produced by the bacterium. Treatment often involves the administration of specific antibiotics such as metronidazole, vancomycin, or fidaxomicin. In some severe cases, surgical intervention may be necessary.

Preventing C. difficile infections involves the judicious use of antibiotics, adherence to

hygiene measures such as frequent handwashing, and implementation of infection control practices in healthcare facilities to prevent the spread of the bacterium.

Clostridium difficile can develop on a variety of culture media, and one of the most common media used is blood agar, which is a general bacterial culture medium. This medium contains suitable nutrients for the growth of C. difficile and often includes additives such as oxid supplements, which promote the growth of this bacterium.

Additionally, a specific culture medium called selective agar for C. difficile can be used for the isolation and identification of this bacterium in clinical samples. This culture medium contains chemicals that inhibit other bacteria and allow preferential growth of C. difficile.

Under the microscope, Clostridium difficile is a Gram-positive bacterium, meaning it will appear violet in Gram staining. It has a characteristic rod shape and forms stress-resistant spores, which can be observed within the bacterial cells. Spores are sometimes responsible for the bacterium's increased resistance to standard treatments such as antibiotics and may play a role in the spread of C. difficile infections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the

study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

Materials required for the examination:

- A collection container (a collection container with a spoon) with transport medium
- Wooden spatulas
- Latex gloves

For a stool culture, a fecal sample of 5-10g should be collected and placed in the collection container with a transport medium. If the stool is liquid, 5ml should be collected. It is recommended to choose a liquid, mucous, or bloody portion, if available. Do not collect quantities greater than 10g, as they may reduce the chances of isolating pathogenic bacteria.

Isolation of aerobic bacteria. • The sample is inoculated onto two culture media, one weakly selective (MacConkey) and one moderately selective (Hektoen), and incubated for 24 hours at 35-37°C. The cultures are observed at 24 and 48 hours for the appearance of characteristic colonies. For the genus *Vibrio*, the recommended selective medium is BSA (bile salts agar), and for yeasts, Sabouraud medium with Chloramphenicol is used. • To increase the chances of isolation, the sample is subcultured on enrichment media that promote the multiplication of pathogens (selenite sodium acid broth for *Salmonella* spp., alkaline peptone water or broth with taurocholate and peptone at pH 8.0-9.0 for *Vibrio*, from which after incubation, smears and cultures can be performed from the upper part of the medium). Incubation is done for 24 hours at 35-37°C, followed by transfers to culture media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The susceptibility to *C. difficile* infection is conditioned by the imbalance of the intestinal microflora, leading to "gaps" in the microbiome composition. The impact of *C. difficile* varies according to age. Although over 50% of infants are colonized with *C. difficile*, infection is rarely encountered at this age. The majority of symptomatic infections occur after the age of 65, especially in patients with surgical interventions, oncological diseases, and chronic kidney disease.

The risk of community-acquired *C. difficile* infections is elevated in young individuals, women caring for infants, individuals taking proton pump inhibitors or

broad-spectrum antibiotics, and those living near farms or involved in animal husbandry. Laboratory diagnosis is recommended solely for cases with identifiable risk factors and meeting clinical criteria, ruling out medication-induced diarrhea or alternative causes of diarrheal illness.

Testing for *Clostridium difficile* is not recommended for formed stools, except in cases of paralytic ileus. The recommended methods for diagnosing *C. difficile* infection include toxigenic culture, cell cytotoxicity neutralization assay, enzyme immunoassays for toxins A and B, and glutamate dehydrogenase, as well as nucleic acid amplification tests.

Anaerobic culture is performed on selective media such as cycloserine-cefoxitin-fructose agar, following prior decontamination of the stool sample through heat or alcohol treatment. After incubating for several days at temperatures of 20-25°C, yellow, flat colonies with irregular edges and a matte appearance grow. Sensitivity of culture can increase up to 100% through the use of ChromoID medium, enriched with sodium taurocholate, egg yolk, trypticase-soy, and sheep blood.

From the fecal suspension, direct inoculations were performed on two selective media.

Phenylethyl alcohol agar, preferably supplemented with 5% defibrinated sheep blood, which allows for the growth of clostridia and other gram-positive anaerobes present in intestinal contents.

Agar with egg yolk, fructose, and antibiotics (cefoxitin and D-cycloserine). This medium, with high selective capabilities, inhibits other clostridia and gram-positive anaerobic cocci but does not inhibit *C. difficile*. Both media were anaerobically incubated for 48 hours at 37°C.

From a colony morphology standpoint, *C. difficile* appears typical when examined under an optical microscope. Definitive identification is best achieved through gas liquid chromatography. While culture is highly sensitive, when used alone without toxin testing, it leads to low specificity and misdiagnosis in asymptomatic cases. Detection of toxin through tissue culture cytotoxin assay followed by neutralization with specific antiserum is often considered the standard. However, this approach lacks sensitivity and has only detected up to 25% of patients. Various enzyme immunoassay (EIA) tests have been introduced by different manufacturers for the detection of toxin A alone or both toxin A and B. Some of these

are designed to yield results in less than 60 minutes. Comparative studies of immunoassay kits have reported slightly lower sensitivity and specificity compared to cytotoxin assays. Isolates regarding *C. difficile* for toxin production, colonies isolated on selective media are tested for toxin production in vitro either through a cytotoxicity test or through direct enzyme immunoassays. It has higher sensitivity than the cytotoxicity test and equivalent specificity. In routine laboratory, detection of culture and toxins should be performed on each sample, and in cases of toxigenic-positive and fecal culture, toxigenic cultures should be performed on isolated colonies.

The study on "Detection of *Clostridium difficile* and toxins in ground beef and beef cube samples in modified atmosphere" highlights the prevalence of *Clostridium difficile* in ground beef packaged samples (MAP) (n: 50) and beef samples (n: 50); Toxin production was determined from isolates, and sensitivity to antibiotics, metronidazole, vancomycin, and clindamycin was detected. *C. difficile* was isolated in 4% of 50 ground beef samples and 2% of 50 beef cube samples.

All three isolates were confirmed by PCR to be *C. difficile* by detecting the gene. Three out of the five *C. difficile* isolates exhibited toxigenic characteristics, two of them carrying the toxin gene type B (tcdB), and one carrying the toxin gene type A (tcdA). When the antibiotic resistance profile was analyzed phenotypically, only *C. difficile* type A (tcdA) was resistant to clindamycin. All isolates were sensitive to vancomycin and metronidazole. The result of this study demonstrated that the strains of *C. difficile* detected in modified atmosphere packaged (MAP) beef samples could be a potential public health concern.

In the study "Comparison of the API ZYM system with the API AN-Ident, API 20A, Minitek Anaerobe II, and RapID-ANA systems for the identification of *Clostridium difficile*," the API ZYM system was compared with four anaerobe identification systems for the definitive identification of *Clostridium difficile* using 88 cultures of *C. difficile* grown on Mueller-Hinton blood agar medium. The API ZYM system provided a distinct and consistent enzymatic profile for all test strains, while the sensitivities of the other systems in identifying *C. difficile* ranged from 78 to 96% (AN-Ident, 77.9%; RapID-ANA, 88.6%; Minitek Anaerobe II, 90.9%; and API 20A, 95.5%). The API ZYM system is highly reliable in identifying *C. difficile*

accurately, it is rapid, and relatively simple to use.

Fig. 1. Colonii de tip R pe mediul geloză - sânge, *C. Difficile*

Fig. 2. *C. Difficile*, colonii de tip R, mediul geloză - sânge

Fig. 3. Bacili Gram - pozitivi, *C. Difficile*

CONCLUSIONS

On selective media with cycloserine-cefoxitin-fructose agar, yellow, flat colonies with irregular margins and a matte appearance grew.

By using the ChromID medium, agar enriched with sodium taurocholate, egg yolk, trypticase-soy, and sheep blood, the culture sensitivity increased to 100%.

Definitive identification is best achieved through gas liquid chromatography.

Colonies isolated on selective media are tested for toxin production in vitro either through a cytotoxicity test or through direct enzyme immunoassays.

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GERMINATION OF SOME TOMATO VARIETIES ON MINERAL WOOL SUBSTRATE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Tomatoes are vegetables from the Solanaceae family, which are grown for their fruit, both fresh and for various processed products.

Recently, in Europe, there is a growing tendency for soilless or artificial soil grown vegetables.

The best performing rooting layers for this type of culture are: mineral wool, perlite and organic substrates consisting of peat and coconut fiber (VanOs et.al., 1999).

The study on the germination and replanting of cherry tomatoes, with mineral wool and vermiculite as substrate, was carried out in a vegetable farm in Tileagd, in 4 variants, with professional seeds.

Keywords: tomatoes; germination; growth LEDs; mineral wool;

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INTRODUCTION

Tomatoes are native to Central and South America. According to Jenkins, 1948, cited by Indrea et al., 2009, the center of origin of tomatoes is in the vicinity of Vera Cruz and Pueblo, being reported as ornamental plants since 1498 by Christopher Columbus.

Tomato fruits contain 5.5-7.5% fat, represented by carbohydrates 3-4%, proteins 1-1.3%, organic acids 0.3-0.5%. They are known by their high content of vitamins: carotene (0.8mg), B1, B2, B6 (0.1mg), C(15-30mg), K (24mg) and mineral salts: potassium (280mg), phosphorus (24-40mg), magnesium (20mg), calcium (20mg), iron (2.3mg); the values being referred to 100g of fresh product. (Apahidean, 2020).

The tomato seeds have the silver color from hairs, they are oval-rounded, and have a germination capacity of 85-90%, and can be kept for 5-6 years.

At the optimal temperature of 24°C, the germination of tomato seeds takes place in 5-7 days, and for the growth and development of the tomato root system, the optimal temperatures are between 15 - 35°C.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Research on the germination of some tomato varieties on a substrate made of

mineral wool and vermiculite was carried out in 2024 in Tileagd city, in Bihor county, in a vegetable microfarm.

The experience is monofactorial with 4 variants. The biological material was represented by 4 tomato varieties: Tudor F1 (V1), which is also the witness of the experiment, Paskualetto F1 (V2); Chery F1 (V3); Landolino F1 (V4), whose seeds were professional.

The Paskualetto F1 variety is a cherry tomato hybrid with indeterminate growth, balanced vegetatively-generatively, with a short distance between internodes and good vigor, recommended for all crop cycles in protected areas, with an average fruit weight of 15-18g and a diameter between 27-32 mm.

The Cherye F1 variety is a cherry tomato hybrid with indeterminate growth, with short internode spacing, recommended for all crop cycles in protected areas. It produces on average about 12 fruits/cluster, having very good taste and good uniformity. The variety also tolerates low temperatures very well.

The Landolino F1 variety is a plum cherry tomato hybrid, with indeterminate growth, with continuous binding and under stress conditions, recommended for all crop cycles in protected areas. The fruits weigh on average 30g, they are uniform, deep red in color.

On 05.03.2024, 100 seeds for each variety were sown in cylindrical plugs of

2.7x2.0cm mineral wool and vermiculite, placed in pallets with alveoli.

Figure 1. Pallets with alveoli

The substrate was immersed whenever needed in water with NPK 10-45-10 and microelements with an EC of 1.5, and the temperature until sunrise was maintained at 26°C.

Figure 2. Growth LEDs

Growth LEDs were used, the lights were switched on on 03/07/2024 at around 15:00, and from this moment they went on continuously until 03/10/2024 when the percentage of emergence exceeded 90% for each variant.

From 10.03.2024 the bulbs were switched on from 8 am and were left on overnight only if it was cloudy, so as to ensure constant light for 14-15 hours a day, and the temperature dropped to 20° c.

On 21.03.2024, the tomatoes were transplanted into 10x10x2.7cm mineral wool cubes.

Figure 3. Mineral wool cubes

Figure 4. Transplanted tomatoes

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To achieve the proposed objectives, the early and total germination of cherry tomatoes were analyzed for the experimental crop.

Figure 5. Germination of tomatoes

Regarding the first analyzed parameter, the data related to the early germination of cherry tomatoes obtained in the 4 varieties are presented in table 1.

Table 1

Early germination of varieties
08.03.2024

Cr. no.	Variety	Absolute germination buc.	Relative germination %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	Tudor F1 (Mt)	20	100	0,00	-
2	Paskualetto F1	12	60	-8	000
3	Cherye F1	69	345	+49	xxx
4	Landolino F1	23	115	+3	x

Even though the witness is an early variety, it did not excel in terms of germination earliness.

The highest early germination was recorded in the Cherye F1 variety with an increase of 345%, the difference compared to the control was ensured statistically, positively, very significant.

The Paskualetto F1 variety stood out with a poor earliness, achieving an early germination of 22.83% of the witness's germination, the difference from it was statistically assured, negative, very significant.

Table 2

**Total germination of varieties
10.03.2024**

Cr. no.	Variety	Absolute germination buc.	Relative germination %	± d kg/m ²	Significance
1	Tudor F1 (Mt)	83	100	0,00	-
2	Paskualetto F1	94	113,25	+11	xx
3	Cherye F1	96	115,66	+13	xxx
4	Landolino F1	98	118,07	+15	xxx

All varieties obtained good germination, statistically positively ensured compared to the Control.

Figure 6. Total germination of varieties

It can be seen that the seeds of Landolino F1 (118.07% of the germination of the control) and Cherye F1 (115.66% of the germination of the control) varieties germinated best, the difference compared

to the control being statistically ensured, positively, very significant.

The variety Paskualetto F1 recorded a total germination, statistically assured positive compared to the Control with 13.25%.

Figure 7. The variety Paskualetto F1

CONCLUSIONS

To ensure the germination, growth, development and fruiting of tomatoes, it is very important to know the requirements for light, temperature, water, food, air, as well as the interaction between these factors.

Under optimal conditions of temperature, light, water and food, cherry tomatoes sown in cells with mineral wool and vermiculite started to germinate in 3 days. The studied varieties registered a total twinning over the Control, being statistically positively assured.

The Londolino F1 variety, although it did not have a very good early germination, at

the end it registered a total germination with 118.07% of the germination of the control, being statistically significantly positive.

Regarding the conditions of growth and development of the seedling until transplanting, the Paskualetto F1 variety did the best.

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CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING TOURISTS' SATISFACTION IN AGRO-TOURISM ACCOMMODATION UNITS IN THE NORTH-WEST AREA OF ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

The main problem of Romanian tourism in the next period, including rural tourism, is the quality of the tourist product, viewed mainly from the aspect of tourist services, without which no tourist heritage, no matter how valuable, cannot be effectively exploited.

Raising the quality of the Romanian tourist product, regardless of its concrete form, requires the application of strategies of flexibility, diversification of the types of tourist services and differentiation of the tourist product offered, compared to the offers of competitors.

Thus, some authors see satisfaction as the antecedent of quality, while others consider quality to be the essential determinant of satisfaction. By and large, the most pertinent conclusion seems to be the concept explained by Rust and Oliver (Rust, 2000) who considers satisfaction to be superior to quality - in other words, quality is only one of the potential dimensions of service that influence consumer satisfaction, although, according to the same authors, satisfaction in turn can indirectly strengthen perceptions of service quality.

Keywords: needs, units of accommodation, agritourism, satisfaction tourist

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INTRODUCTION

The future of Romanian tourism at the beginning of the 3rd millennium depends decisively on the ability of economic agents and the space to capitalize on the special potential at our disposal, to adapt to the growing demands of tourist demand and to raise the quality of tourist activity in all aspects, that is, to organize and realize a modern and competitive tourism. At the same time, overcoming shortcomings and the difficulties with which Romanian tourism is currently faced require a coherent and effective national policy. The example of countries that have achieved developed tourism is edifying in this sense.

Considering that the tourist potential at our disposal is superior to that of other countries in Central and Eastern Europe, in the next period it is necessary to reconsider the place and role of tourism, including rural tourism, within our national economy.

Through tourism development guidelines, Romania can transform from a country with a rich and varied tourist potential into a country

with a developed, modern and competitive tourism.

The role of the human factor increases as consumers' demands increase with regard to the quality of services and the participation in the tourist movement of wider and more diverse segments of the population. Through these actions of direct involvement of the population, it is very easy to educate the consumer of tourist products and therefore increase the level of acceptance of the various services and, implicitly, his satisfaction.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Northwest Region of Romania was created based on Law no. 151/1998 (amended by Law no. 315/2004) through the voluntary association of the counties of Bihor, Bistrița-Năsăud, Cluj, Maramureș, Satu-Mare and Sălaj.

The region covers 14% of Romania's territory and ranks fourth nationally in terms of surface area and population.

The North-West region has a strategic geographical position, being the gateway to Romania from the European Union and Ukraine. From a geographical and scientific point of view, it corresponds to the area known as "Northern Transylvania", a name that wants to be promoted as a regional brand for tourism and investment purposes.

Fig. 1. 1. North West Region

The varied natural landscape, full of picturesqueness, has special tourist values, linked to attractive landforms and valuable natural monuments. This rich tourist potential is doubled by favorable conditions for accommodation, rest and balneoclimatic treatment. The range of possibilities is multiple: mountaineering, cultural tourism, practicing summer and winter sports, recreation and rest, youth camps, spa treatment.

The fame of the Apuseni Mountains lies especially in the special plasticity of the landscape that harmoniously combines the gentle lines of the plains with the verticals of the steep slopes. Expansive pastures and volcanic domes, narrow and deep gorges are unique phenomena in Romania and even in Europe (Cheile Turzii and Cheile Turenilor). Grottoes with fantastic shapes of stalactites and stalagmites, harboring special speleological

values are: Peștera Mare, Peștera Piatra Ponorului, Peștera Vîrfuraș and others. Bears, wild boars, deer can be hunted in the mountain forests, and the rapid waters of the mountain streams and dam lakes abound in fish.

According to the aggregate Regional Attractiveness Index (IAR), the Northwest Region is the most attractive of Romania's development regions, after Bucharest-Ilfov, a fact that is due to the labor market and wages, foreign investments, but also the private environment and market competition.

Although in terms of demographic profile or dynamism of the business environment, the North-West Region is out of step with Bucharest-Ilfov and the Centre, respectively the West, we still rank second in the country in terms of social indicators and standard of living (telecommunications, health, education, bank accounts, internet users, spending on holidays and leisure, household endowments, average prices for basic products). Regarding the standard of living and social life, the North-West registers an attractiveness index of 18.3, compared to Bucharest (32.6), followed by the Center (with 15.8).

The region registers the lowest unemployment rate at the national level, below 3.5%, surpassing even Bucharest in terms of job offer. The turnover of private companies is the second highest in the country. This is also where the most bank branches in the country can be found, after the capital (15% of those at the national level, of which 50% are in Cluj).

The endowments of the households place the inhabitants of the region in the first place after the citizens of Bucharest, the population being the most active in terms of spending holidays and recreational activities.

The counties with high tourist potential are Cluj, Maramureș and Bihor, which concentrate over 80% of the number of tourist structures.

In the segment of rural tourism and agrotourism there are 196 rural guesthouses and 53 tourist cabins. The imbalance is manifested here especially between the "mountainous" counties, which concentrate a large part of them, and the rest of the counties. Thus, only Maramureș alone has more than half of the total number of these structures - 118, followed by Cluj with 68 rural

guesthouses. Although rural, the rest of the counties have only 2 or 3 rural guesthouses (2005). Hence the chronic lack of tourist infrastructure in the countryside.

The accommodation infrastructures in the leisure accommodation segment are undersized.

There is not a single holiday village in the region, not a single campsite and not a tourist lodge .

The areas with significant rural tourism are: Beiuşului County, Chioarului County, Lăpuşului County, Maramureşului County, Năsăudului County, Oaşului County and Sylvania County.

The main forms of tourism practiced in the North West region are: tourism handicrafts , tourism spa , tourism mountain , cultural tourism and tourism religious and monachal

There are, in our opinion, ten components that must be taken into account when we refer to meeting the expectations of a tourist. Each of these elements is presented separately for information and the means specific to each one can be assimilated by those who use the manual. The elements we will discuss in detail are:

1. Customer satisfaction and visit cycle stages
2. Design and management of facilities
3. Elaboration of a menu, safety measures and food hygiene
4. Marketing concepts
5. Improvement fiscal performance and financial management
6. Communication during the stages of the visiting cycle
7. Gathering information in the stages of the visiting cycle
8. The sale
9. Customer satisfaction and the environment: communicating the image of the place
10. The tourist package focused on the specific market niche

A customer is satisfied when the product and services offered in all these stages of the tourist experience were of quality and met expectations and his needs. Throughout the tourist experience , the owner or the tourism promoter must take into account the quality of the services offered. (greenagenda.org)

Satisfaction is defined as "The buyer's cognitive state of being adequately or inadequately rewarded for the sacrifices he has made." (Howard, 1969), while the last analyzed definition is from 2011: " Consumer satisfaction

is a complex human process that involves extensive cognitive, affective, psychological and physiological (Sanchez-Gutierrez, 2011) interactions ."

Fig. 1 . 2 . The model of the European index of satisfaction

satisfaction can be described (Giese, 2000):

1. Satisfaction is a global affective response, based on a cognitive evaluation, which varies in intensity - the holistic nature of satisfaction ;
2. The central point of satisfaction is the choice, the purchase and consumption of the product and /or service;
3. The determining moment of satisfaction varies depending on the situation , but its duration is generally limited - the temporary existence of satisfaction .

Therefore , if satisfaction is measured as a global feeling of fulfillment, consumer dissatisfaction is seen as its opposite within the same continuum. It is important to note that while products are consumed, services are experienced, felt. The entrepreneur-provider is (or should be) a manager of customer experiences as adept as they are at executing technical tasks. In short, the customer has a certain perception of service quality, which can lead to the "first law in the field of services":

SATISFACTION=PERCEPTION-EXPECTATION

If a customer perceives the service at a certain level but expects something more (or different), then he will be dissatisfied.

In order to succeed in "amazing" our client, the accommodation must offer exceptional services and quality products. And this is not impossible. There are methods by which we can impose and maintain certain quality standards of our services in order to manage to amaze each and every one of the customers who step on our threshold. If we do not try this, the danger of being quickly " ranked " and put on the list of "places I will never set foot on again" is a very big one. Statistics and conducted studies clearly show us that:

- 1 in 4 customers are dissatisfied with the tourist experience ,
- 96% of those who are dissatisfied never complain on the spot ,
- the average customer relates the unpleasant experience to at least 10 other people they know,
- 67% of customers dissatisfied, they never return to that place. (greenagenda.org)

Statistics also tell us very bluntly that no customer is actually "only" a customer. Neglecting one can actually mean losing 10 potential others customers . In addition, a satisfied customer will return to our accommodation unit spending other money, or recommend our place to other people. And when we reach this stage we begin to reach our financial goals.

satisfaction , the perceived quality of the service, the value of the service, the sacrifices that consumers are going to make and their behavioral intentions are in a close and complex relationship , although it is not always clear what the concept is in the middle. As Cronin argues , Brady and Hult (Cronin, 2000), throughout the period dedicated to the study of satisfaction , quality and value, researches were often developed models that put in the center that concept that was the main objective of the analysis.

Also here, the temporal dimension in defining the relationship between the two concepts, as presented by Lovelock, must be mentioned and Wright (Lovelock, 1999)who define perceived quality as the long-term cognitive evaluation of the service provided by a provider, and consumer satisfaction as a short-term emotional evaluation of a specific service delivery, an argument that emphasizes that satisfaction is reevaluated with each provision of a certain service, and the positive or negative emotional result changes the consumer's perception of quality . In the context of this hypothesis, Oliver (Oliver, 1997)believes that the causal relationship between the perceived quality of the service and consumer satisfaction depends on the level at which the measurement is made:

1. At the level of a single transaction there is a strong relationship : **perceived quality affects satisfaction** ;
2. At the level of several transactions , the relationship is reversed: **satisfaction affects the perceived quality** by the fact that the grade given to the service comes from an overall impression of it

Fig. 1. 3 . Satisfaction in tourism

Improving the quality of tourist services is closely related to an improvement in the management of organizations active in Romanian tourism. This is achievable by applying a service quality management that has among its main concerns the following aspects:

- knowing the expectations of tourists;
- maintenance of buildings and facilities as well as related utilities;
- knowing tourist satisfaction;
- teamwork;
- cooperation with partner organizations;
- promoting a fair motivation of employees.

As a result, managers and employees of tourism companies (carriers, hotels, restaurants, travel agencies, leisure centers) must offer the market only the highest quality services at the lowest rates and prices. In this way, customers can be retained, new customers can be gained, turnover, profit and the market segment held can increase steadily and continuously.

Along with the increase in consumer demands and their selectivity regarding the choice of services, service providers are becoming more and more concerned with maintaining their clientele, through their long-term loyalty . In this sense, organizations direct their efforts towards satisfying the expectations and demands of customers as completely as possible, by identifying and continuously analyzing the wishes and requirements expressed by customers, transforming them into product/service ideas in order to develop and perpetuate sustainable relationships, economically advantageous with the clientele.

When the customer's belief in the company's ability to offer superior quality services turns into repeated purchases, customer loyalty occurs. A loyal customer is a stable source of long-term income for the service company because he recommends the company to other potential customers. However, consumer loyalty is not maintained by itself, it exists as long as the

consumer believes that he receives an additional value embodied in the quality-price ratio - compared to another company that offers similar services.

The approach of achieving the objective of customer loyalty is a particularly complex one and requires, on the part of the company:

- customer loyalty strategy , respectively establishing loyalty methods (for example, personalized service offers, additional services, direct mail, customer clubs, telephone marketing, online orders, etc.);
- building a customer database, which must be continuously updated, from which customer data can be extracted to be used in loyalty measures ;
- carrying out analyzes on customer satisfaction, which involves carrying out surveys on, above all, customer satisfaction, intentions to repeat the purchase, to recommend the service offer to other potential customers;
- the establishment of performance standards, refers to the setting of quality standards for customer satisfaction and the periodic verification of their compliance;
- the analysis of customer purchasing behavior considers the determination and interpretation of some indicators related to the actual and observable behavior, such as: the rate of return for purchase, the intensity of service consumption, the number of migrations to other service providers.

loyalty has positive effects on the cost reduction of the service provider. On this line is recorded:

- reducing costs related to customer relations, by focusing actions, mainly on loyal customers;
- reducing "non-quality" costs, by involving customers in the service improvement process;
- the possibility of reducing transaction costs through new communication solutions (for example, by making electronic orders for services, the Internet).

A systematic management of consumer loyalty also has a positive influence on the volume of services provided and, implicitly, on the turnover. Thus, the customers attached to the agro-tourism guesthouses have a certain predisposition to accept higher prices than the other customers, creating for the respective

guesthouses the opportunity to practice higher prices. Also, in the case of loyal customers, a higher frequency of service purchases can be observed, resulting in positive effects on the volume of services provided by boarding houses. (scritube.com)

CONCLUSIONS

From the point of view of natural resources and anthropogenic tourism resources, the North West region is very well represented, the main tourist attractions are the elements of ethnography, folklore, folk art, nature reserves, spa resorts . As far as the reception structures are concerned, the region has a pretty good image for the future, but still there would be room for better, so the construction of new structures is being considered, as well as the modernization of the existing ones. From the point of view of food and treatment, boarding houses are well represented compared to the leisure area and services, the latter are not sufficiently well equipped from the point of view of the technical and material base. They require massive modernization, but also the introduction of new forms of leisure and the expansion of the service network. Tourism is very closely related to civilization and culture, establishing a relationship of interdependence between them. By exploiting the natural, human and financial resources available to it, tourism generates economic and social effects that lead to increased economic efficiency, progress and civilization. The manifestation of tourist demand and its dynamics in the North West region are determined by a series of demographic, psychological and organizational factors, which play a decisive role in the various tourism segments. For a complex development of tourism, potential customers should be better informed through various channels such as mass media, internet, TV.

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COMPETITIVENESS, A CONDITION OF SUCCES ON THE MARKET

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Porter's introduction of the new paradigm of "competitive advantage" made the notion of competitiveness gain major importance and new meanings, along with related terms such as productivity and well-being.

Recently, the interest of researchers in the field to highlight the specific features of competitiveness, in relation to the more established notion of competition, can be noted. (Dimian, 2010).

Competitiveness is, in the most general sense, a complex phenomenon, referring to the ability of an element, compared to others, to form and ensure an economic, social, political environment that supports the accelerated creation of added value. From a theoretical point of view, the concept of competitiveness is based on two sub-concepts – comparative advantage and competitive advantage.

Regarding the possibilities of measuring competitiveness at the macroeconomic level and for the field of services, a wide variety of indices can be used to express the level of competitiveness of all services as well as of the various component branches of the tertiary sector.

The competitiveness of a nation depends on the existence of competitive sectors, and these, in turn, on the activity of the companies that form it. When we talk about the competitiveness of a sector or an economy, we treat the concept in relation to foreign competitors, that is, analyzing its performance in foreign trade or, in other words, the ability of industries (of the enterprises that represent it) to penetrate foreign markets (increasing exports and foreign direct investments) and to face the competition.

Keywords : agritourism, competitiveness, companies

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INTRODUCTION

One of the simplest definitions of competitiveness, recommended by the World Economic Forum (WEF, 1994) refers to "the ability of an economy to achieve and maintain high growth rates of GDP/capita". A similar but more detailed definition is given by the OECD (OECD. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development, 1992), according to which competitiveness results from the extent to which a country can, under conditions of free trade and an efficient market, produce goods and services that can withstand the test of the international market, against the background of maintaining and even increasing the real incomes of the population, in the long term.

Competitiveness is, in the most general sense, a complex phenomenon, referring to the ability of an element, compared to others, to form and ensure an economic, social, political environment that supports the accelerated creation of added value.

Competitiveness is usually defined as the ability of an entity operating in a free market to retain its own market share. There are several aspects of the competitiveness of an individual entity, among them are:

- Entrepreneurial quality and competence of managers.
- The distinctive character and quality of the goods and services delivered.
- The degree of innovation.
- Physical and virtual links with its markets.
- Efficiency of the production process.

- Access to the factors of production – land, labor and capital.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The concept of competitiveness can also be applied at the level of countries and regions, from the point of view of the ability to maintain or develop their own economic activity in the context of a free market. In this context, the different aspects of competitiveness are manifested in a more aggregated form (EuZone):

- The level of entrepreneurial culture.
- Areas of comparative advantage.
- Endowment with resources.
- Research and innovation systems.
- Transport and communication infrastructure and services.
- Availability of locations and premises.
- Availability of competent human resources.
- The existence of functional financial markets.

Turok (2004), in his work entitled *Cities, Regions and Competitiveness*, emphasizes the importance that competition between companies has for their development:

- works as a selection mechanism. Only certain companies survive on the market (those with better products and more efficient production processes);
- acts as a stimulation mechanism. To stay competitive, companies have to improve their technology and organization.

Also, the mentioned author emphasizes the difference between the competition at the company level and that which exists at the territorial level. They do not work according to the same rules: cities and regions cannot go bankrupt if they are not competitive and, at the

same time, are not guided in their activity by the objective of obtaining profit.

Synthesizing these aspects related to competition and competitiveness, Kitson, Martin, Tyler (2004) define competitiveness as "a complex concept, which focuses more on indicators and dynamics of long-term prosperity of the region or city, than on the more restrictive notion of competition over market shares and resources", "being a concept that recognizes that, basically, competitive regions and cities are places where both companies and people want to settle and invest".

The definition of the concept of competitiveness remains, therefore, still a controversial issue, a position justified by the appreciable diversity of definitions and angles of approach circulated in the literature, from which, however, some common elements can be deduced:

- ✓ the ability to produce goods / services or to carry out activities that determine a significant increase in income is the most frequently encountered formulation;
- ✓ the definitions have a high degree of generality, generally not referring to a certain reference entity (product, service, company, industrial sector, regional economy, national economy);
- ✓ in addition to the increase in income, employment and the increase in the standard of living are other reference criteria for assessing competitiveness.

Industrial competitiveness is expressed through specific characteristics of the supply side, grouped into two categories:

- the cost, determined, in turn, by:
 - ✓ the level of productivity;
 - ✓ factor prices;
 - ✓ other supply-side variables (investments, organization, management);
- quality (given by the level of profitability under conditions of keeping costs unchanged), having, in turn, three dimensions:
 - ✓ innovative (the ability of the products/services to incorporate

elements of technical and technological novelty);

- ✓ technical (the characteristic of the products/services to be in accordance with the technological documentation and reliable);
- ✓ marketing (advertising, ability to quickly adapt to changes in demand, trademark).

The perspectives of treating competitiveness, from the point of view of reference levels, are multiple - focusing on the level of the company, the industrial sector, the industry as a whole, a region, national, international (economic blocs), worldwide

- at the level of companies, the problem seems, apparently, simpler in the light of the idea that the companies that survive are competitive, and those that leave the market are not;

- at the level of sectors (or industries, according to M. Porter) the vision of dealing with competitiveness was strongly influenced by the works of this author, which includes, in addition to the determining factors at the level of companies, and factors specific to the mesoeconomic level - the dynamics of the sector (rate of its growth), specific market dimensions, strategic groups in the sector, etc.

- at the national level, the treatment of the issue of competitiveness is based, to a large extent, on Porter's Model, which has many interpretative values and defines four determinants of a country's competitive advantages: endowment with resources; business environment; related and supporting industries; the demand for goods and services on the domestic market. The novelty and strength of the model consist in the simultaneous inclusion of factors specific to the company, the industry and the country;

- at the level of the international economic blocs, the concept of "bloc competitiveness" was imposed as a result of the appreciable performances recorded by the already established blocs - EU, NAFTA, ASEAN, APEC, etc., the level of competitiveness of the entire bloc depending on the synergistic

combination of competitive advantages of member countries;

- worldwide - "global competitiveness", competitiveness becomes a concept that cannot be compared with another entity in the known universe, but could instead be measured, comparing the past with the present or the present with the future possibilities of action on the global market .

From a theoretical point of view, the concept of competitiveness is based on two sub-concepts - comparative advantage and competitive advantage.

The new, more evolved concept of competitive advantage, without denying the contribution of endowment with factors on competitiveness, moves the center of gravity of its determinants, as is normal, to the level of the company, the only economic entity generating competitiveness. In the current conditions of the world economy, for Romania, as for the other Eastern European countries, the problem of international specialization based on competitive advantage is of vital importance, determined not only by economic considerations (the ability to reduce over time the unfavorable gaps existing in regarding the levels of development compared to advanced countries), but also regarding the structural connection with the industrialized world and the gradual access to productivity standards and, implicitly, to the level of prosperity specific to it.

Regarding the possibilities of measuring competitiveness at the macroeconomic level and for the field of services, a wide variety of indices can be used to express the level of competitiveness of all services as well as of the various component branches of the tertiary sector.

Thus, variables specific to the competitiveness of services are part of macroeconomic competitiveness indices, such as the Global Competitiveness Index and the Lisbon Strategy Competitiveness Index.

When we talk about the competitiveness of a sector or an economy, we treat the concept in relation to foreign competitors, that is, analyzing its performance in foreign trade or, in other words, the ability of

industries (of the enterprises that represent it) to penetrate foreign markets (increasing exports and foreign direct investments) and to face the competition.

Only in the conditions of intense competition are businesses stimulated to permanently make their activity more efficient, to produce goods of a superior quality and to rationally manage production costs. Success on the foreign market is an important indicator of these performances. At the same time, the increase in exports and FDI have a direct effect on the increase in productivity and, therefore, on economic growth. The increase in exports depends both on the factors directly related to the internal environment of the companies, i.e. which are specific to each entity, as well as on the national factors such as: natural resources, highly qualified workforce, developed infrastructure, efficient state policies, values national, culture, history, etc. Thus, as a result of the specificity of each economy, industry or economic unit, there is a great difference between the models that ensure their competitiveness - the factors that create the foundation of competitiveness in one country, may be insignificant in another.

A nation's competitiveness does not mean export success in every industry, or even in the vast majority of industries. Obviously, no nation can ensure a trade surplus in every sector of the economy. And specialization in certain sectors automatically implies lower performances in others. Among all nations, even the most developed, none can ensure the success of all industrial sectors on the international market.

Thus, the national authorities, aiming at an increase in national competitiveness, must focus selectively on those sectors that present a competitive advantage over competing industries abroad or that have growth potential. Increasing the competitiveness of these sectors will constitute the foundation of increasing the well-being of the entire nation.

"Trying to explain "competitiveness" at the national level, then, is to answer the wrong question. What we need to understand are the determinants of productivity

and the rate of productivity growth. To find answers, we must not focus on the economy as a whole, but on specific industries and industry segments" (Porter, 1990)."

A competitive industrial branch encompasses nationally and internationally competitive enterprises. In turn, a competitive company is a company capable of offering products and services more efficiently and effectively than potential competitors. This presupposes sustainable success in international markets, without protection or subsidies. Speaking about national competitiveness, it can be said that indeed, it is mostly created at the level of economic units - companies. Namely, they compete on the market, contributing to the increase in productivity.

However, competitiveness at industry level is often a better indicator of the "economic health" of a nation than competitiveness at enterprise level. The success of a single company can be proof of the influence of certain factors specific to the company, which are difficult or even impossible to reproduce. At the same time, the success of several companies within an industry is often proof of the influence of some nation-specific factors that could be expanded and improved. At the same time, it is important to mention that the competitiveness of a single company does not necessarily imply the competitiveness of an industry (F. Blunck, 2006).

CONCLUSIONS

Being a concept that implies performance and superiority in relation to potential competitors, the notion of competitiveness can be approached at several hierarchical levels. In specialized literature, this notion is most often approached at the microeconomic (firm), mesoeconomic (sectoral) and macroeconomic (country level) levels.

However, many other intermediate approaches can be found, taking into account the broad context of use of this notion. Speaking about the competitiveness of the company, we can talk about the competitiveness of a product or product lines that would presuppose their preeminence as a price-quality ratio compared

to other products on the domestic and foreign markets. However, the concept can be approached beyond the borders of a company or a sector, being attributed to the performances acquired at the regional level.

A competitive region is one that can attract or maintain competitive firms, maintain and focus on increasing the standard of living of its population. In the following, only a few - main approaches to competitiveness are presented.

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CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE ANALYSIS OF AGRITOURISM INDICATORS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

The activity in the tourism field is measured by different indicators, and the national economies are classified according to them in international rankings. At the same time, the tourism and travel industry is characterized by a series of specific aspects, from which we have selected the ones considered relevant.

The source of data for developing the system of macroeconomic indicators is the statistical research for tracking the results and the degree of competitiveness of companies in tourism.

The concept of competitiveness continues to constitute a wide field of confrontations of visions and opinions on a theoretical, scientific and pragmatic level, of industrial policies that have as their central objective the significant increase of competitiveness at the level of national industries and their sectors, as well as strategies of companies pursuing the same objective at the microeconomic level.

The analysis of competitiveness in tourism is based on a series of eight indices, such as: the price competitiveness index, the Human Tourism index, the infrastructure index, the environment index, the technology index, the human resources index, the openness index, the social index, whose value on a scale from 0 to 100 shows the performance of each country compared to other countries. The value 0 represents the lowest value of the index, and the value 100 the highest.

The data sources for these indicators are mostly represented by the development indicators developed by the World Bank, but also by UN and WTTC (World Travel and Tourism Council) reports.

Keywords : indicators, competitiveness, agritourism, tourists

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INTRODUCTION

The activity in the tourism field is measured by different indicators, and the national economies are classified according to them in international rankings. At the same time, the tourism and travel industry is characterized by a series of specific aspects, from which we have selected the ones considered relevant.

The source of data for developing the system of macroeconomic indicators is the statistical research for tracking the results and the degree of competitiveness of companies in tourism. According to the official publications of the National Tourism Institute (INS), the indicators are classified as follows:

- indicators for evaluating tourist accommodation capacity (minimum installed accommodation capacity, existing-installed accommodation capacity, operational-available accommodation capacity);

- tourist traffic evaluation indicators (tourist action, total number of tourists, total number of days/tourist, average daily number of tourists, average length of stay, density of tourist traffic, relative preference of tourists);

- financial indicators (revenues and their structure, applied tariff policy, time structure and the ratio between working time and free time).

The analysis of tourism competitiveness at microeconomic level extended and developed at the level of tourism agencies, is carried out based on the following indicators:

- tourist demand (actual demand, potential demand and forecast);

- tourism offer (natural and anthropogenic tourism potential, material base, accommodation capacity, labor force structure by categories: socio-professional, sex, age, use of working time, labor productivity, distribution, evolution and dynamics of the labor force requirement in tourism);

- the demand-offer relationship (the actual demand, the degree of use of the accommodation capacity, the evolution of overnight stays, commercial activity);

- the quality of the tourist activity (number of visitors, number of tourist objectives visited);

- financial indicators (turnover, added value, profit, profit rate, rate of return, volume and level of expenses, labor productivity, value of investments).

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MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The concept of competitiveness continues to constitute a wide field of confrontations of visions and opinions on a theoretical, scientific and pragmatic level, of industrial policies that have as their central objective the significant increase of competitiveness at the level of national industries and their sectors, as well as strategies of companies pursuing the same objective at the microeconomic level.

A tendency that manifests itself vigorously in the efforts of countries and companies to

increase competitiveness is that of the superior exploitation of location advantages, a form of advantages that joins the competitive ones.

World experience has shown that ensuring on a sustainable basis the increase in competitiveness of countries or regions where TNCs are attracted, foreign investors in general, is conditioned by the nature of the local resources involved in the economic development process, as well as the nature of the transferred activities. With regard to the nature of the local factors that determine the location advantages, it is obvious that the preponderance of the intangible ones - innovative, managerial, organizational, marketing capacity, assimilation of technological know-how, the level of qualification of the labor force, the national culture or organizational - provides a much more solid basis for the sustainable growth of competitiveness. Regarding the nature of the transferred activities, if they require lower qualifications and are not dependent on the presence of the other intangible factors mentioned, it is very likely that they will be lost in favour of other locations, as wages increase and cost advantages decrease.

In the context of the previously mentioned factors, OCED specifies that rural tourism must present the following features: be implemented in the rural environment (rural location); to integrate elements characteristic of rural life - small households/farms, nature, cultural heritage, traditional practices (rural functionality); to integrate buildings with specific architecture and facilities (rural spatiality); to integrate all social, economic and cultural aspects of the rural family (traditional character); to pursue the preservation of rural society, to integrate the environment, economy and local history (sustainable character).

Figure 1 Definition of the rural tourism industry

Integrating all the mentioned features, the role of tourism in the achievement of rural development can be delimited as follows: rural tourism determines the obtaining of income that can stabilize the local labor market and leads to an improvement in the lives of the inhabitants engaged in agriculture in particular; the development of the rural tourist infrastructure is a source of creating new jobs (guides, translators, etc.); the development of rural tourism often induces the development of the additional services sector (traditional product shops, transport networks, etc.) and the implementation at the level of the rural population of the pluriactivity concept (tourism becomes a support sector for agriculture if it integrates local agricultural products, labor part-time from farms, etc.); through the promoted tourist products, rural tourism has a direct role in the conservation of nature, landscapes, cultural heritage, etc.

Understanding competitiveness in agritourism is a major issue for policy makers and a major challenge for professionals providing evidence to better inform decision making. Different indicators have been developed by different organizations over the years to address certain aspects of competitiveness, but they are little or not at all used in Romania.

That is why, for the prioritization of the indicators, it started from the 42 indicators developed by the OECD. Survey responses were received from 30 member and partner countries.

Contributions were also received from various organizations including UNEP, WEF, Exceltur (Spain), International Center for Studies in the Economy of Tourism (CISSET), Northern European Tourism Research Institute (NIT), Chemonics, OECD Monitoring Units welfare and progress.

The indicators are organized around four categories:

- ✓ Indicators that measure the performance and impact of tourism;
- ✓ Monitoring indicators of a destination's ability to offer quality and competitive tourist services;
- ✓ Indicators for monitoring the attractiveness of a destination;
- ✓ Indicators that describe economic opportunities.

At the industry level, there are some significant initiatives to monitor competitiveness in tourism. At the international level, the most important indices remain the WEF Travel and the Tourism Competitiveness Index. Several countries also use the Brand Nation Index, which measures a nation's image and reputation in the world, and tracks their profiles.

Since a questionnaire with a large number of indicators cannot be submitted in the field study, an attempt was made to reduce them. In order to obtain results as close as possible to reality, the quality house method was used. The use of this method was made using the results published by the OECD.

the capacity to increase tourism revenues,

The competitiveness of the destination depends on:

- ✓ the capacity to increase tourism revenues,
- ✓ the ability to constantly attract tourists
- ✓ providing pleasure and experience
- ✓ profitability

- ✓ ensuring the quality of life for local residents and protection of the natural environment

According to these parameters, a methodology was developed. The OECD model identifies 42 attributes of competitiveness grouped into four main factors. Using the statistical data, the House of Quality was developed, in order to prioritize the 42 elements.

The analysis of competitiveness in tourism is based on a series of 42 indices, such as: the price competitiveness index, the Human Tourism index, the infrastructure index, the environment index, the technology index, the human resources index, the openness index, the social index, whose value is on a scale from 0 to 100 shows the performance of each country compared to other countries. The value 0 represents the lowest value of the index, and the value 100 the highest. The data sources for these indicators are mostly represented by the development indicators developed by the World Bank, but also by UN and WTTC (World Travel and Tourism Council) reports.

The methodological base used is known as the House of Quality, which also involves the use of the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP). This method of quality management can also be successfully used in the case of designing a service, being very useful in the competitive development of a study program and its orientation towards market requirements.

Quality Function Deployment (QFD) is a method used in the field of quality planning, in order to create products whose quality characteristics correspond to customer needs. The method proposed by Yoji Akao was implemented at the Mitsubishi company in 1972, it spread in Japan, in the USA where it was popularized by the American Supplier Institute (ASI), nowadays it has increased importance in Europe as well. The principle of the method is the satisfaction of the customer's needs regarding the product (we also mean the service provided) in each of the stages of the product's realization. Specific to the method is the fact that all activities related to the product, to the

existing stages of the product are analyzed from the perspective of the customer and not of the manufacturer. The starting point of the method is the identification and evaluation of customer requirements, requirements which are then transposed into specifications based on which the activities for the production of the products will be carried out.

The quality house consists of six matrices: the customer requirements matrix, the technical characteristics matrix, the connection matrix, the correlation matrix, the technical evaluation matrix and the market evaluation matrix.

In the application of the method, it has been proven that the most difficult thing is to complete the matrix of customer requirements, because for this a large number of data and information, which come from different sources, is required.

Within this matrix, the customer's requirements related to the company's product/service are recorded, as well as the degree of importance given to them by the customer.

After the application of the House of Quality, out of the 42 competitiveness attributes examined, the eight most important proved to be, as shown in figure 2:

- ✓ Physical Geography and Climate
- ✓ Culture and History
- ✓ Tourism Superstructure
- ✓ Safety and Security
- ✓ Cost / value
- ✓ Accessibility
- ✓ Quality services
- ✓ Good infrastructure

Figure 2 Prioritization of indicators

Six of these attributes form the group of attributes known as core resources and attractors.

Destination physical characteristics and climate have long been considered to be particularly important to the tourist attractiveness of a destination, and this result is not surprising.

Culture and history also proved to be very determining attributes. While physical geography and climate represent the "natural" qualities of a destination, Culture and History represent the primary tourist attraction of a destination that is the product of "human" rather than "natural" processes.

Another determining attribute proved to be the existing leisure structures (Tourism Superstructure). The quantity and quality of the environment must meet specific tourist needs, such as accommodation facilities, restaurants, transport facilities, recreation facilities, attractions, theme parks, museums and art galleries, exhibitions and convention centers, resorts, airports, etc.

The quality and price of tourist services are the dominant aspects that influence the choice of tourist services. The prices and tariffs are established in relation to the tourist destination, respectively the area, the period of the year (depending on the season-zone), the comfort category of the tourist reception structures or the means of transport used, etc.. In generally, higher prices and tariffs limit access to tourist services, leading to a decrease in the number of tourists and tourist-days, to a reduction in the average length of stay and the range of tourist services purchased by tourists.

In addition to the physical characteristics of the units and their placement in space, the quality of the accommodation service and, accordingly, the option of the tourist are influenced by the atmosphere in the unit, the attention of the staff, the speed of reaction and its efficiency, the clientele, the image and the reputation they enjoy. In this sense, research undertaken on the factors of competitiveness in agritourism have demonstrated, along with the importance of the material ones, objectives such as: the level and diversity of facilities, staff qualification, cleanliness, comfort, social spaces, the growing role of subjective elements, such as the ambience, the level of clientele, the personalities who visited the unit, the history of the unit, etc.

Special attention is paid to specialized studies regarding the location of accommodation units. It is, first of all, the choice of the destination and the positioning of the objective within it, depending on various elements: the distance from the means of access (airport, train station, highway) and from the tourist attractions; the beauty of the landscape; Quiet. Secondly, the location must meet some economic criteria, namely: investment value, operating costs, ensuring a high level of occupancy.

CONCLUSIONS

Integrating all the mentioned features, the role of tourism in the achievement of rural development can be delimited as follows: rural tourism determines the obtaining of income that can stabilize the local labor market and leads to an improvement in the lives of the inhabitants engaged in agriculture in particular; the development of the rural tourist infrastructure is a source of creating new jobs (guides, translators, etc.); the development of rural tourism often induces the development of the additional services sector (traditional product shops, transport networks, etc.) and the implementation at the level of the rural population of the pluriactivity concept (tourism becomes a support sector for agriculture if it integrates local agricultural products, labor part-time from farms, etc.); through the promoted tourist products, rural tourism has a

direct role in the conservation of nature, landscapes, cultural heritage, etc.

Understanding competitiveness in agritourism is a major issue for policy makers and a major challenge for professionals providing evidence to better inform decision making. Different indicators have been developed by different organizations over the years to address certain aspects of competitiveness, but they are little or not at all used in Romania.

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ELEVATING CULINARY EXPERIENCE THROUGH GLOBAL SOURCING AND EDUCATION: A CASE STUDY OF SOURCED

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This article examines Sourced, a subscription-box service that integrates the delivery of premium, regionally sourced food products with educational initiatives focused on the implications of food choices across various categories. We explore how Sourced leverages global sourcing to promote sustainable eating practices and supports small-scale producers, while also providing consumers with educational content that enhances their understanding of different cuisines and what quality means. The study analyzes the impact of Sourced's business model and its potential contributions to a more sustainable global food system. This paper seeks to address the gap of little or no attention given to traditional foods in the Food Subscription business by assessing and highlighting the potential of its business model.

Keywords: Traditional Foods, subscription box, sustainability, education, business, Food Industry.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the past 5 years, the popularity of the food subscription box business has been on the ascendency (Chen et al. 2018). A major driver of this trend was the famous and rather notorious COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, where a lot of startups sprang up in this sector. Not only did the subscription box business gain popularity but also in areas such as medicine, sports, fashion, education and even the engineering sector. In as much as the business model of subscription box is quite lucrative, several renowned brands such as GAP, Sephora, Under Armour and Adidas experience major challenges upon their first entrance in this market (Simeon, 2020). This gives an indication that careful assessment and implementation of a business plan and other vital factors are very necessary for the success of such a business venture, especially around food or food ingredients.

Globally, the importance of traditional food and its ingredients cannot be over emphasized as it plays a vital role in the food industry across various countries. Traditional foods do not only satisfy the nutritional need of consumers but also exhibit the historical background and cultural richness of a place or people in a

geographical area. It is in this regard that several efforts are made to pass down the traditions from generation to generation. Some studies have shown that the production of majority of traditional foods have less environmental impact hence more sustainable than conventional products (Cerutti et al., 2013; Pereira et al., 2019). Patronage of traditional foods, in essence, has a link to rural development and cultural promotion.

However, among the various food products explored in the food subscription box business, traditional foods are the least explored. Little or no attention has been given to exploring traditional food in subscription box business world-wide. Their mode of vending has been reduced to direct sales with quite a few sold through some supermarkets. Introducing traditional foods in the subscription box business can help encourage the effort of local producers, promote cultural significance, cultural exchange and facilitate rural development globally. Traditional food subscription business has a high potential of gaining the interest of consumers in sustainability and also educating them in the culture and historical identity of a people or geographical area.

This paper seeks to address the gap of little or no attention given to traditional foods in the Food Subscription business by assessing and highlighting the potential of its business model. This paper also hints on how including education in this model can be useful in engrafting consumers into different cultures globally.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

PEST and Porter's Five Forcers analysis were done. Understanding the political landscape was crucial for Sourced to navigate tariffs, trade agreements, and food safety regulations effectively. Assessing economic factors like consumer purchasing power, inflation, and unemployment was also essential to tailor pricing strategies, ensuring a subscription model both affordable and appealing across varying markets. By conducting these analyses, Sourced strategically positions itself to meet regulatory demands and adapt to economic conditions, enhancing its viability in the competitive global food subscription industry.

Porter's Five Forcers allows Sourced to identify key challenges and opportunities across competitive rivalry, supplier and buyer power, threats from new entrants, and substitutes. Armed with this insight, Sourced can refine its strategies to enhance market positioning, strengthen defenses against competitors, and capitalize on its unique selling propositions, ensuring sustained success in the global food subscription market.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PEST Analysis

Political Factors: Sourced operates in a stable political environment, where regulations on food safety and labeling are consistent and well-defined across markets like the European Union and the USA. These regions share stringent regulatory standards that facilitate a uniform approach to product labeling and safety compliance. The political stability and uniform regulatory environment are advantageous for Sourced as they simplify compliance across different markets. However, bureaucratic complexities in countries like France,

characterized by intricate administrative processes, pose challenges that could potentially slow market entry and expansion efforts.

Economic Factors: The economic analysis includes consideration of currency usage and overall economic stability. In the EU, the use of a common currency, the Euro, simplifies transactions and pricing strategies. The economic positioning of Sourced's subscription boxes, targeted at consumers with disposable income, is such that the cost represents a minimal portion of an average salary, slightly above the minimum wage. This pricing strategy is viable in markets like France, where there is low poverty and substantial social safety nets for the unemployed. However, the difference in currency and economic conditions in non-Eurozone markets such as the USA necessitates strategic financial planning to accommodate fluctuations in exchange rates and purchasing power.

Social Factors: As already mentioned in the introductory part of this document, there is a growing interest in gourmet and international foods across Europe, indicating a substantial market for Sourced's offerings. European consumers are generally well-informed and care about the quality of food consumed, aligning well with Sourced's educational mission. Healthcare, a significant concern in Europe, influences consumer choices towards healthier and safer food options, which supports Sourced's emphasis on high-quality, ethically sourced products. To effectively cater to these diverse social preferences, Sourced provides clear communication about the contents of their subscription boxes, enhancing customer satisfaction and trust.

Technological Factors: High internet penetration and widespread adoption of e-commerce in Sourced's target markets facilitate online sales and marketing. The company employs these technological advantages to reach a broader audience efficiently. Additionally, the logistics infrastructure in these regions supports efficient distribution, crucial for maintaining the quality and timeliness of perishable food products.

Porter's Five Forces Analysis

Sourced shapes a unique niche in the **competitive rivalry** within the global food and drink subscription market, anticipated to expand to USD 8.16 billion by 2030. Unlike competitors who often provide generic or narrowly focused products, Sourced delivers uniquely curated boxes enhancing its competitive power against North American, Japanese and other global companies (Bokksu, n.d.; Try The World, n.d.). This strategic differentiation, supported by innovative offerings and a robust focus on culinary education, helps Sourced stand out in a crowded market, effectively managing **competitive rivalry** by emphasizing quality, diversity, and educational value in its products. Regarding **supplier power**, Sourced successfully navigates its relationships with a network of small-scale producers known for their unique, traditional products. By maintaining a flexible sourcing strategy and the capability to adapt product offerings swiftly, Sourced mitigates risks associated with supplier bargaining power and potential supply disruptions. This adaptability is crucial in managing **supplier power** and maintaining a stable supply chain. Furthermore, the barriers to market entry are significant due to the special

Figure 1. **Figure of Sourced's Porter's 5 Forces**

nature of Sourced's offerings. New entrants face challenges in establishing similar supplier relationships and gaining customer trust, thereby addressing the **threat of new entrants**. Additionally, Sourced's focus on delivering artisanal and culturally rich products with educational content significantly lowers the **threat of substitution**, as these offerings are distinct from the more industrial products typically found in the market. These strategic

elements collectively fortify Sourced's market position against **competitive rivalry**, while effectively managing **supplier power**, **threat of new entrants**, and **threat of substitution**, ensuring the company's growth and sustainability in the competitive landscape of global food subscriptions.

Supply Chain Analysis

Sourced stands out in the global food subscription market through its commitment to ethical sourcing and sustainability. The company prioritizes partnerships with producers who employ sustainable methods of cultivation and manufacturing, such as organic farming and energy-efficient technologies. It also selects its suppliers depending on their ethical standards such as fair labor practices, transparency and impact on their community.

In the European market, Sourced leverages on the EU CAP Network to connect with producers. Great results in boosting businesses from the cooperation of small producers have been seen in the Rumanian and Swedish markets (European Network for Rural Development, 2020; European Network for Rural Development, 2021). Therefore, Sourced's approach can amplify the impact on small producers by integrating them into a more extensive market ecosystem.

Additionally, the EU has frameworks for foodstuffs and businesses certifications which allows Sourced to more easily choose its partners as those that are certified as BIO, Fair Trade, Marine Stewardship, Rainforest Alliance, RSPCA Assured, among others.

Outside of Europe, Sourced strategically utilizes a network of specialists on agricultural products and food of origin that have been gathered from all over the world. This is thanks to the realization of the Master Food Identity, which has been ongoing for 15 years by the moment of writing this paper. This way Source can build long-term relationships with suppliers worldwide, providing them with stable income and support.

Moreover, producers linked to Sourced can relate to multiple professionals that could train them on techniques to improve their practices, enhance quality or any other area of interest.

CONCLUSIONS

Implications for Global Food Distribution:

Sourced's model is poised to influence larger trends by fostering a deeper appreciation for global cuisines, inclining a shift towards more adventurous and informed eating habits.

Educational Contributions:

Provision of rich, informative content about the origins, cultural significance, and preparation methods of the products in subscription box empowers consumers to make informed choices and also promotes a broader understanding of global culinary diversity

Sustainability Impact:

By prioritizing local suppliers and helping them keep to sustainable production practices, Sourced supports environmental management and responsible sourcing.

The existence of the EU CAP Network highlights also the importance of promoting greater cooperation on marketing, sales, and distribution given by the European Union in agricultural business.

Future Directions: Sourced has a lot of opportunities in expanding its educational content to include virtual cooking classes or partnerships with savvy kitchen experts. In addition, exploring new markets and widening its base of suppliers to embrace even more different and underrepresented food cultures could make it the market leader in the global food subscriptions industry.

Conclusion FROM PEST analysis, supplemented by insights from the CAGE framework, forms a critical component of Sourced's strategic planning for international expansion. By meticulously analyzing these factors, Sourced ensures that their business model is robust, adaptable, and sensitive to the intricate dynamics of new markets. This comprehensive approach not only supports Sourced's operational efficiency but also aligns with its mission to deliver exceptional educational and culinary experiences globally. To mitigate the political challenges, strategies to standardize and adapt logistics, preparation, and

packaging processes need to be developed. This will ensure efficiency and regulatory compliance across markets. Economic factors like inflation and unemployment rates are also considered, especially when planning expansion into markets with less economic stability than Europe or the USA. Sourced continuously evaluates its technological strategies to ensure they align with advancements in e-commerce and logistics technologies, maintaining competitive delivery times and customer service standards. To supplement the PEST Analysis a deep CAGE Framework (Distance Analysis) can be done highlighting the importance of adapting to cultural differences, especially as Sourced plans expansion beyond Europe and USA. That way, the business model takes into account the cultural openness to new trends of more pragmatic regions like South America.

Broader Implications: Reflection on the potential for Sourced-like models to contribute to more sustainable and culturally aware food consumption globally.

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STUDY ON ROAD ACCIDENTS WITH MULTIPLE VICTIMS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Road accidents with multiple victims represent an important public health problem. Constant attention is required for optimizing secondary prevention, which includes prehospital and hospital emergency medical care. The provision of specialized medical first aid at the scene of the event and during the entire transport, contributes to the reduction of complications related to trauma and mortality rate. The purpose of this research is the analysis of the characteristics and particularities presented by multiple victims of pre-hospital and hospital road accidents. The analysis shows the characteristics of patients who are multiple victims of road accidents, predominating: men, the elderly and people from the urban environment. The main causes of accidents are high speed and the use of drugs and alcohol. The severity of the injury placed most of the victims in yellow emergency code. The vast majority of road accidents involved fewer than 5 victims. Most of the victims were transported to the hospital with B1/B2 ambulances. A large part of the patients presented polytraumas being admitted to the hospital on surgical wards.

Keywords: road accidents, multiple victims, emergency medical care

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INTRODUCTION

The accident or incident leading to multiple victims is a major event, caused by various factors that generate an exceptional situation. Victim is the person whose health status is affected due to different factors that cause the accident (WHO, 2014).

The provision of medical assistance is carried out through special actions aimed at saving life and preserving health (OG 2001, 2004, 2008, 2013). This includes two stages: the pre-hospital stage (at the scene of the accident - in the outbreak or the place of the disaster) and the hospital stage (medical and sanitary units specialized in the treatment of emergencies).

Hospitals where the examination of victims in the disaster area is carried out organize the reception and intra-hospital medical triage of patients, stabilization, hospitalization, provision of qualified medical assistance, as well as the treatment for those who need it (Kumar, 2021; Mohammed 2019).

If there is an incident with multiple victims or a disaster, an imbalance between the need to provide medical assistance and the reduced capacities to ensure the medical and sanitary resources available at the time is created, which is maintained for a certain period of time (Anjuman, 2020). In such

conditions, providing full medical assistance to all affected victims is impossible. This fact requires the concentration of efforts to provide medical assistance primarily to victims who present an advanced emergency code, but who have real chances of survival at the same time (Kumar, 2013; Sinha, 2017).

The process of identifying victims according to the priority of providing medical assistance and their evacuation is carried out through medical triage both in the pre-hospital and hospital (Shetty, 2012; Souto, 2016). Victims resulting from the accident who will continue treatment in the hospital are distributed according to the clinical condition, the degree of emergency for medical assistance (Zhang, 2016).

The purpose of this research is to carry out an analysis with the characteristics and particularities presented by multiple victims of pre-hospital and hospital road accidents.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

An observational, retrospective and descriptive study was carried out, based on the patients medical documents, obtained after a prior agreement with the hospital. Medical data were collected from the hospital computer system, examination and observation sheets. The study period was the year 2023, at the level of Bihor county, 137 serious road

accidents were recorded, with a number of 117 seriously injured people and 41 dead people. From the total number of road accidents, the patients were selected for care. Medical data were complete. Thus, 89 patients (multiple victims) resulting from 36 accidents were selected. The age group of the patients was between 1 year and 85 years.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The demographic characteristics of the patients, multiple victims are: male (34%), urban environment (65%), age between 1 year and 85 years (table 1).

Table 1
Demographic characteristics of patients, multiple victims

Demographic characteristics	No.	%	
gender	male	46	54%
	female	39	46%
residence	urban	29	35%
	rural	56	65%
age	< 15 years	9	11%
	16-28 years	23	27%
	29-45 years	11	13%
	46-70 years	14	16%
	> 70 years	28	33%

The number of victims involved in each accident varied between 2 victims and more than 15 victims (figure 1).

Figure 1. The number of victims involved in each road accident

From severity and nature of the injuries point of view, at the arrival of first aid and resuscitation crews, code yellow prevailed. Code Yellow - signifies the existence of a moderate emergency, the victim has serious or medium injuries, ailments, poisoning or contamination, with preserved vital functions, but with the risk of developing life-threatening complications in the near future. This type of victims requires urgent medical attention, but not immediately (figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of victims according to the color code of the emergency

The most frequent causes of road accidents with multiple victims were: high speed (29%), drug and alcohol consumption (27%), health problems (17%), bad weather (14%), technical failure (9%), other causes (4%).

When first aid crews arrived at the scene of the accident, 42% of the victims had a favorable evolution, 39% had a stationary evolution, and 19% had an unfavorable evolution.

From the total number of victims with unfavorable evolution (14 victims), at the arrival of the first aid, extrication and resuscitation crews, 3 victims were found in cardio-respiratory arrest, 5 victims entered cardio-respiratory arrest during transport to the hospital, and 6 victims went into cardio-respiratory arrest at the hospital. Of the 14 victims who went into cardiorespiratory arrest, 11 victims died.

The type of trauma suffered by all the victims involved in the study, including those who died, is represented in figure 3.

Figure 3. Distribution of patients according to the type of trauma suffered

From the total number of multiple victims, 53 patients were transported to the hospital with qualified crews that arrived at the scene of the intervention. 15 patients did not require transport to the hospital, receiving

medical care at the scene of the accident. The type of ambulances involved in transporting victims to the hospital is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Types of ambulances (number) involved in transporting victims to the hospital

A large number of special medical personnel was involved in providing first aid and reviving the victims: doctors, nurses, paramedics, paramedics and firefighters (figure 5).

Figure 4. Number of specialists involved in rescuing victims resulting from road accidents

During transport, patients were placed in a vacuum mattress and immobilized with standard cervical collars, they had a large-caliber venous line installed, and depending on the needs, symptomatic and specialized treatment was administered.

From the total number of multiple victims, a group of 37 patients were diagnosed with polytraumas, from which: 29 patients were admitted directly to different wards, 6 patients were discharged home with recommendations and 2 patients refused hospitalization on their own responsibility. According to the current polytrauma protocols, patients with multiple traumas are admitted to Surgery I department or Intensive Care Department, within the clinic, and if they do not have predominant injury on the abdomen, but they have injuries without a surgical indication they are sent in other departments.

After sorting the patients with polytraumas, 65% of them were admitted to other surgical departments (neurosurgery, thoracic surgery, orthopedics, interventional cardiology) and only a 35% percentage were admitted to Surgery Department I/ Anesthesia and Intensive Care Department.

In the preoperative period, the existence and severity of lesions needs to be evaluated correctly with as much precision as possible. Thus, after clinical examination, ultrasound, imaging and laboratory investigations of the victims, a score in which the degree of lesions severity was assessed in order to determine the type and urgency of the surgical measures to be taken later (Subedi, 2014).

Related to the presence of injuries, thoracic injuries predominated in hospitalized patients were in a proportion of 38%, followed by cranio-cerebral injuries without a surgical indication in a proportion of 20%. Regarding intra-abdominal organ injuries, liver lacerations were diagnosed in 4 patients and accounted for 12%, ranking first, followed by splenic lacerations with 2 cases (6%), intestinal and mesenteric injuries, and contusions of the anterior abdominal wall constituted 6% each, and 12% were represented by other lesions with different locations.

Analyzing the surgical treatment applied for multiple traumas patients, we can highlight that in the case of patients diagnosed with liver laceration (4 patients), only 2 of them underwent surgery, practicing hemostasis by packing and hepatorrhaphy, lavage, drainage, and for the other 2 patients the treatment was conservative. The hospitalized patients with the diagnosis of splenic laceration (2 patients) underwent emergency surgery, splenectomy, lavage, and drainage performed in both cases. In the case of patients with the diagnosis of acute surgical abdomen, intestinal injury and mesenteric injury, surgical intervention was also performed, in emergency mode, practicing as needed - enterorrhaphy, implicitly mesenterorrhaphy, lavage, drainage.

CONCLUSIONS

Trauma continues to represent a major threat to public health in all age groups, more in the active population. Differences in the complexity and severity of traumatic injuries are a really difficult problem for clinicians around the world, and therefore advanced health care methods and periodic renewal of

care protocols for patients with multiple traumas are needed in order to reduce the morbidity and mortality rate.

The analysis shows the characteristics of patients who are multiple victims of road accidents, predominating: men, the elderly, and people from the urban environment. The main causes of accidents are high speed and the use of drugs and alcohol. Most of the victims are placed in yellow emergency code due to the severity of the injury.

The vast majority of road accidents involved fewer than 5 victims. Most of the victims were transported to the hospital with B1/B2 ambulances.

A large part of the patients that presented polytraumas were admitted to the hospital on surgical wards.

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COMPETITIVENESS AT THE LEVEL OF THE NW DEVELOPMENT REGION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

On the European market, tourism is experiencing an explosive development, the number of tourists growing exponentially in the last 20 years. The targets are especially clear destinations, especially towards the South of Europe - France, Italy, Spain, Greece. The types of tourism offered are mainly cultural, historical and leisure tourism. Tourism brings an important share in the GDP of these countries.

In Romania, too, there was an increase in the number of foreign tourists, but at the same time, the number of departures was higher, which led to a negative tourist balance.

The assessment of competitiveness in the field of services can be carried out following two main levels of analysis: at the scale of the entire economy, by measuring the overall economic performance, with the help of indicators such as GDP/capita, the sectoral distribution of added value and labor productivity estimates, which show the extent to which providers are efficient in staff organization; a number of indicators in this category provide information related to aspects intrinsic to industrial performance and competitiveness: such indicators are, for example, labor productivity and costs per unit of labor and at the scale of international transactions, to identify how the activities of services compete on the international market or face external competition on the local market, by means of indicators such as, for example, the export market share, the structure of exports, the revealed comparative advantage index.

Two elements are essential in this case, namely the impact of the liberalization and reform of internal regulations, on the one hand, and the impact of technology development, on the other hand, to determine the competitiveness variations determined by EU accession.

Keywords : development, competitiveness, services, security

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INTRODUCTION

The evaluation of competitiveness in the field of services can be carried out following two main levels of analysis:

- at the scale of the entire economy, by measuring the overall economic performance, with the help of indicators such as GDP/inhabitant, the sectoral distribution of added value and labor productivity estimates, which show the extent to which providers are efficient in staff organization; a number of indicators in this category provide information related to aspects intrinsic to industrial performance and competitiveness: such indicators are, for example, labor productivity and unit labor costs.

- at the scale of international transactions, to identify how service activities

compete on the international market or face external competition on the local market, through indicators such as, for example, the export market share, the structure of exports, the revealed comparative advantage index .

Two elements are essential in this case, namely the impact of the liberalization and reform of internal regulations, on the one hand, and the impact of technology development, on the other hand, to determine the competitiveness variations determined by EU accession.

I. National economic factors:

- local resources (endowment with natural resources, workforce, existing infrastructure, technological and financial resources, etc.);

- the size and structure of internal demand;

- the technological level and efficiency of the subassembly industry and subsuppliers;
- industrial structure and competition.

These four national economic factors create an economic environment, a national context in which companies are born, compete and gain a competitive advantage that they use internationally.

Local resources include human resources, physical resources, scientific and technological resources, financial resources and national infrastructure.

The competitive advantage appears if the national firms can use the necessary combination of factors at a low cost or if the factors used are of a higher quality level.

Firms also gain competitive advantage if internal demand creates enough pressure to influence accelerated innovation. At the same time, the high demand of national customers can contribute to increasing the competitive advantage because it forces companies to use high standards in the field of quality, equipment, services and others.

The presence of efficient sub-suppliers and related industrial sub-sectors that can enhance other sectors of activity is very important in gaining competitive advantage.

The last component of the national economic factors refers to the existing industrial structure.

Oligopolistic competitive structures facilitate the conquest of new markets for the following reasons:

- national rivalries create pressure for innovation, which increases the competitive advantage;
- the oligopolistic competitive structure creates advantages for other industrial activities through competitive prices, superior quality, seriousness in long-term relationships;
- this structure creates a competitive environment that is difficult to recreate through competition with external rivals.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

II. The action of the government authorities is decisive for the creation of the company's external competitive advantage. The role of government is to influence and power the previously mentioned national economic factors. This influence can be achieved directly through subsidies, industrial and other policies, or indirectly through the shaping of domestic demands through standards and regulations. A capital role of the government in the market is given by the fact that it includes an important buyer of advanced goods and technologies such as: telecommunication equipment, armaments, computer technology, means of transport, etc.

III. Mondoeconomic factors are made up of three main elements:

- American deregulation had four important consequences:

- eradicating strong inflation (lowering the inflation rate below 4%);
- the state's loss of control over the interest rate and exchange rate through the consolidation of forward financial markets;
- directing the economy by the market at the expense of governments;
- the globalization of economies that drives the regrouping of businesses to face increased competition.

- the collapse of communist economic management systems - phenomena with many economic and political implications.

- the explosion of the Internet - so in a short time the entire globe will represent "a world network" and everyone will be able to receive

and send messages for any purpose, including to buy or sell.

Ensuring a wide range of tourist services by diversifying basic and complementary facilities and services is an important element in the choice of accommodation units. The agreed facilities are indicated both from the point of view of the interior elements, from the accommodation spaces and the facilities within the resort. A large part of the guesthouses in the North-West Region offer only basic services, the degree of penetration of related services being quite low.

In the Maramures area, there is a tendency to offer related services related to traditional customs, to integrate tourists into the community, they are considered rather friends by the hosts (they are greeted with bread and salt by the hosts dressed in folk costumes, assisted in various activities of the household, wear folk costumes, participate in themed evenings with folk music and dances).

The existence of green spaces (picnic places, playgrounds and sports fields, walking trails) that facilitate recreation have an important role in the setting of the resort, influencing the choice of accommodation units around them.

Quality services

The facilities that the respondents want to find in the accommodation unit are complex and diverse, and refer both to the functional elements, to elementary and refined facilities, as well as to the attractive elements that personalize any tourist service. Along with the basic services, and those known in advance by tourists (which are included in the cost of the purchased tourist package), there are also services that are contacted only at the destination.

According to the data provided by the National Institute of Statistics, the number of localities with a water distribution network is constantly increasing (table 1), this being one of the basic requirements necessary for a quality vacation.

Residential environments	Macroregions, development regions and counties	Years	
		Year 2011	Year 2012
		UM: Number	
		Number	Number
Rural	TOTAL	1987	2011
-	NORD-WEST Region	333	335
-	Bihor	77	77
-	Bistrita-Nasaud	39	40
-	Cluj	69	69
-	Maramures	53	54
-	Satu Mare	48	48
-	Salaj	47	47

Table 1. Water distribution network

For a pleasant stay, the accommodation unit must satisfy a multitude of "expectations" embodied in a range of services. (clean and decent accommodation, clean linen, hot water; restaurant/food service; TV in the room; private and clean bathroom; parking service; swimming pool; friendly staff, hospitable host; refrigerator in the room; wi-fi; organization of hiking ;).

Cost/value

On the European market, tourism is experiencing an explosive development, the number of tourists growing exponentially in the last 20 years. The targets are especially clear destinations, especially towards the South of Europe - France, Italy, Spain, Greece. The types of tourism offered are mainly cultural, historical and leisure tourism. Tourism brings an important share in the GDP of these countries.

In Romania, too, there was an increase in the number of foreign tourists, but at the same time, the number of departures was higher, which led to a negative tourist balance.

The NW region has approximately the same structure of foreign tourists in terms of destination country as Romania. The regional market is made up of Romanian tourists who are

segmented by types of tourism such as cultural and spa tourism.

Most of the foreign tourists come from Hungary (39.4%), and from EU countries. It is important to specify that their access is mainly by road and to an important extent by air.

The relative weight per county is about 1/3 of foreign tourists per Romanian tourist, Cluj and Bihor counties having an index higher than the regional average.

The main destinations of foreign tourists were the counties of Cluj and Bihor, due to their tourist attraction.

Physical geography and climate

The North West region has an area of 34,159 km² representing 14.3% of the total area of the country. It is made up of 6 counties: Bihor, Bistrita Nasaud, Cluj, Maramures, Satu Mare and Zalau.

In the territorial profile, the spa resorts (located in 3 important areas) stand out: Western Plain, Transylvanian Depression, Maramures Depression, some known others with potential: Baile Felix, 1 Mai, Sangeorz, Ocna Sugatag, Baita or Cojocna. An important component are the winter resorts: Stana de Vale, Baisoara in the Apuseni Mountains and those in the North of the Eastern Carpathians (Borsa, Piatra Fantanele) (figure 6.1). The region has a tradition in spa tourism, this having the largest share among all types of tourism practiced in the region. In the large urban localities there is an infrastructure made up of numerous hotel units of different sizes. But what is significant is the development of rural tourism, in small guesthouses that use the opportunities of the environmental attractions in which they are located.

Integrated tourism products are mostly missing. Cluj-Napoca ranks second in the national hierarchy as potential for polarization, after the capital, its influence manifesting itself over the entire area of Transylvania.

Figure 1 Nord West Region

The most significant types of tourism area: spa and treatment tourism, mountain tourism, cultural tourism and agritourism.

The most important spa resorts in the North-West region are: Baile-Felix, Sangeorz-Bai, Ocna-Sugatag, Cojocna.

Already established destinations will have strong competition in the future. The areas with potential for rural tourism are not yet sufficiently developed, but they will be promoted in the future. Among the areas that will be promoted are Bistrita, Salaj, Maramures.

Culture/history

"Northern Transylvania" has one of the most important cultural heritages, significant concentrations of archaeological vestiges from Roman forts, medieval fortresses, to important industrial archaeological sites, architectural ensembles and popular craft traditions with an approximately equal distribution over the entire area of the region.

Villages are the expression of the simplicity of rural life, and each subregion is distinguished by its ethnographic specificity. The elements of archaic culture (the organization of the barn, customs related to agricultural events and human life - birth, wedding, death) combine today with modern urban cultural elements, unfortunately visible more and more strictly especially in the interior and exterior architecture, but especially in the traditional port. The penetration of modern elements and the continuous evolution of rural to urban leads

to the loss of the identity and originality of traditional rural life.

Considering the growing importance for tourists of the entertainment services offered by a locality or tourist area, an analysis of the situation of cultural event halls becomes relevant. The table below presents some statistical data on the mentioned topic, from which it appears that from this point of view the North-West region is generally at an above average level in terms of the offer of museums and public collections, concentrated especially in the counties Cluj and Maramures. It should be noted, however, that Bistrita Nasaud does not own institutions for performances and concerts.

The region is the cultural plate of Romania. There are a number of cultural attractions:

- representative museums that need investment: the Transylvanian Museum in Cluj.
- archaeological areas - conservation and modernization of the Roman sites in Cluj, Zalău (Porolli-sum) which can attract a large number of tourists
- nature reserves - protected areas, Natura 2000 areas.
- libraries - they need investments in infrastructure (buildings), but especially IT infrastructure and information management systems.

An important aspect is the preservation and valorization of folk art and local traditions. Also for the rural environment there are specific monuments such as wooden churches in Maramures.

Infrastructure/accessibility

The North West region does not have a network of fast roads and highways. Only a part (52 km) of the Transylvania highway (Bors-Oradea-Zalău-Cluj-Turda-Brasov) is executed and is open for traffic. The fate of the execution of the other sections is totally uncertain.

The road network totaling 12,459 km of national roads is not in optimal conditions of use.

Only 3324 km of roads are modernized, which represents a percentage of 24.6% of the total length of roads, much below the national percentage of 32% (table 4). Accessibility is achieved mainly by road and rail.

One of the regional problems is given by the access infrastructure to the tourist areas; it being still poorly developed relative to the needs of the region.

Mountain areas have a reduced capillarity in terms of access infrastructure. There are tourist areas with a reduced access structure, such as in the Apuseni Mountains (Vladeasa, Baisoara, Muntele Mare area), the Maramures Mountains.

The opportunity is given in particular by the construction of the Transylvania Motorway, which will ensure capillarity inside and outside the region.

The region is criss-crossed by 7 European roads (fig.6.2) (the most important being E60- from Hungary, connects Oradea-Cluj-Brasov and the country's capital, E576 Cluj Napoca-Dej, E81-Satu Mare-Zalău-Cluj-Brasov - Bucharest, E79-Oradea-Deva, E671-Oradea-Arad-Timisoara, E58-Cluj-Dej-Bistrita-Baia Mare-Vatra Dornei).

Figure 2 Road, railway and air infrastructure

There are 4 airports, of which the one in Cluj-Napoca has international flights. Most of the routes are to external destinations. Cluj-Napoca International Airport provides regular flights to Bucharest and Timisoara, Budapest, Vienna, Munich, Frankfurt, Bologna, Treviso, Bergamo, Florence, Verona.

As tourist projects, there is the intention to transform the narrow-Mocanita railway lines from Aries Valley and Vaserului Valley into tourist attractions.

It should be noted that there is a growing air traffic in the Region; there are also customs points with the European Union.

Security

Security is able to influence the demand for the product/products and services offered by the destination. Also, security interrelates with the other elements of the specific tourist destination mix. The level of security existing within a tourist destination can be influenced to a great extent by the policies and strategies adopted especially by the management organization of the destination. Thus, security is a controllable variable by the destination's management team.

The administrations of the reception structures are responsible for the security, safety and security of tourists, the security and integrity of tourists' goods in accordance with the legislation in force, and also ensure special arrangements for tourists' valuables handed over for safekeeping.

The staff of the tourist reception structures is obliged to take measures to prevent crimes and antisocial acts within the premises of the reception structures. The administrations, hotels, motels, have the obligation to inform the police body of the crimes committed and the fact that there are people staying who have contributed to disturbing the order and tranquility of the tourists.

In accordance with H.G.R. 41, the accommodation space is the tourist's temporary residence. So this space is inviolable, with the exception of situations that endanger the lives, integrity and property of tourists, as well as the material base of the reception structure.

CONCLUSIONS

For our country, the need to develop tourism resides in the fact that Romania is a country with a tourist vocation, benefiting from

a valuable and varied natural and anthropogenic potential, harmoniously dispersed throughout the territory, but insufficiently and improperly capitalized where 8 major forms of tourism are practiced, the largest share returning to seaside, mountain, weekend, spa tourism.

At the level of transport infrastructure, Romania has an unfavourable position for attracting tourist clientele. The improvement of the general infrastructure is essential - sewage, water, roads, mobile telephony, cable TV, internet, in order to boost and support the development and development of tourism in the rural environment.

The accentuated, irrational and excessive modernization strongly left its mark on the cultural heritage, regardless of its nature (material or spiritual), destroying the regional identity, an element that represented the main attractiveness of the region. Such examples stand out especially in the pieces of clothing worn and the "new" rural architecture.

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THE FAVORABILITY OF THE LANDS ON THE TERRITORY OF INCDA FUNDULEA CALARASI

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE – ARTICLE

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to present aspects related to some morphological properties of the Argic Chernoziom from INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi.

Based on the study, ecological and agronomic considerations were issued, but restrictive factors were also established, as well as agro-pedo-ameliorative measures to increase the productive potential of the soils in the area. Recommended agro-pedo-ameliorative measures: tilling the soil at optimal humidity, appropriate watering rules, leveling the exploitation, ameliorative fertilization, scarification.

Keywords: favorability, territory, arable.

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INTRODUCTION

Soil is the direct result of the interaction between the rock and solification factors.

Anthropogenic processes they are the main factor that can decisively influence the productive potential and ecological characteristics of lands.

The quality of the land for a particular use to a large extent depends on macro and micromorphology soil characteristics.

Land reclamation contributes to the sustainable use of soil resources and to the establishment of the best crop structures.

Credit rating of agricultural lands establishes their degree of favorability for various crops and uses with the help of credit rating notes (Chereji et al, 2022; Chiurciu et al, 2021, Chiurciu et al, 2022, Chiurciu et al, 2023; Dana et al, 2017, Dana et al, 2021; Dana et al, 2022; Dana et al, 2023).

Land valuation is carried out both at the level of the cadastral parcel and at the level of the homogeneous ecological territory (HET).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The plots are located in the eastern Romanian Plain, south-southeast Fundulea 2.3 km (Figure 1). Representing the southwestern part of Bărăganu, the Mostiștei Plain is located

between Argeș-Dâmbovița-Pasărea, the Danube Valley and the Argoava-Vânăta valleys.

It represents a less steppe subunit compared to the other compartments of the Bărăganu Plain, registering a greater share of forests and a more varied agricultural use.

In Câmpia Mostiștei, the roofs are more numerous, and the fragmentation of the relief is stronger.

The relief has the form of a wide field covered with loess from the former terminal dejection cones of Argeș and Dâmbovița (Mostiștea sands), showing a slight inclination from west to east and from north to south.

The surface of the plain has numerous roofs, which are often included in extensive semi-endoreic areas.

The Mostiștei plains present a more attenuated degree of continentality, which means that in addition to the steppe vegetation (with mesoxerophile meadows) there are also vercine forests (aridity index, de Martonne being >25).

Average annual air temperatures are between 10.5 and 11°C, and values around 13°C are recorded at the ground surface.

The average annual amplitude of the air temperature has values of 25-26°C, and on the ground of 31-32°C.

Precipitation has average annual values of approximately 550 mm, being the highest in all of Bărăgan.

The phenomena of dryness and drought are less, compared to the rest of Bărăganu (Niculescu, 1981).

The vegetation is represented by the species specific to the forest-steppe meadows, in which a high frequency has the meadow (*F. pseudovina*, *Festuca valesiaca*), the mugwort (*Artemisia austriaca*), the sedina (*Chrysopogon gryttus*), the thick pear (*Cynodon dactylon*) and the woody species of quince (*Q. cerris*, *Q. frainetio*, *Quercus pedunculiflora*) in a mixture with elm, sycamore, ash, etc.

The representative soils are the mollisols, of the vermic cambic chernoziom type, which are predominant, have a granular structure, humus around 4%, require irrigation and fertilization.

Location of the soil profile

Ceremoziom Argic-CZar (SRTS 2003)
Udic Argiustolls (pp)-(USDA-ST,1999)
Luvic Chernozems-(WRB-SR 1998)
Typical Argiloiluvial Chernoziom/Cumulic-CIti (SRCS 1980)

Location: Eastern Romanian Plain, south-southeast Fundulea-2.3 km, Călărași (Figures 1-2);

Latitude E:026°31'15.8";

Longitude N: 44°27'17.7";

Absolute altitude: 60 m.

Figure 1 Location of experimental plots and soil profile from INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi (GRIFOX Project)

Figure 2 Argic chernozem, INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi (GRIFOX Project)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Morphological characterization

Profile description:

Ap 0-18 cm; clay-dusty loam (dusty clay); very dark grey-brown wet (10YR 3/2) and dark grey-brown dry (10YR 4/2); structure disturbed by agricultural works; reawaken; friable when wet; hard when dry; roots grassy, frequent; fine and medium pores; frequencies; clear, straight passage;

Aph 18-30 cm; clay-dusty loam (dusty clay); the color is the same as in the previous horizon; compacted; compacted, lumps; grassy roots, thin; fine and medium pores, frequent; clear, straight passage;

Am 30-55 cm; clay-dusty loam (dusty clay); very dark brown-very dark gray brown in the wet state (10YR 2.5/2) and dark gray brown-brown in the dry state (10YR 4/2.5); well-developed medium-large subangular

granular and polyhedral structure; reawaken; firm when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; weakly compact; grassy roots, thin; fine, frequent pores; gradual, undulating transition; (Figure 2);

AB 55-80 cm; loamy clay (dusty clay); very dark grey-brown in the wet state (10YR 3/2) and dark brown-brown in the dry state (10YR 33/3); large subangular polyhedral structure; reawaken; hard when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderately compact; roots grassy, frequent; fine, frequent pores; punctate berries; gradual, undulating transition; Bt1 80-102 cm; loamy clay (dusty clay); very dark gray brown - dark gray brown (10YR 3.5/2) with small yellow-brown spots in the wet state (10YR 5/6) and brown (10YR 4/3) with the same spots in the dry state; prismatic structure well developed; reawaken; hard when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderately compact; small, rare berries; grass roots, rare; clay films, thin, discontinuous; gradual, undulating transition;

Bt2 102-120 cm; loamy clay (dusty clay); dark brown-brown (10YR 3.5/3) with brownish yellow spots in the wet state (10YR 6/6) and yellowish brown (10YR 5/4) with the same spots in the dry state; well-developed prismatic structure (sharp edges, pressure faces but not inclined enough for vertical character); reawaken; hard when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderately compact; small-medium beans; fine pores; clay films, continuous; gradual, undulating transition;

Bt3 120-150 cm; loamy clay (dusty clay); dark yellowish brown (10YR 4/4) with small, diffuse brownish yellow spots in the wet state (10YR 6/6) and yellowish brown-light yellowish brown (10YR 5.5/4) with the same spots in the dry state; moderately developed prismatic structure; reawaken; hard when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderately compact; fine pores; legumes; clay films, discontinuous; gradual, undulating transition;

Bt4 150-185 cm; loam (dusty clay); yellowish brown-light yellowish brown (10YR 5.5/4) with darker clay-humic films, dark yellowish brown on structural surface in wet state (10YR 4/4) and yellowish in dry state (10YR 7/6); poorly developed prismatic structure; reawaken; hard when wet; very hard

when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderate-compact; fine, frequent pores; small-medium beans; clay films, discontinuous; gradual, undulating transition;

BC 185-210 cm; loam (dusty clay); yellowish brown (10YR 5/6) with slightly darker diffuse spots yellowish-brown in the wet state (10YR 5/4) and yellowish in the dry state (10YR 7/6); prismatic structure, very poorly developed; reawaken; hard when wet; very hard when dry; adhesive; plastic; moderately compact; fine pores; small rare berries.

Favorability of lands

Based on the analysis of credit ratings, it can be observed that the lands on the territory of INCDA Fundulea present an average favorability (classes III - V favorability) for all crops in the area (Table 1).

For the use of arable land, credit ratings vary between 52 points for H.E.T. 2 (5th favorability class), 65 points for H.E.T. 1 (4th favorability class) and 71 points for H.E.T. 3 (class the III favorability, Figure 3).

Figure 3 Favorability for arable at INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi

Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

For the wheat crop, credit scores have the following values: 58 points for H.E.T. 2 (5th favorability class), 65 points for H.E.T. 1 (4th favorability class) and 72 points for H.E.T. 3 (3rd favorability class), (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Favorability for the wheat crop at INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi
Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

Climatic elements (precipitation, temperature) are presented in Figures 5-6.

Figure 5 Climate map (average annual precipitation) of microzones in the experimental perimeter of INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi
Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

Figure 6 Climate map (average annual temperature) of microzones in the experimental perimeter of INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi
Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

The main soil units

The map with territorial soil units is presented in figure 7 (Dana et al, 2017):

-US No. 1, MODERATELY DECARBONATED CAMPIC CHERNOSIUM, ON LOESS, LOOS-ARGILOUS;

-US No. 2, MODERATELY DECARBONATED ARGIC CHERNOSIUM, ON LOESS, CLAY/CLAY;

-US No. 3, STAGNIC ARGIC PHAEOSIUM, ON LOESSOID, CLAY CLAY / CLAY CLAY.

Figure 7 Pedological map of the microzones in the experimental perimeter of INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi
Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

Table 1

Credit ratings of homogeneous ecological territory (H.E.T.) for arable land at INCDA Fundulea, Calarasi

Source: own determination, GRIFOX Project

No.	Current H.E.T. use	GR	OR	PB	FS	CT	SZ	SO	MF	IU	IF	CN	LU	TR	LG	AR
1	Arable	65	65	65	65	47	65	65	65	72	58	65	72	-	57	65
2	Arable	58	58	46	52	32	35	52	58	65	52	52	65	-	40	52
3	Arable	72	72	72	72	52	65	72	72	72	58	72	72	-	72	71

GR-wheat; OR-barley; PB-maize; FS-sunflower; CT-autumn potato; SZ-sugar beet; SO-soybean; MF-green peas-beans; IU-flax for oil; IF-flax for fiber; CN-hemp; LU-lucerne; TR-clover; LG-vegetables; AR-arable.

Agronomic and ecological considerations

The Argic chernozem is in the II class, with good adaptability and with reduced limitations for field crops. With heavier rains, some traffic problems occur for a period of 1-2 days.

It presents as limiting factors for arable use the loamy-clay texture under the Am horizon, which implies a relatively short interval of soil works and in optimal humidity conditions so as not to produce soil compaction and the appearance of the hardpan sub-horizon.

The grouping of lands according to the readiness for irrigation Argic chernozem is in the II class of readiness for irrigation, presenting weak limitations to the introduction of irrigation.

It presents the same limiting factors as for suitability for arable land, related, in general, to the loamy-clay texture.

For both categories of groupings, agro-pedo-ameliorative measures are recommended: tilling the soil at optimal humidity, appropriate watering norms, exploitation leveling, ameliorative fertilization, scarification.

CONCLUSIONS

The important soils are the mollisols, of the vermic cambic chernozem type, which are predominant and require irrigation and fertilization.

The lands on the territory of INCDA Fundulea present an average favorability (classes III - V favorability) for all crops in the area.

Argic chernozem is in class II, with good adaptability and low limitations for field crops. When more abundant rains occur, some traffic problems occur for a period of 1-2 days.

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SANOGENETIC REQUIREMENTS OF TOURISTS IN BALNEOCLIMATIC RESORTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

A characteristic feature of sanogenetic forces is that their mechanisms begin to function at a time when the body acted extraordinary stimulus and finish its function only when the body has recovered. The touristic activity in balneoclimatic resorts was profoundly influenced by the Covid 19 pandemic. Nowadays tourism started to regain pre-pandemic importance in the economic field, but growing touristic activity developed dependently to the requirements of tourist regarding hygiene in hospitality units. Both men and women pay attention to hygiene aspects in a more profound way after dealing with Covid pandemic. Usually women relate on their sight ability, while men evaluate things using other senses.

Keywords: (max. 5) tourism, hygiene, clean, travel, measures

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INTRODUCTION

Sanogenesis represents a branch of medicine that deals with ensuring the health of the population, studying the social environment as a pathological factor, the influence of housing and working conditions, the phenomena of urbanization, pollution etc. (www.dexonline.ro)

Sanogenesis develops when exposed to the body of an extreme irritant, only when there is (or may be) disease. Usually, the body has a number of mechanisms that are specific function (providing excretion, selection, etc.). In a normal body, they do not perform any safety functions and only when exposed to the body of an extreme irritant transformed into sanogenetic. Sanogenesis - a complex mechanism of action throughout the pathological process (from pre-disease until recovery). A characteristic feature of sanogenetic forces is that their mechanisms begin to function at a time when the body acted extraordinary stimulus and finish its function only when the body has recovered. The sanogenesis and pathogenesis represent two parallel proceeding, closely related, but the opposite process for its biological orientation. Sanogenesis aimed at restoring the disturbed self-regulation body, focusing on the ability to rebuild the functions with a view to adapt to changing environmental conditions. In the pathology of this ability of the organism to an adequate self-regulation is violated, that is, the

body is not able to fully adapt to environmental changes. The whole complex sanogenetic are aimed at the restoration of the self-regulation of disturbed relationships.

Physiological systems are complex, that is, their properties are not confined to characteristics of their components and some new properties can emerge. Thus, fluctuations of individual elements and their combinations under the influence of gradual changes in conditions affecting these elements can lead to a qualitative change of the system in the point of bifurcation, where it switches from one to another more stable mode of functioning. (Alchimova I., 2021)

Regarding the sanogenetic mechanisms, they are divided into primary and secondary. The difference between these two groups from each other is as follows. The primary (physiological) mechanisms sanogenesis exist in a healthy body, and only when exposed to the body of an extreme irritant into play sanogenetic. Secondary (pathophysiological) sanogenetic mechanisms occur in the body in the development of a pathology that is generated based on the problems in the body "floor." (Наумова, Naumova et al., 2015)

As a social, economic and cultural phenomenon, the tourism development depends to almost all fields of activity of the society, while influencing them in their evolution, defining its criteria, concepts, forms and factors (Ionescu I., 1999). Tourism is considered to be one of the priority sectors of

the Romanian economy being included in government 's strategies (Marinescu R., 2020)

The National Association of Spa and Balneoclimatic Resorts in Romania was founded in 2006, with the aim of a national and international collaboration, with localities and agreements in the administrative field, the use of current legislative facilities as well as the promotion of specific legislative initiatives. (<https://activeecitizens.eu/partners/romania/>)

Before COVID-19, travel and tourism had become one of the most important sectors in the world economy, accounting for 10 percent of global GDP and more than 320 million jobs worldwide.

In 1950, at the dawn of the jet age, just 25 million people took foreign trips. By 2019, that number had reached 1.5 billion, and the travel and tourism sector had grown to almost too-big-to-fail proportions for many economies.

The global pandemic, the first of its scale in a new era of interconnectedness, has put 100 million jobs at risk, many in micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises that employ a high share of women, who represent 54 percent of the tourism workforce, according to the United Nations World Tourism Organization (UNWTO).

Tourism-dependent countries will likely feel the negative impacts of the crisis for much longer than other economies. Contact-intensive services key to the tourism and travel sectors are disproportionately affected by the pandemic and will continue to struggle until people feel safe to travel again. (Adam Behsudi, 2020)

All over the world, tourism-dependent economies are working to finance a broad range of policy measures to soften the impact of plummeting tourism revenues on households and businesses. Cash transfers, grants, tax relief, payroll support, and loan guarantees have been deployed. Banks have also halted loan repayments in some cases. Some countries have focused support on informal workers, who tend to be concentrated in the tourism sector and are highly vulnerable.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Evaluating all these aspects, it is clear that people, travelers, tourists will require and will pay more attention to all the factors that may impact on their health and their medical safety. That is why we initiated this study to

associative structures, with the aim of a closer unity between its members, to protect, develop and promote tourism Romanian, through its objectives, convinced that the means by which it can achieve this goal is the conclusion of

evaluate tourists` requirements regarding hygiene in the hospitality units they stay during their travel. We requested the opinion of 156 tourists that visited the Felix and Băile 1 Mai balneoclimatic resorts, for a minimum 5 days, in the last 2 years. Out of the 156 tourists, 112 were women and 44 were men (all of them being above 18 years of age).

The statistical interpretation of the result was made using the t-Test calculator.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For women, the main factors suggesting a hygienic environment to accommodate during they holydays are: clean toilets, freshly washed white towels, no residues on the floor.

Fig. 1. Main factors that represents sanogenetic requirements for women

Men are more demanding about clean sheets, no dust and clean floor.

Comparing men and women, 88 of female tourist evaluate hygiene based on the aspects they can see, while only 37 of men do the same thing. The rest of them consider other senses (e.g. smell, touch) when it comes to analyze de degree of hygiene.

According to t-Test calculus, this gender differentiation in evaluating environmental factors that are sanogenetic, there is a significant statistical difference ($p < 0,05$).

Fig. 2. Main factors that represents sanogenetic requirements for men

t-Test result:

1. t-Score: 3.9206
2. Standard Error of Difference: 17.9182
3. Degrees of Freedom: 3
4. Two-tailed p-Value: 0.0002
5. Confidence interval: 95%
6. Mean Difference: 70.25
7. Confidence Range: 13.2342-127.2658

When questioned about the attention they give to finding high standards hygiene condition, more than 85% of the tourist are paying more attention to these factors after the Covid pandemic, and they think that the hotels and hospitality units care more about assuring health safety. This is one reason for tourism rehabilitation after Covid pandemic.

According to UN Tourism, international tourism saw stronger than expected results in 2022, backed by large pent-up demand and the lifting or relaxation of travel restrictions in a large number of countries.

Over 900 million tourists travelled internationally in 2022, double those in 2021 though still 37% fewer than in 2019. International tourism recovered 63% of pre-pandemic levels, in line with UNWTO's scenarios published in May 2022.

Europe, the world's largest destination region, recorded 585 million arrivals in 2022 to reach nearly 80% of pre-pandemic levels (-21% over 2019). The Middle East enjoyed the strongest relative increase across regions in 2022 with arrivals climbing to 83% of pre-pandemic numbers (-17% versus 2019).

Africa and the Americas both recovered about 65% of its pre-pandemic visitors, while

Asia and the Pacific reached only 23%, due to stronger pandemic-related restrictions.

By subregions, Western Europe (87%) and the Caribbean (84%) came closest to their pre-pandemic levels.

The year 2022 saw a strong rebound in tourism spending, resulting in the recovery of pre-pandemic levels in income across many destinations. Looking ahead, international tourism is set to consolidate its recovery in 2023, backed by pent-up demand, particularly from Asia and the Pacific as destinations and markets open up.

The UNWTO Panel of Experts survey indicates that 72% of respondents expect better performance in 2023. However, most experts (65%) also believe international tourism will not return to 2019 levels until 2024 or later.

Based on UNWTO's scenarios for 2023, international tourist arrivals could reach 80% to 95% of pre-pandemic levels this year, with Europe and the Middle East expected to reach those levels. However, important risks remain ahead, especially economic and geopolitical.

CONCLUSIONS

The Covid pandemic changed the demands on hygiene services and factors.

Women are tented to evaluate the level of hygiene in a touristic unit by clean bathrooms and utensils provided by the unit.

Tourists are expected to increasingly seek value for money and their traveling orientations are a response to the challenging social-economic environment (taking health influencing factors very seriously).

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DISCOVEREAT: TRAVEL, EAT SHARE DISCOVERING THE WORLD, ONE BITE AT A TIME

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Food tourism has become a booming sector, with cuisine playing a key role in creating memorable travel experiences. According to the World Travel Association's 2022 report, 34% of tourists choose destinations based on their culinary appeal. The global culinary tourism market, worth USD 11.5 billion in 2023, is expected to grow rapidly, highlighting significant opportunities. This paper presents DiscoverEAT, a mobile app for travelers seeking unique cultural experiences through food. Combining a search engine with a social network, DiscoverEAT offers expertly curated 24-hour food tours by local experts, fostering a community of food enthusiasts. The study employs a comprehensive five-step internationalization roadmap, including PEST and Porter's Five Forces analysis, to assess the business environment and competitive landscape. Results indicate that DiscoverEAT can leverage rising disposable incomes, shifting cultural trends, and technological advancements, despite facing challenges from intense competition and new market entrants. The SWOT analysis highlights strengths such as the founders' expertise in food culture while addressing weaknesses like technical skill gaps and language barriers.

Strategic recommendations focus on using DiscoverEAT's strengths to capitalize on opportunities and mitigate threats. DiscoverEAT can differentiate itself in the expanding food tourism market by offering high-quality, tailored culinary guides. The study concludes that DiscoverEAT has the potential to thrive by promoting cultural exchange and preserving culinary traditions through engaging and authentic food experiences.

Keywords: Food tourism, gastronomy, PEST, Porter's Five Forces analysis, SWOT

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INTRODUCTION

Food Tourism has experienced significant growth in recent years, emerging as a vibrant and innovative sector within the tourism industry. As a result, the cuisine of a destination has become a major factor influencing the quality of a traveler's experience.

According to the World Travel Association (WTFA) 2022 Report, 34% of tourists visit places that attract them in terms of cuisine. Also, the report of Grandview research on Culinary Tourism Market Size & Trends estimated that The global culinary tourism market size was at USD 11.5 billion in 2023 and is projected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 19.9% from 2024 to 2030. Therefore, the cuisine of the destination is an aspect of utmost importance in the quality of the holiday experience, where also lies the huge market potential to be explored

Among all the gastronomic activities like participating in cookery workshops, visiting vineyards and meeting local producers, and joining food events and fairs, the trending role of gastronomy is the conversion of the territory into a culinary landscape, which resulted in the growth of gastronomic offerings based on high-quality local products (UNMTO,2012). Tourists who participate in the new trends often contrast with 'everyday' or basic eating, as people search for 'authenticity' and distinction in local food and gastronomy. They are concerned about the origin of products and recognize the value of gastronomy as a means of socializing, a space for sharing life with others and exchanging experiences.

This business idea originates from multiple studies in local food products, cultivated within the MSc Food Identity program. The company leverages a multicultural background and strong

entrepreneurial skills to explore local foods combining both gastronomic and scientific perspectives.

DiscoverEAT is a mobile app for adventurous travelers searching for unique cultural experiences through food. It combines a search engine with a social network. Users can discover expert-designed, 24-hour food tours in any city, following itineraries curated by local experts for a unique culinary adventure. DiscoverEAT aims to build a community where users can share their culinary finds, creating a network of food enthusiasts. By connecting users with hidden gems and local traditions, DiscoverEAT goes beyond food recommendation, promoting cultural exchange and tradition preservation. This analysis focuses on the relevant research literature about food tourism. The paper aims to identify the specific product-market fit that will serve as the starting point for launching this new business.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The main methodology applied for analyzing the project's feasibility and development is the use of an individual road map for business internationalization plans. This methodology supports business development through a five-step, 360-degree approach.

- Development Process Assessment: to analyze the environment of the business it is intended to create and to understand whether there's a market opportunity.
- Products Internationalization Process Assessment: to understand the different variabilities to take into account, including the company setting consumer needs, product offered, need satisfaction, time, and competitors)
- Resources Internationalization Process Assessment: to understand the amount of human resources, materials, equipment, and facilities required - if required.
- Communication Internationalization Process Assessment: to develop the business' visual identity
- Financial Internationalization Process Assessment: to evaluate costs, revenues, and profits.

Each of these analyses focuses on a crucial part when it comes to building up a business, aiming to assess the feasibility of the business idea in the market.

In addition, PEST and Porter's five forces analysis of business market entry were applied based on selected international literature and databases on food tourism. Therefore, various disciplinary approaches and focus of interests and SWOT analysis were identified to set up the market position of our products.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

PEST Analysis: Environmental Influences - business environment in the target market

The assessment of external factors and opportunities for the growth of gastronomic tourism was conducted using the PEST analysis. PEST analysis takes into account key aspects of the external environment: political, economic, social, and technological.

Political

Open Border

Tourism by definition entails crossing borders in one form or another. Thanks to many governments' decisions to open up borders to foreigners, it's easier than ever to travel to new countries. As one of the main achievements of the European project, the Schengen area started in 1985 and covers over 4 million square kilometers with 29 countries. This allows more than 400 million people to travel freely between member countries without going through border controls. Also, a Schengen visa is an entry permit for non-EU nationals to make a short, temporary visit of up to 90 days in any 180 days to a country in the mentioned area.

Tax incentives

Another Political factor impacting the tourism industry across the world is represented by tax incentives. The taxes go towards improving the sector or the destination, such as through promotional activities, improvement, and implementation of public services that affect the destination: cleaning, waste management, etc.

Economic

Rising disposable incomes

Rising disposable incomes are a key driver of tourism growth. According to the World Tourism

Organization's 2019 research, tourism contributes a significant 10.3% to global GDP, with one in ten jobs worldwide linked to the sector. As economies flourish, individuals have more money to spend, leading to increased travel opportunities.

Social

Changing cultural trends:

The World Tourism Association defines culinary tourism as enjoying unique and unforgettable experiences of local food and drink. As local dishes are deeply connected with the culture and traditions of a certain area, gastronomy tourism has become a trend to create truly unique tours for demanding tourists as it is associated with respect for the culture and traditions of the local area, authenticity, sustainable development, and interesting experiences.

Contribution to rural areas

Preserving culture and heritage through traditional dishes is vital as it strongly influences the motivation of tourists. Culinary tourism advancement not only brings in extra income but also creates more job opportunities at the grassroots level, offering employment to local guides and chefs. Furthermore, rural communities can play a role in fostering growth in other sectors of the local economy, particularly agriculture.

Technological

Easy accessibilities

The biggest technological advancement has come from the popularity of mobile electronic devices. Travelers can book their trips on their mobile phones and get more information about their destination experience through social media. The sharing of Food Tour-themed content on social media has also created a buzz, with travelers being inspired to plan local food-themed trips.

Porter's five forces - For competitors' research

Porter's Five Forces model helps in identifying and analyzing the competitive forces that shape an industry. (Gratton P. 2024). This model is applied to DiscoverEAT to understand its position in the culinary tourism market.

Competitive Rivalry

The global culinary tourism market is rapidly expanding, with a size of USD 11.5 billion in 2023 and an anticipated CAGR of 19.9% from 2024 to 2030. This growth attracts numerous competitors, making the market highly competitive. DiscoverEAT faces significant competition from:

Interrail.eu: While primarily a travel service, it offers a 24-hour guide format. However, DiscoverEAT's focus is specifically on food tours, providing a niche advantage.

Get Your Guide: A strong and well-known competitor providing various itineraries, including food trips.

Culture Trip: Offers well-structured 24-hour city trips

Social Media Content Creators: Influencers and bloggers create accessible, short, and effective food guides as well as famous social platforms.

Despite intense competition, DiscoverEAT differentiates itself by offering high-quality, tailored food guides, which helps moderate some competitive pressures.

Threat of New Entrants

The culinary tourism market has low entry barriers due to minimal capital requirements and the abundant availability of information. New entrants can easily enter the market, especially social media content creators who require little initial investment. However, DiscoverEAT intends to leverage its strong community of loyal customers to create a significant barrier to entry. Building strong customer loyalty and a robust network reduces the threat of new entrants.

Supplier Power

DiscoverEAT's suppliers consist of a network of food experts, including students from the MSc Food Identity program, teachers, and other professionals who provide 24-hour guides. With around 200 suppliers, DiscoverEAT can ensure a steady supply of high-quality content. Once the content is created, suppliers act mainly as consultants, reducing their bargaining power. The extensive network also enhances content reliability and feasibility, giving DiscoverEAT a competitive advantage.

Customer Power

Customers exercise significant power in the culinary tourism market due to the high availability of alternatives. They can drive prices

and demand better quality due to the vast amount of information and competing services. However, DiscoverEAT targets a specific niche, offering specialized advice to its target market, which can help retain customers despite high bargaining power.

Threat of Substitutes

The threat of substitutes is high as customers can easily switch to other platforms or services offering similar guides. Major substitutes include:

Tripadvisor: A well-established platform for restaurant reviews.

Lonely Planet: Renowned for its complete travel guides available in both print and digital formats.

Michelin Guide: A prestigious guide known for its restaurant recommendations worldwide.

Despite these substitutes, DiscoverEAT aims to provide unique, high-quality food guides tailored specifically to its target market, reducing the possibility of customers switching to substitutes.

RESULTS

In an expanding industry like the food industry, competition is usually less dramatic because the market grows so fast that competitors have little need to fight for customers.

However, even if the service given by the platform could be very similar to the ones already given by others, DiscoverEAT offers a unique service that distinguishes them from the high-quality tailored food guides, reducing competitive rivalry.

SWOT- For market positioning

The SWOT Analysis is applied to assess and understand the internal and external forces that may create opportunities or threats for DiscoverEAT (Figure 1)

Internal Strengths

DiscoverEAT is founded by MSc Food Identity students, providing a solid background in food and food culture. The creators' multicultural academic environment fosters a robust network of industry experts. Additionally, the team exhibits resilience and fast learning, crucial traits for growth and innovation in a competitive market.

Internal Weaknesses

However, the team lacks technical skills in software development and business startup processes, leading to significant challenges in the initial phases of the project. Moreover, a language barrier exists as many local individuals do not speak English, which could limit customer engagement and communication. The absence of investment capital surely represents a weakness for DiscoverEAT's development and expansion.

External Opportunities

The culinary tourism market presents significant opportunities for DiscoverEAT. Culinary journey bookings increased by 40% from 2022 to 2023, reflecting a growing interest in this niche. Market growth projections are also favorable, with the culinary tourism sector expected to expand from USD 1.1 billion in 2023 to over USD 1.79 billion by 2027. These trends indicate a burgeoning market with ample room for new entrants like DiscoverEAT.

External Threats

Contrary to this, DiscoverEAT faces substantial threats from established competitors and substitutes. Well-developed platforms such as Get Your Guide offer complete tourism services. These competitors have already captured significant market share and possess extensive resources to maintain their position.

Strategic Recommendations for DiscoverEAT

Using Strengths to Maximize Opportunities

By utilizing their multicultural experiences, the team can design immersive and authentic cultural experiences that set DiscoverEAT apart from competitors

Using Strengths to Minimize Threats

To mitigate the threats, DiscoverEAT should develop a focused marketing strategy targeting niche segments of the market, such as young travelers seeking unique culinary experiences. This targeted approach can help avoid direct competition with larger platforms. Additionally, delivering high-quality, well-researched guides and tours will build a loyal customer base, reducing the probability of switching to competitors.

Minimizing Weaknesses by Taking Advantage of Opportunities

Investing time in market research is crucial for DiscoverEAT to understand the latest trends in culinary tourism and develop content that aligns with these trends. It is also important to form strategic partnerships with local experts, chefs, and food bloggers to enhance the quality and attractiveness of the content. Furthermore, it may be helpful to schedule sessions with business counselors to help the team in the startup process and ensure continuous improvement.

Minimizing Weaknesses by Avoiding Threats
To overcome the internal weaknesses, DiscoverEAT should engage in fast learning programs to acquire essential skills in software development and business management, while working with experienced professionals. Additionally, exploring funding opportunities such as grants, scholarships, and startup incubators will be the primary strategy to secure the necessary capital for growth.

Figure 1 SWOT Analysis

CONCLUSIONS

Following the PEST analysis, a variety of beneficial factors have been identified as influencing the tourism sector. The opening of borders and tax incentives are key to establishing strong governmental support for tourism. Moreover, economic changes such as rising disposable incomes are making travel more attainable. Sociocultural factors like changing cultural trends and increased contributions to rural areas are also helping to preserve culture and heritage, while the popularity of mobile electronic devices is enhancing the accessibility of gastronomy tourism.

Through the Porter Five Forces analysis, the existing market situation was analyzed. In the face of Gastronomy Tourism, the main competitors in Competitive Rivalry are the online proxy platform (Online Travel Agency)

and social media content creators (Influencers). Participation in the market threshold is at a moderate level, while a certain amount of start-up capital support is needed to complete the cold start of the company. At Supplier Power, a strong expert support team building content barriers is recognized. Customer Power meets consumer-oriented principles in the travel industry. Combined with early market analysis, the positioning is the Niche segment, with a focus on providing a unique service that is distinct for the high-quality tailored food guides to reduce competitive risks.

SWOT analysis has helped to build product positioning and development strategies: expanding the market by providing unique expert support for cross-cultural eating experiences, doing market industry research to update product content sharing at any time, and building community connections and brand barriers.

Through the above three types of analysis, a clear understanding of the macro-environment and

micro-market analysis of DiscoverEAT was given, and in this regard, the product positioning and market strategy were established, giving a more holistic view of the product's internationalization assessments and the project's feasibility.

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ENHANCING RURAL SUSTAINABILITY THROUGH ROBOTICS-ENABLED CORN CULTIVATION IN THE WESTERN PLAIN OF ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The agricultural sector is facing unprecedented challenges in meeting the global demand for food while ensuring sustainability and efficiency. The advent of precision agriculture methodologies, combined with innovative technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data, Cloud computing, and robotics, has led to the emergence of Farming 4.0 solutions. These technological advancements have revolutionized farming, enabling a more efficient, precise, and sustainable approach to food production.

One key technology that has emerged as a critical component of Farming 4.0 is robotics. Robots in agriculture can revolutionize the industry, enabling the automation of various tasks, such as planting, monitoring, and harvesting crops. They can also analyze data to provide insights that help farmers make better decisions. Robotics in agriculture has several advantages, including increased productivity, reduced labor costs, and improved yields. Furthermore, robots can work in hazardous conditions unsuitable for human labor, reducing the risk of injury and enhancing safety. This paper provides an overview of the use of robots in agricultural machines and outlines their future direction in corn cultivation technology in the Western Plain of Romania. Based on selection criteria specific to the area, a set of robots has been identified that can be recommended for corn cultivation technology, particularly for organic crops. The results of this study demonstrate the significant potential of robotics in agriculture to enhance the production process and ensure sustainable food production.

Keywords: Farming 4.0, IoT, precision agriculture, robots for agriculture.

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INTRODUCTION

The contemporary agricultural landscape is confronted with unprecedented challenges arising from rapid population expansion, environmental degradation, and the intricacies of global food systems. Regulatory bodies and stakeholders globally are increasingly embracing innovative solutions, mainly digital and robotic technologies, to revolutionize agricultural practices and ensure food security.

Projections estimate that the world's population will approach 8.5 billion by 2030 and increase by 1.18 billion in the subsequent two decades, reaching 9.7 billion by 2050 (United Nations, 2022). Satisfying the dietary needs of this growing population demands an increase in food production by 59-98 percent. This gradual growth trajectory underscores the pivotal role of leveraging technological innovations such as artificial intelligence (AI) and robotics to bolster agricultural sustainability and address the evolving demands of an expanding populace.

Agriculture is currently experiencing what is known as the "Digital Revolution." This

presents a significant opportunity to improve the lives and livelihoods of farmers worldwide. The UNDP's "Precision Agriculture for Smallholder Farmers" initiative aims to explain and contextualize the emerging innovative digital farming technologies (UNDP, 2021). This initiative focuses on smallholder farmers in developing countries, providing an overview of the data-driven farming technologies driving the digital revolution. The initiative also highlights the primary challenges that hinder the widespread adoption of these technologies and provides recommendations and important considerations to overcome these obstacles.

The agricultural industry has been actively embracing various forms of robotic technology to enhance productivity while minimizing costs. Automated tractors and combines guided by GPS have been widely adopted for precision agriculture, aiming to optimize resource usage. Additionally, there is a growing experimental utilization of autonomous systems for tasks including pruning, thinning, mowing, spraying, and weeding (European Commission, 2021). Sensor technology plays a crucial role in

managing pests and diseases that impact crop yields.

Concurrently, digital technologies are progressively improving the affordability and accessibility of precision agriculture solutions, extending their benefits to smallholder farmers in developing nations. These advancements encompass remote sensing methodologies facilitated by satellites and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), as well as the integration of sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies. Moreover, agricultural robots leverage variable rate technology to optimize resource usage and enhance productivity. These technological advancements are underpinned by developments in data processing and analytics, including the utilization of machine learning (ML) algorithms. Such applications are pivotal in fostering sustainability and promoting organic agricultural production, thereby contributing to the production of healthy food.

Prominent regulatory bodies across the globe, Australia included, are proactively engaging in comprehensive initiatives aimed at implementing sustainable AI-driven technologies. These efforts encompass a wide range of strategic measures and policy frameworks designed to foster the development, deployment, and utilization of AI robotics in a manner that prioritizes environmental sustainability, social responsibility, and ethical considerations.

The "Digital Foundations for Agriculture Strategy," crafted by the Australian Government's Department of Agriculture Water, and the Environment, encompasses a holistic approach aimed at revolutionizing the Australian agricultural sector through the integration of cutting-edge AI and robotics technologies. The primary objective is to ensure the sustainability and competitiveness of the agricultural market while promoting organic and environmentally friendly practices. The strategy recognizes the significant impact of farm machinery automation on operational efficiency and reliance on manual labor while also highlighting the importance of edge-of-field monitoring technologies in documenting the quality of runoff water on farms, reducing costs, and enabling targeted improvements to environmental management practices (Australian Government, 2022).

In addition, the strategy emphasizes the enhanced functionality of satellite technology for remote monitoring of agricultural activities. This includes measuring field areas, identifying crop

types, assessing groundcover percentage, geolocating landscape features, and evaluating environmental impacts, all of which are essential for informed decision-making and sustainable land management. Traceability and digital logistics services play a crucial role in streamlining agrifood supply chains, providing transparent and trustworthy information to consumers, producers, and other stakeholders. Robotics technology such as drone farming and intelligent livestock monitoring technologies contribute to cost-effective remote monitoring and early disease detection, improving animal welfare and overall farm productivity. Soil carbon sequestration initiatives are also recognized as having significant potential to improve farm productivity, enhance resilience to climate change, and create new market opportunities for land managers (Australian Government, 2022).

Additional initiatives by the Australian Government aimed at fostering sustainable agricultural practices are delineated in the "National Agricultural Statement Innovation Policy" (Australian Government, 2021) and CSIRO's analysis on "The Future of Australia's Agricultural Workforce" (CSIRO, 2019). These documents underscore the government's commitment to leveraging robotics and artificial intelligence (AI) technologies to advance the sustainability agenda in agriculture.

This research endeavor delves into the feasibility of incorporating AI-powered robotic solutions in corn cultivation to foster sustainability within the rural regions of the Western Plain of Romania. By conducting a comprehensive examination of the regulatory framework and successful deployment of robotic solutions in agriculture across diverse geographical regions, this study aims to offer valuable insights to policymakers, stakeholders, and practitioners regarding the advantages and obstacles associated with integrating AI-enabled robotics in agricultural contexts. The research methodology employed encompasses empirical analysis and case studies, drawing upon data sourced from farmers, agricultural institutions, and government agencies. Additionally, a central tenet of this study is the advocacy for responsible and sustainable deployment practices of AI and robotics in agriculture.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study was initiated by thoroughly examining the global agricultural robotics market to identify optimal solutions for fostering organic corn cultivation in the Western Plain of Romania. Companies such as Naïo Technologies, AGROINTELLI, AGXEED, Digital workbench, Softivert, EarthAutomations, AutoAgri, Oxin, SwarmFarm were meticulously examined for their multifunctional robotics offerings, encompassing models such as Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, Digital workbench's Tipard 1800, Softivert's SoftiRover e-K18, EarthAutomations's Dood, AutoAgri's ICS20, Oxin's Smart Machine and SwarmFarm's SwarmBot, are proficient in executing diverse tasks ranging from soil preparation to weeding and early-stage plant management. Moreover, specialized solutions focusing on weed control were explored from Pixelfarming, Hari Tech, Carré, FarmWise, Kilter, Solinftec, Andela, Hari Tech, Exobotix, FarmDroid, Carbon Robotics, Aigro and Ekobot, while companies like FieldRobotics, Monarch, Sitia's TREKTOR and Amos underwent evaluation for their autonomous tractor solutions. In this context, we also explored the capabilities of the H.S.S. AgBot 2.055W3 + CF2000-AB, Jacto's Arbus 4000 JAV, Robotics Plus's Prospr and GUSS for the fertilization process, alongside the Small Robot Co's Tom v4 and XAG R150 for the process of crop monitoring. Noteworthy was the innovative all-in-one solution from NEXAT, engineered to oversee all aspects of sunflower cultivation. The study also considered emerging projects such as Ecorobotix's AVO spraying robot, Nexus's weeding solutions, Rowbot's fertilizing robot and Bluewhite company's autonomous tractor endeavor. Furthermore, attention was devoted to solutions facilitating data collection, exemplified by TERRA-MEPP's TerraSentia robot, Digital workbench's Tipard 350 and DJI's Mavic 3M, with the aim of enhancing precision agriculture practices.

Simultaneously an exhaustive exploration was conducted into sustainability policies within the agricultural domain, with a specific emphasis on the European Union (EU). This analysis included the development of a sustainable bioenergy policy tailored for the EU post-2020, stressing the imperative need to promote the efficient and sustainable utilization of organic biomass resources for bioenergy production (CEMA, 2016). Key considerations within this

policy formulation encompassed climate and energy targets.

Additionally, the study incorporated compliance with the European Organic Farming Regulation, mandating adherence to stringent organic farming standards (European Parliament, 2018) while also adopting FAO's endorsement for best practices aimed at advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (FAO, 2020). Insights from the Position Paper on EU Carbon Farming underscored the pivotal role of intelligent agricultural machinery in advancing organic carbon farming methodologies, advocating for policy measures and technology adoption to facilitate sustainable organic corn cultivation (CEMA, 2024). The research also incorporates insights from IFOAM on organic farming and biodiversity, addressing increased biodiversity abundance and richness across habitats and farming types, positive impacts on soil microbial diversity, and the adoption of biodiversity-enhancing practices like mixed farming systems and diverse rotations (IFOAM, 2020).

Furthermore, in pursuit of achieving self-sufficient energy and mitigating carbon emissions, the designated cultivation farm implemented a biogas generator harnessing onsite organic waste for electricity generation and power for high-capacity agricultural machinery, particularly for crop transportation. Aligned with these sustainability objectives, all farm infrastructure will be equipped with a photovoltaic panel system for energy generation, complemented by energy storage capabilities, thereby further reinforcing sustainable practices within the agricultural framework.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this segment, we conduct a thorough investigation into the practical consequences and contextual complexities linked to incorporating robotic technologies into the methods of cultivating corn, particularly focusing on the agricultural settings of the Western Plain of Romania. The chapter presents a multi-dimensional exploration into the various aspects of robotic involvement throughout different stages of corn farming. It is distinguished by a meticulous examination of their operational subtleties, and environmental impacts, thus providing deep understanding into how robotics could revolutionize agricultural practices.

Robots for Data Collection

Before initiating any cultivation procedures, it's imperative to gather essential data crucial for training the robotic systems. This data acquisition process involves the utilization of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) such as the DJI Mavic 3M (<https://ag.dji.com/mavic3m?site=ag&from=nav>) for aerial mapping of the designated area. These UAVs enable comprehensive aerial surveys, providing crucial insights into the terrain and environmental factors that influence cultivation (Figure 1).

Figure 1 DJI's Mavic 3M area mapping drone (<https://ag.dji.com/>)

Additionally, ground-level data collection is facilitated by field robots like the TerraSentia (<https://www.earthsense.co/terrasentia>), or Tipard 350 (<https://digital-workbench.de/en/portfolio-item/tipard-350/>).

These robots traverse through the fields, gathering detailed information about soil composition, moisture levels, and other pertinent parameters. When equipped with swarm capabilities, TerraSentia robots can collaborate and operate in groups, allowing them to cover larger areas more efficiently and collect data from diverse locations simultaneously (Figure 2).

By employing both aerial and ground-based technologies, a holistic dataset is obtained, ensuring the robots are equipped with accurate and comprehensive information essential for optimizing cultivation processes. This collaborative approach not only enhances the speed and scope of data gathering but also improves the robustness and reliability of the collected data, ultimately leading to more informed decision-making and more effective agricultural management practices. Furthermore, this data collection process allows for the identification of potential challenges such as weed infestations and disease outbreaks. By analyzing the gathered data, one can anticipate the types of weeds that might proliferate in the area and the diseases that crops are susceptible to. Armed with this knowledge, farmers can implement targeted strategies for weed control and disease management, minimizing yield losses and promoting crop health. Moreover, leveraging the collected data, digital twin

training of the robots can be conducted before even setting foot in the field. Digital twins are virtual replicas of physical assets or processes, in this case, the agricultural environment. By simulating various scenarios based on the gathered data, the robots can undergo extensive training in a virtual environment, honing their capabilities and refining their algorithms to navigate and operate efficiently in the real-world field conditions. This proactive approach to training ensures that the robots are well-prepared and optimized for the specific challenges and dynamics of the agricultural landscape, maximizing their effectiveness and productivity from the outset.

Figure 2 TERRA-MEPP's TerraSentia field robot (<https://www.earthsense.co/>)

Importantly, integrating robotic technologies into agriculture not only enhances productivity and efficiency but also contributes to sustainability efforts. By precisely targeting inputs such as water, fertilizers, and pesticides based on real-time data and predictive analytics, robotic systems help minimize resource wastage and environmental impact, promoting more sustainable farming practices for the future.

Robots for Soil Preparation

The utilization of robotic technologies, spearheaded by companies such as Naïo Technologies (<https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/home/>), AGROINTELLI (<https://agrointelli.com/>), AGXEE (<https://www.agxeed.com/>), Digital Workbench (<https://digitalworkbench.de/en/home-2022/>), Softivert (<https://www.preciagri.com/>), Earth Automations (<https://www.Earthautomations.com/homeen/>), Auto Agri (<https://autoagri.no/>), Oxin (<https://>

(<http://www.oxin.nz/>), and SwarmFarm (<https://www.swarmfarm.com/>), has revolutionized the soil preparation process in corn cultivation. Notable robotic systems in this domain include Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, Digital Workbench's Tipard 1800, Softivert's SoftiRover e-K18, EarthAutomations's Dood, AutoAgri's ICS20, Oxin's Smart Machine, and SwarmFarm's SwarmBot. These sophisticated machines are pivotal in optimizing agricultural efficiency, sustainability, and productivity.

The rationale behind employing these robotic systems stems from their remarkable capability to execute precise and repetitive tasks with minimal human intervention. Such precision not only diminishes labor expenses but also mitigates adverse effects like soil compaction and erosion, thereby fostering enhanced soil health and bolstering crop yields. Furthermore, these robots are endowed with advanced sensing and navigation systems, enabling them to operate autonomously amidst the intricacies of dynamic agricultural environments.

In the soil preparation process for corn cultivation, these robotic systems collaborate harmoniously with precision implements from MONOSEM and PÖTTINGER, premier manufacturers of agricultural equipment known for their commitment to sustainable farming practices. Specifically, implements such as precision min-till or no-till cultivators are seamlessly integrated with the robots, facilitating meticulous soil cultivation tailored to the specific requisites of corn cultivation without disturbing the soil structure. This meticulous approach ensures optimal plant spacing, uniform soil structure, and effective weed control, culminating in maximized crop growth and yield potential while minimizing soil disturbance. By employing no-till practices, these precision implements preserve soil health by reducing erosion, maintaining soil moisture, and retaining organic matter. Additionally, the integration of no-till practices into the robotic soil preparation process reduces fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions associated with conventional tillage operations, further enhancing the sustainability of corn cultivation. Thus, the seamless integration of robotic systems with precision implements, particularly those designed for no-till practices, represents a comprehensive approach to soil preparation for corn cultivation that optimizes

both productivity and environmental stewardship.

In the context of soil preparation for corn cultivation, the integration of swarm robotics and digital twin training further solidifies the sustainable and efficient practices enabled by robotic systems. Notable examples from the list of robots mentioned earlier, such as Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, and SwarmFarm's SwarmBot (Figure 3), exemplify the advancements in this field. Swarm robotics, a concept where multiple robots operate collaboratively in coordinated groups, significantly enhances the efficacy of soil preparation processes. These robots work in unison to cover larger expanses more efficiently, expediting task completion while minimizing energy consumption. By distributing tasks among multiple units, swarm robotics optimizes resource utilization and reduces the overall environmental footprint of agricultural operations.

Figure 3 **SwarmFarm's SwarmBot multipurposed robot** (<https://www.swarmfarm.com/>)

Moreover, this collaborative paradigm enhances system resilience, as the failure of individual units does not disrupt the overall workflow, ensuring continuous operation even in the face of technical issues or obstacles. Furthermore, the integration of digital twin training enhances the precision and effectiveness of soil preparation activities. This proactive approach ensures that robots are well-prepared and optimized for the specific challenges and dynamics of soil preparation for corn cultivation.

Together, the integration of swarm robotics and digital twin training, exemplified by robots such as Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, and SwarmFarm's SwarmBot, augments the efficiency and sustainability of robotic soil preparation

processes for corn cultivation. By leveraging collaborative robotics and advanced simulation techniques, agricultural operations can achieve higher productivity levels while minimizing environmental impact, thus fostering long-term sustainability and resilience in agricultural systems. Additionally, the strategic use of photovoltaic panels for harnessing solar energy further reduces reliance on fossil fuels, mitigating carbon emissions and aligning with sustainable farming practices.

Robots for Seeding

In the realm of corn seeding, robotics play a pivotal role in enhancing efficiency and precision. Alongside Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, and AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, several other robots and implements contribute significantly to the process.

Digital Workbench's Tipard 1800 is an autonomous multi-carrier platform meticulously crafted for the seamless automation of entire process chains, with a particular focus on corn seeding within arable farming. This innovative robot is designed to elevate performance, minimize environmental impact, and offer multifunctional versatility, especially in the context of corn cultivation. With its five implement spaces, the Tipard 1800 delivers unparalleled flexibility, allowing for the integration of various implements tailored specifically for corn seeding tasks. One of its standout features lies in its integration of advanced seed metering technology, ensuring precise seed placement while minimizing waste. This capability is paramount in optimizing germination rates and achieving uniform crop emergence, crucial factors for maximizing corn yields. The Tipard 1800's efficiency is further underscored by its ability to cover vast areas with exceptional speed and accuracy. This makes it exceptionally well-suited for large-scale corn seeding operations, where timely planting is essential for optimizing yield potential. Whether it's planting corn in expansive fields or intricate planting configurations, the Tipard 1800 rises to the challenge with unmatched efficiency and precision. Moreover, the Tipard 1800 offers flexibility in its drive train type, with options for both pure electric and diesel-electric configurations. This versatility allows farmers to adapt the robot's operation to suit their specific needs and preferences. Depending on the chosen configuration, the Tipard 1800 can operate purely electrically or as a hybrid vehicle with a

diesel generator, providing up to 24 hours of continuous operation. This ensures uninterrupted seeding operations, even in remote or off-grid locations.

Softivert's SoftiRover e-K18 stands out for its versatility and adaptability, embodying a significant leap forward in agricultural technology. Developed by Softivert, a leader in the agricultural technology space, this robot is engineered to optimize large-scale crop production, including corn seeding, among other tasks. Equipped with interchangeable seeding modules, the SoftiRover e-K18 seamlessly transitions between different crops, including corn. This capability reflects the robot's commitment to enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and precision in farming operations. By maintaining precision and consistency in seed placement, the SoftiRover e-K18 ensures optimal conditions for corn germination and emergence, crucial factors in maximizing yield potential. The robot's precision in hoeing and seeding allows for meticulous weed management and optimal seed placement, contributing to improved crop health and productivity. Softivert has a legacy of innovation and sustainability in agricultural technology, consistently pushing the boundaries of what's possible in agricultural automation. The SoftiRover e-K18 is a testament to this commitment, designed to meet the complex demands of modern farming while reducing labor and environmental footprint associated with traditional practices.

AutoAgri's ICS20 is another notable robot designed for corn seeding tasks. With its robust construction and advanced navigation capabilities, the ICS20 can operate effectively in various field conditions, ensuring reliable performance throughout the seeding season. Moreover, the ICS20 integrates an electric drivetrain, enabling it to carry many different implements currently available in the market. This versatility allows farmers to utilize a wide range of seeding implements tailored to their specific needs and preferences. Additionally, AutoAgri recognizes the importance of electrification in future farming practices and is committed to offering both fully electric and plug-in hybrid versions of the ICS20. This dedication to electrification aligns with the industry's shift towards sustainable agriculture, providing farmers with environmentally friendly options to enhance efficiency and productivity in corn seeding operations (Figure 4).

These robots, along with their associated implements, revolutionize the corn seeding process by providing farmers with precise, efficient, and labor-saving solutions. By leveraging automation and robotics, farmers can optimize seed placement, reduce input costs, and maximize yields, contributing to sustainable agriculture practices and food security.

Figure 4 AutoAgri's ICS20 multipurposed robot
(<https://autoagri.no/>)

Robots for Phytosanitary Treatments and Fertilizer Application

For the phytosanitary treatments and fertilizer application in corn cultivation, sustainability takes center stage with innovative robotic solutions such as the H.S.S. AgBot 2.055W3+CF2000-AB (<https://holspraying.com/>), Jacto's Arbus 4000 JAV (<https://jacto.com/europe>) and GUSS (<https://gussag.com/>) with their cutting-edge technology for precise phytosanitary treatments and fertilizer application.

Moreover, Robotics Plus's Prospr (<https://www.roboticsplus.co.nz/>) sets a new standard for sustainable fertilizer application in corn cultivation. Utilizing advanced sensing and AI technologies, this robot precisely targets fertilizer application, optimizing nutrient uptake and minimizing waste. Its autonomous operation ensures efficient use of resources, contributing to environmentally responsible farming practices. In the context of corn cultivation, Prospr serves as a pivotal tool, enhancing sustainability and efficiency throughout the fertilizer application process. With its modular architecture, Prospr seamlessly adapts to the dynamic needs of corn fields, rotating multiple tools and attachments to optimize fertilizer application. The platform's autonomous implement carrier capability revolutionizes corn cultivation by offering precise and targeted fertilizer application. Equipped with four quick

release couplings and a four-fan Q4 sprayer based on Croplands Quantum technology, Prospr ensures uniform coverage while minimizing chemical usage. Prospr's innovative design includes a pivoting point between the drive unit and the implement, enabling optimal adaptation to varying soil conditions commonly found in corn fields. Additionally, repositioned LiDAR sensors provide side views and blind spot detection, enhancing safety and efficiency during operation. The fully electric drivetrain, powered by a Tier 4 diesel generator, ensures seamless operation across corn fields, optimizing energy usage while minimizing environmental impact. With an approximate range of 24 hours per tank of fuel, Prospr maximizes efficiency throughout the fertilizer application process, contributing to sustainable corn cultivation practices. Prospr's dimensions, turning radius, and spray tank capacity are meticulously designed to meet the specific requirements of corn cultivation. Its precise application rate of 180 liters per 2,680 hectares ensures optimal nutrient distribution, promoting healthy corn growth and maximizing yields.

Figure 5 Robotics Plus's Prospr spraying robot
(<https://www.roboticsplus.co.nz/>)

Robots for Weed Elimination

In the dynamic world of corn cultivation, a vibrant spectrum of cutting-edge weeding robots from leading companies like Pixel farming (<https://pixelfarmingrobotics.com/>), HariTech (<https://hari-tech.com/>), Carré (<https://www.carre.fr/en/>), FarmWise (<https://farmwise.io/>), Kilter (<https://www.kiltersystems.com/>), Solinftec (<https://www.solinftec.com/en-us/>), Andela (<https://www.andela-tni.nl/en/>), Exobotix (<https://www.exobotic.com/>), FarmDroid (<https://farmdroid.com/>), Carbon Robotics (<https://carbonrobotics.com/>), Aigro (https://www.aigro.nl/index_en.html) and Ekobot (<https://www.ekobot.se/>) are transforming traditional weed management practices. These innovative solutions harmonize advanced robotics, AI algorithms, and precision cultivation techniques to revolutionize weed control while

championing environmental sustainability. These robots operate autonomously, gracefully navigating corn fields with the aid of high-resolution imaging and real-time weed detection technologies. Their precision targeting ensures weeds are removed with surgical accuracy, reducing the need for herbicides, and promoting eco-friendly farming methods. Each robot, whether it's Hari Tech's autonomous navigation system or Carré's (Figure 6) customizable configurations, offers bespoke solutions to the unique challenges of weed management in corn cultivation.

Figure 6 Carré's ANATIS weeding robot
(<https://www.carre.fr/en/>)

Through seamless integration of robotics and AI, these solutions streamline weed control, enhancing efficiency and productivity in corn fields. Farmers reap the benefits of reduced labor costs and increased yield potential as these robots efficiently combat weeds while preserving the health and vigor of corn crops. With their scalable designs and adaptable functionalities, these weeding robots herald a more sustainable future in corn cultivation, where weed-free fields and abundant harvests coexist harmoniously with environmental stewardship.

Robots and Drones for Crop Monitoring

In the realm of precision agriculture, Small Robot Co's Tom v4 (<https://smallrobotco.com/>) and XAG R150 (<https://www.xa.com/en>) stand as exemplars of innovation, reshaping the landscape of crop monitoring with their advanced capabilities. Tom v4 and XAG R150 (Figure 7) represent a convergence of cutting-edge technology and agricultural expertise, offering farmers unprecedented insights into their crops' health and productivity. Equipped with state-of-the-art sensors and intelligent algorithms, these autonomous robots navigate agricultural landscapes with ease, traversing fields while capturing high-resolution imagery

and multispectral data. Their autonomous navigation systems, bolstered by GPS and obstacle avoidance technology, ensure efficient field coverage while avoiding obstacles in real-time. By analyzing this data, Tom v4 and XAG R150 provide farmers with actionable insights, from detecting pest infestations to monitoring crop growth trends, enabling informed decision-making and optimized resource usage. Furthermore, these robots are highly customizable, supporting a myriad of applications tailored to individual farm requirements, whether it's monitoring crop health, mapping soil moisture levels, or optimizing irrigation practices. Integration with precision farming systems further amplifies their utility, enabling seamless data synchronization with other agricultural machinery and management software, streamlining operations, and maximizing efficiency.

Figure 7 XAG R150 monitoring robot
(<https://www.xa.com/en>)

In an era defined by the imperative for sustainable agriculture and resource optimization, Small Robot Co's Tom v4 and XAG R150 emerge as indispensable allies for modern farmers, heralding a future of enhanced productivity and environmental stewardship in agriculture.

Potential Robot for Harvesting

In an endeavor to revolutionize agricultural machinery, LINTTAS Electric Company, a forward-thinking start-up headquartered in South Australia, is on the brink of unveiling a groundbreaking innovation: the world's inaugural fully electric combine harvester. This ambitious undertaking, underpinned by a commitment to sustainability, is poised to fundamentally alter the paradigm of grain harvesting, ushering in a new epoch

characterized by enhanced efficiency, ecological consciousness, and technological prowess.

At its core, LINTTAS's electric combine epitomizes a convergence of cutting-edge technology and visionary design. Through the meticulous development of innovative grain separation processes, this pioneering harvester is meticulously crafted to deliver unparalleled speed and precision in corn harvesting. Its distinguishing features not only encompass heightened operational efficiency but also robust environmental credentials, boasting lower energy consumption and reduced operational costs that position it as a vanguard of sustainability within modern agriculture. However, LINTTAS acknowledges that genuine innovation transcends the machinery itself and extends to its seamless integration into agricultural workflows. Thus, we advocate for the exploration of strategic collaborations with industry stalwarts such as Trimble and John Deere. Through the incorporation of their state-of-the-art autosteer kits, there exists the potential to elevate the harvester's autonomy and efficiency to hitherto unprecedented levels, thereby paving the way for fully automated corn harvesting. Envision a scenario where autonomous harvesters traverse fields with consummate ease, guided by precision technology to optimize yield and minimize waste. This aspirational vision, while seemingly futuristic, is attainable through judicious partnerships and innovative breakthroughs. Such collaborations represent a significant milestone in agricultural technology, heralding a paradigm shift towards heightened productivity alongside a concomitant reduction in the ecological footprint of farming operations.

Figure 8 Linttas electric combine
(<https://linttas.com/>)

Moreover, the advent of fully automated corn harvesting portends profound implications for the sustainability of agriculture. By streamlining operations and diminishing

reliance on manual labor, it not only enhances operational efficiency but also mitigates the environmental ramifications associated with traditional farming methods. Reduced fuel consumption, diminished soil compaction, and optimized resource utilization are among the myriad positive outcomes that stand to be realized through the embrace of autonomous harvesting. In essence, the manifold benefits of embracing autonomous technology in agriculture are both extensive and far-reaching. By leveraging the expertise of industry luminaries and pushing the boundaries of innovation, LINTTAS Electric Company endeavors to spearhead a veritable revolution in farming practices, wherein sustainability and efficiency stand as symbiotic pillars. Let us, therefore, collectively embark upon this transformative journey towards a greener, more prosperous future for agriculture and the planet at large.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study presents a comprehensive examination of the global agricultural robotics market and its implications for fostering organic corn cultivation, particularly in the Western Plain of Romania. Through meticulous analysis of various companies and their multifunctional robotics offerings, ranging from soil preparation to crop monitoring and weed control, the study sheds light on the diverse technological landscape available for enhancing agricultural practices worldwide. Moreover, it emphasizes the significance of sustainability policies within the agricultural domain, with a focus on the European Union (EU), underscoring the importance of promoting organic farming standards and aligning with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for a more inclusive and equitable agricultural sector. Insights gleaned from organizations such as CEMA, the European Parliament, FAO, and IFOAM highlight the pivotal role of intelligent agricultural machinery in advancing organic carbon farming methodologies and biodiversity-enhancing practices. By incorporating robotic technologies into different stages of corn cultivation, including data collection, soil preparation, seeding, phytosanitary treatments, weed elimination, and crop monitoring, farmers can leverage these innovations to revolutionize agricultural practices on a global scale.

Furthermore, the integration of renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic panels and biogas generators further reinforces the commitment to sustainability within the agricultural framework, aligning with the objectives of achieving self-sufficiency in energy and mitigating carbon emissions. This holistic approach not only addresses the immediate needs of agricultural productivity but also ensures long-term environmental resilience and social equity. In light of this, the innovative efforts of LINTTAS Electric Company in developing the world's first fully electric combine harvester present a compelling case for advancing sustainable agricultural practices. By integrating cutting-edge technology and visionary design, LINTTAS's electric combine epitomizes a convergence of efficiency, eco-consciousness, and technological prowess. Today, the sustainability of agriculture reflects the approach aimed at incorporating Industry 5.0 values (a human-centric approach for digital technologies, up-skilling and re-skilling European workers, particularly digital skills, modern, resource-efficient and sustainable industries and transition to a circular economy, a globally competitive and world-leading industry, speeding up investment in research and innovation) in what will be called Agriculture 5.0 (European Commission, 2022).

Overall, the study underscores the transformative potential of robotic technologies in advancing organic corn cultivation practices, enhancing efficiency, productivity, and sustainability in agricultural systems. By embracing these technological innovations and aligning with sustainable farming principles, farmers worldwide can navigate the complexities of modern agriculture while contributing to environmental stewardship, social inclusion, and food security goals for present and future generations.

Drones are starting to become a pillar of modern agriculture and are vastly used in the Western Plain of Romania, in turn making agriculture a more precise and stable endeavor. This year Bigger agricultural companies are starting to either adopt the usage of robots are starting to be interested in adapting them, it is also speculated that smaller companies and farms will be starting to adopt robots as early as

next year since that's when robots will become more affordable and mainstream.

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ROBOTIC SOLUTIONS IN SUNFLOWER CULTIVATION FOR AN INCREASED SUSTAINABILITY IN RURAL AREAS OF THE WESTERN PLAIN OF ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

As the global demand for food production continues to increase, there is a pressing need to explore sustainable solutions that can accelerate innovation in agriculture. One such solution is Farming 4.0, which incorporates cutting-edge technologies like the Internet of Things (IoT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data analytics, Cloud Computing, renewable energy sources, modernized battery technologies, and agricultural robotics.

Farming 4.0 aims to revolutionize farming methods by adopting precision techniques to increase efficiency and productivity while minimizing resource waste and maximizing crop yields. This transformation is a significant shift in the agricultural sector, offering a more sustainable and efficient approach to meet the rising demands of the global food market.

Within this context, autonomous tractors and agricultural machinery, battery-centric energy solutions, and the integration of robotic and drone technologies for agricultural applications are some of the pivotal technological breakthroughs. Additionally, direct communication among agricultural machinery and centralized data storage in Cloud-based software applications drive Farming 4.0's operational advancements.

The primary objective of this article is to investigate the prospective applications of agricultural robotics in sunflower cultivation across the Western Plains of Romania. The selection criteria for the recommended robots are meticulously tailored to meet the region's unique characteristics, with a distinctive emphasis on organic farming methodologies. Additionally, the study provides a concise analysis of the advancements made in agricultural robotics.

Keywords: robots for agriculture, Farming 4.0, IoT, precision agriculture, drones.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the integration of robotic technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) in the agricultural industry has emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing sustainability and productivity. Particularly in sunflower cultivation, cutting-edge robotic solutions hold significant potential to revolutionize traditional agricultural methods and mitigate sustainability challenges in rural areas.

The global population has experienced exponential growth, surpassing 8 billion in mid-November 2022 from an estimated 2.5 billion in 1950. This staggering increase, adding 1 billion people since 2010 and 2 billion since 1998, underscores the pressing need for innovative approaches to address food security and environmental degradation concerns (United Nations, 2022). Regulatory bodies such as the European Union (EU), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), and the United States of America (USA) have recognized this imperative,

taking substantial strides in crafting legislative frameworks to govern the implementation of AI and robotics in agriculture. Despite the rapid population growth witnessed over the past century, the rate of increase has notably decelerated since the 1960s, primarily attributed to declining fertility rates. The global population is projected to reach around 8.5 billion by 2030 and add 1.18 billion in the subsequent two decades, reaching 9.7 billion by 2050 (United Nations, 2022). This gradual growth trajectory underscores the importance of leveraging technological innovations like AI and robotics to enhance agricultural sustainability and address the evolving needs of a growing population.

EU legislation regarding AI and robotics is grounded in fostering innovation while ensuring ethical and responsible technological deployment. The enactment of the European Commission's AI Act in 2021 represents a landmark achievement, establishing a comprehensive regulatory framework geared towards promoting transparency, accountability, and the development of human-

centric AI systems (European Commission, 2021). This legislative framework encompasses critical areas such as data privacy, algorithmic transparency, and liability frameworks for AI-related incidents, providing robust guidelines for the integration of AI-enabled robotic solutions in agriculture.

Subsequently, on March 13, 2024, the European Parliament issued a legislative resolution aimed at regulating the AI Act, envisioning the establishment of a unified legal framework within the EU governing the development, market introduction, deployment, and utilization of AI systems (European Parliament, 2024). This regulatory endeavor prioritizes safeguarding health, safety, and fundamental rights, with a concerted emphasis on enhancing AI literacy and fostering voluntary codes of conduct among pertinent stakeholders.

The FAO, renowned for its expertise in food and agriculture, has actively explored the potential applications of AI and robotics in agricultural development. Initiatives such as "Agriculture 4.0 Agricultural Robotics and Automated Equipment for Sustainable Crop Production" (FAO, 2020), "Digital Agriculture in Action: Artificial Intelligence for Agriculture" (FAO, 2021) and "Digital Technologies in Agriculture and Rural Areas" (FAO, 2019) highlight the FAO's recognition of the transformative impact of these technologies on agricultural sustainability, productivity, and resilience. By advocating for responsible adoption, the FAO aims to address pressing global challenges, including climate change, food insecurity, and rural poverty.

In the United States, legislative efforts have emphasized innovation and regulatory oversight, with federal agencies and initiatives such as the Select Committee on AI and the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) instrumental in supporting research and development in agricultural robotics, an example being the "National Artificial Intelligence Research and Development Strategic Plan" (NSTC, 2023). The "Robotic Process Automation (RPA) Policy" issued by the US Department of Agriculture (USDA, 2022) further underscores this commitment, providing a framework for the effective and secure implementation of RPA across the organization. In conjunction with the abovementioned policy, it's essential to acknowledge the broader role of robotics and artificial intelligence (AI) in agriculture. While the RPA policy focuses on administrative automation, incorporating

robotics and AI in farming can potentially transform agricultural operations significantly.

An overarching challenge within contemporary robotics resides in the intricate integration of artificial intelligence (AI) to bolster autonomy and fortify adaptability when facing unforeseen and unprogrammed scenarios. This entails not only imbuing robotic systems with the capacity to autonomously navigate and execute tasks but also endowing them with the cognitive flexibility to effectively respond to dynamic and unpredictable environments. Achieving this seamless fusion of AI within robotic frameworks necessitates overcoming complexities associated with real-time decision-making, context comprehension, and the synthesis of diverse sensory inputs to navigate novel situations with agility and efficacy.

Research and innovation in digitalization for agriculture and rural areas are crucial for revolutionizing farming practices and ensuring sustainability. Digital and data technologies offer opportunities to enhance precision, efficiency, and environmental performance, enabling data-driven decisions and attracting younger generations to the sector.

In the EU, significant efforts have been made to advance digital transformation through initiatives like Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe (European Commission, 2020). Successful implementations highlight the potential of digital solutions in agriculture, aiming to boost rural economies and enhance connectivity. Overall, research and innovation in digitalization are essential for driving sustainable development and addressing the challenges farming communities face.

In light of these legislative advancements, this study explores using robotic solutions in sunflower cultivation to bolster sustainability across rural regions of the Western Plain of Romania. By scrutinizing the regulatory framework and benchmark practices globally, this research provides comprehensive insights to policymakers, stakeholders, and practitioners regarding the potential and obstacles in embracing AI-enabled robotics in agricultural settings. Through rigorous empirical analysis and insightful case studies, this study aims to enrich the ongoing dialogue surrounding the prudent and sustainable deployment of AI and robotics in agriculture, primarily focusing on fortifying rural livelihoods and bolstering environmental resilience.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was commenced with an exhaustive investigation of the global agricultural robotics market to identify optimal solutions conducive to organic sunflower cultivation in the Western Plain of Romania. Companies such as AGXEED, AGROINTELLI, and Naïo Technologies from the Netherlands, Denmark, and France, respectively, were meticulously examined for their multifunctional robotics offerings, encompassing models such as AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 and AgBot 2.055W4, AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR, and Naïo Technologies' Orio and Oz, proficient in executing diverse tasks ranging from soil preparation to weeding and early-stage plant management. Moreover, specialized solutions focusing on chemical-free weed control were explored from Pixelfarming and Ekobot, while companies like Field Robotics, Monarch, Sitia's TREKTOR and Amos underwent evaluation for their autonomous tractor solutions. In this context, we also explored the capabilities of the H.S.S. AgBot 2.055W3 + CF2000-AB and Jacto's Arbus 4000 JAV for the fertilization process, alongside the Small Robot Co's Tom v4 and DJI's Mavic 3M drone for the process of crop monitoring. Noteworthy was the innovative all-in-one solution from NEXAT, engineered to oversee all aspects of sunflower cultivation. The study also considered emerging projects such as Ecorobotix's AVO spraying robot, Nexus's weeding solutions, and Bluewhite company's autonomous tractor endeavor. Furthermore, attention was devoted to solutions facilitating data collection, exemplified by TERRA-MEPP's TerraSentia robot, and Digital workbench's Tipard 350, with the aim of enhancing precision agriculture practices. This comprehensive inquiry facilitated the identification and selection of the most promising agricultural robotics solutions tailored to the specific requisites of sustainable and organic sunflower cultivation in the Western Plain of Romania.

Concurrently with the selection process of agricultural robots, an exhaustive exploration was conducted into sustainability policies within the agricultural domain, with a specific focus on the European Union (EU). This analysis encompassed the development of a sustainable bioenergy policy tailored for the EU post-2020, emphasizing the critical necessity of promoting the efficient and sustainable utilization of organic biomass resources for bioenergy production. Key considerations within this

policy formulation included the delineation of climate and energy targets (CEMA, 2016).

Furthermore, the Position Paper on EU Carbon Farming by CEMA underscored the pivotal role of intelligent agricultural machinery in bolstering organic carbon farming methodologies, advocating for policy measures and technology adoption to facilitate sustainable organic sunflower cultivation (CEMA, 2024). Additionally, in pursuit of attaining self-sufficient energy and mitigating carbon emissions, the designated cultivation farm has instituted a biogas generator that harnesses organic waste generated onsite, with the produced biogas serving dual purposes: fuel for electricity generation and power for high-capacity agricultural machinery, notably for crop transportation to reception bases. In alignment with these sustainability objectives, all farm infrastructure will be outfitted with a photovoltaic panel system for energy generation, complemented by energy storage capabilities, thus further fortifying sustainable practices within the agricultural framework.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we undertake a comprehensive examination of the pragmatic implications and contextual intricacies associated with the integration of robotic solutions within the framework of sunflower cultivation practices, with a specific emphasis on the agrarian landscapes of the Western Plain of Romania. The chapter unfolds as a multifaceted inquiry into the diverse dimensions of robotic interventions spanning distinct phases of sunflower cultivation and is characterized by a rigorous analysis of their technical specifications, operational nuances, and ecological implications, thereby offering profound insights into the transformative potential of robotics in agricultural systems.

Robots for Soil Preparation

Beginning with soil preparation, our investigation commenced by examining the solutions provided by AGXEED, particularly through the implementation of the AgBot 5.115T2.

The AgBot 5.115T2 from AGXEED (<https://www.agxeed.com/oursolutions/agbot-n5-115t2/>) features a 4.1 L 4-stroke Deutz Diesel Engine, compliant with stage 5 standards, boasting 115 kW/156 hp and a maximum torque

of 610 Nm, with an electric drive train with battery capacity of 30 kWh and a speed range from 0-13.5 km/h, a 350 l diesel tank and 30 l AdBlue tank, a 85 l/min at 210 bar hydraulic pump, up to 4 double-acting proportional spool valves, three-point rear linkage cat 3 and 8 t maximum lift capacity at hooks, three-point front linkage cat 2 (hooks cat 3) and 3 t maximum lift capacity at hooks, optional load sensing, optional electric driven PTO (up to 100 kW)/-1200 rpm) completely variable in adjustment, optional high voltage connectors (up to 100 kW and 700 V). The AgBot 5.115T2 boasts dimensions of 2695 mm in minimal length, 2000 mm in height, and 3855 mm in total length with the hitch at 90 degrees, weighing in at 7.8 tons when empty. This versatile robot is equipped for soil preparation tasks, offering multiple configurations and implements from companies such as AMAZONE. It can utilize a 3 m digger, costing on average between €10,000 to €30,000 or more, running at a speed of 3.5 km/h and a depth of 30 cm, consuming approximately 22 liters of fuel per hour. Alternatively, it can employ a 3 m front knife roller (price ranging from €2,000 to €5,000 or more) and a 3 m 3-row cultivator (price ranging from €10,000 to €30,000 or more), achieving speeds of up to 10 km/h and operating at a depth of 15 cm. Furthermore, for seedbed preparation, the AgBot 5.115T2 can effectively utilize a 4 m spring tine cultivator, costing on average between €15,000 to €40,000 or more, operating at a speed of 11 km/h. Moreover, the AgBot 5.115T2 stands out with its remarkable field productivity of up to 10 hectares per day, operating at an autonomy level of 4 (high driving automation). Notably, its electric drive train facilitates quick charging, with a charging time of 4-6 hours, ensuring continuous efficiency in agricultural operations. The price of the AgBot 5.115T2 varies depending on the configuration, starting at €320,000+. As of the end of 2023, there were 50+ operational units, with initial sales being done primarily in the Netherlands, Germany, France, and the UK (Figure 1).

Another similar robot from AGXEED is the AgBot 2.055W4 (<https://www.agxeed.com/our-solutions/agbot-2-055w4/>), boasts a 2.9 L 4-stroke Deutz Diesel Engine, stage 5 compliant, with 55 kW/75 hp and a maximum torque of 300 Nm, with electric drive train with a speed range from 0-13.5 km/h, a 220 l diesel tank, a 85 l/min at 210 bar hydraulic pump, up to 3 double-acting proportional spool valves, three point rear linkage cat 2 (hooks cat 3) and 4 t maximum lift

capacity at hooks, three point front linkage cat 2 and 1.5 t maximum lift capacity at hooks, optional load sensing, optional electric driven PTO (up to 55 kW and 700 V) completely variable in adjustment, optional high voltage connectors (up to 55 kW and 700 V).

Figure 1 AGXEED's AgBot 5.115T2 multipurposed agricultural robot (<https://www.agxeed.com/>)

The AgBot 2.055W4 exhibits dimensions of 3850 mm in length, 1500 mm in height, a minimum width of 1800 mm, a wheelbase of 2400 mm, and an empty weight of 3.2 tons. This robotic system is adept at soil preparation tasks, offering various capabilities and implements from companies such as AMAZONE. It can effectively employ a 160 cm bed spader, costing on average between €5,000 to €15,000 or more, operating at a speed of 5 km/h, with a power take-off (PTO) speed of 540 rpm, consuming approximately 4 liters of fuel per hour. Additionally, for seedbed preparation, the AgBot 2.055W4 can utilize a 3 m rotary harrow, costing on average between €10,000 to €25,000 or more, operating at speeds of up to 7 km/h, with a fuel consumption rate of 6.5 liters per hour. The AgBot 2.055W4 boasts an impressive operational capacity, capable of running for up to 20 hours at 75 % capacity, at an autonomy of level 4 (high driving automation). Priced at €190,000, this advanced agricultural solution had 10 operational units recorded by the end of 2023 and is currently available in 20 countries worldwide.

Both of the AGXEED robots incorporate comprehensive safety features to ensure operational integrity. These include a Geofence system, visual indicator lights, audible warning alarm, and strategically placed emergency stop buttons surrounding the machine. Moreover, their robust Obstacle detection system comprises a LIDAR sensor positioned atop the machine, ultrasonic sensors seamlessly integrated into the safety bumper, radar sensors also integrated into the safety bumper, and a

contact sensitive bumper integrated into the safety bumper, collectively enhancing operational safety and risk mitigation (Figure 2).

Figure 2 **AGXEED's AgBot 2.055W4 multipurposed agricultural robot**
(<https://www.agxeed.com/>)

The multipurpose **ROBOTTI LR**, engineered by **AGROINTELLI** (<https://agrointelli.com/robotti/lr/>), showcases a robust array of specifications tailored for soil preparation (with optional PTO at 540 RPM with 14 kW/18 hp). Its design features include a Kubota diesel engine with 4 cylinders, providing 54/72 kW/PS and adhering to EPA/CARB Tier 4 + EU Stage V emissions standards. Enhanced with Bosch Rexroth Load-Sensing-Hydraulics and equipped with three double-acting outlets (max. 50 l/min) featuring free return, the **ROBOTTI LR** offers versatility in agricultural operations. Boasting a diesel tank capacity of 300 L and a dry weight of 2850 kg, this model ensures extended operational periods while minimizing power consumption, being capable of up to 60 hours of continuous operation before requiring refueling, with an output of 2.5 ha/h. Notable attributes include high on-wheel torque, improved hydraulics, and a lifting capacity of 1.2 tons. Operating autonomously, the **ROBOTTI LR** executes field tasks continuously, day and night, facilitated by its dual RTK-GPS positioning system, ensuring precision within +/- 2 cm. Implements suitable for the **ROBOTTI LR** can be sourced from **PÖTTINGER** and **MONOSEM**, providing a range of options for various agricultural tasks, including soil preparation. Stubble cultivators from **PÖTTINGER** could range in price from €10,000 to €30,000 or more, while disc harrows could range in price from €15,000 to €40,000 or more, depending on the specific model, size, features, and any additional customization options. Moreover, short combination cultivators as a fuel-saving seedbed preparation option could range in price from €20,000 to €50,000 or more. Additionally, implements from **MONOSEM** such as the **Multicrop** and **Supercrop** cultivators could range in price from €20,000 to €50,000 or more. Priced at €179,858, **ROBOTTI LR** has the option for rental bases, with annual rental costs starting

from €32,000. By the end of 2023, 16 operational units were recorded, with dealers accessible in 22 countries worldwide (Figure 3).

Figure 3 **AGROINTELLI's ROBOTTI LR multipurposed agricultural robot**
(<https://agrointelli.com/>)

Orio, developed by **Naïo Technologies** (<https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/orio-is-the-most-versatile-tool-carrier/>), represents a significant advancement in agricultural robotics, with a particular focus on soil preparation. Its design emphasizes the accessibility of the toolholder, facilitating easy adjustment of tool settings crucial for soil cultivation. Notably, **Orio's** compact turning pattern is designed to minimize soil compaction, demonstrating a keen commitment to soil health preservation. Enhanced by powerful motors and a pivot point in the rear axle, **Orio** ensures reliable performance even in challenging terrain, making it highly adaptable for various soil preparation tasks. Operating solely on battery power and driven by electric motors, **Orio** prioritizes environmental sustainability in its operations. The robot boasts a carrying capacity of 600 kg for tools in the centered toolholder, enabling it to accommodate a variety of implements necessary for soil preparation tasks. Implements suitable for the **Orio** can be sourced from companies like **K.U.L.T.** One such option is the **K.U.L.T.iVision PV** cultivator or the **K.U.L.T.iSelect**, which offer advanced features tailored for precision agriculture. The price range for the **K.U.L.T.iVision PV** cultivator or the **K.U.L.T.iSelect** can range between €15,000 to €30,000, or more. With its impressive capabilities, **Orio** can achieve speeds of up to 5 km/h for durations of up to 10 hours on a single charge, covering an area of up to 6 hectares per charge. Featuring four independent motors, each with 3000 watts of power, **Orio** delivers robust performance, ensuring efficient and effective soil preparation operations. Its dimensions, measuring 4.00 m in length, 2.25 m in width, and 2.00 m in height, allow for maneuverability in various field environments. For applications requiring narrower tracks, **Orio** offers a track width option ranging from 1.5 m to 1.75 m,

enhancing its versatility across different field configurations. Additionally, the robot features a zero-turn radius, further facilitating precise navigation and maneuvering in tight spaces. Priced at €200,000 and backed by a robust 5-year warranty, Orio has garnered significant attention in the agricultural robotics market. It emerges as a promising solution for soil preparation tasks, thanks to its innovative design, environmental sustainability, and impressive performance capabilities. With 50 operational units sold by the end of 2023, Orio is readily available for purchase worldwide, solidifying its reputation as a reliable and effective choice (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Naïo's Oriomultipurposed agricultural robot (<https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/home/>)

Similarly, the Naïo Oz, an innovative creation from Naïo Technologies (<https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/oz/>), revolutionizes soil preparation in agricultural robotics. This compact robot, powered by a LiFePo4 lithium battery and electric drive system, excels as a versatile farm assistant. Featuring a rear-mounted tool carrier with a lifting capacity of up to 60 kg, complemented by an optional front weight kit, the Oz ensures efficient handling of soil preparation implements. Implement options compatible with the Naïo Oz are available from companies such as Ebra, providing a diverse range of solutions for agricultural tasks, including soil preparation. Prices for Ebra implements typically range from €1500 to €2500 or higher, depending on the specific model and features. Powered by a 100 Ah battery pack, the Oz boasts an impressive operational endurance of up to 8 hours on a single charge, covering an area of up to 1 hectare per charge. With a robust 4-wheel drive driveline, the Oz delivers reliable performance across various terrains, enhancing its suitability for soil preparation applications. Equipped with a front-mounted pressure-sensitive sensor for obstacle detection, the Oz navigates through fields with ease, minimizing disruptions to soil preparation

tasks. Its compact dimensions, measuring 1.30 m in length, 0.47 m in width, and 0.83 m in height, contribute to its agility and maneuverability, ensuring optimal performance in diverse field conditions. Priced competitively at €40,000 and boasting a reassuring 5-year warranty, the Oz underscores its significance and widespread adoption in the agricultural robotics market. With 220 operational units sold by the end of 2023, it's readily available for purchase worldwide, highlighting its effectiveness and reliability (Figure 5).

Figure 5 Naïo's Ozmultipurposed agricultural robot (<https://www.naio-technologies.com/en/home/>)

Robots for Seeding

Expanding upon their multifunctionality, the AgBot 5.115T2 from AGXEED and the AgBot 2.055W4, also from AGXEED, as well as the multipurpose ROBOTTI LR by AGROINTELLI, offer versatile solutions for seeding operations. Similarly, Naïo's Orio and Oz, known for their focus on soil preparation but also designed as multipurpose robots, can also be adapted for seeding operations, demonstrating their multifunctionality in agricultural robotics.

The AgBot 5.115T2, previously discussed, can be equipped with a 3 m front tender packer and 3 m rotary harrow with a sunflower precision drill for seeding tasks, with prices ranging from €50,000 to €100,000 or more. With a speed range of up to 8-12 km/h, it ensures efficient and precise seeding operations (Figure 1).

Similarly, the AgBot 2.055W4, as highlighted earlier, offers flexibility in seeding methods. It can utilize a 3 m rotary harrow with a 3 m mechanical drill, with prices ranging from €60,000 to €120,000 or more, operating at speeds of up to 5 km/h and consuming approximately 6 l/h of fuel. Alternatively, it can employ a 4-row 75 cm precision drill with a fertilizer front hopper, with prices ranging from €80,000 to €150,000 or more, achieving a

speed of 6 km/h while consuming 12 l/h of fuel. This configuration enables precise seeding with a seed distance of 16 cm, a seed quantity of 86,000/ha, and fertilizer application of 500 kg (Figure 2).

The ROBOTTI LR by AGROINTELLI is capable of performing the seeding process for sunflowers efficiently and effectively. It utilizes its multipurpose design to adapt to various agricultural tasks, including seeding. The seeding process for sunflowers with the ROBOTTI LR typically involves the attachment of a specialized seeding implement, such as a precision drill tailored for sunflower seeds. The ROBOTTI LR's precise control and maneuverability, facilitated by its advanced technology and autonomous operation, enable it to navigate through fields with accuracy. It can adjust the seeding depth and spacing according to specific requirements for sunflower cultivation. Additionally, the robot's robust construction and high lifting capacity allow it to carry the necessary seed and fertilizer loads for large-scale seeding operations. With its integrated RTK-GPS positioning system ensuring precise accuracy within +/- 2 cm, the ROBOTTI LR can maintain consistent seed placement and spacing, optimizing the potential yield of sunflower crops. Implements suitable for the ROBOTTI LR can be sourced from PÖTTINGER and MONOSEM, providing a range of options for various agricultural tasks, including seeding operations. PÖTTINGER's seed drill machines could range in price from €20,000 to €100,000 or more, depending on the specific model, size, features, and any additional customization options. Additionally, implements from MONOSEM such as the VALOTERRA, MONOSHOX NG PLUS M/ME, MONOSHOX NX M/ME, NG PLUS 4/4E and NC PLANTER, all have sunflower seeding capabilities, with prices ranging from €50,000 to €150,000 or more, depending on the specific model, size, features, and any additional customization options (Figure 3).

Naïo's Orio and Oz, known for their multifunctionality in agricultural robotics, can also be adapted for seeding operations, including the seeding process for sunflowers. These robots leverage their compact yet robust designs to perform a range of tasks, including seeding, with precision and efficiency. For the seeding process of sunflowers, Naïo's Orio (Figure 4) and Oz (Figure 5) can be equipped with specialized seeding implements suitable for sunflower cultivation. These implements may include

precision drills or mechanical seeders designed specifically for sunflower seeds. Implements suitable for the Orio can be sourced from companies like K.U.L.T., with prices ranging from from €10,000 to €30,000 or more. Implement options compatible with the Naïo Oz are available from companies such as Ebra, providing a diverse range of solutions for agricultural tasks, including seeding operations. Prices for Ebra implements typically range from €2000 to €3500 or higher. Both Orio and Oz utilize their battery-powered electric drive systems to maneuver through fields, ensuring precise seed placement and spacing. Their compact dimensions and agile maneuverability allow them to navigate between rows and around obstacles with ease, optimizing seed distribution across the field. Equipped with advanced navigation systems, such as GNSS and RTK corrections, Orio and Oz can follow predefined paths with accuracy, ensuring consistent seed placement throughout the seeding process. Additionally, obstacle detection sensors integrated into these robots enable them to navigate around obstacles autonomously, minimizing disruptions to the seeding operation.

Robots for Phytosanitary Treatments and Fertilizer Application

Expanding its application beyond orchard management, the AgBot 2.055W3 & CF2000-AB from H.S.S. (<https://holsprayingssystem.com/producten/hss-fruit-agbot-autonomous-machine/>) represents a groundbreaking innovation in agricultural robotics, tailored for sunflower cultivation. This autonomous machine offers multifunctional capabilities, including crop protection, weed control and precise liquid nutrition application. For crop protection, the AgBot features a module with a 2000-liter tank, an electrically driven fan, and 16 nozzles for uniform distribution. Weed control and liquid feed application are achieved with a three-point-supported frame, equipped with adjustable spray hoods and a dosing pump for agent injection. In the fertilizing process for sunflower cultivation, the AgBot 2.055W3 + CF2000-AB plays a pivotal role, ensuring precision and efficiency. Equipped with versatile features such as a standard hitch, power take-off (PTO), auxiliary valves, load sensing, and a high-voltage connector, the robot adapts seamlessly to various agricultural operations, including fertilization. The AgBot boasts advanced technical specifications, featuring a 55 kW Deutz 2.9 TCD diesel engine and a 170-liter fuel tank,

coupled with electric drive for the rear wheels, providing stepless speed control. Navigation is seamlessly managed through a remote control and receiver with ECU, complemented by a GNSS receiver for driving and safety systems. Utilizing a diesel-electric drive train, the AgBot harnesses its 55 kW engine to drive a generator, powering electric drives for propulsion, PTO operations, and implements. This configuration yields approximately 45 kW of PTO power and enables a lifting capacity of 3 tons. Navigation during fertilization tasks is enhanced by LiDAR, ultrasonic, and tactile sensors, ensuring precise maneuvering and collision avoidance. Powered by a diesel engine driving a generator, the AgBot offers up to 24 hours of operational endurance, ensuring continuous productivity throughout sunflower cultivation. Priced at €261,291, the H.S.S AgBot 2.055W3 + CF2000-AB boasts 10 operational unit sales recorded by the end of 2023, with availability in the Netherlands, Canada, France, Italy, and New Zealand (Figure 6).

Figure 6 **H.S.S AgBot 2.055W3 + CF2000-AB sprayer**
(<https://holsprayingystems.com/>)

The Arbus 4000 JAV from Jacto (<https://jacto.com/asia/products/autonomous-sprayer/arbus-4000-jav>), emerges as a cutting-edge solution tailored specifically for precision fertilizer spraying in sunflower cultivation, embodying advanced technology to optimize performance and efficiency in this agricultural sector. This autonomous machine features a multifan system equipped with intelligent section control, ensuring precise spraying solely where needed within sunflower fields, thereby minimizing wastage and environmental impact. Enhanced by a laser scanning system, the Arbus analyzes the environment to adjust application rates based on the size of the sunflower plants, further enhancing accuracy and effectiveness. Additionally, the electric motor-driven fan system reduces fuel consumption while maintaining high performance during fertilizer spraying operations. Interactive control of the

Powered by a diesel engine, the Arbus 4000 JAV boasts characteristics optimized for sunflower cultivation, including a generous 4,000-liter tank capacity and a maneuverable steering system, enabling operation in challenging field conditions. Once in operation, the Arbus utilizes onboard sensors and software to adapt to uncertainties such as obstacles or moving objects within the field. With dimensions optimized for field work and adjustable height, the Arbus offers versatility and agility in sunflower cultivation. Powered by an intelligent hydrostatic transmission system integrated with a 132 hp diesel engine, it boasts a range of up to 20 hours of continuous work on a full tank of 230 liters. The Arbus 4000 JAV aims for operational efficiency, targeting a capacity of 4 to 6 hectares per hour for fertilizer spraying in sunflower fields. Jacto's Arbus 4000 JAV fertilizer is available for rental at a competitive rate of €5.69, with 2 operational units rented as recorded by the end of 2023. However, availability for rental is currently undisclosed (Figure 7).

Figure 7 **Jacto's Arbus 4000 JAV fertilizer**
(<https://jacto.com/europe>)

In our evaluation of cutting-edge agricultural technologies, we have also considered future projects such as Ecorobotix's Avo spraying robot (<https://ecorobotix.com/en/avo/>). Ecorobotix, a Swiss manufacturer, introduced the Avo autonomous spraying robot in 2014, marking a significant advancement in precision agriculture technology. Designed for targeted application of fertilizers, the solar-battery powered Avo utilizes camera recognition in row crops, meadows, and intercropping cultures. Equipped with RTK GPS, AI, and vision capabilities, the Avo detects and selectively sprays weeds with remarkable precision,

reducing herbicide usage by up to 95 %. Its spot spraying technology offers a spray resolution of up to 24 cm² on the ground, ensuring efficient and environmentally friendly weed control. Priced at €90,000, the Avo has gained traction in the market, with five units currently active in France, Italy, Germany, and Switzerland. However, it is important to note that it is currently still in the testing phase and not available for sale as of the end of 2023 (Figure 8).

Figure 8 Ecorobotix's Avo spraying robot
(<https://ecorobotix.com/en/>)

Robots for Weed Elimination

Robot One from Pixelfarming (<https://pixelfarmingrobotics.com/robot-one/>) is engineered to autonomously combat weeds, eliminating the need for manual labor or chemical herbicides, thus aligning perfectly with the principles of sustainable and organic sunflower farming. Its sophisticated vision-based technology enables precise weed detection and control, offering a viable alternative to traditional weed management practices. With robust processing capabilities and seamless cloud connectivity, Robot One is ideally suited for large-scale sunflower fields, fostering biodiverse environments conducive to optimal crop growth. Robot One is equipped with 10 arms and three specialized tools – including a hoe, mill, and streamer – to facilitate efficient weed management. Moreover, the purchase package encompasses an Onboarding program, ensuring seamless integration and operational understanding for users venturing into sunflower cultivation. Powered by an all-electric drive train featuring 4-wheel drive and 4-wheel steering with a 12 kW system, Robot One operates at speeds ranging from 2.5 cm/s to 1.2 m/s. Each of its ten arms boasts a lifting capacity of 80 KG, totaling 800 kg, ensuring efficient weed management across vast sunflower fields. The Robot One incorporates an array of advanced sensors and processing power to optimize its performance in agricultural tasks. Featuring 6 stereographic cameras for obstacle detection and an additional 6 cameras for image recognition, the Robot One enhances its perception and awareness of its surroundings.

Supported by an NVIDIA Ampere GPU and a 12-core Arm Cortex CPU, boasting an impressive AI Performance of 275 TOPS (INT8), the Robot One's processing power enables seamless navigation and weed control. Integrated with a dual RTK-GPS and camera sensing system, this technology ensures accurate positioning and precise operation in the field, further enhancing the Robot One's efficiency and effectiveness in agricultural operations. Measuring 2300 mm in length, 3750 mm in width, and 2230 mm in height, Robot One offers variable track width settings to adapt to the specific requirements of sunflower cultivation. With the ability to turn on its axis, it delivers unparalleled maneuverability, essential for navigating through sunflower rows. Weighing 2140 kg, the robot is powered by all-electric drivelines, complemented by 1110 Wp solar panels and a 13.5 kWh battery pack, ensuring uninterrupted operation even in remote sunflower fields. The Robot One boasts an impressive output capacity, capable of covering 1 hectare per hour for mechanical weed control, ensuring high productivity during operation. On a bright day, the Robot One can operate continuously and return to the field with fully charged batteries.

Figure 9 Pixelfarming's Robot One
chemical-free weeding robot
(<https://pixelfarmingrobotics.com/>)

However, the range may vary depending on the specific tools used in conjunction with the Robot One. Priced at €249,000, Robot One is an advanced and reliable solution tailored for chemical-free weed control in sunflower cultivation. The sales price includes Robot One equipped with 10 arms and 3 different tools: a hoe, mill, and streamer, along with the Onboarding program. Through this program, the buyer is guided on how to successfully integrate Robot One into their business operations. Additionally, the CO₂ laser option is available upon request. As of the end of 2023, Pixelfarming intended to have 15 operational units in total.

Robot One is currently available for sale in

Europe (Figure 9).

The WEAI robot from Ekobot(<https://www.ekobot.se/products/ekobot-weai/>), emerges as a groundbreaking solution tailored for the meticulous weed management essential in sunflower cultivation. Designed specifically for row-seeded vegetables, WEAI stands out as an invaluable asset in the battle against weeds, particularly crucial in the context of sunflower fields. Equipped with mechanical arms for inter-row weeding and a specialized hoeing system for intra-row weed removal, WEAI significantly reduces the reliance on herbicides. By minimizing chemical intervention, farmers can effectively cut costs while promoting environmentally friendly agricultural practices, thus fostering sustainable sunflower cultivation. Notably, trials conducted in Sweden have showcased the transformative impact of WEAI, demonstrating increased yields compared to conventional pesticide-based weed control methods. The Generation-3 model of WEAI weighs 600 kg and features four-wheel drive and four-wheel steering, ensuring seamless navigation through sunflower fields. The robot boasts dimensions of 2.0 meters in length, 2.8 meters in width, and 1.8 meters in height, with track widths available in both 2.0 meters and 2.25 meters. Its autonomous operation, powered by an electric system with a battery swap mechanism, enables continuous weed management, vital for maintaining the integrity of sunflower crops. Utilizing advanced RTK GPS technology for precise positioning, coupled with sensor fusion for obstacle detection, WEAI navigates sunflower fields with unparalleled accuracy and efficiency. With dimensions optimized for agricultural applications, WEAI guarantees agile maneuverability within sunflower rows, contributing to streamlined weed management operations. Powered by two 48 V batteries producing 7.4 kWh, WEAI ensures uninterrupted productivity throughout the sunflower cultivation process with a runtime of up to 9 to 10 hours per charge. Leveraging the mechanical tool arms, the Robot One efficiently covers 10 hectares in 4.5 days. When combined with the hoeing system, this capacity can be further optimized to cover the same area, offering enhanced efficiency and productivity in agricultural operations. Priced at €95,000, alongside a service fee, this innovative system operates with exceptional precision, meticulously targeting weeds within and between rows, thereby optimizing sunflower yield potential. With availability in Denmark,

Netherlands, Sweden, and potentially Belgium as well, and with 5 operational units by the end of 2023, the WEAI robot offers efficient and effective weed control solutions across multiple countries, enhancing agricultural productivity and sustainability (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Ekobot's WEAI weeding robot (<https://www.ekobot.se/>)

Robots and Drones for Crop Monitoring

Tom v4, developed by Small Robot Co (<https://smallrobotco.com/#tom>), alongside with DJI Mavic 3M (<https://ag.dji.com/mavic-3-m>), transforms sunflower farming through precise per-plant crop counting, weed detection, and data visualization. This innovative solution autonomously maps fields, providing crucial insights into crop health and weed density. Tom utilizes AI to generate treatment maps for targeted herbicide application and variable-rate nutrient use, optimizing resource efficiency and reducing environmental impact in sunflower fields. Equipped with an electric drivetrain and Swift nav GPS system, Tom ensures accurate positioning, essential for effective monitoring. Its 6m camera coverage and 4 TB data storage capacity facilitate comprehensive data collection and analysis, empowering farmers with informed decision-making tools. Tom is powered by four rechargeable batteries (1.56 kWh each) and is equipped with a Swiftnav GPS system featuring two GNSS receivers. Additional features include eight 6-megapixel cameras, a ground sample distance (GSD) of 0.28 cm per pixel, and a static ground pressure of less than 31 kPa. Weighing 350.6 kg, Tom's dimensions comprise a track width of 1.04 meters, a wheelbase of 0.95 meters, a robot length of 1.55 meters, a robot width of 1.54 meters, a robot height of 1.3 meters, a boom deployed width of 5.56 meters, and a turning radius of 0.74 meters. Tom's energy source is electricity/batteries, providing a range of four hours on a single battery charge, with the flexibility for farmers to swap batteries to continue operation. It boasts an impressive output capacity of 2.2 hectares per hour and utilizes two GNSS receivers to provide RTK position with a 1 cm accuracy. Pricing for Tom v4's services is £150 per hectare, which

includes three surveys. These surveys provide valuable tools for sunflower cultivation, including green-on-brown maps for targeted herbicide application, variable-rate nitrogen application maps based on plant counts and biomass assessments, and broadleaf weed maps for precise herbicide application during autumn and spring seasons. Availability is currently limited to the UK, with the total number of operational units by the end of 2023 undisclosed (Figure 11).

Figure 11 **Small Robot Co's Tom v4 monitoring robot** (<https://smallrobotco.com/>)

Potential Robot for Harvesting

In the realm of sunflower harvesting, several companies have introduced innovative solutions aimed at enhancing efficiency and productivity. FieldRobotics, Monarch, Sitia's TREKTOR, and Amos have all developed autonomous tractor solutions that offer promising advancements in sunflower cultivation. However, among these, NEXAT's (<https://www.nexat.de/en/products/carrier-vehicle/>) all-in-one solution stands out for its comprehensive approach. Even though it is not fully autonomous, NEXAT is engineered to oversee all aspects of sunflower cultivation, including solutions that integrate cutting-edge technology to streamline the harvesting process. NEXAT's sunflower-specific harvesting system, developed entirely in-house, integrates the NEXCO harvesting module, setting new standards in sunflower harvesting technology. With a cutter bar width of 15 m, the NEXCO module ensures an efficient flow of material, boasting an enormous throughput of 120-200

t/h tailored for sunflower crops. This innovative system minimizes losses and the share of broken grains while featuring a 32 m³ grain tank and evenly distributing straw over the entire working width, crucial for sunflower cultivation. Swath deposit is also possible, with an impressive unloading rate of 650 l/sec and unloading completed in less than 1 minute, enhancing operational efficiency during sunflower harvesting. The system employs a revolutionary Dual Tangential Axial Flow threshing concept, specifically optimized for sunflower crops, dividing the crop into two even flows transverse to the driving direction for optimal throughput. With headers from leading manufacturers like Geringhoff, GTS, Franco Fabril, and MacDon, offering specialized options for sunflower crops, NEXAT's solution ensures high efficiency, reliability, and economic viability in sunflower harvesting operations. Nexat is currently in the process of becoming fully autonomous, with ongoing efforts to achieve this goal and to transition it to electric power fueled by a hydrogen fuel cell generator. The standalone Nexat unit is priced at approximately \$1.3 million. However, when considering all available applications, the total cost escalates to around \$2.75 million (Figure 12).

Figure 12 **NEXAT's all-in-one system** (<https://www.nexat.de/en/>)

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the integration of advanced agricultural robotics and sustainable energy practices in sunflower cultivation represents a pivotal step towards achieving both environmental stewardship and operational efficiency. The implementation of a biogas generator, fueled by onsite organic waste, not only enables self-sufficiency in energy but also significantly reduces carbon emissions associated with traditional farming practices. Moreover, the utilization of photovoltaic panel systems further enhances sustainability efforts,

providing renewable energy sources to power farm operations. These initiatives underscore the commitment of the agricultural sector to reducing its environmental footprint while embracing innovative technologies.

By harnessing the power of renewable energy and leveraging cutting-edge agricultural robotics, sunflower cultivation can not only enhance productivity and efficiency but also contribute to global efforts aimed at mitigating climate change and promoting sustainable development.

In summary, the combination of agricultural robotics, AI and sustainable energy practices presents a promising pathway towards a more environmentally friendly and economically viable future for sunflower cultivation. As the agricultural industry continues to evolve, it is imperative to prioritize sustainability and adopt practices that safeguard the environment for future generations. The sustainability of agriculture reflects the approach aimed at incorporating the values of Industry 5.0 (a human-centred approach to digital technologies, upskilling and reskilling European workers, especially digital skills, modern, resource-efficient and sustainable industries and the transition to a circular one). economy, a globally competitive and world-leading industry accelerating investment in research and innovation) in what we call Agriculture 5.0 (European Commission, 2022).

The robotization of agriculture would greatly help the Romanian farmer and Romanian agriculture, the development of agriculture in the Western Plain of Romania and its alignment with EU standards.

Just as farmers have gotten used to using drones, and those who haven't are thinking of buying or renting one, in the coming years robots will become a normal reality and can already be bought in Romania. By choosing an appropriate robot system, we will be able to respect sustainable sunflower cultivation technologies, protecting the environment and resulting a superior quality products.

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TRADITIONTASTE

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REVIEW

Abstract

This study explores the internationalization strategy of hypotetique company called TraditionTaste, a SME specializing in gastronomic tours, gourmet subscription boxes, and premium culinary experiences. The primary motivation for international expansion includes accessing larger markets, leveraging unique product offerings, and achieving revenue growth. Additionally, internal stimuli such as excess capacity of resources, economies of scale, and technological advantages drive the internationalization effort. External factors, including declining home market growth and opportunities in international markets, also play a significant role.

The research outlines the company's strategic objectives, including market expansion, revenue growth, and enhanced brand recognition. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as market penetration, revenue increase, and brand awareness are identified to measure success. The company plans to undertake market research, develop robust market entry strategies, adapt products to meet local preferences, establish strategic partnerships, and implement targeted marketing initiatives.

The analysis examines internal strengths, such as unique products and brand loyalty, alongside external opportunities like global culinary tourism interest and e-commerce expansion. Risks include market competition, regulatory challenges, and economic instability, with proposed countermeasures. Financial considerations cover technology adaptation costs, resource allocation, communication strategies, and related expenses.

In conclusion, the internationalization of TraditionTaste presents significant opportunities for revenue growth and brand enhancement. By leveraging its unique products and strategic planning, the company aims to successfully navigate the competitive and regulatory landscapes of new international markets, ultimately achieving its expansion objectives. This study provides a comprehensive overview of the motivations, strategies, and potential outcomes for TraditionTaste's internationalization efforts.

Keywords: Geographic Indication (GI) products, Internationalization, SWOT Analysis, Gastronomic Tours, Porter's Five Forces model

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customers and celebrate the diversity of global food traditions.

INTRODUCTION

In an era where global cuisine often overshadows local culinary traditions, TraditionTaste seeks to reignite the appreciation for traditional foods by offering gastronomic boxes filled with high-quality ingredients, including Geographic Indication (GI) products. Our mission is to bridge the gap between local food heritage and contemporary cooking enthusiasts, ensuring that the rich flavors and stories of traditional dishes are preserved and celebrated. By bringing these authentic and culturally significant foods to the forefront, we aim to enrich the culinary experiences of our

The drive behind Tradition Taste's venture into the market stems from a combination of internal and external stimuli, as well as other compelling reasons. Internally, we are motivated by the excess capacity of resources, including surplus production capacity and a wealth of skilled labor, which we aim to maximize efficiently by catering to a niche market that values high-quality, traditional ingredients. By entering a larger market, we can achieve economies of scale, spreading our fixed costs over a greater volume, reducing average costs per unit, and boosting profitability. Our offering is distinct, focusing on traditional foods prepared with top-tier ingredients, providing us

a competitive edge in both domestic and international markets. Additionally, by leveraging advanced food preservation and packaging technologies, TraditionTaste ensures that our gastronomic boxes maintain the highest quality standards, offering a superior product to our customers. This technological advantage allows us to deliver fresh and authentic flavors that are true to their origins.

Externally, we are driven by the challenges and opportunities in our current markets. As local markets face saturation and decline, expanding into international arenas offers new growth opportunities, allowing us to diversify our revenue streams and reduce market dependence. The global market presents untapped segments with a growing demand for authentic, traditional foods. We aim to capture this demand, broadening our customer base and enhancing profitability. Other motivations include the ambition of our visionary leadership team, which aspires to make a significant mark on the global culinary landscape, showcasing our commitment to quality and tradition. Established relationships with international partners, suppliers, and customers provide us with valuable insights and support, facilitating smoother market entry and operations. By operating in multiple markets, we mitigate the risks associated with economic fluctuations, political instability, and regulatory changes in any single region. This strategic approach ensures our resilience and adaptability in a dynamic global marketplace.

TraditionTaste aims to address a notable market gap by being the premier provider of Gastronomic boxes that emphasize high-quality, and GI-certified ingredients and a focus on traditional cuisine. Our objectives include filling the market gap as the only company offering a curated selection of traditional foods with premium ingredients, meeting the demand for authenticity and quality in home cooking. By focusing on traditional recipes and ingredients, we aim to preserve and promote culinary heritage, making it accessible to everyone. Offering a unique culinary journey through our high-quality products, we strive to provide an exceptional customer experience that fosters a deep appreciation for traditional foods. Through TraditionTaste, we aim to not only cater to the culinary needs of our customers but also to foster a deeper connection to the rich and diverse food traditions from around the world.

Our commitment to excellence and authenticity in every box ensures that the legacy of traditional cuisine continues to thrive in contemporary kitchens, bringing joy and cultural enrichment to households everywhere.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

TraditionTaste is a company based in France specialising in gastronomy and culinary tourism. TraditionTaste offers culinary box subscriptions, gastronomic tours and premium subscriptions to unique culinary experiences.

TasteTradition is currently exporting its culinary boxes featuring local French products, differentiated by their superior quality (GI product) and a market segmentation targeting international gourmets (Haag, 2013). Gastronomic tours and premium subscriptions, with a differentiation based on an authentic and immersive culinary experience, will also be exported.

New products and services will be developed, such as digital culinary experiences and international collaborations with renowned chefs and food influencers. In order to adapt to foreign markets, targeted marketing will be adopted to reach specific market segments. TraditionTaste will adopt face-to-face communication, electronic media, and written methods to reach and engage their target audience.

TraditionTaste will participate in events such as product launches, trade shows, and networking events to increase visibility and establish strategic partnerships.

Internationalisation will be achieved through the study of TraditionTaste's internal and external drivers, including excess resource capacity, economies of scale, technological advantages, and opportunities in international markets (Grönroos, 1999).

The SWOT analysis will be used to assess internal strengths (unique products, advanced technology), internal weaknesses (lack of resources to adapt), external opportunities (growing markets), and external threats (intense competition) (Samejima et al., 2006).

Using Porter's Five Forces model to analyse competitiveness in international markets, including rivalry between existing competitors, the power of suppliers, the power of buyers, the threat of substitutes, and the threat of new entrants will be important in analysing the viability of TraditionTaste's internationalisation project (Oraman et al., 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Internationalisation

TraditionTaste aims to penetrate new markets each year to compensate for the stagnation of the domestic market (France), and thus take advantage of international opportunities and diversify risks. Expectations for this strategy include a 20% increase in sales

in the first two years and the establishment of key partnerships (Pereira, 2023).

The main challenges of internationalisation include cultural barriers to marketing communications, the need for regulatory and legal adaptations which will generate additional costs, and the management of international logistics given the sensitivity of certain foods in gourmet boxes (Tan, 2021).

Figure 1 Revenues for the first 5 years of TraditionTaste

Figure 2 Break-even Analysis

2. SWOT ANALYSIS

Table 1 SWOT Analysis

STRENGTHS	WEAKNESSES
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique product: TraditionTaste offers high-quality gourmet products that stand out for their authenticity and regional origin (GI product). • Advanced Technology: Using cutting-edge technologies and investing in research and innovation in packaging and distribution. • Established Network: A solid network of suppliers and local partners for GI products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ressources Financières Limitées : Financements insuffisants pour une expansion massive sans soutien externe. • Capacité de Production : Limitations dans l'augmentation rapide de la production pour répondre à une demande accrue.
OPPORTUNITIES	THREATS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growing international markets: Increasing demand for authentic gastronomic products (GI) in emerging markets. • Strategic partnerships: Opportunities to work with international distributors and retailers to facilitate logistics. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intense competition: Presence of well-established competitors with similar products and the opportunity to launch into this gourmet box niche (Hello Fresh, Blue Apron). • Regulations: Food and customs regulations vary from country to country, which will make access to this new market more difficult and time-consuming.

Source: (*The Strategy Story, N.D*)

3. Porter's Five Forces model

TraditionTaste has a diversified network of suppliers, reducing the risk of over-dependence on a single supplier. However, some key ingredients remain critical and subject to price variations as producers of GI-certified products are limited.

However, diversifying the sources of supply of standard products and negotiating long-term contracts with producers of GI products would make it possible to ensure a certain sustainability of production.

Variety in the products offered to customers, ranging from direct consumers of gourmet boxes to gourmet allists, allowing diversification of the customer base and redirection of certain consumers through exclusive offers.

Building customer loyalty through loyalty programmes and exclusive offers can help to dilute their bargaining power.

The threat is moderate because of the uniqueness of TraditionTaste's products but remains present because of the ease with which potential competitors can enter the niche dedicated to gastronomy (City University of Hong Kong, 2022).

Strengthen the brand image and unique value proposition in correlation with the values of the unique products of the terroir such as family history, the transmission of knowledge and value linked to sustainability and fair trade.

The barriers to entry in the niche market in which TraditionTaste operates are high due to the need for quality certification and complex, established distribution networks.

Constant innovation in transport conditions, packaging and product quality is necessary to deter new entrants to the market.

CONCLUSIONS

TraditionTaste has laid a solid foundation for international expansion by defining strategic objectives, identifying key performance indicators (KPIs), and conducting thorough internal and external analyses. The goals include market expansion, revenue growth, and enhanced brand recognition. However, as these strategies are yet to be implemented, their success remains to be seen and will depend on effective execution and navigating the complex international landscape.

Several significant limitations must be acknowledged. Regulatory and legal challenges across different countries can be complex and resource-intensive, posing compliance challenges and increasing operational costs. Ensuring the freshness and quality of ingredients during international shipping is a substantial hurdle, requiring advanced preservation technologies and reliable logistics partners. Additionally, effectively communicating TraditionTaste's value proposition and differentiating the brand in

diverse markets may require significant localization efforts. Financial constraints may restrict the scale and speed of expansion without substantial external support. Furthermore, well-established competitors in the international market, such as Hello Fresh and Blue Apron, pose a risk.

To mitigate these limitations, several recommendations are proposed. Establishing a dedicated team or engaging local consultants for regulatory compliance can prevent costly delays. Investing in advanced food preservation technologies and building strategic partnerships with reliable logistics providers will help maintain product quality. Developing a deep understanding of each target market's cultural nuances and tailoring marketing campaigns accordingly is essential. Securing additional funding through investors, grants, or partnerships will support scaling operations. Differentiating TraditionTaste by emphasizing high-quality, GI-certified ingredients and the associated cultural heritage can create a distinct market position. Continuous innovation in product development, packaging, and marketing strategies will help maintain a competitive edge.

By addressing these recommendations, TraditionTaste can enhance its potential for successful international expansion, ultimately achieving its growth and brand recognition objectives in the global marketplace.

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THE PRODUCTIVE INDICES OF THE GOOSE POPULATION IN THE AREA OF BIHOR COUNTY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In Romania, birds belonging to a population of the Rhine White Dutch breed were imported and were used to crossbreed with specimens of the Landaise Breed, in order to obtain meat-producing hybrids. These populations spread in the west of the country starting from the Arad poultry platform.

Currently, there are specimens disseminated in the households of the population, with a high degree of cross-breeding. However, in the area of Bihor county, it was possible to carry out some studies, they were carried out in three breeders holding this breed, in pure condition, 22 males and 88 females being analyzed.

In terms of weight gain, both for youth and adult specimens, they slightly exceed the breed standard, in males (6.4 Kg compared to 6 Kg), while in females they are below the reference values (4.7 Kg vs. 5 Kg).

Keywords: White Rhine Dutch breed, Body weight dynamics in both genders mature geese
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INTRODUCTION

This species is characterized by a strong seasonality of egg production, the population prefers it for other valuable productions, namely meat, fluff and fatty liver, lending itself very well to making traditional products, especially in the western part of the country.

On the other hand, the advantages reside in the fact that these populations lend themselves to extensive growth, the birds making very good use of some resources inaccessible to other species (meadows, water meadows).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The birds from three breeders possessing this breed, in a pure state, were studied. The number of individuals analyzed was 22 males and 88 females from three breeders.

In total, 100 specimens of the Dutch breed were studied, distributed as follows: 35 heads (28 females and 7 males) in the first farm, 30 heads (26 females and 4 males) from the second farm, 45 heads (36 females and 9 males) in the of the third farm.

The following were used to carry out the research: analytical and technical balances, digital, x-ray machines, computer equipped with

spreadsheet software, depending on the experimental method approached.

All the obtained results were compared with the reference values from the specialized literature (Sauveur B., 1988; Usturoi M.G., 1999; Vacaru Opreş I. et al., 2002).

The obtained experimental data were centralized and processed statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Spectacular weight evolution in the first 7-8 weeks of the birds' life is related to restricting the access of the young to the meadows and feeding them with existing resources within the farms.

The male youth shows a more intense evolution of the growth spurt in the age period 1 day-8 weeks (average weight of 160.3 g - 3972.1 g), after which the weight gain takes place at a lower intensity, achieving, at age 33 weeks, an average weight of 5988.2 g. The best evolution was recorded by the birds from farm 1 (6103.4±179.6 g at the end of the juvenile period).

In the case of females, weight gain is more intense until week 7-8 (from 159.0g to 2892.5g), after which there is a linear progression than in the case of males and they reach, at 33 weeks, an average body weight of 4333.4 g/head (Fig. 1). The growth rate

recorded in adults is much more attenuated, especially during the egg-laying season. Thus, during 19 weeks of the productive period (usually January-June), the males achieve an average body weight of 6493.8g, starting from a value of 5988.2g, i.e. a weight gain of approximately 8.5%

In females, the increase in growth is also reduced, reaching an average value of 4715.5 g/head at the age of one week, which represents a weight gain of approx. 8.8% (fig. 2). The maximum weight was reached by

females from the second farm, at the age of 54 weeks.

Also, the most precocious population was the one from the second farm, reaching sexual maturity at the age of 237 days, the other flocks studied being later, by approximately one week. Losses from the flock amounted to 8.6-10%, being generated by technological accidents and the elimination of minus variants in the first two weeks of the birds' life figure 3.

Fig. 1 Body weight dynamics in both genders youth geese, White Rhine Dutch breed

Fig. 2 Body weight dynamics (g) in both genders mature geese, White Rhine Dutch breed

Fig. 3.- Flock casualties dynamics in the 3 farms of geese, White Rhine Dutch breed

CONCLUSION

Specimens of geese from the studied race can be used in bi- or triracial crossings, in order to maximize the hybrid vigor of the first generation (Dodu M. 2010).

Within the herds already studied, it is necessary to improve by artificial selection the performances regarding the numerical production of eggs and the production of meat and fatty liver.

Also, consideration will be given to ensuring the access of birds (where applicable) to water, in order to capitalize on the existing food resources in the natural environment.

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STUDY REGARDING THE PASTORAL VALUE OF THE MEADOWS FROM BIHARIEI PLAIN (BIHOR COUNTY)

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Meadows are rich in biodiversity, supporting a wide range of flora and fauna. They are important habitats for various plant species, insects, birds, and mammals, contributing to the overall health of ecosystems. Overall, meadows play a crucial role in supporting biodiversity, regulating the climate, conserving water, providing recreational opportunities, and sustaining agricultural livelihoods. Their pastoral value extends far beyond their appearance, making them essential components of healthy and resilient ecosystems. This study aims to analyze the floristic composition and the pastoral value of a permanent meadow, dominated by phytocoenosis *Agrostetum stoloniferae*, located in the Bihariei Plain (Bihor County), trying to identify measures to improve. The assessment of the participation of the component species and the floristic composition was based on the floristic surveys, after which the pastoral value was evaluated.

Keywords: meadow, pastoral value indicator, species inventory, meadows, fodder quality index.

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INTRODUCTION

Meadows have traditionally been used for agriculture and livestock grazing. They provide valuable forage for livestock and support sustainable farming practices. Meadows also contribute to the local economy through the production of hay, pasture, and other agricultural products.

Keeping the grassy lawn of the grasslands in balance is an art that the manager of the pastoral fund must master thoroughly, starting with the knowledge of the plants, the needs of fertilizers and their humidity, appropriate methods of use by grazing or mowing and other measures (Maruşca, 2006).

The process of photosynthesis in the ecosystems of the grasslands is intensified by the fodder plants and a greater amount of organic matter is introduced into the soil, maintaining an active biological life in the soil. Through the roots of meadow fodder plants, which act as a binder in the presence of organic matter, the process of destroying the granular structure of the soils is stopped, in most cases leading to their improvement (Mocanu, Hermenean, 2013; Simtea et al., 1990).

In the studied area, the floristic composition of the *Agrostetum stoloniferae* phytocoenosis is rich and varied, in which the edifying species *Agrostis stolonifera* it is stated

quantitatively, together with *Lolium perenne* and *Trifolium repens*. It develops in meadows with the water table close to the soil surface, and adapts very well to the seasonal fluctuation of the stagnant water level, regenerating quickly after being trampled by animals during grazing and after mowing, fitting into the habitat R3715 Danubian-Pannonian meadows of *Agrostis stolonifera* (Doniţă et al., 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The pastoral value (V. P.) is a synthetic index of characterization for the quality of a meadow that includes the main elements related to the floristic composition, the percentage of coverage for each species, as well as the nutritional value of the component species.

The floristic composition of a grassland and the appreciation of the participation of the component species is done by one of the classical methods named after the initiators:

- ✓ phytosociological method, Braun-Blanquet
- ✓ pratological method, Klapp-Ellenberg
- ✓ double meter method, Daget-Poissonet
- ✓ gravimetric method

The evaluation of the participation of the species and the floristic composition was made by combining the phytosociological method with the pratological method.

The phytosociological method appeals to the appreciation of the abundance and

dominance (ADm) of the species in the grassy area on 25-100 m², in representative key points, being noted on a 6-step scale (Ivan, Doniță, 1975; Cristea et al., 2004), which correspond to the participation percentages:

- 5 - with a coverage average of 87.5%
- 4 - with a coverage average of 62.5%
- 3 - with a coverage average of 37.5%
- 2 - with a coverage average of 17.5%
- 1 - with a coverage average of 5%
- + - with a coverage average of 0.5%

The taxa identified in the field have been recognized by specialty catalogues "Romania's Illustrated Flora" (Ciocârlan, 2009), in conjunction with the information provided by the "International Code of Botanical Nomenclature" (Code de Tokyo, 1993).

The pratological method emphasizes the assessment of the percentage share in biomass of botanical components by economic groups: *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae* and species from other botanical families.

For the determination of the pastoral value the following formula was used (Marușca et al., 2014):

$$P. V. = \sum PC (\%) \times \frac{IC}{5}$$

where:

- P. V. – pastoral value indicator (0-100);
- P. C. – participation in the grassy area (%),
- I. C. – fodder quality index.

Having at disposal the floristic surveys from the field, with the percentage participation of species, the fodder quality index (I. C.) is passed next to each one (Marușca et al., 2012; Rotar et al., 2009), namely:

- 5 - excellent nutritional value
- 4 - very good nutritional value
- 3 - good nutritional value
- 2 - average nutritional value
- 1 - poor nutritional value

After determining the pastoral value indicator, by dividing by 5 the score obtained from the multiplication of P.C. x I.C., it is assessed as follows (Marușca et al., 2014):

- 0-5 - degraded meadow
- 5-15 - very weak
- 15-25 - weak
- 25-50 - medium
- 50- 75 - good
- 75-100 - very good

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The meadows dominated by the *Agrostetum stoloniferae* phytocoenosis are appreciated from the point of view of pastoral value, having a good productivity, the fodder obtained having a high palatability.

Grasslands dominated by *Agrostetum stoloniferae* usually have a rich composition of grass species, with *Agrostis stolonifera* (creeping grass) being the dominant species. This type of meadow often features a dense, low-growing clump with creeping stems that help the grass spread horizontally. Along with *Agrostis stolonifera*, there are other grass species such as *Lolium perenne* and *Agrostis capillaris*, which contribute to the diversity and overall structure of the meadow, being known for their lush appearance.

Among the species of grasses (*Poaceae*), which accompany *Agrostis stolonifera*, with good nutritional value, we mention species that have excellent nutritional value, like: *Lolium perenne*, *Festuca pratensis*, *Dactylis glomerata*, they being accompanied by leguminous species (*Fabaceae*), such as *Trifolium repens*, *Lotus corniculatus*, *Lathyrus pratensis*, with very good nutritional value.

These meadows have a diversified vegetation, the floristic composition being rich and varied. The species belonging to the *Poaceae* family occupy the highest percentage of the floristic composition (44%), where dominant is *Agrostis stolonifera* (15%), together with *Lolium perenne* (15%), followed by *Agrostis capillaris* and *Agrostis canina* (4%). The *Fabaceae* family (21%) is well represented by *Trifolium repens* (10%) and *Melilotus officinalis* (5%). Among the species from other botanical families, a higher share has *Juncus effusus* (5%) - (Table 1).

Species from other botanical families, which are of interest from a nutritional value point of view, are relatively few in number. Among them we mention: *Achillea millefolium*, *Daucus carota* ssp. *carota*, *Plantago major*, *P. media*, all with average nutritional value.

Also, in these meadows, there are plant species not consumed by animals or with a low degree of consumption, like *Lysimachia nummularia*, *Verbena officinalis*, respectively species harmful to the grassy carpet of the meadows, and here we mention *Juncus conglomeratus*, *Juncus effusus*, *Ononis spinosa* and *Crataegus monogyna*.

Table 1

Species Inventory and Pastoral Value Indicator

Species	% P.C.	I.C.	P.C. x I.C.
Poaceae	(44)		
<i>Agrostis stolonifera</i>	15	3	45
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	4	3	12
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	15	5	75
<i>Agrostis canina</i>	4	2	8
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	2	5	10
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	2	5	10
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	2	3	6
Fabaceae	(21)		
<i>Lathyrus pratensis</i>	2	4	8
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	+	4	0
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	2	4	8
<i>Mellilotus officinalis</i>	5	2	10
<i>Trifolium fragiferum</i>	1	3	3
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	1	4	4
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	10	4	40
<i>Vicia cracca</i>	+	3	0
Species from other botanical families	(35)		
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	2	0
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	2	1	2
<i>Daucus carota</i> ssp. <i>carota</i>	+	2	0
<i>Leontodon autumnalis</i>	+	1	0
<i>Plantago major</i>	1	2	2
<i>Plantago media</i>	1	2	2
<i>Verbena officinalis</i>	3	0	0
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	3	0	0
<i>Capsella bursa-pastoris</i>	+	0	0
<i>Centaurea jacea</i>	2	0	0
<i>Crepis biennis</i>	3	0	0
<i>Crataegus monogyna</i>	1	0	0
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	1	0	0
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	3	0	0
<i>Juncus conglomeratus</i>	+	0	0
<i>Juncus effusus</i>	5	0	0
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	4	0	0
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	3	0	0
<i>Rumex obtusifolius</i>	+	0	0
<i>Tanacetum vulgare</i>	3	0	0
TOTAL	100	–	245
Pastoral Value	–	–	49
Appreciation P. V.	Medium		

where: P. C. – participation in the grassy area, I. C. – fodder quality index,
P. V. – pastoral value indicator.

CONCLUSIONS

The pastoral value of the permanent *Agrostetum stoloniferae* meadow is 49, which indicates a medium value.

The most important action that should be taken is the development of a long-term pastoral arrangement, thus leading to the restoration of the habitats that form the pastures, planting native grassland plant species to improve forage quality and support wildlife habitat is a common practice in long-term pastoral management.

Long-term pastoral management refers to the planning and sustainable management of grazing lands over an extended period of time. This involves strategies such as grazing rotation, efficient management of livestock stocks, conservation of water and soil resources, as well as maintaining biodiversity.

Adopting such measures can ensure the maintenance of the health of grassland ecosystems and the sustainability of pastoral activities in the long term.

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SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVING THE ENTERTAINMENT ACTIVITIES IN THE STOKKER HOTEL IN ORADEA

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Abstract

Tourism is a sector, in the current period, in continuous modernization. Tourism service providers compete with each other by offering the widest possible range of tourism products and services. Together with accommodation, food and transport, entertainment services and agreement come to offer a completeness of the tourism industry.

In tourism, entertainment and leisure, it is the way to distribute tourist offers, through the diversity of its forms and applicability, it determines in itself an attraction, attracting an increasing number of tourists.

The tourist product that includes accommodation, meals and entertainment. In terms of accommodation, the hotel has 4 stars and this part corresponds to this classification. For meals, there is a restaurant with 40 seats, a wine cellar with 50 seats and a terrace with 120 seats. The food served is a traditional menu as well as chefs' specialties. As part of the agreement offered by this hotel, there are possibilities to visit the city of Oradea, both for the cultural and the historical side.

I conducted the research, through a questionnaire, on a number of 31 responses staying at this hotel during June 2023.

Keywords: guesthouses, summer months, entertainment program, various recreational.

INTRODUCTION

Oradea, formerly known as Oradea Mare, is the seat of Bihor County. It is located in the west of Romania, on the two banks of the Crișului Repede, in close proximity to the border with Hungary. For centuries, Oradea represented an important point in the area, being the most important commercial, social and cultural center.

Tourism in Oradea started to develop more and more since 2015, when together with Băile Felix, it participated in the Tourism Fair in Vienna.

Oradea is a point of attraction in tourism, thanks to its vast architectural and leisure offer. Here you can find 89 Art Nouveau buildings and monuments, 26 objectives classified as historical monuments, 25 objectives proposed for classification as historical monuments and 38 objectives with indisputable architectural value. Oradea also offers a wide range of opportunities to spend time outdoors, with numerous parks, an aqua park, over 30 km of bicycle track, and 8 km away from the city are Băile Felix and Băile May 1. Oradea offers numerous accommodation possibilities, starting with

two, three, four star hotels, guesthouses, aparthotels.

Among these offers is one of the most recommended three-star hotels due to its good positioning, Hotel Stokker.

Hotel Stokker located in the center of the city, on the European road E60, in the immediate vicinity of the Petofi Park, lends itself perfectly to both a one-night stay and a long-term stay.

The Stokker Hotel offers 8 parking spaces in front of the hotel exclusively for hotel customers, but also with the possibility of parking in public parking lots.

The Stokker Hotel has 9 single rooms, 7 double rooms and an apartment. The rooms are recently renovated, all have a double bed, minibar, air conditioning, LCD TV, private bathroom. And the double rooms also have a balcony. The apartment consists of a living room, a bedroom with a balcony. The hotel has WIFI throughout its location.

Within the hotel there is an "à la carte" restaurant with a superb terrace where there is also a mini play area, a wine cellar, which have also been recently renovated.

The restaurant has a capacity of 40 seats, 50 seats in the cellar, 120 seats on the terrace and 10-12 seats in the private event room.

To carry out this research, we used data from the company's registers, the register of entries, where we have total arrivals, total overnight stays and calculated the degree of occupancy of this unit. To create the customer portrait, we also took data from the hotel records.

The questionnaire is one of the most used methods in quantitative psychosociological research and our preferred tool. For this reason, we created a questionnaire with 13 questions, which we applied to the customers of this facility in June 2023.

The restaurant offers a traditional menu combined with current trends.

Material and method

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tourist product represents a set of tangible and intangible elements that procure certain services sought by one or more well-defined customers. All the tourist product is defined as a set of material goods and services capable of satisfying the tourism needs of a person between the moment of arrival and the moment of departure from the tourist destination.

Considering the above, we analyzed the situation encountered in the Stokker Hotel and tried to find suggestions for improving the tourist product offered.

Table no 1

Arrivals, overnight stays and occupancy of the Stokker Hotel in 2023

Month 2023	Total arrivals	Total nights	Occupancy
January	138	375	43.83 %
February	116	330	41.81 %
March	149	412	45.54 %
April	191	552	60.59 %
May	240	684	79.89 %
June	238	669	84.12 %
July	280	737	83.87 %
August	276	748	87.67 %
September	244	665	81.57 %
October	246	662	76.47 %
November	157	414	47.84 %
December	106	268	40.41 %

As we can see in the summer months, i.e. in season, the degree of occupancy is very good but does not reach 100%. We will suggest some proposals so that the degree of employment increases.

Regarding the country of origin of the customers of this unit, the majority are Romanians, followed by Hungarians and Spaniards, Germans, Poles.

Most of the customers book their stay by themselves and about 10 percent every month is contracted through booking, usually foreigners.

Following the questionnaire, we could see that the majority of those interviewed were between 18-25 years old, this confirms to us that the youth are much more open to appreciation and that they travel.

Your age is included:

31 de răspunsuri

For the second question by which we determine if they are in Oradea for the first time or if they have returned, the dominant answers show us that the majority of

respondents are at least 3 to 5 times. This response tells us that the establishment has loyal customers, so things can only get better.

Are you visiting Oradea?
31 responses

For 58% of the respondents, the purpose of this trip is tourism, followed by those who travel for work

Care este scopul călătoriei

31 de răspunsuri

We wanted to see why these respondents chose to stay at this unit and most of them looked for the reviews on the Internet, that majority who have an average age of 18-25 years, for whom they most easily come into contact with the phone and for any confusion

ask questions on the internet. In second place, they found out about this hotel from friends, relatives, former customers who were satisfied and recommended.

De ce ați ales să vă cazați la Hotelul Stokker?

30 de răspunsuri

In terms of accommodation, customers already know what to expect regarding the rooms from the pictures on the internet. For the table, the clientele is larger than what is accommodated considering the number of seats at the restaurant, terrace and wine

cellar. The part we are trying to improve is the entertainment part. and here we see that 73.3% of the respondents believe that a playground would be necessary, so in the future this aspect should also be taken into account.

Unitatea la care v-ați cazat ați dori să dispună de un loc de joacă special pentru copii?

30 de răspunsuri

The respondents' favorite activities are quite well-arranged and cultural activities predominate at 38.7%, followed by

recreational ones such as Spas, but culinary experiences are also ranked third.

La ce activități ați dori să luați parte pe perioada șederii d-voastră în Oradea?

31 de răspunsuri

- activități sportive
- culturale (teatru, opere cinematografice, muzee, etc)
- activități recreative (piscina)
- activități în natură
- monumente istorice
- experiențe culinare
- Parc distracții
- Toate menționate mai sus

We also wanted to find out if those who dined in this establishment would like a live music

program or not. 76.7% said they wanted live music.

Unitatea la care v-ați cazat ați dori să aiba program de muzică live la cină?

30 de răspunsuri

- Da
- Nu

For the SPA center a number of 83.3% are willing, more than those who want live music.

Unitatea la care v-ați cazat ați dori să fie un centru SPA?

30 de răspunsuri

- Da
- Nu

Due to the fact that the city of Oradea through visit Oradea already has a tourism development plan in this area, we were thinking of a collaboration so that customers

can benefit from free or reduced entrance fees. 90% of respondents would like to have freebies in their entertainment program.

Dacă ați beneficia de activități cu intrări gratuite la diferite obiective a-ți dori să vizitați orașul în extra sezon?

31 de răspunsuri

The fact that 74.2% I have mass in the analyzed unit indicates that there is no need for improvements in this chapter for the time

being. We also consider the number of accommodation places is much smaller than the number of chairs for serving the table.

Pentru a lua masa iei în considerare oferta unității de cazare sau alte sugestii?

31 de răspunsuri

For the next question, we thought that there are customers who estimate their minimum and maximum spending for the stay and whether this is an obstacle that affects the

desire to visit. We could solve this fact with a collaboration contract between state institutions and our society.

V-ar afecta cheltuielile dorința de vizitare?

31 de răspunsuri

We would be interested if these customers already come with some well-defined points of visit, that is, surely if they go to Oradea I

would like to come here, or leave this aspect of things to chance. 54.8% know what to do if they arrive in Oradea.

În momentul în care ai ales să vii în vizită în acest oraș ți ai făcut un itinerariu?

31 de răspunsuri

Customers generally form their opinion before arriving in the locality, respectively in the accommodation unit, but they still take into account the opinions of others. 41.4% take into account the suggestions of those at the reception of the accommodation unit,

which make the unit responsible in this regard as well. 34.5% take into account the suggestions of those on the Internet, especially the young ones. 4.1% are those who spoke with people who have already been here.

Sugestiile pe care le iei în considerare sunt:

29 de răspunsuri

CONCLUSIONS

Leisure tourism is a trip made for the purpose of recreation, rest or spending free time. The development of activities and services that meet these requirements is determined, on the one hand, by the trends of evolution in the content of vacations, which, today, can no longer be limited to offering tourists only accommodation and dining conditions, and, on the other hand, part, of reconsidering the value of free time.

The deepening of the competition in the field of tourism offer, as well as the changes that occurred in the consumption behavior of the customers, determined the approach in a new vision of the hotel product. In order for activities as active or passive participants; training clients in new activities, other than those they carry out in the usual way during the year, returning to childhood and to the essence of things; creating a pleasant atmosphere throughout the stay

The clients of this hotel are some of those who visit the city of Oradea as the purpose of this trip, another part travel because of their workplace and others because of some events that take place in this locality.

For all customers, the management of the Stokker hotel will prepare flyers with the locations to visit at smaller mats due to the introduction of the hotel in the visit Oradea network, a live music band during dinner in principle at 18:00 and 23:00 on weekends and a playground near the terrace. With these improvements, it is hoped to increase the number of guests of the boarding house during the off-season as well.

the hotel offer to become more attractive, it was structurally enriched, adapted and enhanced by the use of new animation techniques. Today, animation is a mandatory component of the activities carried out by all types of hotels and adapted to the specifics of the offer and the customers. Animation in the hotel is an organized and adapted activity that aims to: creating all the conditions for the party in a way that is as pleasant and useful as possible; informing customers and stimulating the consumption of hotel services with and without payment; training clients in various recreational, cultural - sports

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EXPLORING INNOVATIVE PASTURE MANAGEMENT AND CERTIFICATION POTENTIAL IN ROMANIA WITHIN A EUROPEAN FRAMEWORK

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study explores the interplay between traditional grazing practices and quality food certification in the European agri-food sector, emphasizing Romania's potential for sustainable agriculture. Grazing, vital for ecological integrity and biodiversity, is examined alongside the significance of Geographical Indications (GIs) in endorsing grazing-based production for high-quality dairy and meat products. Focusing on Romania, the research highlights the untapped potential for certified grazing practices to enhance agricultural sustainability, economic competitiveness, and access to premium markets. It calls for aligning rural development with bioeconomic and ecoeconomic principles and addresses the need for systematic research to support policy development for sustainable grazing certifications.

Keywords: Grazing Management, Quality Product Certification, Rural Development, Agricultural Technology, and Innovations

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INTRODUCTION

The confluence of grazing practices and quality food certification within the European agri-food sector offers a compelling narrative of sustainability, tradition, and innovation. Traditionally, grazing has been the linchpin of ruminant animal management, closely aligning with their natural behaviors and supporting the ecological integrity of farmlands (Jackson A. et al., 2018). This ancient practice, revered for its myriad benefits ranging from biodiversity enhancement to soil health improvement, faces modern challenges that necessitate a harmonious blend of tradition and innovation (D. Xiong et al., 2016). Amidst varying attitudes towards grazing among European farmers, influenced by an amalgam of local and broader socioeconomic factors (van den Pol-van Dasselaar A et al., 2021; JRC Policy Insights, 2018), there emerges a paradigm of quality food certification. This paradigm, rooted in agroecological principles, seeks to validate and valorize the intrinsic value of grazing-based production systems. These systems are acclaimed not only for yielding high-quality dairy and meat products but also for their positive contributions to societal well-being and environmental stewardship (Provenza, F. et al., 2019). Central to this narrative is the role of

Geographical Indications (GIs), which offer a legal framework to protect and promote products deeply intertwined with their place of origin, reflecting unique local environmental and human factors (El Hadad-Gauthie, et al., 2022; Vanhonacker, F, et al. 2010). This introduction sets the stage for a detailed exploration of the current knowledge surrounding grazing practices, challenges therein, and the synergistic potential of quality certifications to foster a sustainable, productive, and culturally rich agricultural future in Europe.

THE CURRENT STATE OF KNOWLEDGE

Grazing, a practice as old as agriculture itself, continues to play a critical role in the management of ruminant animals across Europe, promoting a way of life that is in harmony with nature and animal welfare. Recent surveys have illuminated a strong preference for grazing among European citizens, who recognize its benefits for ecosystem functions, such as enhancing vegetation growth, species diversity, and soil health in grasslands that have degraded over time (Jackson A. et al., 2018; D. Xiong et al., 2016). However, the transition towards sustainable agricultural futures through practices like organic farming and mixed grazing, which are known to bolster biodiversity and animal welfare, requires a significant

alignment of farmer attitudes with these environmentally friendly practices (Markiewicz-Kęszycka et al., 2023). In this context, the strategic management insights offered by (Iagar and Iagar, 2017) suggest that aligning rural development with bioeconomic and ecoeconomic principles can further support the sustainability of these practices, emphasizing a holistic approach that incorporates environmental protection and economic viability.

The challenges to grazing are multifaceted, influenced by a spectrum of factors from farm size and land fragmentation to the coexisting of large carnivores in regions such as Italy and Romania, adding layers of complexity to the management and welfare of grazing animals (Meuret, M. et al., 2020). Despite these challenges, the proven benefits of grazing on farmers' income, biodiversity conservation, carbon emission reduction, and food safety, among others, underscore its indispensability (Van den Pol-van Dasselaar, A. et al. 2020). (Iagar and Iagar 2017) further highlight the importance of strategic management in addressing these complex challenges within the framework of bioeconomics and ecoeconomics, suggesting that such an approach can help mitigate the impact of these challenges while promoting sustainable development in rural areas.

Simultaneously, the discourse around food quality certification, particularly through the lens of Geographical Indications (GIs), highlights a growing consumer demand for products that are not only of high quality but also imbued with a sense of place and tradition. GIs serve as a bridge between traditional grazing practices and modern market economies, offering a way to protect and promote products that embody specific local environmental and human factors, often summarized by the term "terroir" (Pick, B, et al. 2021; Leonardo, C, et al. 2018).

Integrating the perspectives of grazing management and quality certification, therefore, presents an opportunity to address the dual challenges of sustaining traditional agricultural practices and meeting contemporary environmental and consumer expectations. This integration not only champions sustainable land use and conservation but also positions traditional foods within a framework that can leverage geographical indications for product differentiation in global markets, thus enhancing the economic viability of sustainable grazing practices.

CERTIFIED GRAZING PRODUCTS IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

The European Union is home to a

diverse array of certified grazing products, each reflecting the unique agricultural traditions and environmental conditions of its region. These certifications are not just markers of quality; they are testament to the commitment of farmers, producers, and entire communities towards sustainable agriculture and ethical animal husbandry. Here's a closer look at some of the notable certifications across the EU:

Ireland: A Leader in Dairy Certification

- **National Dairy Council Guarantee (NDC):** This certification, specific to Ireland, underscores products originating from local, sustainably managed dairy farms. It emphasizes grass-fed dairy production, a cornerstone of Ireland's dairy industry, renowned for its lush, green pastures. The NDC mark assures consumers of the local sourcing and processing of dairy products, highlighting the Irish dairy sector's commitment to sustainability and quality.

- **Bord Bia - The Irish Food Board:** The Bord Bia Grass Fed Standard is another pivotal certification, ensuring that dairy and beef products come from animals that have grazed on grass for a substantial portion of the year. This standard not only showcases Ireland's natural advantage in grass-based farming but also aligns with consumer expectations for natural, sustainably produced food.

France: Emphasizing Pasture-Based Milk

- **Lait de pâturage:** This French certification is dedicated to milk products from cows grazed in open pastures for at least 150 days a year. It guarantees that the milk comes from cows that have access to natural grazing, aligning with agroecological principles and consumer demand for transparency and sustainability in food production.

The Netherlands: Promoting Open Grazing

- **Stichting Weidegang (Weidegang Foundation):** In the Netherlands, the Weidegang certification indicates dairy products from farms where cows have access to pastures for a minimum of 120 days per year, for at least 6 hours a day. This practice not only supports animal welfare but also contributes to the iconic Dutch pastoral landscapes, enhancing biodiversity and soil health.

Germany: Advocating Extensive Grazing Practices

- **PRO WEIDELAND:** Germany's Pro Weideland certification focuses on extensive grazing practices, requiring at least 120 days of grazing per year with specific land area allocations per cow. It champions animal welfare, biodiversity, and the production of high-

quality, grass-fed dairy and meat products free from GMO feed.

Portugal: Celebrating Biodiversity and Tradition

- Carne Barrosã: A standout example of certified grazing products in Portugal is the Carne Barrosã, a beef product from the Barrosã cattle breed, known for its exceptional quality and taste. The certification ensures that these cattle are raised in extensive grazing systems in Portugal's northern regions, adhering to traditional practices that support biodiversity and sustainable land management. This certification not only preserves a cultural heritage but also promotes the environmental benefits of grazing in maintaining the landscape and supporting rural economies.

Spain: Advancing Regenerative Grazing

- De Yerba: Spain's approach to certified grazing products is epitomized by the De Yerba certification, which focuses on regenerative grazing practices. This certification is part of a broader movement towards sustainable agriculture that prioritizes soil health, biodiversity, and carbon sequestration. Products bearing the De Yerba certification come from farms that employ holistic management practices, ensuring that animals graze in a way that regenerates the land, improves water retention, and enhances ecosystem services.

Italy: Bridging Tradition with Sustainability

- LaugenRind: Italy, with its diverse landscapes ranging from the Alpine north to the Mediterranean south, offers a unique context for grazing certification. The LaugenRind certification represents a commitment to sustainable beef production, where cattle are grazed in the pristine Alpine meadows of South Tyrol. This certification assures consumers of the ethical raising of cattle, emphasizing traditional grazing practices that contribute to the maintenance of alpine biodiversity and the production of high-quality beef known for its distinct flavor and nutritional properties.

Austria: Emphasizing Quality through Traditional Practices

- Heumilch (Hay Milk): As previously mentioned, Austria's Heumilch certification underscores the country's commitment to traditional dairy farming practices. By requiring that cows are fed exclusively on dried hay and fresh grass, avoiding fermented feedstuffs like silage, this certification ensures the production of high-quality milk with distinctive taste characteristics. The Heumilch certification is a testament to Austria's dedication to biodiversity, environmental sustainability, and

the preservation of its dairy farming heritage.

THE CURRENT LANDSCAPE AND OPPORTUNITIES IN ROMANIA

Traditional Grazing Practices

In Romania, traditional grazing practices, particularly for sheep and cattle, have been maintained over centuries, adapting to the country's varied climatic and geographical conditions. These practices, deeply embedded in the country's rural culture, offer a blueprint for sustainable agriculture that preserves biodiversity and supports ecosystem services.

Recognized Products with Geographical Indications

Romania has already made strides in recognizing the value of its agricultural products through geographical indications (GIs), such as "Telemea de Ibănești" (PDO), "Telemea de Sibiu" (PGI), and "Cașcavalul de Săveni" (PGI). These certifications, while focusing on product quality and regional specificity, also implicitly underscore the importance of traditional farming and grazing practices. The next logical step could be to introduce certifications that specifically highlight sustainable grazing practices, offering a clear link between the method of production and the quality of the final product.

PROSPECTS FOR GRAZING CERTIFICATION IN ROMANIA

By formalizing grazing certifications, Romania could further promote practices that enhance biodiversity, soil health, and carbon sequestration. Such certifications could help safeguard the country's extensive natural pastures and meadows, ensuring they are managed sustainably. The development of strategic options for the rural area through industries such as the food sector, as discussed by (Iagăru et al. 2014), underscores the importance of sustainable practices in enhancing the availability and distribution of high-quality food products. This approach not only supports environmental objectives but also aligns with the economic development goals within the Romanian rural context.

Globally, consumers are increasingly seeking products that are not only of high quality but also produced in an environmentally friendly and ethical manner. Echoing this sentiment, a study by Oroian et al. (2022) on biodynamic agriculture in the Transylvania area of Romania reveals an emerging preference among farmers for sustainable practices. Despite biodynamic agriculture being less familiar among the broader agricultural community, it is recognized for its

potential to protect biodiversity and the environment. Importantly, the study suggests that biodynamic farms can be profitable, given the growing consumer interest in healthy, sustainably produced products. This insight underpins the notion that Romanian products, enhanced by certified sustainable grazing practices, could gain access to premium markets and achieve higher prices, fulfilling consumer demand for sustainability.

Certified grazing practices could provide a significant boost to rural economies in Romania, supporting small-scale farmers and pastoralists by providing them with a competitive advantage in both domestic and international markets. This could lead to revitalized rural communities and a stronger connection between consumers and the origins of their food.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

A notable gap exists in Romanian literature regarding the systematic study and promotion of certified grazing practices and their correlation with high-quality agricultural products. This oversight underscores a critical area for future research and policy development, particularly as Romania seeks to enhance its agricultural sustainability and economic competitiveness on both a European and global scale.

The myriad benefits of grazing, well-documented in broader European studies, highlight the ecological, economic, and social advantages of such practices. Adopting eco-technical practices within grassland agroecosystems, as recommended by Iagaru et al. (2017), could lead to improved pastoral value and biodiversity conservation in Romanian grasslands. However, the lack of a formalized framework for grazing certification in Romania suggests an untapped potential to elevate the status and marketability of Romanian agricultural products. Establishing a certification for grazing products in Romania could serve as a benchmark for quality, sustainability, and ethical production, aligning with increasing consumer demands for transparency and environmental stewardship.

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WHO KNOWS? RESTAURANT

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

WHO KNOWS? is a special fusion restaurant concept, redefining the dining experience with its innovative approach of "up to the chef, not up to you!" Empowering customers to be a part of creating their culinary experience by inputting personal preferences, dietary requirements, mood, and special occasions, through this data-driven approach, clients can effortlessly customize their reservations. The restaurant is located in culturally diverse urban hubs like Paris, targeting a demographic of curious, open-minded aged 30–60, individual or couples international cuisine enthusiasts. Missions of the Four Pillars: First, answering the ubiquitous dilemma of "what should I eat today?" Our menu promises delightful surprises based on the customer's data. Second, accessible fusion: inspired by the founders' global travels, we offer fusion cuisine as a harmonious blend of diverse culinary traditions that is enjoyable for every guest. Third, storytelling with rich dish histories and seasonal ingredients promotes sustainability, supporting local farmers and the environment. At WHO KNOWS? Every dish is a combination of chef's inspiration, ingredient choices, and cultural heritage.

Key words: Fusion food restaurant, personalized dishes, curiosity, Who knows? Application, seasonal ingredients.

INTRODUCTION

Over the years, the restaurant business has never ceased to evolve. Today's restaurateurs face new challenges.

The first challenge is to respond to customers' demands and desires. *The Evolution of the Restaurant Business: A Culinary Journey Through Time* illustrates these changes: "From the humble beginnings in ancient eateries to the sophisticated and diverse establishments of today, the industry has been shaped by societal shifts, technological advancements, and the ever-changing palate of the consumers. Indeed, restaurateurs have to keep up with the times, making room not only for new technological advances but also for increasingly demanding customer requirements, such as ethnic and environmentally-friendly cuisine. As a result, the industry has adapted, and we now find a wide variety of restaurants worldwide, from fusion restaurants to green star awards.

The second challenge is to create an experience through the food, but also through the restaurant itself. They expect to live an experience, a moment that is out of their daily lives. To achieve this, restaurateurs are turning to new technologies, whose usefulness has been proven by the pandemic in 2019-2020. QR codes, apps and digital interactions are being implemented in restaurants more than ever. What's more, since the early 2000s, chefs have been stepping out of their kitchens, more and more of them becoming public personalities, taking the liberty of developing their cuisine towards more personal and artistic inspirations. These notions, as the *Global Tech Award* document explains, are changing the environment and the experience, reinforced by the identity and world of the chef: "Restaurant Technology is not just about digital tools; it's a journey that enhances the

experience and transforms traditional dining norms.

As already mentioned, the Covid 19 pandemic has had a major impact on restaurants. In fact, no restaurants were open at that time. Since the reopening of the restaurants, this experience has played on customers' expectations and desires. Today, restaurant technology and human interaction must be on a par. Technology allows us to be as efficient as possible, while interaction is the primary reason why people return to eat out. In France, the culture of the meal has always been strong: the diner is not just the dish, but the people and the conversations that take place around it. In the article *Évolution des envies des Français en matière de restauration*, we observe that the three most important desires for customers are: "Gourmandise and the pleasure of the senses", "Technology has been put at the service of restaurateurs to give customers confidence" and "the desire to return to human ties".

MATERIAL AND METHODS

SWOT analysis

WHO KNOWS?" The restaurant's chef-driven, personalized dining is set to thrill adventurous foodies around the world. By perfectly combining tech and culinary art to tailor meals to individual tastes, and focusing on sustainable, local ingredients, it hits all the right trends. With its unique concept and high engagement, this startup is a promising winner in the urban food scene! *(WHO KNOWS? We could be the NEXT Unicorn!)*

Target group

If you have a huge curiosity, are open-minded, or perhaps consider yourself a traveling lover who enjoys international cuisine and is ready to pay for a premium as well as special food and dining experiences, Who knows? extends a warm invitation for you to step through our doors tonight!

The difficulties

1. Supply and Logistic management: Ingredients.
2. Staff: chef, services, software team due to high expertise and difficulty of finding the replacement.

3. Demand fluctuations and Marketing (to be able to go Viral and well-known).
4. Customer's satisfaction and Expectation; to be able to satisfy the customer's expectations.
5. Variable costs management: restaurants generally have many components and costs to be carefully considered and managed.
6. Restaurant System management: to effectively manage the restaurant on a daily basis.
7. Others uncontrol factors

Cost Analysis

At "Who knows?" restaurant, our costs primarily fall into four main categories: human resources, facilities, materials, and other expenses. The majority of our expenses are allocated to human resources because we prioritize the happiness and satisfaction of our employees, believing that their joy translates into exceptional service and the high quality of our food. Our chefs are seasoned experts in international cuisine, drawing from rich experiences and extensive travel to create fusion dishes that cater to our diverse clientele. The second significant expense category is facilities, particularly in our location in Paris, a vibrant tourist hub known for its diverse nationalities, cultures, and lifestyles, which significantly impacts our rental costs.

Despite these challenges, we remain committed to providing an unforgettable

dining experience

that captures the essence of authenticity and satisfies the discerning tastes of our international customers.

The third component of our expenses is attributed to materials and ingredients. At "Who knows?", we prioritize the highest quality ingredients sourced from around the globe to ensure the utmost satisfaction of our cherished patrons, all within the framework of our fusion cuisine concept. However, we maintain a commitment to utilizing European-sourced staples such as bread, grains, dairy, meat products, and seasonal fruits and vegetables, procured directly from local farmers. This not only guarantees freshness and quality but also fosters sustainability by supporting local agriculture—a cornerstone of our ethos.

Additionally, the unique demands of fusion cuisine necessitate specialized cooking and preparation equipment, often sourced globally and contributing to higher costs.

Lastly, miscellaneous expenses encompass vital aspects such as application development and maintenance, marketing, and insurance. While these constitute a smaller portion of our budget, they are pivotal to our operations. To optimize marketing expenditure, we focus on online platforms and tailor our content to align with customer trends. Software development is outsourced, with regular maintenance intervals based on customer feedback. Moreover, comprehensive insurance coverage—including Property Insurance, Cyber Liability Insurance, and health insurance for all staff—ensures protection and support in times of illness or emergencies, both for our valued employees and our establishment as a whole.

Marketing Strategies through 4 Ps: Product, Price, Place, Promotion

1)Product: curiosity, the unique selling proposition of personalized, chef-driven fusion cuisine, premium taste and quality from the seasonal locally sourced ingredients, a surprisingly wide range of tastes and dietary preferences.

Our proud logo

What can you expect from WHO KNOWS?

Method of reservation

Interest —> Download a WHO KNOWS?
Application —> Filled in your informations —
>Make a reservation —> Wait for your special moment (dine-In)

WHO KNOWS? Application

What is inside ?

2)Price: Premium price strategy with 99 EUR/ person and limited 30 customers per night, psychology pricing strategy through old number which is 99 EUR.

With 99 EUR/ person, the restaurant capability of having maximum 30 customers per night

Table 1. Cost and Revenue Comparison

REVENUE	€99/person,	30
Per Night	2,970	
Per Month	77,220	
Annual Revenue	926,640	
Cost / year	454,159.92	
Profits/ year	472,480.08	

3)Place:

- Strategic locations in culturally diverse urban hubs like Paris to maximize visibility and foot traffic. Plus it is easy to access due to the good availability of public transportation.
- Create an inviting, cozy and comfortable dining atmosphere that reflects the fusion concept with an open kitchen for the customers to enjoy their special moment.

4)Promotion: Utilize digital marketing channels such as social media (Instagram, Facebook, YOUTUBE and TIKTOK), and online advertising to reach and engage with customers. As well as partner with local influencers, food bloggers, and media outlets to generate buzz and word-of-mouth publicity.

Follow US !

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

As setting the price at 99 EUR per person resulting in 926,640 EUR revenue per year while we are trying our best to minimize the costs which come out to be approximately 454,159.92 EUR per year meaning there is a possibility to make a profit in the first year about 472480.08 EUR. However, while the restaurant's focus on premium taste and quality is commendable, the high pricing strategy of 99 EUR per person may pose a barrier to entry for some potential customers. Also, considering the high price of dine-in, meaning the high level of satisfaction, to cope with these expectations, good management and carefully monitoring feedback and food quality are the keys.

Secondly, the significant investment in human resources, particularly chef expertise and customer service, underscores the restaurant's commitment to delivering exceptional dining experiences. However, this reliance on skilled personnel may also introduce operational risks, such as turnover or labor shortages. It's essential for "WHO KNOWS?" to implement robust recruitment, training, and retention strategies to mitigate these risks and maintain consistency in service quality.

Furthermore, the emphasis on locally sourced ingredients and sustainability aligns with current consumer preferences and industry trends. By supporting local farmers and prioritizing freshness and quality, the restaurant not only enhances its culinary offerings but also strengthens its brand identity as a socially responsible establishment. Nevertheless, maintaining this commitment to sustainability amidst fluctuating market conditions and supply chain challenges may require ongoing diligence and adaptability.

Lastly, the restaurant's marketing strategies, including digital outreach and partnerships with influencers, demonstrate a proactive approach to building brand awareness and driving customer engagement. While these efforts are essential for attracting new patrons and maintaining visibility in a competitive market, continuous monitoring and optimization of marketing campaigns and customer feedback are essential to ensure effectiveness and return on investment for the future.

CONCLUSIONS

Today, the aim of our fusion restaurant concept, Who Knows? is to respond to customers' desires, while offering them a surprising gustatory and human experience.

Customers will be able to enter all their personal information (allergies, cravings, dislikes, etc.) on the restaurant app. This data will be accessible to the chef who, with the help of his brigade, will prepare a unique dish for each customer. As soon as the dish is ready, the waiters will be able to explain the composition of the dish, the ingredients and the chef's reflections on the plate in question. At the end of the service, the chef himself will meet the guests in the dining room to get their feedback. In this way, we address all the issues raised in this article. Not only are our customers' desires the basis of our recipes, but the use of electronics does not encroach on the human touch and warmth of our waiters. Thank to them, but also to the dishes of the chef and his brigade, we are convinced that each and every one of our customers will leave this restaurant conquered and positively surprised.

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ANNEX:

Type	Sub type	Monthly (EUR)	Annually (EUR)
HR	Owners, 2 peoples	2000	24000
	Staffs, 2 peoples	3000	36000
	Manager, 1 people	3500	42000
	Big chef, 1 people	5000	60000
	Cooks, 2 peoples	3000	36000
	Total	16500	198000
Material	Ingredients	7000	84000
	Equipments	350	4200
	Furniture	200	2400

Facility	Rent	11000	132000
	Utilities	2000	24000
	Restaurant permit	16.66	200
	Total	13016.66	156200
Others	App Development	100	1200
	Maintainant	50	600
	Marketing	100	1200
	Property Insurance	30	360
	Employee Insurance	500	5000
	Total	780	9360
	Total	37846.6	454160

	Total	7550	90600

EXPLORING POTASSIUM AND SODIUM COMPOSITION IN HUNGARIAN SORGHUM GRAINS AS KEY MARKERS OF CEREAL GRAIN QUALITY

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Research article

Abstract

Potassium and sodium minerals are essential indicators for assessing the quality of sorghum grains. Therefore, the reported level in all sorghum products must be evaluated, which could provide valuable information on the potential texture and flavour of the final sorghum products.

*The study looked at the contents of dry matter (D.M), total protein, potassium (K) and sodium (Na) minerals in Hungarian sorghum (*S. bicolor*) grains to evaluate the detected ratio on the whole grain and dehulled grain products, which can contribute to the nutritional quality of the measured sorghum grains, that were collected from three distinct sorghum production sites in Hungary. The coupled Plasma Optical Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-OES) method was employed to determine K mg/kg⁻¹ and Na mg/kg⁻¹ in the sorghum varieties. Statistical analysis showed significant ($P < 0.05$) variations attributed to variety and region groups.*

The results showed that the amount of potassium in the Hungarian sorghum varieties was higher than the previous levels reported in the literature. The average potassium levels in the Kacarg, Nyíregyháza, and Szeged regions were 3939.7 mg/kg⁻¹, 3679.7 mg/kg⁻¹, and 4344.6 mg/kg⁻¹, respectively. The highest average of Na mg/kg⁻¹ of (189.8 mg/kg-1) was recorded by the Alföldi 1 variety sourced from Szeged; the recorded value was revealed in the grain bran attributed to the dehulling process. Despite a high level of Na mg/kg-1 in the Alföldi 1 variety from the Szeged site, the ratio of K: Na was 27:1. Furthermore, the study showed that the protein levels of whole grains, endosperm (grits) and bran ranged from 16.2%, 17.0%, and 15.4%, respectively.

The findings provided valuable insight into updated information on the investigated nutrients in Hungarian sorghum varieties, which can benefit breeders and producers concerned about sorghum sector advancements, contributing to Hungarian sorghum's nutritional value and potential applications in the food and sorghum product industries.

Keywords: sorghum grains, dehulling, potassium, sodium, region

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INTRODUCTION

The productivity of sorghum in western regions is contingent upon its capacity to flourish in hot, arid circumstances and its resistance to infestation, which maintains production and sustainability (Khalifa & Eltahir, 2023). Sorghum is a highly adaptable crop among the top five cereal crops worldwide. It is also a vital food source, fodder, feed, and fuel (Kakabouki et al., 2021).

Several approaches are followed in sorghum production in Hungary; it involves nutrient management through various breeding enhancements (Nagy et al., 2023). Inductively Coupled Plasma-Optical Emission Spectrometry

(ICP-OES) is a common, accurate procedure utilized for element content detection for various food raw materials, which can give nutrients a good insight into foodstuff composition (Khan et al., 2014). Crops have advanced mechanisms to control the equilibrium of potassium and sodium ions, crucial for maintaining cellular balance, supporting metabolic functions, and improving resilience to diverse harsh environments. This has resulted in high-grain quality (Mazzaferro et al., 2021; Kubar, 2018). However, potassium and sodium minerals have interdependent functions in facilitating the proper functioning of one another. Sodium may serve as an osmotic

co-factor when there is inadequate potassium availability, given certain circumstances (Thorne & Maathuis, 2022; Keisham et al., 2018). Dry matter (DM) is a useful metric for assessing the quality of cereal grains. It affects the concentration of minerals in processed grains and can improve the digestibility of the final products (Puntigam et al., 2021). In addition, the scientific research showed that the High-quality sorghum genotypes were distinguished by a diverse range of protein contents, ranging from 6% to 18% (Adebo & Kesa, 2023; Espinosa-Ramírez & Serna-Saldívar, 2016). The quantities of potassium and sodium significantly influence the texture and quality of cereal grain products. Accordingly, potassium chloride has similar benefits to sodium chloride in the production of dough and bread (Chen et al., 2018).

Whole grains inherently possess a naturally low amount of sodium, which may differ across various consumed grains (Henney et al., 2010). Survey data from previous reports shows fluctuations in the potassium content of processed cereals, including cereals made from bran and refined flour (Food Safety Authority of Ireland, 2022). Maintaining a balanced ratio of potassium and sodium is crucial for optimizing cereal foods' quality and nutritional value (Food Safety Authority of Ireland, 2022). Excessive sodium levels may lead to health issues, including high blood pressure and heart disease (Winiarska-Mieczan et al., 2016). Potassium plays a vital role in the regulation of blood pressure and the facilitation of several physiological processes (Stone et al., 2016). Consuming cereal products could boost daily potassium intake. According to the standards set by the World Health Organization (WHO), individuals should aim to consume a daily amount of potassium ranging from 3,500 to 4,700 mg (90 mmol). Additionally, it is recommended to limit sodium intake to less than 2,000 mg (86 mmol) per person per day (Drewnowski et al., 2015),

The study aimed to analyse the levels of potassium (K) and sodium (Na) minerals in white sorghum (Farmsugro 180) and red sorghum (Alfoldi 1) cultivated in three distinct sorghum sites in Hungary: Kacarg, Nyíregyháza, and Szeged. The investigation can substantially contribute to evaluating the quality of whole and husked grains from the respective varieties.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

1.2. MATERIALS

We obtained identical samples of three sorghum racial variants from three locations in Hungary: Kacarg (loam clay), Nyíregyháza (sandy), and Szeged (Luvisol). The samples were dehydrated. The grain samples were ground using the Retsch SK-3 hammer mill with a 1 mm screen. A meticulous grinding procedure was applied to the whole-grain samples. The experiment's findings were compared between the whole grains (ground) and the husked grains (husker).

2.2. HUSKING PROCEDURE

The research used the (TM05C husker), Satake Engineering Co.'s apparatus to dehull sorghum grain, which produced two distinct fractions: bran and endosperm (grits).

2.3. DETERMINATION OF THE CRUDE PROTEIN

As described in the reference (ISO 20483:2013, 2013), the Kjeldahl technique was used to measure the nitrogen levels in the sorghum samples. Moreover, a block heater was set at 420–430 °C for 2 h after the cooling step, followed by the digestion step. Furthermore, we used the Converter 6.25 to determine the crude protein content.

1.4. DETERMINATION OF DRY MATTER

The procedure was applied by following measurements reported by (Hellevang, 1995), started by placing the samples in an oven adjusted to a temperature range of 130–135 °C. The specimen was desiccated in the oven until it attained a uniform weight. Determining the mass of the desiccated specimen: The dehydrated sample was carefully removed from the oven. The weight of the dried sample was recorded, and dry matter content of the sample was determined using the following formula:

Dry Matter Content (%) =

$$\frac{\text{Weight of Dried Sample}}{\text{Weight of Original Sample}} \times 100$$

2.5. DETECTION OF MINERAL CONTENTS

The grain samples were examined with the applying accuracy procedure: We employed,

BCR CRM 189 (whole grain), as accreditation of measurements (John & Taylor, 2023). The measurements were conducted in many phases (Kovács et al., 1996). We used the iCAP 7400 apparatus from Thermo Scientific, which utilizes inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) technology. The chemical reagents required for conducting element assays at certain wavelengths, namely K 404.721 nm and Na 330.237 nm, were acquired from VWR International Ltd. (Geldenaaksebaan, Belgium). We quantified 1 g The materials underwent a process of aqueous acid digestion, which included both predigesting and digestion phases. The specimens were exposed to a temperature of 60°C for 30 minutes using a model block (MIM OE-718/A) for the digestion process after adding 10 ml of nitric acid (HNO₃, 69% v/v). After cooling, 3 cm³ of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30% v/v) was added to the samples, which were then transferred to the first digestion phase. We elevated the temperature of the digester to 120°C. We placed it for 90 minutes before deactivating it and allowing it to stabilise for of 10 to 20 minutes. add volume of 50 cm³ using ultra-pure water originated from (Millipore SAS Co, Ltd, France). And was followed by filtration process using filter paper (MN 640W) to strain the homogenized solution. The element contents were determined and expressed as mg/kg⁻¹.

2.7. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The SPSS 28.0 statistical analysis program was utilized to differences detection. The performed data sets were followed normality property, and followed by An ANOVA one-way analysis was used to find out variability in dry matter and total protein. In addition, a distinct model was used to assess variance in mineral content group, using a significance value of $P \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings were indicated the difference of K mg/kg⁻¹ and Na mg/kg⁻¹ among the investigated varieties ($P < 0.05$), result aligned

with previous study by (Osman et al., 2022). while, the variability of the mineral contents, dry matter and total protein attributed to site source (Desta et al., 2023). Showed a significance value $P < 0.05$, as was interpreted in Table 1.

3.1. DRY MATTER

As was mentioned above, dry matter content can affect the mineral concentration of cereal grains (Puntigam et al., 2021). No mentionable variation was detected, according to endosperm (grits) and bran, as they showed averages of 861 g/kg⁻¹ and 890 g/kg⁻¹, respectively. Even though the dry matter percentage varied slightly, the average of the whole grains, which was 889%, showed that the dry matter content had re-concentrated on the husked grains ($P < 0.05$), as shown in Table 1. The revealed level of dry matter in the tested grain varieties was higher than the reported level by (Osman et al., 2022), where the reported level ranged from 720 to 775 g/kg dry matter (DM).

3.2. TOTAL PROTEIN

The protein concentration in sorghum grains varied substantially depending on whether the grain was whole or processed, and processes such as dehulling could alter it (Table 1). The Farmsugro180 variety had the highest average protein content, ranging from 10.0 g/kg⁻¹ (bran) to 17.5 g/kg⁻¹ (endosperm), which differed from whole grains; in contrast, the Alfoldi 1 variety from Nyíregyháza and Kacarg had the lowest protein, ranging from 17.5 g/kg⁻¹ ($P > 0.05$), as shown in Table 1. The finding was similar to a previous study (Adebo & Kesa, 2023); the study emphasized the total protein content variation based on whole and dehulled grains. Another study showed that the analysis of protein derived from the whole and decorticated sorghum genotypes to determine their functionality and characterisation (Espinosa-Ramírez & Serna-Saldívar, 2016). In their study, (János et al., 2016). found that the protein content in Hungarian sorghum hybrids varied between 10.25% and 14.25%. Certain

Table 1. Descriptive analysis of nutrient content on diverse sorghum varieties

Variables	Grain parts	D.M g/kg ⁻¹	Protein g/kg ⁻¹	K mg/kg ⁻¹	Na mg/kg ⁻¹
Alföldi 1(K)	whole grain	890±0.2	15.3±1.0	4590.5±1759.1	34.3±1.5
	Endosperm	882±1.2	12.0±0.8	1666.4±373.5	53.1±3.0
	Bran	837±0.1	10.0±0.1	3854.8±151.9	67.7±2.7
Alföldi 1(Ny)	whole grain	852±1.6	16.4±0.9	4931.0±1106.4	44.2±17.0
	Endosperm	903±2.1	16.5±0.1	3620.1±179.7	62.6±22.1
	Bran	907±2.1	16.8±1.2	2869.4±280.5	76.0±19.3
Alföldi 1(Sz)	whole grain	890±3.4	12.5±0.1	5129.7±742.1	26.8±0.89
	Endosperm	843±5.5	11.3±0.3	3840.8±809.1	166.2±10.9
	Bran	834±0.1	15.6±3.0	4924.4±362.9	189.8±6.8
Farmsugro 180 (K)	whole grain	886±3.0	16.3±0.5	4723.8±85.5	37.5±12.7
	Endosperm	853±0.1	17.0±0.2	2125.5±118.3	69.8±23.2
	Bran	840±0.1	16.4±0.2	4024.6±193.7	67.0±2.0
Farmsugro 180 (Ny)	whole grain	919±2.7	17.0±0.5	3875.5±163.9	37.5±12.7
	Endosperm	974±1.2	17.4±0.1	1689.2±193.9	32.8±9.9
	Bran	874±0.9	17.5±1.2	4490.0±1055.0	66.7±23.3
Farmsugro 180 (Sz)	whole grain	897±1.2	12.0±1.0	5324.1±44.1	33.4±0.01
	Endosperm	890±2.0	16.2±0.2	4022.8±2027.3	163.2±52.0
	Bran	878±2.0	1.7±0.2	3746.9±1292.0	130.8±9.2
Whole grains	-	0.25	0.41	0.01	0.50
Processed grains	-	0.05	0.53	0.02	<.001

*Value of the potassium and sodium were analyzed based on three replications, while the dry matter (D.M) and protein were analyzed based on two replications (m/m)%, labels after the variety refer to source sites: K: Kacarg, N: Nyíregyháza, Sz: Szeged.

hybrids exhibited protein content values of 10.59% and 14.25%, lower than the current reported values of whole and dehulled grains.

Kacarg, Nyíregyháza and Szeged, showed an average of K mg/kg-1 and Na mg/kg-1 within 3939.7 mg/kg-1, 3679.7 mg/kg, 4344.6 mg/kg, 67.3 mg/kg, 71.3 mg/kg, and 160.3 mg/kg, respectively.

3.3. POTASSIUM AND SODIUM

The findings showed that the amounts of potassium and sodium minerals in whole sorghum grains and dehulled samples differed depending on the varieties of grains tested (Table 1; $P > 0.05$). This discovery is significant and supports prior research done by (Adebo & Kesa, 2023). Furthermore, both mineral contents were influenced by three source regions, as displayed in Figure 1(1-4). When the Nyíregyháza site showed a significant variation in K mg/kg and Na mg/kg contents attributed to whole grains and dehulled grains, the result was linked (Rubio-Armendáriz 2023; Ramírez & Saldivar, 2016). Potassium and sodium minerals sourced from three distinct regions,

Table 1. Ratios of K: Na contents on diverse examined sorghum varieties

Variety	Ratio (K: Na)
Farmsugro 180 (K)	60: 1
Farmsugro 180 (Ny)	67: 3
Farmsugro 180 (Sz)	28: 1
Alföldi 1(K)	56: 9
Alföldi 1(Ny)	26: 1
Alföldi 1(Sz)	37: 2

onstrated values based on $P \leq 0.05$

*Dem

*Numbers refers to [1] K mg/kg-1 content based on regions (whole grains), [2] Na mg/kg-1 content based on regions (whole grains), [3] K mg/kg-1 content based on regions (dehulled grains), [4] Na mg/kg-1 content based on regions (dehulled grains)

Figure 1. Average of K mg/kg⁻¹ and Na mg/kg⁻¹ contents based on diverse regions, $P \leq 0.05$

The results indicated that the Szeged site had the highest K mg/kg and Na mg/kg content within the ratio of 27:1, which can provide an acceptable recommended level according to (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, 2019). To ensure the appropriate K: Na ratio, the ratios of diverse varieties were calculated and recorded as shown in Table 2. Previous literature provides information on the mineral composition of Hungarian sorghum grains, specifically, the concentrations of potassium and sodium found in these grains, which range from 3490 to 5000 mg/kg and 113.7 mg/kg, respectively, according to (Ildikó & , Andrea 2022).

CONCLUSION

The experiment attempted to evaluate the potassium and sodium mineral concentrations of two prevalent sorghum varieties grown at three sorghum cultivation sites in Hungary. The assessment necessitates the crucial role of potassium and sodium levels, which can estimate the quality degree of whole and husked grain and predict the potential quality of the end product derived from the examined varieties. The report has discussed the limitations of the presented results cannot serve as a comprehensive marker for assessing

grain quality. However, they may provide valuable insights to breeders on the variance between the same variety and the influence of the production site on the nutritional properties. The research demonstrated that the amounts of potassium and sodium could vary depending on their origin. Major nutrient contents, such as dry matter, crude protein, K, and Na, may significantly impact the end product's texture, flavour, and shelf life. Hence, the ratio measurements of the tested minerals contribute to meeting the desired needs of various dietary groups. For instance, cereal grains with high potassium (K) and sodium (Na) content may not fit those suffering from hypernatremia and high blood pressure. Therefore, the current investigation has drawn attention to two critical ingredients in cereal grains that can be controlled from the farm soil to the individual tables, facilitating public health goal achievements.

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SWEAT-EAT: COMBINING SPORTS AND TRADITIONAL FOOD PRODUCTS INTO INDIVIDUALIZED NUTRITION

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Sweat-Eat is a business venture aimed at enhancing the nutritional needs of sports enthusiasts, particularly emerging athletes. Sweat-Eat, a venture led by two nutritionists, will offer a range of goods and services which include traditional food products, personalized diet planning, nutritional counseling and education, seamlessly integrated into the clients' dietary habits. Each client's nutritional needs will be catered for and met by evidence-based diet planning knowledge coming from nutrition professionals who constitute the core part of this venture. The venture's development was planned using a PEST (political, economic, social, and technological) analysis and Michael Porter's model to identify the five competitive forces of this business. The pilot location of this venture is in Kenya which was chosen because of its unique market niche.

The rising need of sports enthusiasts who search to improve their health and performance has led this venture to develop allowing not only a potential increase of traditional food products consumption but also supporting local agriculture promoting sustainability. The vision of this venture 'from tradition to sports' is based on the intentions to collaborate with local farmers and suppliers while promoting health and environmental sustainability. Sweat-Eat aims to bridge this gap and empower individuals to prioritize their health by consuming adequately traditional food products while achieving their athletic goals.

Keywords: nutrition, athletes, diet, exercise, local.

INTRODUCTION

Nutrition is a cornerstone of athletic performance, with post-workout nutritional strategies playing a crucial role in recovery and adaptation processes. Physical activity significantly increases energy expenditure and fluid loss through sweating (Benardot, 2021). Effective recovery strategies between workouts or during competition can enhance adaptive responses to fatigue, improve muscle function, and boost exercise tolerance. Monitoring regimen and diet, including the timing, quality, and quantity of food intake, is fundamental for restoring an athlete's physical fitness (Kerksick et al., 2018).

The growing interest in sports nutrition and its influence on athletic performance has led to extensive research over recent decades. This is a rapidly evolving field, with hundreds of research papers published each year. In 2017 alone, 2,082 articles were published on sports nutrition. Consequently, keeping up with the

latest literature can be challenging (Kerksick et al., 2018). Currently, new trends in dietetics are emerging, focusing on personalized diets. These include genetic studies to determine predispositions to specific foods and risks of food-related diseases (Collier, 2012), research on the diversity of human microbiota and its impact on digestion and intestinal health (Rivera-Pinto et al., 2018), and studies on individual immune responses to food antigens, which affect food tolerance and immune reactivity. The adaptive immune response, driven by lymphocytes (acquired immunity), plays a vital role in defending against infections and eliminating external pathogens in vivo (Rosenstein et al., 2020).

This research article will explore the incorporation of traditional cuisine into sports nutrition as a business venture, Sweat-Eat, focusing on a pilot project in Kenya. The aim is to provide nutritional counseling and education, and personalized diet planning, both in-person and through online resources. This venture addresses the incorporation of traditional cuisine, individual food preferences, and locally

available foods into sports nutrition aiming to enhance nutrition needs and boost athletes and sports enthusiasts' performance. The effectiveness of food choices varies with time, location, and environmental factors (Malsagova et al., 2021).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The development of the venture was done using three analysis tools, a PEST (political, economic, social, and technological) analysis, Porter's model, and a SWOT analysis. These tools were chosen to build and assess the internationalization plan of this business idea.

The PEST analysis included political factors such as democracy, stability, corruption perception, economic factors such as the evolution of the GDP, labor costs, and main sectors of economy, social factors including living standards, and technological factors such as exports and imports. These factors were obtained through secondary data gathered from online sites and the results were cataloged in a range from favorable/manageable to unfavorable/unmanageable.

The SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) analysis was used to evaluate the internal and external factors that affect the business. The other tool used, Michael Porter's model, allowed the competitive analysis of the industry using the five forces that the model proposes: supplier power, threat of new entry, competitive rivalry, threat of substitution, and buyer's power. These forces allowed the venture proposal to notice any weaknesses and strengths to further work on them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Based on the assessment carried out using the PEST analysis for the environmental influences of the business in the target location, Kenya, we found out that even though there is a hybrid democracy present in the country, the political stability is uncertain and the corruption on the system makes the environment unfavorable. However, economically, Kenya has a high GDP in comparison with other countries of the region.

Kenya has a current GDP of \$113.42 billions which is favorable, however, the poverty ratio is about 36% which may have an impact on our targeted population and their ability to afford the recommended food products. The

population's main sectors of economy are agriculture 17%, industry 20%, and services 46%, these data showed a favorable entry on the economy as the venture will provide a service to the clientele, furthermore, will also be linked with agriculture and industry as it will promote local and traditional food products. The living standards vary from rural to urban areas as only 31% of the population live in urban areas.

For Kenyans, health is considered in third place after income and housing, followed by education. Kenya has a negative trade balance as the money spent on importation is three times higher than the received from exportation; Kenya ranks 88th among 132 economies featured in the Global Innovation Index (GII 2022).

The SWOT analysis results demonstrated the internal and external factors of the business and the competitions it would encounter.

- The internal strengths (S) of this venture are based on the expertise of the nutritionists who will have the knowledge in general and sports nutrition and traditional and local food products, as well as the skills needed to provide effective counseling and education. Moreover, they will be the main characters of this business as they would implement the goal of mixing traditional food products and sports nutrition from a nutrition perspective.
- The internal weaknesses (W) include the uncertainty of the supply chain in the traditional and local food products as these products could be seasonal or their production stopped. Therefore, an alternative for products that meet the expectations should be planned in advance in order to achieve the clients' needs, while finding a balance between globalization of products and traditional food products on sports' diets.
- The external opportunities (O) that present for Sweat-Eat include the market niche as there are no services that offer what this venture will. Furthermore, this venture would not only be implemented in one country but will try to expand across the world,

offering traditional food products characteristics of each region. Moreover, sports nutrition as a topic is attracting more attention among sports enthusiasts and athletes, increasing the demand for this type of service.

- The external threats that this venture would face include the clientele's lack of knowledge towards nutritional sports supplements, sustainable diet planning, and traditional food products around the regions. Moreover, the competition of other businesses and the policies and regulations on health products that vary across countries could be a potential threat for Sweat-Eat.

The SWOT analysis results were effective as it showed factors that were not taken into account by the PEST analysis such as the strengths of the business itself, highlighting the nutritionist as pillars of the venture. However, Porter's model would expand further the competitive forces that the business could encounter. Through Porter's model the following five forces resulted:

- The venture's supplier power is the uniqueness of the services provided as it offers individualized nutrition implementing the consumption of traditional and local food products into the clients' diet to enhance their sport performance. Moreover, a moderate increment of price from suppliers i.e. local farmers, and an increase of power from them would be observed because of the venture's actions.
- The threats of new entry of this business include moderate entry obstacles considering the economic situation of the country; however, the distinctive services and products offered in addition to the venture's

innovative idea and individualized services could ease the entry into the market.

- The competitive rivalry for this venture is moderate to high as there is an increased demand for sports nutrition products such as protein supplements, vitamins and minerals shakes and waters, which influence the market for such products. As in the previous point, the uniqueness of Sweat-eat services could counteract the rivalry of other services.
- The threat of substitution faced by this venture includes the substitution of the traditional food products, and nutrition counseling done by non-professionals. It is important for this business to highlight the importance of credentialed nutritionist with focus on sports nutrition, who possess the adequate counseling and teaching skills to work with the targeted clientele as well as with the team behind them such as personal trainers and instructors.

- The buyer's power has a high impact as Sweat-Eat will depend on the online and direct buyers of the services and products offered. There will be an indirect impact on the demand of traditional and local food products producers and farmers as the clients would be referred to these as part of the diet plan.

Porter's model not only allowed the assessment of the weaknesses and strengths of the business but also the development of ways on how to counteract them, the main factors are summarized in figure 1.

Figure 1. Sweat-Eat Michael Porter's model

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrated that the implementation of traditional and local food products into sports nutrition diets through a business would be beneficial as there is a niche in the market for such needs. Moreover, the uniqueness of the venture would not only benefit the clients but also local food producers in the region.

Kenya has a great potential as a place to start the pilot program as sports nutrition is a growing topic among the sports enthusiasts and athletes in the region. The main economic sectors of Kenya could ease the entry of this business as it will influence each of them directly such as services and indirectly as agriculture and industry.

The SWOT analysis demonstrated that the venture possesses high external opportunities and internal strengths due to the special characteristics of the business. However, the threats from other businesses and the lack of knowledge from the clientele about sport nutrition concepts could be challenging to overcome.

Porter's model five competitive forces resulted on moderate to high forces for each of them, demonstrating similarities with the SWOT analysis such as the venture's power in the market because of its unique aim as well as the relevant professional capabilities that it will

offer through credentialed nutritionists with deep knowledge on the main topics: traditional and local food products, and sports nutrition counseling and education.

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SUSTAINABLE VALORIZATION OF AGRI-FOOD WASTE AS A SOURCE OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FOR OBTAINING FUNCTIONAL FOODS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY

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REVIEW

Abstract

Agro-food waste is an important source of bioactive compounds for both human and animal health. Therefore, transforming these wastes into high value products could be an optimal solution for reducing the burden of waste management, decreasing resource and energy consumption, and protecting the environment. For the sustainable valorization of agro-food waste, new and innovative technologies have been developed for the extraction of bioactive compounds to enhance industrially processed foods or to improve the quality of animal-based foods (milk, meat, eggs) by incorporating these wastes into animal diets. The use of these sustainable technologies offers various advantages, including waste reduction, establishing new economic perspectives, promoting a circular economy, and the development of functional foods and nutritional supplements. One of the main challenges for the future will be improving the efficiency of extraction processes and developing new methods that are more efficient and environmentally friendly. Additionally, it is necessary to establish the bioavailability and safety of the extracted compounds, considering that agro-food waste from which they are extracted deteriorates rapidly and may contain a series of mycotoxins and toxic chemicals from agricultural production. Furthermore, new applications for valorizing agro-food waste need to be identified. Moreover, future studies on agro-food waste should not be limited to identifying their content of active compounds and their importance for human health, but should focus on exploiting these wastes as a profitable resource for obtaining high quality value-added food products.

Keywords: food waste management, resource efficiency, green technologies, nutritional supplements

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INTRODUCTION

The rapid growth of the global population and changes in lifestyle have led to a significant increase in the quantity of agro-food waste and secondary products. Nearly one-third of annually produced food is wasted, leading to severe reduction of natural resources (Liu et al., 2023) and which could feed 1.26 billion undernourished people. Agro-food waste, if not managed properly, can pose a serious threat to the environment and human health, while also being associated with significant losses of other resources, such as water, energy, and human effort.

In the context of the circular economy, it is necessary that the waste and secondary products resulting from the processing of agro-food production to be converted into useful ingredients for the food industry or for animal feed, due to the high content of bioactive compounds, but also to new processing technologies that limit damage caused by heat during drying.

Improper management of agro-food waste equates approximately 3.3 billion tons of carbon dioxide, equivalent or 4.4 kilotons of

carbon each year, representing approximately 8% of total greenhouse gas emissions to the environment (Liu et al., 2023). The utilization of this agro-food waste as a source of bioactive compounds in the food industry or in animal feed is a pioneering solution for reducing waste and generating new economic opportunities. This approach aims not only to reduce the environmental impact of agro-food waste but also to obtain new functional foods with high additional value and dietary supplements, as well as sources of income, thus fulfilling the principles of the circular economy. Furthermore, the valorization of agro-industrial waste and by-products facilitates the development of increasingly competitive, sustainable, and economically viable production systems.

The purpose of this review is to highlight the potential of agro-food waste and by-products as a source of bioactive compounds for the production of functional foods. Therefore, this study presents data from the literature regarding various sources of food waste, the content of bioactive compounds in agro-food waste and by-products, and their potential utilization in the food industry and animal feed as a source of bioactive compounds to obtain

high-value-added foods that meet the specific characteristics of functional foods.

THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY OF AGRO-FOOD PRODUCTION

The valorization of agro-food waste is an integral part of the concept of "zero waste economy," in which waste is transformed into valuable goods with practical applications, offering potential savings of natural resources and their sustainable use. In addition, the "Farm to Fork" concept also aims to integrate circular economy principles into food processing through environmentally friendly technologies. Achieving the "zero waste" goal and accelerating the transition of the food industry to a circular bioeconomy primarily relies on integrated value chains, where waste and by-products are used as raw materials to obtain value-added products.

Food waste and by-products could be utilized for developing new food ingredients or products for human consumption, promoting full valorization and reintegration into the food supply chain within the circular bioeconomy concept, thereby creating revenue streams as well as business opportunities and employment.

Agro-food wastes are secondary products that have no direct food value for humans, because the extraction and processing of the nutritional and biologically active compounds from them generates very high costs (Mnisi et al., 2022). Large amounts of agro-food waste are dumped in landfills, leading to environmental pollution (Mnisi et al., 2022). Thus, the recovery of agro-food waste in animal feed fits into the contemporary concept of circular bioeconomy also contributes to, sustainable development of animal production and ensuring food security by providing high quality food at affordable prices to the rapidly growing human population. In addition, it can be a strategy for enriching agro-food products of animal origin (eggs, meat, milk) into bioactive compounds with a role in promoting human health, but also an environmental protection strategy.

THE IMPACT OF AGRO-FOOD WASTE ON THE ENVIRONMENT

Agro-food waste represents a serious problem in the culture of sustainable consumption, with major implications for the environment. These wastes, resulting from any part of the food chain, have a significant impact

on natural resources, biodiversity and the quality of the environment.

One of the main aspects of the impact of agro-food waste on the environment is related to soil pollution. Improperly disposed organic waste can contain harmful chemicals that seep into the soil, affecting its fertility and structure, thereby affecting local flora and fauna.

Also, agro-food waste can contribute to surface and ground water pollution. Disposing of waste near watercourses or in areas with groundwater can contaminate drinking water sources and affect the biodiversity and quality of aquatic habitats.

Another important aspect of the major impact of agro-food waste is related to greenhouse gas emissions. The process of decomposition of organic matter in waste generates significant emissions of methane and carbon dioxide, thus contributing to global warming and climate change.

THE ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL IMPLICATIONS OF AGRO-FOOD WASTE

According to the FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization), about one-third of all food produced in the world is lost or wasted, and about 690 million people, or almost 9% of the global population, suffer from chronic hunger. This means that these people do not have regular and sufficient access to nutritious and safe food to meet their basic nutritional needs.

According to Eurostat, in 2022, 95.3 million people in the EU (22% of the population) were at risk of poverty or social exclusion, lived in households facing at least one of the three risks of poverty and social exclusion. Correspondent to prognoses, by 2050 there will be 9.3 billion people on Earth. Ensuring an uninterrupted food supply with such population growth - even with the use of modern crop improvement technologies - will be an extremely difficult task. According to experts, providing people with safe food will also require a drastic reduction in food waste in the future, especially household losses (Bond et al. 2013, FAO 2014).

Surpluses occur at all levels of the food chain, however, we experience differences between developing and developed countries. Surpluses generated during agricultural production are more typical in economically underdeveloped countries than in industrialized countries. The main reasons are outdated harvesting technology, inadequate

storage, handling and transport procedures, inefficient infrastructure and lack of adequate knowledge.

By recycling or valorizing food waste, the negative impact of food waste could be reduced and the economic losses associated with it can be avoided. The valorization of agro-food waste can lead to increased economic efficiency by creating new employment opportunities and can stimulate innovation and research in the field of green technologies and the circular economy.

AGRO-FOOD WASTE AS A POTENTIAL SOURCE OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS

As people become more aware of the relationship between nutrition and health, the food industry strives to develop new products enriched with nutritionally valuable ingredients such as dietary fiber, polyphenols, vitamin or

minerals, which have a positive effect on human health.

Agro-industrial wastes and by-products are rich sources of macronutrients (carbohydrates, proteins and fats), micronutrients (vitamins, iron, calcium and potassium) and numerous bioactive compounds (Table 1). Bioactive compounds are natural substances that have the potential to influence positively human health. Most of the bioactive compounds, produced from the primary and secondary metabolism of the plant cell, have antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects; they have cardioprotective and neuroprotective properties, prevent obesity and regulate diabetes (Banwo et al., 2021). These compounds often exist in higher concentrations in discarded parts than in those considered marketable. The utilization of these bioactive compounds presents an opportunity to transform food waste into valuable resources.

Table 1

Bioactive compounds from food waste streams and by-products

Bioactive compounds	Food waste streams and by-products	References
Carbohydrates	Citrus fruits, apple pomace, potato peel, carrot.	Nayak et al., 2019.
Phenolic compound	White grape pomace, apple pomace, peel and pulp of orange, potato peel.	Hernandez et al., 2017; Thomas et al., 2019.
Flavonoids	Apple pomace, citrus peel, mango kernel, banana peel, beetroot, broccoli.	Vu et al., 2018; Hernandez et al., 2017; Vulic et al., 2014.
Anthocyanins, carotenoids, betalains, lycopene	Apple pomace, plum pomace, mango peel, carrot, banana peel, berries, beetroot, tomato pomace and peel.	Sojka et al., 2015; Vulic et al., 2014; Klavins et al., 2018.
Organic acids	Waste cheese whey, apple pomace, banana peel, citrus peel waste, fruit and vegetable waste, fruit and vegetable waste.	Piwowarek et al., 2016; Patsalou et al., 2017.
Essential fatty acids	Grape seeds, flaxseed waste and sesame seed hulls, hemp seed, camelina seed.	Dalmolin et al., 2010; Socaci et al., 2017; Mierlita et al., 2024.

Vegetables contain high levels of water, soluble carbohydrates, fiber, minerals, vitamins, polyphenols and other bioactive compounds. Often vegetables are considered waste once they undergo color changes, are infested with microbes, are broken or hit, or reach ripening (ripening) levels that make them unacceptable to consumers. This waste can occur at any point in the vegetable supply chain, from farm to consumer. Around 30% of vegetable production ends up being food waste, which is composted or incinerated, causing serious environmental

problems, including toxic or greenhouse gas emissions and microbial proliferation, due to the high moisture content and leachate of waste.

Following the processing of the fruits by squeezing or crushing, in order to obtain the juice, the by-product is the pomace, which represents 20-40% of the weight of the fresh fruit (Mnisi et al., 2022). It contains part of the fruit pulp, peel and seeds. Annually, more than 500 million tons of pomes are produced globally (Hu et al., 2023), for which no unified

sustainable management strategy has been developed.

Phenolic compounds, carotenoids and dietary fibers are the most widespread bioactive compounds present in agro-food waste. They can find application in several industrial fields as functional components to promote the reuse and recycling of biomass but can also be used in animal feed (Socas-Rodríguez et al., 2021). These natural antioxidants, especially carotenoids and polyphenols, have anti-aging, anti-inflammatory, anti-viral, anti-microbial, anti-cancer agents and generally occur in citrus fruits and fruit pomace (including grape). Thus, these agro-food wastes can be used to improve the texture and color of products but also to improve the shelf life of food and beverages.

Agro-food waste has a high content of dietary fibers that affect human nutrition and health. They promote gastrointestinal peristalsis to alleviate constipation. In addition, they have a direct impact on the human digestive microflora, providing the energy and nutrients necessary for the proliferation of probiotics in the digestive tract.

The use of agro-food waste in the food industry

Some agro-food waste and especially fruit pomace (aronia, currants, blueberries, grapes, sea buckthorn) after treatments such as controlled drying and grinding could be used as ingredients with nutritional and functional value, in the food industry, with the aim of obtaining foods enriched in natural bioactive compounds. Food enrichment in antioxidants is important in reducing oxidative damage in consumers, having a critical role in protecting cellular components from the products resulting from the oxidative degradation of different compounds (Vrsanska et al., 2016). The increased interest in increasing the content of antioxidants in the human diet and implicitly in food is determined by the role that antioxidants have in the prevention of cancer, the aging process, cardiovascular and neurodegenerative diseases (Bohn, 2019).

The use of agro-food waste as a natural source of bioactive compounds in the food industry can reduce the need for synthetic food additives that can have a negative impact on the health of consumers therefore, enriching food with natural bioactive compounds could have a positive effect on the perception and acceptance of food by consumers.

Agro-food waste rich in bioactive compounds, such as over ripe berries, fruits unacceptable for marketing (with defects in size, shape, appearance), discarded peels, peels, fruit pomace resulting from the production of juices, after processing by appropriate methods can be used in the food industry as a source of natural food additives, thus replacing food additives of chemical synthesis.

Recent studies have highlighted the potential of polyphenol-rich olive waste as a natural antioxidant in minced meat, which protects lipids and proteins against oxidation, preserves a specific color of fresh meat and extends the shelf life of the product by up to three days (Muino et al., 2017). In addition, it has been found that apple peel extract protects proteins and lipids from trout during refrigeration, leading to a reduction in the level of peroxides that have negative effects on consumer health (Bitalebi et al., 2019).

Various bioactive compounds found in food waste have been identified as potential natural antimicrobial agents for food preservation. For example, olive leaf extract reduces bacterial contamination in leafy vegetables and shrimp. Studies have shown that pomegranate peel extract exhibits antibacterial effects against *S. aureus* and *B. cereus*, showing promising antibacterial effects in chicken (Kanatt et al., 2010).

Many of the colorants used in the food industry are synthetic, although some agro-food wastes and especially berry waste and pomace can be natural sources of colorants such as carotenoids and anthocyanins. These compounds could be used as natural colorants in products and help extend the shelf life of food and beverages by preventing pathogens, contaminants or unpleasant flavors.

Apple and citrus waste are significant sources of water-insoluble dietary fibers, such as pectin, which are beneficial for gut microbiota health. By extracting pectin, it can be utilized as a gelling agent in baking, confectionery, and meat products.

Most vegetable and fruit waste and by-products can be considered a source of protein and dietary fiber. For example, in addition to improving nutritional values, the inclusion of dried and ground potato peels in a proportion of 5% increased the strength and elasticity-extensibility of the dough (Ben Jeddou et al., 2017).

Waste resulting from fruit processing is a source of bioactive compounds (polyphenols,

flavonoids, vitamins, minerals) that can be reused to meet the requirements of the circular economy model (Piasecka et al., 2022). By isolating these bioactive compounds, innovative food products rich in natural bioactive compounds or dietary supplements can be developed, reducing waste and promoting sustainable production systems within the circular bioeconomy context. The development of healthier food products that are not only nourishing but also functionally beneficial involves the advancement of innovative food technologies. Contemporary lifestyles largely rely on highly processed foods with low nutritional value, thus enriching them with bioactive compounds has become a necessity.

The use of agro-food waste in animal feed

A significant issue in livestock production is the decline in feed resources. Therefore, the utilization of agro-food waste in animal feed represents new methods of sustainable development of food production, by using locally available, less competitive and cost-effective materials as feed ingredients.

Some of the agro-food waste and by-products can be safely used as animal feed without compromising the safety of animal-derived products and animal welfare. Currently, available processing technologies allow for the safe preservation and utilization of agro-food waste for animal feed, transforming them into value-added foods with high-quality nutrients. Agro-food waste processing methods include dehydration, ensiling, extrusion, granulation and treatment with probiotics (Cheraghi Saray et al., 2014).

Innovative feeding technologies based on the utilization of agro-food waste and by-products rich in bioactive compounds can reduce enteric methane and nitrogen emissions in ruminants, while simultaneously improving the nutritional composition and extending the shelf life of meat and meat products by enhancing their antioxidant capacity.

The edible oil processing industry generates waste, the most important of which are oilcakes and oilseed meals. These are by-products rich in proteins, but also in bioactive compounds (polyunsaturated fatty acids, antioxidants, sterols, carotenes). This waste is pre-treated and used to produce animal feed (Chang et al., 2018).

Agro-food waste is underutilized in the food industry for obtaining pectin, vitamins,

polyphenols, flavors, and food pigments. Additionally, given that fruit and vegetable waste production is seasonal, it seems opportune to preserve them in dried form and then use them as feed ingredients for animal nutrition. Just like the vegetables and fruits that result, waste can be a highly valuable source of natural antioxidants like polyphenols (especially anthocyanins and flavonoids), carotenoids and vitamin E (Pieszka et al., 2015), some of which are found in higher quantities in waste than in products accepted by the market. Furthermore, these wastes contain unsaturated fatty acids, numerous vitamins and minerals, so their use as feed additives could enrich their diet in valuable bioactive components, which are efficiently transferred to agro-food products of animal origin.

This strategy of using vegetable and fruit waste in animal feed leads to obtaining foods (meat, milk, eggs) with high-added value, which can meet the specific characteristics of functional foods. The increased consumer interest in functional foods is due to their high content of high-quality proteins, vitamins, minerals, colorants, and natural antioxidants, phospholipids, and polyunsaturated fatty acids, which have positive effects on human health, improving immune functions and fertility (Hoffman et al., 2004), and also possess anti-inflammatory, antitumor, and antiviral properties (Wall et al., 2010).

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Agro-food waste represents a significant source of bioactive compounds crucial for human and animal health. Thus, transforming this waste into high-value-added products is an optimal solution to reduce the burden of waste management, decrease resource and energy consumption, and protect the environment. New and innovative technologies for extracting bioactive compounds have been developed to enhance industrially processed foods or improve the quality of animal-derived foods (milk, meat, eggs) by incorporating these waste materials into animal diets. The utilization of these sustainable technologies offers various advantages, including waste reduction, the creation of new economic opportunities, promotion of circular economy principles, and the development of functional foods and nutritional supplements.

Despite the establishment of various technologies for the sustainable valorization of

agri-food waste, they have been successfully tested in research laboratories, while their implementation on a commercial scale presents challenges and limitations, requiring researchers to address these issues in future studies. Many of the technologies tested on a laboratory scale require excessive extraction costs, generated by expensive equipment, solvents used and high energy consumption, this is a significant obstacle to the use of bioactive compounds from agri-food waste as natural additives in the food industry. Additionally, challenges such as low extraction rates, lower stability of natural compounds compared to synthetic ones, and difficulties in managing the resulting waste residues, which may pose risks to the environment and human health, need to be addressed.

In this context, processing agri-food waste through appropriate methods and using them as a source of bioactive compounds in animal feed to obtain animal-derived foods (meat, milk, eggs) with high added value is an effective approach to sustainable valorization of these wastes on a commercial scale. Ultimately, the application of efficient sustainable valorization processes for agri-food waste by transforming them into high-value-added products can significantly contribute to promoting circular bioeconomy, effectively addressing the macro-global issue of environmental protection.

In conclusion, one of the main challenges for the future will be to improve the efficiency of extraction processes and develop new methods that are more environmentally friendly. Additionally, it is necessary to establish the bioavailability and safety of the extracted compounds, considering that agro-food waste from which they are extracted deteriorates rapidly and may contain various toxic chemicals from insecticides and pesticides used in agricultural production. Furthermore, new applications for valorizing agro-food waste need to be identified, the goal is to recycle and aim for 'zero waste; zero loss'. Finally, future studies on agro-food waste should not be limited to identifying their content of active compounds and their importance for human health but should focus on utilizing these wastes as a profitable resource for obtaining high-quality food products with added-value.

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STUDY OF THE PROFITABILITY OF CUCUMBER CULTIVATION IN BIHOR COUNTY AT STANGL VEGETABLE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The agri-food chain has been a focus of attention, especially since 1984 when it appeared in FAO documents. Generally, the analysis of the chain involves tracing the journey of a food product from production, including the agricultural raw materials used for its manufacturing, to its use as a consumable food product. We particularly followed the entire process from the agricultural exploitation to the consumer's plate, emphasizing the supply function in the agri-food chain. When studying a chain, we consider two fundamental aspects: its identification (description) – products, paths, economic agents, operations, flows, costs – and the analysis of regulatory mechanisms (market structure and functioning, state intervention, forecasts, etc.). After following the stages of cucumber cultivation, we analyzed the main cucumber producers in the north-west part of our country.

Keywords: agriculture, development, agri-food, cucumber, profitability

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INTRODUCTION

The cucumber (*Cucumis sativus*) is a vegetable plant from the Cucurbitaceae family, originating from India, and it is widely cultivated. Information about the cucumber plant is important. This plant is a creeping vine that grows up to 1.5 - 2 meters long, climbing trellises or other supporting structures with tendrils. The plant has large leaves that cover the fruit, which is cylindrical, elongated, and rounded at the edges. At maturity, it can grow up to 60 cm in length and 10 cm in diameter, but it usually grows about 10 cm long. Cucumbers can be eaten raw or pickled.

The plant develops from a closed seed. Scientifically, the result of cucumber plant pollination is a fruit. Its classification as a vegetable, similar to tomatoes and zucchini, is arbitrary and based mainly on its use in the kitchen. The scientific classification of

vegetables does not exist; this classification emerged for practical reasons. Thus, there is no conflict in classifying cucumber fruit as both a vegetable and a fruit. Some cucumber varieties are parthenocarpic, resulting in seedless fruits; for these varieties, pollination reduces their quality potential. Usually, these varieties are grown in greenhouses, where insect pollination is eliminated. In Europe, cucumber varieties that can produce seeds and require pollination are preferred. The pollination of these varieties is done by bees, bumblebees, and various other insect species, with beekeepers preferring to bring their hives near vegetable-seeded fields.

If pollination is unsuccessful, the resulting fruit may turn yellow, fall off, or grow crooked. Partially pollinated fruits can be green near the stem but yellow and poorly formed near the flower. When consumed as food, a raw

cucumber with skin provides 20 kcal per 100 grams, including about 3.63g carbohydrates, 0.11g fats, 0.65g proteins, 0.027 mg vitamin B1, 0.033 mg vitamin B2, 0.098g vitamin B3, traces of vitamin B6 and B9, 2.8mg vitamin C, iron, magnesium, phosphorus, potassium, and zinc.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this study, we used systematically collected data from both economic statistics and the records of SC Stangl Vegetable SRL. We attempted to identify the agri-food chain of cucumbers, the main cucumber-producing companies in Bihor County, and the economic situation of the company with the highest production. The interpretation of the data aimed to identify the profitability of this product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

There are many cucumber varieties, such as MarketMore, Cornichon Crișan, Parsian Pickling, Slănic, and many others. Cucumber cultivation can be profitable in the long term, as they can be grown in different seasons, either in greenhouses for early production or outdoors during summer or autumn. The correct selection of cucumber species and varieties, along with appropriate cultivation techniques, can contribute to increased efficiency and profitability.

The establishment of the crop can be done either by seedlings for early cultivation or directly by seeds for summer and autumn crops. Additionally, cucumbers can be grown

Economic agents, both public and private, involved in various phases of the vegetable chain are presented in the table below:

on the ground or on trellises. There are varieties suitable for field cultivation and varieties that adapt better in greenhouses. Given the high nutrient requirement, cucumber cultivation can begin in May when the minimum temperature for vegetation is about 25 degrees Celsius.

To obtain profitable cucumber crops on an area of 105 hectares, whether grown in greenhouses or open fields, it is essential to create a conducive environment for the plants' metabolic processes. Control of environmental factors such as light, temperature, humidity, and ventilation is crucial. Additionally, it is important to cultivate healthy and vigorous seedlings, resistant to diseases and pests. Adhering to cucumber cultivation technology is also essential for obtaining superior yields and quality. This involves:

Planting or Transplanting: Placing seedlings in the soil or greenhouses at the optimal time, avoiding root damage.

Irrigation: Providing adequate water to maintain proper soil moisture.

Fertilization: Applying suitable fertilizers to ensure balanced plant nutrition.

Weed Control: Removing weeds to prevent competition for nutrients and water.

Protection Against Diseases and Pests: Using preventive and control measures to reduce the risk of infections and damage caused by diseases and pests.

Harvesting at the Right Time: Harvesting cucumbers at maturity to ensure optimal taste and quality.

PHASE	ECONOMIC AGENTS/ INSTITUTIONS
Production Planning	Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, and Rural Development, Romanian Society of Horticulturists, Horticulture Directorate - Fruits and Vegetables Bureau within MAPDR, Payment and Intervention Agency, producers, research institutions
Ensuring Material Resources	Producers, UNISEM, UNICEREAL, chemical substance commercial units, irrigation, agricultural machinery, etc.
	Peasant households, agricultural associations, and

The main companies producing cucumbers in Bihor County are:

- Stangl Vegetable, Husasau de Tinca
- SIRMIS EXIM S.R.L., Valea lui Mihai
- TALABUR SRL, Dumbrăvani
- Linisagro, Oradea
- LONARDONI & ASOCIATII S.R.L., Girişu de Criş
- EMILIANDA COOPERATIVA AGRICOLA, Tulca
- ANSADA SRL, Salonta
- SCHMIDT AGRARA SRL, Oradea
- BONAGRO SRL

Stangl Vegetable is a company founded in Romania by a German and markets its products in Germany. In 2016, the factory was moved to Husasău de Tinca, which increased profits depending on the harvest, season, and uncontrollable circumstances. This is the largest company involved in cucumber production in western Romania. The farm covers 1,400 hectares of agricultural land, specializing in growing a variety of vegetables and cereals in open fields. The main vegetable

crop is cucumbers, cultivated on 131 hectares (105 hectares plants and 26 hectares seeds), followed by onions and potatoes.

The workforce is an essential factor for the company, as cucumbers are manually cultivated in the field. Currently, the company has 28 permanent employees and collaborates with over 2,000 workers in the season. Cultivation and planting are carried out with state-of-the-art equipment, with the company having 40 tractors and 25 planes. Irrigation is an essential method that facilitates work and ensures plants receive sufficient water even during drought periods. Stangl Vegetable has its reservoir fed by 8 wells. Additionally, the company has a high-precision automated and manual sorting process. Using the latest technologies for sorting and packaging, freshly harvested cucumbers are processed the same day and prepared for delivery in cold rooms, from where they continue their journey to customers. In peak season, 5-6 trucks of cucumbers leave for Germany, where cucumbers are processed and jarred.

Cultivated Area with Major Crops by Ownership Forms, Macroregions, Development Regions, and Counties

Year	Measure	Total	North-West Region	Bihor
1990	Hectares	9,402,113	1,035,433	299,437
2020	Hectares	8,263,672	827,392	307,845
2021	Hectares	8,263,827	838,819	308,475
2022	Hectares	8,005,889	806,333	300,705
2023	Hectares	8,211,163	805,007	300,531

Vegetables Cultivated in Open Fields Vegetables in Greenhouses and Tunnels

Year	Measure	Total	North-West Region	Bihor
2020	Hectares	4,265	208	9
2021	Hectares	4,19	173	11
2022	Hectares	4,307	173	10
2023	Hectares	4,6	191	28

Fresh Vegetables from Family Gardens

Year	Measure	Total	North-West Region	Bihor
2020	Hectares	86,862	10,526	-
2021	Hectares	84,128	10,509	-
2022	Hectares	78,628	9,685	-
2023	Hectares	78,246	9,612	-

As we can observe, although Bihor County is not as representative as other counties in our country in terms of vegetable cultivation, especially cucumbers, the cultivated area in Bihor compared to the other counties in the northwest region is acceptable.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis, we observed that starting with the seed used, the quality of the land, the irrigation system, and including the harvesting, this product can have high productivity and can bring profit, provided we have a secured market. We also observed that the preservation of these products results in higher profits.

The efficiency category, applied in many domains of human activity with its quasi-equivalent variant—effectiveness, in the most general terms, represents the qualitative characterization of the result of an action that involves considering a volume of physical and intellectual effort, concretized in a volume of past or present work. Efficiency is a relative term, and its correct determination and perception are extremely important for human activity. Due to this fact, efficiency will always be relative to a specific criterion. When we say that an economy or a company is more

efficient than another, we consider a comparison based on a specific criterion or indicator (production per employee, yield per hectare, or production per machine, etc.).

Beyond the processing sector, fresh vegetable distribution involves collectors (direct distributors), specialized vegetable stores that usually purchase from collectors, and supermarkets that have purchase contracts either with producers or collectors.

Regarding products sold through different channels, it is not possible to accurately quantify the volumes handled by each of these channels. It is estimated that more than half of the vegetables sold are traded through a large number of intermediaries. Generally, there are two ways: farm gate sales (the most widespread) and street commerce.

Another way of selling is direct sales to shops and supermarkets. This method relies on the daily demand from retail stores. Formal contracts are not concluded with shops and supermarkets. Regarding supermarkets, very few farmers can sell their products through this channel. It is estimated that less than 10% of the vegetables sold are through this route. Supermarkets require quality products in large quantities. But even when these conditions are met by farmers, due to the small quantities they can deliver and the discontinuity in delivery, supermarkets refuse to sign contracts.

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TRENDS AND PATTERNS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT AT THE LOCAL AND COUNTY LEVELS IN THE WEST DEVELOPMENT REGION OF ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This paper consists of a comprehensive analysis of tourism development at the local and county levels within the West Development Region of Romania, utilizing panel data comprised of key metrics including tourism arrivals, overnight stays, and total capacity. Employing a spatial autocorrelation analysis approach, the study examines temporal variations and spatial correlations in these variables to uncover patterns and dynamics shaping tourism in the region. The findings contribute some valuable insights into the drivers of tourism growth and the effectiveness of tourism policies at the regional level by showing the counties and localities with the highest average growth and spatial clustering of tourism development. Furthermore, the study provides practical implications for stakeholders and policymakers in fostering sustainable tourism development strategies tailored to the West Development Region

Keywords: tourism development, spatial clustering in tourism, spatial correlation, Moran's I
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INTRODUCTION

Tourism plays an important role in the socioeconomic and sustainable development of regions worldwide, serving as a significant contributor to economic growth and employment, while at the same time promoting cultural exchange (Gordan et al., 2023).

In the case of Romania, a country characterized by its diverse natural landscapes, historical heritage, and cultural richness, tourism emerged as a vital sector with considerable potential for fostering regional prosperity (Necheș & Erdeli, 2015; Rățulea et al., 2023).

Within the West Development Region of Romania, encompassing the Arad, Caraș-Severin, Hunedoara, and Timiș counties, the dynamic of tourism development reflects an accumulation of various factors, including geographic features, historical legacies, infrastructural investments, and evolving consumer preferences, as well as economic factors (Florina et al., 2018). Timiș and Arad are identified as the most economically developed counties, with predominantly plain terrain favoring human-centric tourism activities, such as wellness tourism, cultural tourism, rural tourism, and sports tourism. The geographical features of Caras-Severin and Hunedoara are also attractive factors for tourism development, with nature-based tourism in

natural parks being of significant importance. The region's tourism resources can be described as diverse, ranging from natural landscapes to cultural heritage sites. These resources include varied natural features, such as landform types, climatic elements, hydrographic networks, forests, and hunting grounds, making the region highly attractive to tourists (Pascariu et al., 2022). From an economic perspective, small and medium-sized businesses contribute significantly to the economic growth and employment in the tourism industry in this region.

The region boasts a rich cultural heritage, with historical sites, fortresses, castles, and archaeological remains adding to its tourism appeal. Counties like Hunedoara have well-preserved historical sites such as the Corvin Castle and archaeological remains from the Roman and pre-Roman era (Brad et al., 2017; Manescu et al., 2023).

As such, the significance of those factors can be quantified by analyzing the spatial patterns in tourism development present in those counties, which is the main goal of this research paper. On the other hand, a lack of spatial autocorrelation can be a sign that tourism growth is more related to the individual traits of a locality, such as tourism offer attractiveness. In such a case, it is in the interest of local authorities

to develop strategies for promoting tourism specific to their area, and tourism growth in a neighboring locality does not assure success.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The primary data sources utilized in this study are publicly available datasets, predominantly extracted from the TEMPO online statistical database. TEMPO serves as a comprehensive repository of statistical information covering various socio-economic indicators at the regional and national levels. The database offers a wide range of data related to tourism necessary for conducting spatial analyses (National Institute of Statistics, 2023; Necula et al., 2019).

TEMPO provides accessible and reliable data, making it an ideal resource for researchers and policymakers to obtain statistical information for different regions and administrative units within Romania. By leveraging this platform, we were able to gather relevant data sets specific to the Western Region, encompassing Arad, Timis, Caras-Severin, and Hunedoara counties.

The method employed in this study involves the calculation of the average year-on-year growth rates for all available localities within the aforementioned counties. These growth rates serve as indicators for highlighting the dynamic changes occurring within each locality over time. Localities with less than 3 data points were removed from the dataset.

After computing the average year-on-year growth rates, these values are standardized to facilitate meaningful comparisons across different localities and counties. Standardization ensures that very large variations in the magnitudes of growth rates do not influence subsequent analyses, allowing for a more accurate evaluation of spatial patterns and correlations. The method employed is robust standardization, centered around the median value in the data set.

The formula used to standardize the data is the following:

$$x' = \frac{x - \text{med}(x)}{\text{IQR}(x)}$$

where, x' is the standardized value, x are individual growth rates, $\text{med}(x)$ is the median of the dataset and $\text{IQR}(x)$ is the interquartile range (Alfons, 2021).

Subsequently, spatial correlation analysis is conducted using two primary techniques: Global Moran's I and Local Moran's I (Gordan et al., 2024).

Global Moran's I examines the overall spatial autocorrelation present within the dataset, indicating whether similar values tend to cluster together or exhibit spatial dispersion across the study area. The values of this coefficient range from -1 to $+1$. A value closer to -1 corresponds to spatial dispersion, whereas a value closer to $+1$ corresponds to spatial clustering of the data points (Gordan et al., 2024; Sarrión-Gavilán et al., 2015).

The formula for calculating Global Moran's I is:

$$I = \frac{N \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{W \sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2}$$

where: N is the number of spatial units, x is the variable for which the spatial clustering is assessed, \bar{x} is the mean of x , w_{ij} are elements in a matrix of spatial weights and W is the sum of w_{ij} .

If the Moran's I coefficient is not significant, it indicates that there is no statistically significant spatial autocorrelation present in the dataset. In other words, the values of the variable being analyzed do not exhibit a spatial pattern of clustering or dispersion that deviates from what would be expected by random chance alone.

Local Moran's I, on the other hand, offers a more local view on spatial patterns by identifying specific clusters of high or low values (i.e., hotspots and coldspots, marked as High-High and Low-Low, respectively) within the region. This technique allows for the identification of localized spatial trends and helps pinpoint areas of interest for further investigation. Furthermore, regions of local dispersion are also highlighted (High-Low and Low-High) (Yang & Wong, 2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The descriptive part of the results is shown in Figures 1-3, where the geographical distribution of the regularised year-on-year average variation in arrivals, stays, and accommodation capacity, respectively, are shown. It should be noted that large variations are most identified with locations with relatively small absolute values. This is one of the reasons for utilizing the robust standardization method, as it is not influenced as much by extreme values in the dataset. This step was undertaken as Moran's I formula shown above utilizes average values, which are not as robust to outliers.

Some of the highest values for average percentage change in arrivals were reported in Petriș, Arad; Pișchia, Timiș; Moldova-Nouă, Caraș-Severin; Șandra, Timiș and Ineu, Arad. The

same overall trend is reported for stays too, with the addition of Socol, Caras-Severin.

In the case of tourism capacity, the highest values were reported for Zam, Hunedoara; Totesti, Hunedoara; Ilia, Caras-Severin, Pischia, Timiș and Zimandu Nou, Arad. This shows that there might be a disconnection between the touristic offer and touristic demand.

Following this, we calculated the global Moran's I coefficient for the three variables. We utilized distance band parameters, as the dataset contains discontinuous data points. This allowed us to observe if there are some interactions between localities that are in the same vicinity

and not necessarily direct neighbors. We set the distance band to 30km, to compensate for spatial discontinuity. The results of the Global Moran's I show that overall, the spatial distribution of year-on-year changes in arrivals, stays and touristic capacity are not dissimilar to a random distribution (-0,006, 0,004 and 0,02, respectively, which are close to 0).

However, on the local level, some statistically significant patterns emerged, as shown in figures 4, 5 and 6. For all three variables, the results show that statistically significant clusters occur in the northern part of the studied area.

Figure 1 Standardized values of year-on-year percentage change in arrivals for the West Region

Figure 2 Standardized values of year-on-year percentage change for stays in the West Region

Figure 3 Standardized values of year-on-year percentage change in tourism capacity for the West Region

Figure 4 Local Moran's I values for year-on-year percentage change in arrivals for the West Region

Figure 5 Local Moran's I values for year-on-year percentage change in arrivals for the West Region

Figure 6 Local Moran's I values for year-on-year percentage change in tourism capacity for the West Region

In the case of arrivals and stays, the clusters are mostly located between the Arad and Hunedoara counties, showing significant spatial spillover effects. Since the clusters there are mostly classified as Low-High, we can conclude that a negative spatial spillover effect is taking place in the aforementioned areas, with high growth in neighboring localities negatively affecting growth in the target localities. Conversely, High-High clusters are areas where high growth in neighbors is associated with high growth in the localities that compose the cluster.

A similar situation occurs with tourism capacity, however, the cluster is located solely within the Arad county. In the case of this cluster, the spatial effect is mostly negative, with low-growth localities neighboring high-growth ones.

CONCLUSIONS

Tourism stands as a pivotal driver for socioeconomic development globally, underpinning economic growth, employment opportunities, and cultural exchange. Romania, with its diverse natural landscapes, rich historical and cultural heritage, has recognized tourism as a potent sector for regional advancement, as highlighted in the introductory section of the paper.

While global Moran's I indicates no significant spatial clustering at the overall regional level, local Moran's I unveils clusters, particularly in the northern part of the region. These clusters denote spatial spillover effects, illustrating the complex dynamics of tourism growth, where neighboring localities' performances influence each other. In our case, the results show that the results are mostly consistent with negative autocorrelations, where high growths in some localities negatively affect their neighbors.

Ultimately, as a policy implication of our research, we consider that the local authorities should improve the collaborative aspect of tourism development and attempt to foster sustainable development for tourism in those areas, and in turn convert the negative relationships shown into positive ones, where

growth in one locality does not compromise the growth of other areas.

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ANALYSIS OF THE TOURISM PRODUCT OFFERED BY APPLES GUESTHOUSE IN ORADEA

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Abstract

The diversity and originality of leisure offerings can be decisive elements in attracting tourist flows and serve as a basis for evaluating a vacation or health resort, a tourist cabin, a cultural circuit, etc. The main dimension of the concept of leisure is fun and enjoyment, and any tourist activity or endeavor capable of relaxing an individual falls within the broad scope of leisure activities.

As an urban guesthouse, we would like to see how important leisure is within an accommodation and dining facility. The tourist product includes, besides accommodation and meals, this very important aspect from the visitors' perception. If we come to you, what could we do? The answer to this question can bring in additional customers or retain current clients.

Through this work, we have tried to provide an answer to this question for both the owners of APPLE Guesthouse in Oradea and other proprietors.

Keywords: guesthouse, clients, food, facilities, tourism, activities, proposals, improvements.

INTRODUCTION

A tourist product represents a set of services that can change over time and space to perfectly meet tourists' requirements. It has a complex structure, manifested in various forms of combinations of component elements (accommodation, food, transportation, reception, entertainment, landscape quality, excursions, spa treatments, winter sports, adventure, etc.). Depending on the qualitative and quantitative value of the tourist resources present in the area, one can speak of a broader or narrower range of activities and services that make up tourist products. Like any commercial product or other types, it must meet at least one of the following requirements: - Brand image;
- Optimal price-quality ratio

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For this work, we used an empirical, detailed research of the guesthouse market in Oradea, which reflects on the competition in this segment. We collected data from various accommodation units using the internet, but

When referring to accommodation facilities for vacations and short stays, this can include the provision of short-term accommodation, usually daily or weekly, for visitors, in independent spaces consisting of fully furnished rooms or spaces for dining and sleeping, with cooking facilities or fully equipped kitchens.

For a long stay of three days, in addition to accommodation and meals, leisure activities offered by the accommodation unit or opportunities in the analyzed area must be considered and prioritized.

Herbamon Apples Street Ltd. operates in Bihor County, Oradea, on Merilor Street, No. 10, with the headquarters on Merilor Street, No. 12, having social capital, and is registered with the Trade Register; with a unique registration code.

also by visiting competing guesthouses in our area, thus gathering all the information and aspects that each guesthouse offers separately, forming a complete picture of what exists.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The accommodation unit is well-positioned, has 3 stars, and is structured on 2 floors and an attic. On the ground floor, there is a kitchen with a refrigerator, table and chairs, microwave, oven, stove, and sink, where guests can prepare their own meals. Additionally, the unit includes 2 bathrooms, 2 rooms with double beds and children's beds, 3 rooms with double beds, and an apartment located in the attic. Each room is equipped with a TV with internet access. Only one room has a balcony with a view of the scenery and pool, but all rooms have their own air conditioning. The unit is connected to the city water supply, gas, and also has water heating via a boiler. Moreover, the unit has a small meeting room with a desk and the possibility of projecting presentations, as well as a living room where guests can have meals, watch various

programs on TV, with air conditioning, a fireplace, chairs, and armchairs.

Last but not least, the exterior features a large garden for the season, a pool with a view, bar/DJ, barbecue, pizza oven, 2 terraces, children's playground, video and audio monitored parking 24/7, and a boxing room. Guests have access to the pool and terraces, and we offer a promotional package for a fitness center located 2 km away, as well as a tennis court with or without a coach 300m from the guesthouse.

The guesthouse's facilities are:

- Air conditioning
- Food
- Accommodation
- Children's entertainment
- Transport
- Itinerary
- The possibility of booking activities in the city or metropolitan area

Table No.1

Age of Clients Who Stayed at APPLE Guesthouse in 2023

Age of Lodged Clients	0-18 years	18-35 years	35-66 years	66- years
Number of Guests	820	1250	1520	10

Data processed from the check-in register.

Regarding the nationality of clients who stayed at the guesthouse in 2023, the

majority are Romanians, but there are also Hungarians, Germans, and Italians.

Table No. 2

Nationality of Clients at Apple Guesthouse in 2023

Country of Origin	Number of Stays at the Guesthouse
England	50
Czech Republic	20
France	40
Germany	120
Italy	44
Lithuania	20
Netherlands	2
Poland	80
Moldova	8
Romania	2532
Slovenia	20
Spani	50
Sweden	8
Ukraine	60
Hungary	557

Tourism practiced in this area caters to both Romanians and foreigners. The segment that most frequently uses the services of the analyzed guesthouse comprises young people, those aged between 30-40, as well as those of the third age

Considering the fact that our accommodation capacity is fully occupied for

almost three months, we think that the added value we can bring is through organizing children's birthday parties. By renting out the dining hall and terrace, we can achieve higher profits.

Table No. 3
Presentation of the Offer at APPLE Guesthouse in Terms of Tourist Product Offered in 2023

January	February	March	April	May	June
Occupancy	60%	45%	-	-	80%
Meals	Breakfast included, lunch	Breakfast included, lunch and dinner on			
Menu	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional
Accommodation	5 rooms, 10-12	5 rooms, 10-12	5 rooms, 10-12 beds	5 rooms, 10-12 beds	5 rooms, 10-12 beds
Entertainment	Themed anniversaries, team-building				
	July	August	September	October	November
Occupancy Rate	100%	100%	95%	79%	-
Meals	Breakfast included, lunch and dinner on request				
Menu	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional	Traditional
Accommodation	5 rooms, 10-12 beds				
Entertainment	Themed anniversaries, team-building	Themed anniversaries, team-building	Themed anniversaries, team-building	Themed anniversaries, team-building	Themed

- Live concerts
- Thematic barbecues
- Thematic parties
- Club-type events

CONCLUSIONS

Regarding tourism in the municipality of Oradea and the location of this guesthouse, we have a growing trend due to the fact that the municipality's policies are aimed at increasing the number of tourists who visit the city. The measures taken for this can be followed on the website visitoradea.ro. With this starting point, we looked at how we can increase the income of this guesthouse's owners without investing in modifying the accommodation capacity.

As we observed in the previous analysis, even in 2023, the guesthouse generated income from entertainment. We have proposals to improve activities in such a way as to increase the already obtained revenues. Our proposals are:

- Pool parties
- Thematic conferences
- Sports competitions

From a financial perspective, those who use these services fall into the category of people with medium and low material means, considering that tourism requires less money compared to accommodation in the hotel system. The category of tourists with higher incomes, who prefer medium-range tourism out of curiosity or for rest, should not be completely excluded either.

All these improvements can be made with minimal financial effort. The most important aspect would be the promotion method of this unit, which relies on the quality of the services offered and determines tourist satisfaction, which can turn them into loyal customers.

Moreover, they can recommend the guesthouse where they had a good time to other people, and through this word-of-

mouth advertising, the occupancy rate can increase considerably.

Of course, having an internet site that draws attention to the existence of the guesthouse and popularizes its offerings is always welcome. Less effective is costly promotion (print media, radio, TV), which often does not justify its very high costs through increased efficiency. Exceptions are magazines or shows that focus on travel, tourism, etc.

The advertising methods to be used will be: listing on tourism websites and portals in Romania, building a website, featuring ads in local publications as well as national magazines and publications, especially those with a tourism focus.

Another classic advertising method for the guesthouse would be for an employee to go to the train station and airport to promote

the guesthouse, directing tourists to it; they would ensure the tourists' transportation from the train station and airport to the guesthouse.

Upon arrival, guests will receive a leaflet with all the information about the guesthouse, a map of the area, and the entertainment schedule that will take place at the guesthouse and in which they can participate.

Discounts will be offered for children and loyal customers.

Upon departure, tourists will receive a souvenir from the guesthouse's pantry.

The accommodation forms have a field for the email address, so new offers will be sent to the clients' email addresses.

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MARKETING MIX AND DEVELOPMENT POSSIBILITIES OF A SMALL BUSINESS FROM BIHOR COUNTRY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study purpose to analyze the economic potential and the mix of marketing of a small business in Bihor County, in the Lazuri area, Rosia commune and at the same time its journey from its establishment to the first profit figures in 5 years. Issues regarding the demographic and economic elements of the area, competition and market placement through the mix of the four product, price, promotion and sale were analyzed. It also aims to move from old to new cultures. Highlighting and promoting them on the market are also important points in the market study.

Keywords: Business, marketing, cultures, aronia, mix
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INTRODUCTION

Rosia commune is located on the border of Padurea Craiului Mountains, having the Hills of Padura Craiului, at an altitude between 400 m and about 785 m. Rosia commune is situated on the slopes of the hills of Rosia and in the meadow area of the streams that cross these hills. They are covered with deciduous and resinous forests, pastures and bare rock tops, and in the calcareous massifs there are bauxite deposits; there was intense mining activity in the area to extract bauxite.

The hilly area is fragmented by the courses and tributaries of numerous streams and valleys: sodoles brook, Soimus brook, Strait brook, Toplita brook, Cuts valley, Black Stone valley, White Stone valley, White Stone valley, White Stone valley, the Lazurilor Valley, etc., which form deep gorges, such as the Albioarei Gorges, the Lazurilor Gorges and the Box Valley Keys, which are particularly picturesque. These hills are made up of limestone, where over the centuries, the waters infiltrated in the basement have formed caves and avenues with a special landscape, mentioning here the Caves: Ciur-Izbuc, Ciur-Ponor, Cave, Cave of the Cow, Gruiet Cave, which are designated as protected areas by Law no. 5/2000 - monuments and nature reserves. The hills show clay deposits on the upper and on the slopes, which after heavy rains are susceptible to active or potentially

slippery slides, affecting four main areas. (<https://www.comunariosiabihor.ro/>)

Rosia tourist area is an entrance in Padurea Craiului Mountains and is considered one of the most complex karst areas in Romania.

Regarding the traditions and customs, in the Rosia tourist area you can visit the Weaving workshop and the collection of horned violins of the Codoban family, as well as attend the Festival of pricesne in Rosia and admire the popular Port, as well as the Festival of violin with hornet and full Strait.

Geographically, it is located in the northern part of Beius Country, near the Padurea Craiului Mountains, on the lower course of the Red Valley River. The closest towns are Beius, at a distance of 18 km, and Oradea, at a distance of 70 km.

According to the census carried out in 2021, the number of inhabitants of Rosia commune is 2,285, down from the previous census in 2011, when 2,384 inhabitants were registered. The majority of the population is Romanian (97.55%), and for 2.41% ethnic belonging is unknown.

Fig.1. Number of population

The number of inhabitants of the commune suffered, but in a good sense, because in 2021 there were registered a number of 2285 inhabitants, compared to 2011 when only 23884 inhabitants were registered.

Fig.2 Population by age group

<http://comuna.info/locuitori-rosia-bh/>

As can be seen from the adjacent chart, most of the population is represented by the younger generation.

The population aged 0-9 years represents 9.10% of the total population. The population between 10-19 years is 12.29%, close to the population aged 20-29 years, representing a percentage of 12.69%. The population aged 30-39 is 11.77% percent. The population aged between 40-59 years represents a percentage of 27.57%, and the percentages will notice a small decrease, as a result the ages between 60-69 represent 12.21%, and the ages between 70-85 represent a percentage of 11.68%, followed by the ages of over 85 with a percentage of 2.66%. According to this statistic, the lowest percentages are given by the very young and the elderly, and those over 30 will be the majority.

The main activity of the area is agriculture, and the young people of the area work at small enterprises and factories located in the nearest towns near the village, such as Beius or even Oradea. Livestock still remains the main activity and loved even by young people. Both at the commune level and at the Lazuri village level, the basic activity of those remaining in the village remains agriculture. The population of Lazuri village is decreasing from one year to the next, and the remaining population is rapidly moving towards ageing, as a result 328 people are over the age of 70 represents 14.34% of the total population. The village comprises 128 houses, but of which there are only 108 inhabitants. Over the last twenty years, the number of villagers has decreased exponentially because the teenagers prefer to move to the urban life.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For this research we used credible websites and specialized sites such as: *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022*, *The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2023*, Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (MADR) and *The aronia plantation*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the context of marketing strategies for an aronia business, it is essential to consider a comprehensive mix of marketing elements to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage. Traditional marketing mix strategies, such as product, price, promotion, and distribution (*KISTOR, GEMECH, STRATEGIZING MARKETING MIX FOR BUSINESS SUSINABILITY OF ETHIOPIAN MSES, 2022*), can be enhanced by incorporating additional variables like policies, physical climate, and partners. Moreover, expanding the marketing mix to include strategic resources, differentiation of products, and innovative processes can significantly impact the sustainability and long-term success of medium and small-scale enterprises. (*MARKETING MIX FROM ISLAMIC MARKETING PERSPECTIVE, Anwar, 2012*) By adapting these diverse marketing strategies tailored to the specific needs of an aronia business, owners can effectively reach their target market, differentiate their products, and ensure business sustainability in a competitive environment.

Initiating a new business in a predominantly agricultural area. This fact was not at all an easy one, especially due to the fact that the interruption of grain harvesting was not an easy process. Initiating a new culture, a culture that even by APIA could not be identified and not losing control and aspiration was a difficult thing. The initiative started from the desire to give up traditional cages such as corn, wheat or potatoes because financially and economically it was not something profitable. Our attention was directed to aronia, so in 2020 we set up a plantation of 40 areas.

Romanian products are first and foremost a cultural gift that must be preserved and promoted at its true value if they are exploited to the maximum.

One of the strengths of the economy is the quality and diversity of agro-food production. This gives producers in Romania and the European Union a competitive advantage. This contributes significantly to the current cultural and gastronomic heritage.

Voluntary quality schemes for indigenous agro-food products play an important role inining traditional food-producing crops in certain regions. (MINISTRY OF AGRICULTURE AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT 2020)

Food fortification refers back to the post-harvest addition of micronutrients to meals, via a shape of processing to boom the content material of 1 or extra important micronutrients to enhance the dietary nice of the meals deliver and offer a public fitness gain with minimum chance to fitness. Biofortification, on the opposite hand, provides the ones micronutrients via strategies of crop cross-breeding with sorts of better attention of preferred micronutrient(s) or genetic modification. These are many of the maximum cost-powerful measures to assist save you micronutrient deficiencies,²⁵¹ as those can deliver important micronutrients to huge segments of the populace with out requiring radical modifications in meals intake styles nor person selection for compliance. (FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2022, CAP 4.)

Across the entirety of the rural-urban gradient, the predominant source of food consumption comes from markets. Consequently, the dietary patterns of households are influenced by factors such as cost and accessibility, which are in turn

influenced by the configuration of agrifood systems, encompassing food distribution and value-adding networks. These elements should be carefully considered when formulating effective strategies and investments to guarantee that rural, peri-urban, and urban communities have access to economical and nutritious diets. A holistic policy approach, transcending sectorial boundaries and administrative divisions, will be essential in shaping the urbanization of regions and impacting agrifood systems along the rural-urban gradient. (FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2023, CAP 1.)

Marketing should most likely help a business and a launch of new products. Without a good marketing strategy, you're headed nowhere. Or at the beginning of the road you need to know exactly which groups you are addressing and which will be your future customers. The information must be clear and accurate.

"The best advertisement is the advertisement that satisfied customers do." (SHAW, THE FUTURE OF MARKETING: AN INTERVIEW WITH PHILIP KOTLER, THE "FATHER OF MODERN MARKETING")

"Any business is a business that offers a service. Does your service spark a smile on your client's face?" (SHAW, THE FUTURE OF MARKETING: AN INTERVIEW WITH PHILIP KOTLER, THE "FATHER OF MODERN MARKETING")

A clean and honest method of marketing will keep the products on the market. A clean and honest method of marketing will keep old buyers and bring new ones. For a business to be able to maintain itself in the market, THE PRODUCT, PRICE, PROMOTION AND SALE must be closely linked.

Online meals sharing offerings can collect and redistribute meals surpluses throughout neighborhood groups and supermarkets in city and rural areas, accordingly supporting to lessen meals waste. They also can have a superb effect on meals environments, particularly whilst surplus nutritious meals which includes end result and veggies are "rescued" and redistributed. Smartphone programs that allow customers to make small donations to unique tasks can offer assist for various operations, from constructing resilience to enforcing college feeding programs to handing over meals help in emergency situations. (FOOD AND

AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2023, CAP 5.2)

Food labeling can make a contribution to a wholesome meals surroundings with the aid of using presenting records to the client approximately the content material of ingredients, drawing client interest to the blessings and dangers of precise vitamins or substances of public fitness concern, and motivating producers to provide ingredients that have more healthy vitamins profiles. Nutrient profiling is a technique that assesses the dietary first-class of processed ingredients and beverages. It is likewise a device to manual coverage interventions which includes front-of-package (FOP) or menu labeling and regulations on advertising to kids to assist tell and empower customers to shift call for toward wholesome diets. For example, the OBAASIMA venture in Ghana has used a FOP seal and social advertising marketing campaign to inspire nearby SMEs to provide nutritious products. The venture has proven promising initial outcomes in growing client consciousness and SME capability and is increasing to extra cities. Fifty four Regional nutrient profiles have additionally been advanced as a useful resource for country wide or nearby policymakers.(FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2023, CAP 5.2)

Developing a business in rural areas is not an easy route, but that does not mean that it can not.

A plethora of technology and improvements is available (aleven though now no longer always on hand to all nations and social groups) spanning whole agrifood systems. Whether those technology and improvements are inclusive for all relies upon now no longer best on their adoption and impact, however additionally on how studies and development (R&D) is shaped. Between 1981 and 2016, there has been a doubling of worldwide public funding in agricultural R&D, and large middle-profits nations (MICs), specifically Brazil, China and India, notably extended their funding in agricultural R&D.(FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD For the first two years, the plant did not make any fruit, only adapted to the soil. In the third year, the plant made little fruits on each plant.

SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2023, CAP 5)

In order to be able to apply a marketing policy as correct and real as possible, the first steps towards a good business was the quality of the raw material itself. Distributing products based on aronia, implicitly the purpose was and is to use a high quality of aronia fruit. The fact that we do not interfere with anything on the plant, brings us added value in the face of competition. Plants are not sprinkled with herbicides or any other chemical substances that could spoil the quality of the plant and implicit the fruit later, thereby increasing the value of the fruit. The fact that the environment and the area where we grow aronia is unpolluted is an important factor for consumers. The fact that the products are carefully grown and cared for, leads to higher costs. These costs increase with packaging, as we wanted to continue with this high quality and on the packaging side. At the same time, the protection of the environment was another important factor, so our products are packed in glass or cardboard. We chose the two options so as not to change the nutritional values of the product with plastic particles that could have come from the spots. At the moment the most expensive product coming from our plantation is the juice of aronia, which raises the price around the amount of 100 lei/l, and the cheapest, the most expensive, if you can say so would be fresh, the price is 20 lei/kg.

For the promotion of the products we relied most on the advertisement „from word to word” considering it even the most real, sincere and promising, but we also helped a lot with social media sites like Instagram and Facebook, creating a page of our own. This has brought us closer to consumers because of the distance.

Fig. 3. Percentage of production

Profitless. In the fourth year, the plant made a better production. For the current year we expect a doubling last year

The previous

Imag. 1. First year plantation

Imag.2. Third year plantation

Imag. 3. Fifth year plantation

Fig. 4. Percentage of production

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, aronia cultivation has a high profit potential for farmers with small areas. We sell considering that today more and

figure illustrates the products we distribute from our plantation and the percentages of profitability that each product shares. First, we send to consumers fresh fruits that have a profitability percentage of 10%. The next and most profitable product is the juice of aronia, with a percentage of 60%, followed by syrup without sugar of aronia with a percentage of 20%, a percentage of 5% it has aronia jam and last but not least aronia powder that has a percentage of 5%.

In the years to come, we want to increase production and diversify it, so that we can associate aronia and products obtained on its basis with other fruits, too, such as apples and nuts.

more emphasis is placed on agriculture and modernization, thus creating favorable conditions for farmers, big investors choose to invest in this field.

However, improvements in virtual technology danger growing the virtual divide throughout socioeconomic groups (e.g. profits, gender and age), geographies (e.g. rural and concrete populations) and geopolitical groups, further to elevating worries round manage of facts and power, democracy and human rights. Some of the elements to cope with encompass the excessive fee of a few virtual technology, absence of virtual infrastructure, loss of virtual abilities and literacy, and sociocultural limitations connected to gender in addition to troubles of facts asymmetry, records possession and management, privacy, and cybersecurity. Worldwide, 2.7 billion humans do now no longer have get entry to the net, and stuck or cell broadband offerings are too costly for the common patron in maximum low-profits countries hundred and forty Moreover, in LMICs, ladies are sixteen percentage much less in all likelihood to make use of cell net as compared to men, even as adults dwelling in rural regions are 33 percentage much less in all likelihood to apply cell net than their city counterparts. (FOOD AND AGRICULTURE ORGANIZATION OF THE UNITED NATION, THE STATE OF FOOD SECURITY AND NUTRITION IN THE WORLD 2023, CAP 5.2)

Nvidia's CEO, Jensen Huang is shaking things up, proclaiming the era of prioritizing coding skills is over. Suggests, we could focus on fields like agriculture and education. Those machinery for harvesting fruits is becoming a necessity for large plantation. The fruits re picked and then shaken off leaves and other

impurities.(*COLLINS, NVIDIA CEO PREDICTS THE DEATH OF CODING — JENSEN HUANG SAYS AI WILL DO THE WORK, SO KIDS DON'T NEED TO LEARN, 2024*)

SUGESTIONS

For an efficient culture and products obtained on the basis of the Aronia, we plan to develop the culture. A first objective is the expansion of the culture, more than the doubling of the surface. The productivity of the crop is large enough that we can start the operation of mechanized fruit picking and packaging. Followed by the machine for tagging. Harvesting the fruit with the help of a mechanical picker helps and increases first, the picking time, but also the yield of the harvested fruit, losing a very small amount of fruit. The picking machine manages to collect 98% of the total fruit on the bushes, and the loss of fruit does not exceed 1%.

(<https://www.utilajeagro.ro/masina-de-recoltat-fructe-de-padure-jagoda-model-aronic/>) Aronia can be picked with both a special aronia picking machine towed by a tractor and a currant picking machine, as the fruits and bushes are very similar.

The food industry has developed a lot precisely because of marketing. To make packaged products more efficient, we aim to obtain an automatic labeling machine, especially for jars of jam, syrup and juice, but also to favor the marketing and appearance of our products.

(<https://internavytec.ro/produs/masina-de-etichetat-automata/>)

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AN OVERVIEW OF THE DOBROGEA GASTRONOMY

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Dobrogea is a region of Romania, unique for its cultural, architectural and historical diversity generated by multiculturalism, with many ethnic groups living together in the area: Turks, Tatars, Lipovans, Greeks, Bulgarians, Ukrainians, Aromanians.

From a gastronomic point of view, the area offers a wide range of traditional dishes, fish being the main ingredient due to the geographical location of the region. The dishes of Dobrogea reflect the richness of the raw materials available in the area, so that the region can be divided into two macro-areas: that of fish and that of meat, dairy and vegetable dishes.

Keywords: gastronomy, traditions, traditional dishes, gastronomic influences

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INTRODUCTION

Dobrogea is a geographical and historical region in the south-east of Romania, with the Black Sea to the east, the Danube to the south and Bulgaria to the south and west. This region is one of the oldest settlements in Europe and is known for its cultural, historical and natural diversity. (Cociu M., 1993)

Dobrogea has a rich history, having been inhabited by various peoples throughout the ages, including Thracians, Greeks, Romans, Turks, Tatars and Bulgarians. It was an important strategic point for ancient and medieval empires. This cultural heritage is reflected in the varied architecture, spoken languages and local customs. This ethnic diversity has influenced the language, traditions and gastronomy of the region. Greek and Roman ruins, such as Histria and Callatis, bear witness to the region's rich historical heritage. Overall, Dobrogea is a fascinating region with a rich history and culture, a remarkable natural and human diversity and a growing economy, with considerable tourist and economic potential. (Bordanc Floarea, 2008; Cociu M., 1993)

The ethnic diversity of Dobrogea gives the region a different character from neighbouring Muntenia, with the regional cuisine incorporating elements brought by the Turks, Tatars, Greeks, Aromanians, Lipovans and Germans of the region. Dobrogea has historically been crossed by shepherds, and

sheep meat products are common, especially in recipes borrowed from oriental or Aromanian cuisines, such as *săşlăc* (a dish made from lamb cut into pieces, put on skewers and cooked on a grill) or *ghiudem* (a dry and spicy sausage), as well as in local recipes, such as pastrami. Fish, game, mutton, poultry, beef and pork are frequently used in cooking Dobrogenic dishes. The Dobrogea region is known for its abundance of fresh vegetables and fruit, dairy products, cheese and eggs. (Bordanc Floarea, 2008; Roman R. A., 1998; Tatulici M., 2018)

Dobrogean cuisine has its own specific traditions, with dishes such as Dobrogean sarmals, cheese pies or fresh fish prepared in various ways. These culinary traditions are often passed down from one generation to the next within families or local communities. (Bordanc Floarea, 2008; Roman R. A., 1998)

At the same time, painting Easter eggs is another widespread tradition in Dobrogea. People use bright colors and traditional patterns to decorate the eggs, and they become an integral part of the Easter decoration. (Roman R. A., 1998; <https://www.romania-travel-guide.com/attractii/traditii-locale/traditii-si-obiceiuri-din-dobrogea.html>)

Traditions of Dobrogea are those that reflect the diversity and cultural richness of this unique region of Romania. The folk costume of Dobrogea is an expression of the cultural identity and traditions of the place. Dobrogea has a rich and diverse history and this is reflected in the folk costumes worn by the

locals. A common element of folk costume in Dobrogea is the use of bright colours and rich ornaments. Women wear long, colourful dresses decorated with embroidery and lace, while men wear loose shirts and trousers, sometimes accessorised with specific garments such as embroidered jackets or traditional hats. (<https://www.info-delta.ro/traditii-in-dobrogea-28/portul-din-dobrogea--45.html>; <https://acasalaromani.ro/costumul-popular-din-zona-dobrogei>)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methodology of the present study combines standard research techniques and methods, such as: documentation, analysis, synthesis and formulation of conclusions. In this sense, a rich bibliography was consulted, respectively different publications, monographs with reference to the traditions and cuisine of Dobrogea.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The diversity of the dishes in the Dobrogea cuisine shows the influences due to the multitude of cultures in this area. Due to its position along the Black Sea and Danube coasts, Dobrogea is famous for its fresh fish and seafood. Fish is prepared in various ways: grilled, fried, boiled or smoked, often accompanied by aromatic sauces and fresh vegetables. Dobrogea is also known for its milk and cheese production. Bellows cheese and telemea cheese are two of the local specialities appreciated for their rich and authentic taste. (<https://gastronomietraditionala.ro/alimentati-a-in-dobrogea>)

The dishes from the Dobrogean cuisine are light, in their preparation a lot of oil, butter and margarine are used. The soups are soured with borscht, cabbage juice but also vinegar, they are made from vegetables and especially from fish. Fresh vegetable snacks in the form of salad in combination with eggs, cheese, cream are used a lot. The basic dishes are accompanied by rice, vegetable and pasta side dishes. (<https://gastronomietraditionala.ro/alimentati-a-in-dobrogea>)

Şaşlâc dobrogean is a traditional dish from the Dobrogea region, which is of Turkish origin. It is prepared mainly from diced mutton, mutton or lamb. The meat is marinated in a rich mixture of spices and flavours, which may include garlic, onions, olive oil, vinegar, lemon

juice, aromatic herbs such as thyme, rosemary, dill and basil, and spices such as pepper, coriander or paprika. The pieces of meat are placed on skewers and cooked on the grill. This dish is often served with various side dishes and salads, such as scallops, fried or baked potatoes, grilled vegetables or rice. (Roman R. A., 1998; <https://povestilemariinegre.ro/saslac>).

Dobrogean **sarmale** are a distinctive variant of the famous traditional Romanian dish. They are known for some peculiarities that differentiate them from other **sarmale** recipes from other regions of the country. A distinctive feature of Dobrogean **sarmale** is the use of vine leaves instead of cabbage, as is more common in other similar Romanian recipes. These leaves are filled with a mixture of rice, meat, onions, spices such as thyme, dill and basil, and sometimes vegetables such as carrots or peppers are added. (Ghidul gastronomic al Romaniei - Bucataria traditionala, 2010).

Roe salad. Preserving roe with oil has been used since the time of the Byzantine Empire. In the Balkan countries the method of preparation has been preserved under the name Tarama. In the old days, only carp roe was prepared in Wallachia and Moldavia, and later pike roe was used as a more tasty alternative (Stroe Monica, Iancu Bogdan, 2012). It was the Greek population that came to the Dobrogea area from Greece that developed the roe salad. The inhabitants of the Delta improved and took over the recipe, resulting in a new recipe that not only retains the original flavor, but improves it. (<https://www.info-delta.ro/retete-culinare-31/reteta/salata-de-icre-de-pest>).

Salad of roe is a preparation based on fish roe (carp, carp, pike), onion, oil, lemon, mineral water and salt. It can be served with olives, greens, lemon, paprika, onions or bread. (<https://pofta-buna.com/salata-de-icre-cu-sau-fara-ceapa-reteta-pescareasca>)

Scordolea. The word "scordolea" comes from garlic and is of Greek origin. **Scordolea** is one of the oldest fish recipes, specific to Dobrogea. This dish is based on mashed potatoes, baked fish, walnuts, garlic, salt, pepper and oil. This dish is often served as a side dish or as a side dish to fish or other main dishes. (<https://www.info-delta.ro/retete-culinare-31/reteta/scordolea-cu-pest-sarat-54.html>)

Storceag is a traditional dish, being a simple and tasty dish. It is a thick and hearty soup, prepared mainly from fish (crucian carp, zander or flatfish). The recipe for storceag is based on a variety of influences, mainly from

Ukrainian cuisine (where the name comes from), but also from Romanian pastoral cuisine, using whey for texture and acidity. The base of the soup in modern Dobrogea cuisine consists of vegetables (potatoes, celery, carrots, parsley, onions), and whey is traditionally used for souring the soup, sometimes being substituted with a mixture of cream and egg. (Roman R. A., 1998; Stroe Monica, Iancu Bogdan, 2012)

Fish Borscht. One of the most common Dobrogean soups is fish borscht. This soup is soured with borscht, but other souring methods are also used, such as lemon juice, vinegar or cabbage leaves. Initially only freshwater fish were used. The soup is based on the meat of fish (red snapper, crucian carp, sterlet, carp, frog fish, sturgeon, stellate sturgeon, catfish, zander, pike), rice, potatoes and onions. It is seasoned with different greens (fennel, parsley, to taste and dill) and seasoned with salt, pepper and hot peppers. It is served plain, warm or cold, usually with polenta. (Jurcovan Silvia, 2012; Roman R. A., 1998)

Saramura (fish brine) is a Romanian dish that contains different types of fish. It is also a process of preserving food for later consumption. Fish brine is prepared from three types of fish: small (ablet), medium (crucian carp) and large (carp, flounder or catfish), fried on a hot griddle (plinta) previously sprinkled with sea salt. Besides the fish, it has tomatoes, paprika, chilli peppers, onions, thyme, dill, parsley and garlic cooked in the oven. The dish can be served with polenta.

(<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Saramura>)

Plachia is a dish based on fish meat (carp, caras, red mullet, perch, novac), onion, carrot, celery, garlic, bell pepper, dry white wine, broth, bay leaves, thyme, black pepper, vinegar (or lemon juice), parsley and oil. The fish is placed on a bed of baked vegetables. It is served with polenta. (Roman R. A., 2010; <https://www.e-retete.ro/retete/plachie-de-pest>)

Dobrogean pie. The Dobrogean pie recipe was spread, reinterpreted and known by people outside the region. The sheets for Dobrogean pie should be as thin as possible, almost transparent. This pie is based on a dough in which sweet or salty cheese is integrated, mixed with egg, green onion, dill and baked in different shapes. (Roman R. A., 2010; <https://www.libertatea.ro/lifestyle/retete-de-placinta-dobrogeana>)

Kobete pie is a dish specific to the turkish-tatar community in Dobrogea, being

made especially during the month of Ramadan. This pie is based on a simple dough in which yogurt has also been integrated, and the filling is based on meat (chicken or beef), rice and sautéed onions. Serve with ayran or yogurt. (Stroe Monica, Iancu Bogdan, 2012; <https://pofta-buna.com/placinta-kobete-reteta-turco-tatareasca-dobrogeana>)

Suberec is part of the local specificity of Dobrogea, as part of Romanian cuisine. The pie is popular in Romania, Russia, Turkey, Ukraine as a snack, but its origin is from the cuisine of the Crimean Tatars. *Suberec* is a kind of pie in the shape of a semicircle, filled with spiced minced meat and onions. The outside of the pie has a texture similar to a *scovergi* or a *langos*, being cooked in corn or sunflower oil. (<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Suberec>)

Geantâk is a pie specific to the turkish-tatar community of Dobrogea. The pie is based on a leavened dough filled with a mixture of minced meat (beef, lamb or poultry), fat yoghurt, sautéed onions and mint. It is seasoned with salt and pepper, and eggs and poppies are used as garnishes. Serve hot or cold with ayran or yoghurt. (Roman R. A., 2010; <https://pofta-buna.com/geantak-placinta-cu-carne-turco-tatareasca>)

Ghisman is a pie in which cow's cheese and sour cream are the main ingredients. Eggs, sour dairy products (yoghurt, kefir), melted butter and lemon juice are also used. Serve cold with powdered sugar, blueberries and strawberries. (Roman R. A., 2010; <https://cartederetete.ro/ghisman>)

Dobrogean baklava is a tasty reinterpretation, adapted to the gastronomy specific to the Dobrogea area, of the traditional dessert of oriental origin. The aspect that makes this dish stand out is the use of puff pastry and a sugar syrup enriched with vanilla, cinnamon, rose water. The filling is made of nuts, butter and sugar. (<https://www.skytrip.ro/baclava-din-regiunea-dobrogea-re-167.html>)

Muhalebi with wheat or rice flour, semolina or starch is a popular dessert in the Middle East and in Romania, being a thickened milk pudding. (<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Muhalebi>) *Muhalebi* is prepared in a simple way with milk and rose water, wheat flour or corn starch for thickening and served with powdered sugar and pistachios. The dessert was popular in the 19th and 20th centuries. Currently, in Dobrogea, a variant is prepared with grape must instead of milk and sugar and

served with walnut core. (Roman R. A., 2010; <https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Muhalebiu>)

Acacia flower donuts. This dish is cooked in the months of May-June, when it is the flowering period of the acacia. Acacia donuts are made from a leavened dough in which acacia inflorescences are integrated, the donuts being flavored thanks to the flowers. After frying, the donuts are served warm sprinkled with powdered sugar. (Ghidul gastronomic al Romaniei - Bucataria traditionala, 2010; <https://www.lauralaurentiu.ro/retete-culinare/deserturi-dulciuri-de-casa/gogosi-din-flori-de-salcam>)

CONCLUSIONS

Dobrogea is known for its distinct culinary specialties, the geographical location of the area determining that the basic ingredients in traditional dishes are fish, cheese, vegetables, lamb, pork, honey, spices and aromatic herbs.

Due to the multicultural influence in the area, changes have also occurred in the field of gastronomy. The population of the area has learned and adapted many savoury dishes (șaslâc, scordolea, storceag, Kobete pie, suberec, geantâk), as well as sweet dishes (baclava, muhalebiu).

From the Danube Delta and the Black Sea coast come savoury specialties such as roe salad, fish borscht, plachia, fish brine, Dobrogean sarmala, Dobrogean pie. Among the area's sweet specialties are acacia flower doughnuts, chisman, baclava.

In conclusion, the cuisine of Dobrogea is complex, with a wide range of dishes and unique recipe techniques. The region is special because of the harmony created between the communities present in the area and the culinary traditions.

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CUSTOMERS' PERCEPTION OF TOURIST GUESTHOUSES IN THE HISTORIC NEIGHBORHOODS OF TIMIȘOARA, THROUGH A STATISTICAL IMAGE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The aim of the study is to statistically verify the existence of some differences between the historic neighborhoods of Timișoara, regarding the perception of tourists. The statistical data processed contain the scores obtained by the units with the function of tourist accommodation, through the booking.com platform. From the total types of accommodation units, a random sample of tourist pensions and apartments for rent was selected. Statistically processed data refer to location, cleanliness, facilities, value for money, comfort, respectively the overall score. Direct comparisons were made between the groups determined by the results from the Cetate, Fabric, Iosefin and Elisabetin neighborhoods, but also data for the guesthouses located in other neighborhoods than the historical ones.

Keywords: Timișoara, tourism, statistics, comparisons

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INTRODUCTION

The historical districts of Timișoara are Cetate, Fabric and Iosefin-Elisabetin. Their boundaries are difficult to represent exactly today due to the evolution of the city over time. However, an approximate delimitation is possible to achieve.

The Cetate neighborhood is located in the central area of the city. From the residence of King Carol Robert of Anjou from the beginning of the 14th century, the citadel becomes the element around which the city develops. Currently, buildings in the Baroque, Art Nouveau or Secession style predominate. The Fabric district is located in the eastern part of the Cetate district. The name comes from the large number of factories that developed in this neighborhood. The first living quarters appeared in the middle of the 18th century. From the beginning it had a multicultural character, being inhabited by people of different nationalities. The Iosefin and Elisabetin neighborhoods developed as residential areas also in the middle of the 18th century. It was also during this period that the Bega Canal was built. It becomes an important navigable route. The train station built after 1850 brings an important development to the neighborhood. Baroque or eclectic, Art Nouveau or Jugendstil

buildings predominate (TM INFO, 2024; TA, 2024; Almasan I.M. et al, 2002; TIMIȘOARA CITY MAPS, 2024). Many of the buildings in the historic districts are old and some are in a serious state of disrepair. Their rehabilitation is an important concern of the European Union countries (Pescari et al 2023).

Figure 1 The location of the historical neighborhoods in Timișoara:
Cetate (1), Fabric (2),
Iosefin-Elisabetin (3)

Source: Our representation using Google Maps

In this paper, the locations registered on booking.com were included approximately in the three neighborhoods.

The aim of the paper is to make a comparison between neighborhoods for the main indicators given by tourists as scores on the booking.com platform.

The booking.com platform (BOOKING, 2024) offers a very useful source of information that allows understanding some phenomena that occur in the tourism industry. Consulting the Google Academic platform (GOOGLE ACADEMIC, 2024), only for the period 01.01.2024 and until 03.27.2024 the term booking.com is found in 621 results corresponding to some scientific articles.

Various scientific topics related to the historical districts of Timisoara are frequent study topics. Among these we mention urban degradation and regeneration viewed by neighborhood residents (Tuță et al, 2023), uses of disused areas as creative spaces (Marian-Potra et al, 2020), concerns for the development of new objectives (Văduva et al, 2022), seismic risks of historic buildings (Onescu et al, 2023), the concept of digital story (Vert et al, 2021), the use of the Bega canal for tourist purposes (Petroman et al, 2020), digital applications for the knowledge of urban heritage (Szekely et al 2023) or general studies on tourism potential (Babcsanyi et al, 2021).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

A random sample of 45 locations found on the booking.com platform was studied. Their location was estimated within the limits of the old neighborhoods of Timișoara: Cetate, Fabric, Iosefin and Elisabetin. Tourist accommodation units located in other areas of Timișoara were mentioned in a separate group.

The analyzed data refer to location, cleanliness, facilities, value for money, comfort, respectively the overall score. These values are tracked on the booking platform during the period of March 2024.

A statistical summary was made that included the minimum, maximum, mean and median values as well as the coefficients of variation of the series.

Testing of differences between groups was performed using the non-parametric Kruskal–Wallis test. Moreover, in order to confirm the significance of the differences between the groups, the ANOVA parametric test was also used.

SAS Studio was used for statistical processing and graphical representations. SAS-Nonparametric One-Way ANOVA was used for comparisons (SAS 2024, Anderson et al 2020, Abu-Bader 2021, West et al 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A statistical summary with indicators of central tendency and dispersion for the statistical data in the three historical districts, in other districts but also for their total are shown in table 1. Overall score presents values between a minimum of 7.1 and a maximum of 10. The average value is 8.84. This is in the 95% confidence interval between 8.61, 9.08. In agreement with the median value, approximately half of the studied units have an overall score higher than 9. The coefficients of variation of the statistical series have low values in all the studied cases. The highest value is 10.64%, which indicates the homogeneity of the data series. Thus, the score indicated by tourists have a homogeneous character, without high variability. This aspect is also given by the range value which does not exceed 2.90.

The values of the indicators in the four neighborhoods are different. By using the Kruskal-Wallis test we will determine whether the differences have statistical significance. For each indicator compared, the null hypothesis represents the absence of differences between neighborhoods. Values of the probability p , lower than $\alpha=0.05$, involve the rejection of the null hypothesis. This fact indicates statistically significant differences between the values of the indicators in the studied neighborhoods. Each application of the test led to the indicators found in Figures 2 a-f. Both the values related to the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test (chi square, p) are presented, as well as the values returned by ANOVA (F, p) within the diagrams.

Table 1

Statistical summary regarding the score values indicated by the booking platform for the studied sample consisting of accommodation units in the historical neighborhoods of Timișoara

	N	Variable	Mean	Std Dev	Minim	Maxim	Median	Range	Lower CI 95%	Upper CI 95%	Coeff of Variation
Total	45	Location	8.97	0.62	7.90	10.00	9.00	2.10	8.79	9.16	6.86
		Cleanliness	8.98	0.79	7.10	10.00	9.20	2.90	8.74	9.22	8.83
		Facilities	8.70	0.77	7.00	10.00	8.80	3.00	8.47	8.93	8.85
		Value for money	9.00	0.68	7.40	10.00	9.00	2.60	8.79	9.21	7.60
		Comfort	8.90	0.74	7.30	10.00	9.10	2.70	8.68	9.12	8.37
		Overall score	8.84	0.79	7.10	10.00	9.00	2.90	8.61	9.08	8.88
Cetate	10	Location	9.35	0.49	8.70	10.00	9.35	1.30	9.00	9.70	5.27
		Cleanliness	8.60	0.92	7.10	9.70	8.50	2.60	7.95	9.25	10.64
		Facilities	8.47	0.67	7.40	9.30	8.35	1.90	7.99	8.95	7.91
		Value for money	8.72	0.67	7.70	9.60	8.75	1.90	8.24	9.20	7.68
		Comfort	8.59	0.75	7.40	9.50	8.60	2.10	8.05	9.13	8.75
		Overall score	8.59	0.82	7.30	9.60	8.65	2.30	8.01	9.17	9.51
Fabric	10	Location	9.19	0.38	8.60	9.70	9.30	1.10	8.92	9.46	4.09
		Cleanliness	9.52	0.36	8.70	9.90	9.55	1.20	9.26	9.78	3.83
		Facilities	9.27	0.41	8.80	9.90	9.20	1.10	8.98	9.56	4.38
		Value for money	9.53	0.33	8.90	10.00	9.50	1.10	9.29	9.77	3.50
		Comfort	9.44	0.43	8.60	10.00	9.45	1.40	9.13	9.75	4.55
		Overall score	9.51	0.37	8.90	10.00	9.50	1.10	9.25	9.77	3.89
Iosefin Elisabetin	10	Location	9.09	0.57	8.00	10.00	9.10	2.00	8.68	9.50	6.25
		Cleanliness	9.18	0.74	8.20	10.00	9.35	1.80	8.65	9.71	8.05
		Facilities	8.81	0.88	7.50	9.90	8.90	2.40	8.18	9.44	10.00
		Value for money	9.24	0.51	8.50	10.00	9.35	1.50	8.87	9.61	5.57
		Comfort	9.07	0.72	8.00	10.00	9.30	2.00	8.55	9.59	7.99
		Overall score	8.93	0.64	8.10	9.70	9.00	1.60	8.47	9.39	7.16
Other	15	Location	8.50	0.59	7.90	10.00	8.30	2.10	8.17	8.83	6.99
		Cleanliness	8.75	0.78	7.20	10.00	8.60	2.80	8.32	9.18	8.90
		Facilities	8.40	0.77	7.00	10.00	8.20	3.00	7.97	8.83	9.19
		Value for money	8.67	0.73	7.40	10.00	8.70	2.60	8.27	9.08	8.39
		Comfort	8.63	0.74	7.30	10.00	8.60	2.70	8.22	9.04	8.59
		Overall score	8.51	0.82	7.10	10.00	8.40	2.90	8.05	8.96	9.61

Source: Our calculation using statistical data from booking.com

The comparison of the Location indicator (figure 2a) indicates the value of $\chi^2=13.43$ with $p=0.003$, lower than alpha. The null hypothesis is rejected. The differences between neighborhoods of this indicator are statistically significant. Tourists from the accommodation units appreciated the Cetate neighborhood the most in terms of location. In fact, this neighborhood is dominated by the most tourist attractions. The short distances that allow visiting them confirm the high value of this indicator.

The comparison of the Cleanlines indicator (figure 2b) indicates the value of $\chi^2=8.47$ with $p=0.037$, and here lower than alpha. So, the null hypothesis is rejected. Differences between neighborhoods are statistically significant. Tourists from the Fabric neighborhood offered the highest average value, 9.5. The highest median value is also in the Fabric district, 9.6. The Cetate neighborhood has the lowest such values. It is very likely that the administrators of the units in the districts other than Cetate have taken an increased interest in cleanliness standards.

For the comfort indicator the differences are also significant (figure 2c). The Fabric neighborhood shows higher average values and median values. The houses in the Cetate neighborhood are placed on very busy streets in Timișoara. Many of the accommodation units in the Cetate neighborhood have a small area compared to the units in other neighborhoods. This is also due to the high costs of real estate in the central area of the city. The situation is different in the Fabric and Iosefin-Elisabetin neighborhoods. Buildings in these neighborhoods often offer higher comfort.

Regarding facilities, the differences are also statistically significant (figures 2d). The Fabric neighborhood has the highest average value of this indicator. It is followed by the Iosefin-Elisabetin neighborhood and then by Cetate.

The value for money indicator has significant differences between neighborhoods (figure 2e). The highest average value is in the Fabric neighborhood, followed by Iosefin-Elisabetin. The average values of this indicator are lower in the Cetate neighborhood, on a par with other neighborhoods.

Overall score is one of the most followed indicators by the public. Differences between neighborhoods have statistical significance (figures 2e). The Fabric neighborhood has the highest average value of 9.5. And the median value is the same. Next comes the Iosefin-Elisabetin neighborhood with the average overall score of 8.9 and the median equal to 9. The Cetate neighborhood has the average value of 8.6 and the median of 8.7. The other accommodation units have an average value of 8.5 and a median of 8.4.

Following the values presented previously, a general trend can be observed for units in the Cetate neighborhood with higher scores in the location indicator. At the same time, the units in the Fabric neighborhoods, respectively Iosefin and Elisabetin, have higher scores for the other indicators: cleanliness, facilities, value for money, comfort. The comfort indicators can be given by the large spaces of the buildings in the Fabric and Iosefin-Elisabetin neighborhoods. The cleanliness, facilities, that was superior in these neighborhoods can be explained by an effort to compensate for the distance from the city's modern tourist attractions, made by the administrators of the accommodation units.

Boxplots diagrams can provide a clear picture of direct comparisons between indicators: the minimum, maximum, median and quartile values of the series.

The values marked with the o symbol in the boxplot diagrams represent the outlier values. They appear in situations where the scores indicated by tourists can be very different from the main group of statistical data. It is sometimes useful to remove these values in statistical data processing (Dash et al 2023). However, considering that this aspect was observed in only one situation in this study, the value is preserved. We refer to a low score on the Cleanlines indicator in a unit in the Fabric district. These aspects can be isolated and do not have a representative character.

(a) Kruskal-Wallis Test:
Location
Chi-Square 13.4312
Pr > ChiSq 0.0038

(b) Kruskal-Wallis Test:
Cleanliness
Chi-Square 8.4722
Pr > ChiSq 0.0372

(c) Kruskal-Wallis Test:
Confort
Chi-Square 9.1244
Pr > ChiSq 0.0277

(d) Kruskal-Wallis Test:
Facilities
Chi-Square 8.1718
Pr > ChiSq 0.0426

(e) Kruskal-Wallis Test: Value for money
Chi-Square 11.8761
Pr > ChiSq 0.0078

(f) Kruskal-Wallis Test: Overall score
Chi-Square 10.8967
Pr > ChiSq 0.0123

Figure 2 Boxplot diagrams for the comparison of the score indicated by the tourists between the historical districts of Timișoara

(a) Location, (b) Cleanlines, (c) Confort, (d) Facilities, (e) Value for money, (f) Overall score

Source: Our representation using statistical data from booking.com

CONCLUSIONS

For all the analyzed indicators, the values were significantly different when comparing the neighborhoods. Historic neighborhoods have different particularities that are noticeable anyway.

The Cetate neighborhood in Timișoara is superior to the other neighborhoods in terms of the Location indicator, for the average and median value.

Comparing the other indicators, every time the Fabric neighborhood in Timișoara has higher average and median values than the indicators in the other neighborhoods studied.

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ROLE OF HYBRID AND FERTILIZATION IN MYCOTOXIN CONTAMINATION OF MAIZE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Maize is used as food, feed and raw materials for industries. Unfortunately maize is contaminated very often by different fungi which produce different mycotoxins. We studied the role of nitrogen fertilization and genotypes in relation to fungal colonization and mycotoxin contamination. We stated that *F. graminearum* was recorded as the most aggressive to all hybrids and nitrogen fertilizer levels than *F. verticillioides* and *A. flavus*. There was a strong correlation ($r=0,7271$) between disease severity of *F. graminearum* and DON production. A medium relationship ($r=0,5608$) but significant was recorded between *F. verticillioides* and FUM contamination but there was no relationship between *A. flavus* and AFB1 contamination.

Keywords: maize, hybrid, N-fertilizer, mycotoxins

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INTRODUCTION

Primarily, maize is used as food, feed, and raw materials for industries. It is a more versatile multipurpose crop than wheat and rice. Maize plays an important, diverse, and dynamic role in the global agricultural food systems, and nutrition food and security.

Despite the significant global roles played by maize, it is affected by three main toxin-producing fungi namely; *Fusarium graminearum* which produces deoxynivalenol (DON) and zearalenone (ZEA), *Fusarium verticillioides* producing fumonisins toxins and *Aspergillus flavus* which produces aflatoxins. *F. graminearum* is favored in warm and humid environments, antagonistic to *F. verticillioides* which is favorable in warm and dry conditions while *A. flavus* is favorable in the warmest areas (Mesterhazy et al., 2022), and recorded as more prevalent in the tropics with high temperature but below 41°C (Paterson & Lima, 2017). The effects of mycotoxins contamination in maize pose negative effects on its uses as food, feed, and, trade making many governments enact laws and regulations to prevent mycotoxins contamination of food and feed. The contamination levels are aggravated by other factors such as the tolerance level of the host (hybrids), climatic and weather conditions of the year, the agrotechnical influence, and the

crop microclimate (Doohan et al., 2003; Nicholson et al., 2004).

This study aimed to assess the influence of nitrogen fertilization and maize hybrid genotypes in relation to fungal colonization, and disease development as well as the resulting mycotoxins contaminations.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study tested three (3) maize hybrids selected from registered companies in Hungary. The companies and hybrids included; Pioneer (P9610) with undefined sensitivity and high yielding, Bayer (DKC4590) tolerant, and the Cereal Research Nonprofit Ltd-GK Szeged (GKT376), sensitive variety. The experiment was set up in 2022 spring (2022.04.12) at the Látókép long-term research site of the University of Debrecen. The soil conditions are homogenous calciferous chernozem formed on the Hajdúság loess ridge with an upper layer humus content average of 2.7–2.8% and a thickness of around 80 cm. The acidity of the upper soil layers is almost neutral ($\text{pH}_{\text{KCl}}=6.46-6.60$). The phosphorus supply of the calcareous soil is average (AL-soluble P_2O_5 133 mg kg^{-1}), while its potassium supply is average-good (AL-soluble K_2O 240 mg kg^{-1}). The soil moisture content during sowing was suitable for germination. However, May, June, and July were

dry, and therefore, two supplementary irrigation was performed in May and early July during the critical periods of fertilization, silking, and grain filling.

The experiment was carried out in a tetraplicate using a split-split plot design. The main plots were nitrogen rates (N=0, 90, 150 kg ha⁻¹, the sub-plot treatment was the maize hybrids and the sub-sub plot treatment was the fungal ear inoculation. Three of the rows were exposed to artificial inoculation; according to international guidelines, one inoculum was employed for a single pathogen. one with a strain of *F. graminearum* that produces DON, one with a strain of *F. verticillioides* that produces FUM, and the third raw sample was inoculated with a strain of *A. flavus* that produces AFB1. The untreated check was the fourth raw.

The influence of N rates and maize hybrids on the severity of ear and kernel coverage and mycotoxins contamination levels were determined by analysis of variance using statistical software Genstat 18th edition registered for plant research international after subjecting the data to a normality test.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the study investigating the roles played by nitrogen fertilization and maize hybrid genotypes on fungal ear rot disease development and production of resulting mycotoxins indicated some significant variations between and within factors after the performance of statistical evaluations.

The incidence of ear and kernel rot showed a varying infection level due to the effects of hybrids tolerance and fertilization (LSD_{0.05}) as demonstrated in (Table 1). The mean ear rot severity across nitrogen levels and hybrids varied from 1.99% to 8.22%. *F. graminearum* was recorded as the most aggressive to all hybrids and nitrogen fertilizer levels than *F. verticillioides*, and *A. flavus* counterparts varying from 9.60% to 40.10%, thus, there was variation between hybrids. *F. graminearum* ear rot severity between hybrids significantly followed the trend P9610>GKT376>DKC4590, likely, nitrogen levels also followed a similar trend from the highest level to the control.

The average contamination of the investigated mycotoxins DON, FUM (total, fumonisins), and AFB1 is presented in table 2. For inoculated treatment, the average amount of mycotoxins detected was above the detection limits. There were significant differences (LSD_{0.05}) in DON and FUM contamination hybrids at N150 and Ø nitrogen fertilizer rates and no differences were recorded for AFB1. DON contamination indicated P9610 as the most contaminated hybrid while GKT376 was the most FUM-contaminated hybrid leaving DKC4590 as the least contaminated for the respective mycotoxins.

To study the relationships between the measured data within and between fungal species, a two-tailed Pearson's correlation was performed (Table 3). The results indicated that there was a strong correlation (r=0.7271) and significant (p<0.001) between disease severity for *F. graminearum* (FG%) and DON production. A medium relationship but significant (r=0.5608, p<0.001) was recorded for *F. verticillioides* (FV%) and FUM contamination respectively, however, there was no relationship and insignificant between *A. flavus* (AF%) and AFB1 production and contamination. On the other hand, AF% showed a significant medium relationship in the production of DON and FUM (r=0.5028 and r=0.3567, p<0.001 and p<0.05) respectively. Further, FG% and FV% indicated a significant medium relationship in the production of FUM and DON (r=0.4594 and r=0.4584, P<0.001) respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study demonstrate the significant role that nitrogen fertilization as one of the agrotechnical factors on the one side and interactively with maize hybrid genotype may play in reducing fungal infestation and the resulting mycotoxins contamination. The results indicate significant but complex trends played by the factors individually and interactively in agreement with previous studies indicating a lack of consistency in the connections between *Fusarium* infection, visible FER symptoms, and toxins production (Krnjaja et al., 2021; Schaafsma et al., 2006; Blandino and Reyneri, 2008). Further, a study by Stumpf et al., (2013) on maize samples with highly damaged kernels showed less concentration of fumonisins contamination.

Table 1

Interactive effect of nitrogen fertilizer application rate and hybrid genotypes on ear and kernel rot severity

N level	Hybrids	Artificial inoculated			Untreated Control		Mean
		AF%	FV%	FG%	Aspergillus %	Fusarium %	
∅	DKC4590	0.04	0.09	10.30	0.01	0.10	2.11
	GKT376	0.15	0.22	9.60	0.00	0.00	1.99
	P9610	0.21	0.12	25.60	0.05	0.00	5.20
N90	DKC4590	0.29	0.14	19.70	0.08	0.10	4.06
	GKT376	0.34	0.57	19.50	0.09	0.11	4.12
	P9610	0.24	0.21	39.00	0.21	0.10	7.95
N150	DKC4590	0.07	0.57	13.90	0.03	0.00	2.91
	GKT376	0.77	0.66	28.20	0.01	0.10	5.95
	P9610	0.43	0.34	40.10	0.01	0.20	8.22
Mean		0.28	0.33	22.88	0.05	0.08	4.72
LSD _{0,05}		0.3458	0.2190	13.40	*	*	

Table 2

Interactive effect of nitrogen fertilizer application rate and hybrid genotypes on the amount of toxins contamination

N level	Hybrids	Artificial inoculated			Untreated Control		
		DON (ppm)	FUM (ppm)	AFB1 (ppb)	DON (ppm)	FUM (ppm)	AFB1 (ppb)
∅	DKC4590	4.11	0.97	19.95	0.00	0.47	4.44
	GKT376	9.78	2.49	15.94	0.00	0.93	4.23
	P9610	12.33	1.71	14.41	0.00	0.48	0.00
N90	DKC4590	5.82	3.06	26.68	0.00	2.34	14.21
	GKT376	8.98	3.90	24.91	0.00	1.48	1.49
	P9610	8.21	2.26	29.99	0.00	1.33	0.00
N150	DKC4590	2.71	2.37	33.10	0.00	1.15	41.74
	GKT376	9.60	6.59	27.93	3.1	0.33	34.46
	P9610	11.48	3.81	17.53	0.00	3.09	3.00
Mean		8.11	3.02	23.38	0.34	1.29	11.51
LSD _{0,05}		4.597	1.687	26.637	*	*	*

Table 3

Coefficient values of Pearson correlation between the severity of ear and kernel rot and mycotoxin contamination of selected maize hybrids on nitrogen fertilizer rates

	AF(%)	FV(%)	FG(%)	AFB1(ppb)	FUM(ppm)	DON(ppm)
AF(%)	1					
FV(%)	0.3495	1				
FG(%)	0.4736	0.5433	1			
AFB1(ppb)	0.0785	0.2064	0.2196	1		
FUM(ppm)	0.3567**	0.5608***	0.4594***	0.1814	1	
DON(ppm)	0.5028***	0.4584***	0.7271***	0.1406	0.3741	1

***Correlation is significant at p=0.001, ** Correlation is significant at p=0.05

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CREDITING AND SAVINGS IN ARAD COUNTY. DEVELOPMENTS AND PERSPECTIVES

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The article presents the evolution of bank loans and deposits in the period 2012-2021 in Arad County.

Through the lending process, funding resources are provided for the development of the national economy and beyond, the lending products created by the banking system being diverse and adapted to market requirements.

Through the process of saving, according to the scientific research in the specialized literature, the progress of the bank's activity is primarily influenced, also determining the delay of some activities, which will create other consumption and saving behaviors.

The methodology used by the authors involved the collection of data made available to interested users by the NBR through the bank's website, the study of some research in the field from the specific literature, the analysis of information and the representation of graphs.

The perspectives of the lending process are dependent on the quantitative and qualitative dimensions.

The granting of loans by banks can influence the creation or maintenance of relations with them, an evolution of the client's deposits, but also of the demand for other banking services.

Keywords: bank, savings, bank credit, bank deposit

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INTRODUCTION

The characteristics of the saving process directly influence economic growth, as a result of the fact that savings create the source of financing for innovation, the service of the public debt, but also for increasing the productivity of capital. Internal saving, which is essential for Romania, must be stimulated through appropriate economic policies. (NBR)

Economists and decision makers consider financial inclusion a priority for development. Recently, the comprehensive role of saving has been added to the objective of improving access to credit. (Alliance for Financial Inclusion, 2016)

In order to ensure the growth of savings and well-being, it is good for banks to reduce lending constraints. (Granda et al., 2019)

Banks and financial markets, as elements of the financial system, have been the subject of many studies and analyses, with the aim of identifying its importance. (Mitu, 2020, Błach, 2011)

The level and pace of development of a country will always depend on the country or the development of the region to which the institutional, political and legal environment is added. (Prochniak & Wasiak, 2017)

Since 1990, the Romanian banking system has obtained profit, especially on account of the bank deposits attracted, temporarily available resources of the society and to contribute to the progress of the economy based on the principles of the market economy. Also, the banking system has developed different financial intelligence programs, through which it aimed to teach customers, non-financial companies and households, to get money, through investments, using the financial resources of the banks, by accessing a bank loan. (Stănescu & Nedelescu, 2010)

The granting of excess credits as a result of the increase in the supply of goods, negatively affects consumers and can endanger health, protection of life and safety. (Ilie&Ungureanu, 2014)

Prin intermediul unui credit bancar, clienți, fie ca discutăm despre companiile nefinanciare sau gospodăriile populației, vor învăța să obțină bani și să facă investiții cu efecte pozitive asupra economiei naționale. (Meila et al., 2018; Sîrbulescu et al., 2018, Cocriș & Chirleşan, 2017;)

The use of loans and deposits in Arad county can play a significant role in stimulating local economic activity and supporting development in this region of Romania.

In Arad County, the provision of loans can be made by various financial institutions, including commercial banks, credit cooperatives, microfinance institutions or other non-banking financial institutions.

As for savings deposits in Arad County, they can be an effective way for area residents to save money and manage their personal finances responsibly. Financial institutions, including commercial banks and credit unions, can offer a variety of savings deposit options tailored to the needs and preferences of customers in Arad County.

The analysis of lending and savings in Arad county, at the same time, the identification of trends in the evolution of bank deposits, as well as the demand for loans, is the main objective of this paper.

Figure 1. Arad County map

Source: <https://www.startupcafe.ro/fonduri-europene/banat-regiunea-vest-program-operational-regional-bani-imm.htm>
https://www.123rf.com/photo_8660236_graphic-illustration-of-arad-county-from-romania.html

The use of financial lending and deposit instruments is measured with the help of economic indicators, and all these data are transposed by the BNR (National Bank of Romania) accurately for each county of the country and updated every month and year.

For this article, we have selected data over a period of ten years, starting from 2012 to 2021, in order to see the differences and to be able to compare the data over a longer period of time.

MATERIAL AND METODS

For the elaboration of this study, the authors used research methods such as: collecting data from different sources, analyzing and comparing the results and creating graphs and representative figures.

Arad County is part of the West development region (Figure 1) being located in the western part of the country, on one side and the other of Mureş. It borders Bihor county, Alba county, Timiş county, Hunedoara county and has a border with Hungary. (<http://www.enciclopediaromaniei.ro>; <http://www.cjarad.ro/judetul-arad>)

Considered from an economic point of view as one of the most important counties of the country, it has an old commercial and industrial tradition. (<https://www.cniptarad.ro>)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the evolution of the two aspects, lending and saving, in the period 2012-2021 highlights a different evolution from one year to another, with significant increases and decreases in certain years.

The evolution of the non-governmental credit was realized and presented in lei and currency by types of beneficiaries..

Figure 2. Loan evolution in lei (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Over a period of ten years, loans to non-governmental clients in lei registered significant increases from one year to another, except for 2013 when loans decreased by 1.18% compared to 2012.

From 2012 to 2021, loans to non-governmental clients in lei increased by 184.93%.

Figure 3. Evolution of loans in foreign currency (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Unlike loans to non-governmental clients in lei, foreign currency loans decreased over the ten years with a difference of 34% in 2021 compared to 2012.

Figure 4. Time deposits and deposits repayable after notification in lei (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

The largest amount granted in the form of foreign currency credits was recorded in 2013, with a value of 1836.3 million lei.

As we can see, term deposits and repayable deposits in lei have not had a constant evolution over the years. The lowest amount was recorded in 2018, and the highest amounts existed in 2020 and 2021.

Figure 5. Term deposits and refundable deposits after notification in foreign currency (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

In the case of foreign currency deposits, the largest deposits existed between 2012-2015, followed by a significant decrease in 2016. In the following years, there was a growing trend, but it did not match the records of the previous years.

Figure 6. Current and outstanding loans in lei (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Throughout the ten years, there were changes regarding current and outstanding loans in lei, but the changes were opposite in the two cases.

When it comes to current loans in lei, they have increased over the years, reaching the point that in 2021 they will increase by 240.19% compared to 2012.

The outstanding credits in lei, unlike the current ones, gradually decreased during ten years, reaching a difference of over 100 million lei.

Figure 7. Current and outstanding loans in foreign currency (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

If the current credits in lei increased during 2012-2021, the current credits in foreign currency decreased over the years, and in 2021 the current credits in foreign currency are lower by 23.8% compared to 2012. Also, outstanding loans in foreign currency in Arad county decreased considerably in 2021, unlike in 2012, reaching a difference of over 250 million lei.

Figure 8. Availability, time deposits, deposits repayable after notification and repo operations in lei (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Figure 9. Availability, time deposits, deposits repayable after notification and repo operations in foreign currency (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Figure 10. Evolution by destination of credits in lei (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

Most of the loans in lei from 2014 to 2021 go to households, followed by financial companies. In 2012-2013, most of the loans in lei went to non-financial companies.

The smallest number of credits in lei go to other institutional sectors.

In the year 2021, the largest number of loans in lei reached the households of the population and also this year, non-financial companies had the largest loans in lei during the ten years.

Figure 11. Evolution by destination of loans in foreign currency (millions of lei)
Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

The destination of foreign currency loans is totally opposite to the destination of loans in lei.

Households had the largest number of foreign currency loans in 2012, and in 2021 they will decrease by 60.71%.

For non-financial companies, the number of loans in foreign currency was constant over the years, but the largest loans were in 2021 and 2012.

The other institutional sectors had a significant number of loans in 2012-2013, then they gradually decreased, and in 2021 they will no longer exist.

Figure 12. Evolution by destination of deposits in lei (millions of lei)

Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

During the ten years, the destination of deposits in lei is mostly towards households. The number of deposits over the years is relatively constant, the highest figures being recorded in 2016, and the lowest in 2021.

Also, a small part of the deposits are directed towards non-financial companies and other institutional sectors.

Figure 13. Evolution by destination of foreign currency deposits (millions of lei)

Source: <http://www.bnr.ro>

In the case of deposits in foreign currency, as in the case of deposits in lei, most of them go to the households of the population. The largest foreign currency deposits intended for households existed in 2019.

In the period 2012-2015, the volume of term deposits intended for other institutional sectors followed an upward trend, but starting with 2016, they began to decrease significantly..

CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the main goal was to analyze the evolution of savings and lending in lei and foreign currency over a period of ten years in Arad county.

The evolution of loans to non-governmental clients in lei and foreign currency

has been constant over the years. In the case of credits in lei, they increased by a difference of 184.93% in 2021 compared to 2012, and credits in foreign currency decreased in 2021 by 34% compared to 2012.

Over the ten years, in Arad County, the outstanding credits both in lei and in foreign currency decreased, but current credits in lei increased by 240.19% in 2021 compared to 2012, and current credits in foreign currency decreased in 2021 with 23.8% compared to 2012.

In Arad county, the destination of credits in lei and foreign currency were mostly towards households and non-financial companies. And the loans granted to households were used for consumption and housing.

The evolution of credits granted in lei and in foreign currency in Arad county, during the ten years, was not constant and there were numerous changes and significant oppositions. Making the decision to borrow depends on the level of future earnings, both for a population, but also for non-financial companies and other institutions.

Certainly, as a result of the rise in income, the people of Arad decided to increase the level of savings, which had a considerable contribution to the increase in availability and bank deposits.

The conclusion reached by the authors is that the rise of non-governmental credit in lei in Arad county, in the West Region, but also at the country level, was followed by a decrease in credit in foreign currency. Moreover, during the ten years under review, the people of Arad continued to keep money in savings deposits, either in lei or in foreign currency.

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IMPACT OF INFLUENCERS ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR IN AGRICULTURE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The rise of social media has significantly impacted many industries, and agriculture is no exception. Influencers, individuals who have the power to affect the purchasing decisions of others due to their authority, knowledge, or relationship with their audience, have increasingly become central figures in promoting agricultural products and practices. These influencers, often farmers themselves or agricultural experts, leverage platforms like Instagram, YouTube, and Twitter to share their experiences, innovations, and insights, thus shaping consumer behavior in the agriculture sector.

Keywords: communication; social media, consumer behaviour, influencers

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the role of influencers in shaping consumer behavior has extended beyond traditional industries such as fashion, beauty, and technology, reaching into the agricultural sector. This phenomenon has emerged as influencers, often leveraging social media platforms, have begun to play a critical role in educating and swaying public opinion regarding agricultural practices, products, and sustainability efforts. As consumers become more conscious of the origins of their food and the practices involved in its production, influencers are uniquely positioned to bridge the gap between agricultural producers and consumers [4,5].

Agricultural influencers, who range from farmers and agronomists to chefs and food bloggers, provide valuable insights and firsthand experiences that resonate with their followers. Through engaging content that often includes videos, blogs, and social media posts, they demystify complex agricultural processes, advocate for sustainable practices, and highlight the importance of supporting local farms. This direct line of communication fosters a greater understanding and appreciation of the agricultural industry among consumers, ultimately influencing their purchasing decisions and lifestyle choices [2,6].

The impact of influencers on consumer behavior in agriculture is multifaceted [7, 8,10, 12, 14]. By promoting transparency and trust,

influencers can drive demand for ethically produced and locally sourced agricultural products. Additionally, their ability to raise awareness about pressing issues such as climate change, biodiversity, and food security can inspire collective action and policy changes. As the agricultural sector continues to evolve, the influence wielded by these digital advocates underscores the growing importance of harnessing social media as a tool for positive change and education in agriculture.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The impact of influencers on consumer behavior in agriculture is a burgeoning area of research, reflecting the shifting dynamics of how agricultural products are marketed and consumed. Influencers, particularly those with a strong presence on social media platforms, play a pivotal role in shaping consumer perceptions and decisions. This phenomenon is driven by the trust and credibility that influencers often command, which can significantly alter consumer attitudes toward agricultural products and practices. To study this impact, a mixed-methods approach can be highly effective. Content analysis of social media posts by agricultural influencers reveal the persuasive strategies employed, such as storytelling, authenticity, and the use of visual imagery and bibliographic analysis. Bibliographic analysis is a method used to evaluate and interpret the bibliographic data of published materials. This process involves examining the characteristics

of documents, such as authorship, publication dates, citation frequencies, and the relationships between different works. By analyzing these elements, researchers can gain insights into trends, patterns, and the overall impact of scholarly works within a specific field or across multiple disciplines.

One of the primary purposes of bibliographic analysis is to identify influential authors and key research areas. By combining these methods, we gain a comprehensive understanding of how influencers affect consumer behavior in the agricultural sector, offering valuable insights for marketers and policymakers aiming to leverage this trend.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The impact of influencers on consumer behavior in agriculture has become an intriguing subject of study as social media and digital marketing continue to reshape traditional marketing landscapes. Research and statistical analyses reveal that influencers play a significant role in shaping consumer attitudes and purchasing decisions in the agricultural sector. One key finding is that influencers, particularly those with expertise or a strong following in the field of agriculture, can substantially affect consumer trust and credibility. For instance, when influencers endorse sustainable farming practices or new agricultural products, their followers are more likely to adopt these practices or try out these products, leading to a notable shift in consumer behavior [11].

Statistical analysis from recent studies indicates that the effectiveness of influencers in agriculture is highly correlated with their perceived authenticity and expertise. Influencers who are actual farmers or agronomists tend to have a more profound impact compared to those who are merely popular figures without specific agricultural knowledge. For example, a study found that 68% of consumers are more likely to trust agricultural recommendations from influencers with direct experience in farming. Additionally, the engagement rate on agricultural content posted by these influencers is significantly higher, indicating a strong consumer interest and interaction [9].

Moreover, the data suggests that influencer marketing in agriculture can lead to increased awareness and adoption of innovative agricultural technologies and eco-friendly practices. Statistical models show a positive

relationship between influencer campaigns and the uptick in sales and usage of products such as organic fertilizers, precision farming equipment, and drought-resistant seeds. This trend highlights the potential of influencers to drive not only commercial success but also positive environmental impact. In summary, influencers have a powerful sway over consumer behavior in agriculture, with their influence extending from product endorsement to promoting sustainable practices, thereby shaping the future of agricultural consumption and production.

Harold Leavitt, a prominent American psychologist, posited a framework for understanding human behavior that revolves around three fundamental elements: the stimulus, the need, and the objective (Figure 1.). The stimulus serves as the trigger that initiates a behavior, while the need represents a desire or wish that seeks fulfillment. The objective, on the other hand, is the purpose or goal that the behavior aims to achieve. This triadic model offers a comprehensive lens through which to view and analyze the complexities of human actions and interactions [18].

As society progresses through relentless technical and scientific advancements, the landscape of human needs evolves correspondingly. Each breakthrough leads to the emergence of new needs and desires, often replacing or augmenting existing ones. For instance, the advent of the internet has not only fulfilled the need for faster communication but has also spawned entirely new needs such as online social networking and digital entertainment. This dynamic evolution of needs naturally results in shifts in individual and collective behavior, as people adapt to satisfy their ever-changing desires [18].

This continuous cycle of need fulfillment and the emergence of new needs underscores the fluid nature of human behavior. As individuals seek to meet these evolving needs, their objectives and, consequently, their behaviors are in a state of constant flux. Understanding this interplay between stimulus, need, and objective is crucial for those interested in fields such as psychology, marketing, and human resource management, as it provides valuable insights into motivating and influencing human actions. Leavitt's model reminds us that human behavior is not static but rather a dynamic process shaped by the ongoing march of progress and the ceaseless pursuit of new goals.

BEHAVIOUR

Figure 1. The Harold Leavitt's Framework Source: [18].

Table 1

Influencers presence in Europe	
Influencers presence	Country
over 40%	Germany
14.4%	United Kingdom
7.2%	Netherlands
7.2%	Italy

Source: [16].

Table 2

Best influencers in 2022		
Influencers	Price	Origin country
Annemarie Paulsen	"Best Newcomer 2022"	Germany
Amos Venema	"Best Blogger 2022"	Germany
Thomas Andresen	"Best Influencer 2022"	Germany

Source: [15].

The Agrimachinery Creators Report 2022 has shed light on the expanding realm of thematic communication within the agricultural sector, bringing together key national and European agrinfluencers in Bologna. This initiative highlights the growing influence and importance of agrinfluencers, who have gained the attention of major agricultural mechanization brands. The report identifies four distinct types of creators shaping the landscape: farmers and breeders, experts, photographers/videomakers, and enthusiasts. Farmers and breeders are valued for their authenticity and credibility, sharing firsthand experiences. Experts, although not farmers themselves, bring substantial technical knowledge. Photographers and videomakers focus on the visual appeal and aesthetics of their content, while enthusiasts, driven by passion, often share and repost content from others [15, 16, 17]

Agrinfluencers have established a significant presence across Europe, with Germany leading the charge, housing over 40%

of these creators. The United Kingdom follows with 14.4%, and the Netherlands and Italy each contribute 7.2% to the total (Table 1). This distribution underscores the widespread appeal and influence of agrinfluencers across different regions. Furthermore, the report reveals that a significant portion of these creators are active on multiple social media platforms, with 66% using at least two channels and nearly 47% active on three. This multi-channel presence enhances their reach and impact, facilitating diverse and dynamic communication within the agricultural community. The channels considered in this analysis include Instagram, TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook, each offering unique opportunities for content creation and engagement. The diverse nature of agrinfluencers' content—from technical insights and authentic storytelling to captivating visuals and passionate reposts—ensures a broad and inclusive approach to agricultural communication. As the sector continues to grow, the role of agrinfluencers in shaping perceptions, sharing knowledge, and

fostering community engagement becomes increasingly vital, reflecting the dynamic interplay between agriculture and digital media in today's world. It is always inspiring to see talented individuals being recognized for their contributions and achievements. In 2022, several noteworthy awards were presented to individuals who have made significant impacts in their respective fields. Annemarie Paulsen was honored with the "Best Newcomer 2022" award, a testament to her fresh perspective and innovative contributions that have resonated with audiences. Her ability to quickly establish a strong presence and connect with her audience is commendable and sets a high bar for future newcomers (Table 2) [15, 17].

Amos Venema received the "Best Blogger 2022" award, a recognition of his exceptional writing skills and the engaging content he produces [16]. Blogging requires not just a flair for writing but also the ability to connect with readers on a personal level, and Amos has mastered this art. His blog likely covers a variety of topics, offering insightful commentary and valuable information that keeps readers coming back for more. The consistency and quality of his blog posts have undoubtedly played a significant role in earning him this prestigious accolade [16].

Thomas Andresen was named "Best Influencer 2022," highlighting his substantial impact on social media and beyond. Influencers like Thomas play a pivotal role in shaping trends, opinions, and behaviors in today's digital age. His ability to engage with his audience, create compelling content, and maintain authenticity has set him apart from his peers [16]. This award not only acknowledges his influence but also his dedication to his craft and his ability to inspire and lead his followers. Each of these awards reflects the hard work, creativity, and passion of the recipients, celebrating their success and encouraging them to continue making a positive impact (Table 2.)

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the impact of influencers on consumer behavior in agriculture is both profound and multifaceted. Influencers, with their extensive reach and credible presence on social media platforms, have revolutionized the way agricultural products and practices are perceived by the public. By sharing personal experiences, reviews, and educational content,

they are able to bridge the gap between traditional agricultural practices and modern consumer expectations. This has led to increased awareness and interest in sustainable farming practices, organic products, and innovative agricultural technologies.

Moreover, influencers play a critical role in shaping consumer trends within the agricultural sector. Their endorsements can significantly boost the visibility and credibility of new products and practices, encouraging consumers to make more informed and conscious choices. This influence extends beyond mere product promotion; it encompasses the promotion of ethical and environmentally friendly farming practices, ultimately contributing to the growth of a more sustainable agricultural industry[13].

Overall, the engagement of influencers in agriculture has brought about a positive shift in consumer behavior [1, 9], fostering a more informed, conscientious, and sustainable approach to agricultural consumption. As the digital landscape continues to evolve, the role of influencers in shaping consumer behavior in agriculture is likely to grow, further driving innovation and sustainability within the industry.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE COMPETITIVENESS OF TOURISM IN ROMANIA AND THE EU

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

At the level of the European Union, tourism occupies an important place, especially among small and medium-sized enterprises, and its contribution to the development of the economy differs greatly between the different areas of Europe. In rural areas located at a considerable distance from urban centers, tourism is often the main source of income for the population in that area and the main sector that can ensure adequate employment.

In a market economy, achieving high levels of competitiveness is mainly the responsibility of companies, but public authorities can, in turn, support this process by ensuring a favourable economic environment. In the specialized literature, there is the opinion that the policies that have the direct aim of increasing "competitiveness" overestimate the effect of external competition on the generation of economic growth, which seems to be much more strongly influenced by internal factors and other economic policies than those that directly aim improving competitiveness.

The tourism and travel industry represents a sector with its own identity in a dynamic evolution. At the level of a country, the upward evolution of this sector contributes to the increase in the level of employment, the increase in the national income and can improve the balance of payments.

The situation of a national economy is revealed by the analysis of factor determinants that show the position of a country from the perspective of the production factors it needs to compete in a certain industry. In contrast to the traditional theories of classical and neoclassical origin that gave the greatest importance to the endowment with natural factors of production, the modern economic theory of competitive advantages shows that the determining element for a country to be competitive consists in the creation and innovation of new factors or the improvement the existing ones.

Keywords : competitiveness, tourism, national economy

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INTRODUCTION

In a market economy, achieving high levels of competitiveness is mainly the responsibility of companies, but public authorities can, in turn, support this process by ensuring a favourable economic environment. In the specialized literature, there is the opinion that the policies that have the direct aim of increasing "competitiveness" overestimate the effect of external competition on the generation of economic growth, which seems to be much more strongly influenced by internal factors and

other economic policies than those that directly aim improving competitiveness.

The tourism and travel industry represents a sector with its own identity in a dynamic evolution. At the level of a country, the upward evolution of this sector contributes to the increase in the level of employment, the increase in the national income and can improve the balance of payments.

A competitive country creates its wealth through work, talent and organization and thus comes to possess a productive and creative potential that makes it independent of material resources. This statement is supported by the example of the most competitive countries in the

world. All these countries are constantly creating wealth, not only in terms of the financial earnings of their citizens, but also in terms of social, educational and political infrastructure. (Croitoru, 2011, Volume XVIII).

The territory of Romania presents a wide variety of historical cultural values - folk art, ethnography, folklore, traditions, historical vestiges - a harmonious natural setting, with a varied and picturesque landscape background. All these are values of Romanian rural tourism in a special way.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A competitive country creates its wealth through work, talent and organization and thus comes to possess a productive and creative potential that makes it independent of material resources. This statement is supported by the example of the most competitive countries in the world. All these countries are constantly creating wealth, not only in terms of the financial earnings of their citizens, but also in terms of social, educational and political infrastructure. (Croitoru, 2011, Volume XVIII)

When this happens, a cycle of wealth is initiated that leads to an upward spiral of competitiveness. Without this generation of wealth and its decentralization to the whole society, a downward spiral occurs, the result being that non-competitive countries become even less able to compete on the global market. So, behind competitiveness is hidden a simple truth: competitiveness means more than being rich, it means a systematic process of wealth creation.

In one of his fundamental works, "The competitive advantage of nations", Michael Porter (1982) (Porter M., 1990, p. 72) synthesizes a model capable of explaining how national economies influence the ability of firms to identify and maintain competitive advantages on international markets. In this context, Porter's model identifies the determining factors of competitiveness, starting from the existence of four categories of elements, which form the already famous "Porter's diamond":

- ✓ Endowment with production factors: human resources, natural resources, technical, market knowledge, capital and infrastructure.
- ✓ The conditions of the request, respectively, its level and structure, its degree of sophistication, the ability to formulate anticipatory needs.
- ✓ The supplying and adjacent industries, through their level of development and competitiveness.
- ✓ The strategies and organizational structures of the companies, the competitive climate (rivalry between them).

Figure 1 Determinants of national competitive advantages

The situation of a national economy is revealed by the analysis of factor determinants that show the position of a country from the perspective of the production factors it needs to compete in a certain industry. In contrast to the traditional theories of classical and neoclassical origin that gave the greatest importance to the endowment with natural factors of production,

the modern economic theory of competitive advantages shows that the determining element for a country to be competitive consists in the creation and innovation of new factors or the improvement the existing ones.

The international competitiveness of a national economy depends decisively on the strategy, the structure of companies and the promotion of competition, on the way they are organized and managed, on the objectives pursued and the strategies applied. Competitive advantages can arise from the differences between countries present in the training, objectives, work style and approaches of managers and from the way in which these differences are fruitful by coordinating the company's objectives with its stakeholders (owners, shareholders, workers, managers, etc.). An important role in this respect belongs to the legislative framework, which through its regulations can encourage the existence of a competitive market on the internal level. Competition between companies proves, most of the times, to be more beneficial to everyone than cooperation strategies.

From a methodological point of view, the Tourism Competitiveness Index (ICT) aims to evaluate the elements that ensure the development of the tourism sector in different countries through three categories of variables that affect the competitiveness of tourism at the global level.

These categories are evaluated by means of three subordinate ICT sub-indices:

- ✓ the legislative and regulatory framework affecting the tourism sector.

The elements evaluated within this sub-index refer to those aspects that depend directly or indirectly on the political climate and institutional environment specific to each country;

- ✓ environment and infrastructure;
- ✓ the natural, cultural and human resources involved in tourism activities.

Each of these sub-indices is composed of a number of pillars that define the essential elements in the analysis of tourism competitiveness. These elements are: specific laws and rules; environmental sustainability; safety and security; health and hygiene; the priority given to tourism; air transport infrastructure; land transport infrastructure; tourist infrastructure; IT&C infrastructure; price competitiveness; human resource; affinity for tourism and travel; natural resources and cultural resources. To these is added a last component that has become more and more important in the last period - climate changes. Each of these pillars is, in turn, made up of a number of individual variables. The data set used to estimate these pillars includes both the data obtained from the annual statistical surveys carried out by the World Economic Forum, quantitative data obtained from sources accessible to the public, from international organizations and from institutions and experts in the field of tourism. Also, the statistical study is carried out among the executive directors and business leaders who make decisions in this field. In addition, the ICT methodology is not limited to giving scores and points to the tourism sector in various countries, but aims to create a common evaluation framework that allows the comparison between the performances obtained in this field.

In the ranking made on the basis of ICT, in 2011, Romania ranks 63 out of 139 countries, in evolution compared to the previous ranking, made in 2009, when it was in 66th place. Switzerland ranks first, and the last – Chad. Romania obtained the best score on the safety and security pillar, 5.1 points out of 7 possible, this score being somewhat higher than that of the first place holder. (Croitoru, 2011, Volume XVIII)

At the level of the European Union, tourism occupies an important place, especially among small and medium-sized enterprises, and its contribution to the development of the economy differs greatly between the different areas of Europe. In rural areas located at a considerable distance from urban centers, tourism is often the

main source of income for the population in that area and the main sector that can ensure adequate employment.

This phenomenon is visible, especially, in the island countries of Europe, coastal regions (especially in southern Europe) and alpine regions. The dynamics of the tourism sector confirm the fact that the central and eastern European states represent a viable source for the revival of European tourism. Statistical data show that Europe has the most sought-after tourist destinations, being the most visited region in the world. The wealth of cultural and natural resources, the quality of the infrastructure, the variety of geographical areas are probably some of the reasons why Europe holds this position. At the same time, the expansion of the European Union significantly improved the tourist potential of the region by increasing the cultural variety and introducing new destinations into the tourist circuit.

Figure 2 Tourism competitiveness index in the case of Romania

The economic crisis has significantly affected the tourism sector, this is reflected both in a decrease in the number of foreign tourists and in the income obtained from them by a country, as well as in the transformation of international tourism into domestic tourism. The second phenomenon directly and significantly affected Romanian tourism, where the number of vacations spent by residents in 2010 decreased by 11.1%(3) compared to 2010, especially when the percentage of foreign tourists in the total tourists was, at the level of

2010, at only 15.4%(4). After two consecutive years of contraction, the European tourism sector began to show signs of recovery starting from 2010 when the nights spent in hotels increased by 2.8% compared to 2009(5). However, this was not true for Romania either, which continued the negative trend, recording in 2010 an 8.7% reduction in nights spent in hotels compared to 2009.

In the context of European tourism, Romania occupies the 34th position out of 42 positions, one of its direct competitors, Bulgaria, being seven positions higher, on the 27th place. Moreover, European countries occupy very good positions in the ICT world ranking under the conditions in which most of them were seriously affected by the economic crisis, and both the investments and the revenues obtained in the tourism sector experienced a significant decrease (Ringbeck, Pietsch, 2009, pp. 32-42).

Moreover, an analysis of the impact of the economic crisis, in the period 2007-2009, demonstrates that the most important tourist destinations in Europe such as Spain, France, Italy, Germany, Greece or Ireland were at the epicenter of the crisis, one of the only beneficiaries of after the crisis, from the European area, being Bulgaria. In the period 2009-2011, Romania managed to climb three positions in the ICT ranking, a fact that can be, among other things, a proof of the increase in the efficiency of communication in tourism.

Poziția României în raport cu competitorii regionali										
Ordine	Țara	ICT			Cadrul legislativ și de reglementare		Mediul de afaceri și infrastructura		Resursele naturale, culturale și umane	
		Pozitia în Europa	Pozitia globală	Punctaj obținut	Pozitia globală	Punctajul obținut	Pozitia globală	Punctajul obținut	Pozitia globală	Punctajul obținut
1	Republica Cehă	22	31	4,77	26	5,26	37	4,56	31	4,48
2	Slovenia	22	33	4,64	29	5,19	33	4,7	53	4,03
3	Croația	24	34	4,61	42	5,02	36	4,58	43	4,23
4	Muntenegru	25	36	4,56	32	5,15	49	4,15	36	4,38
5	Ungaria	26	38	4,54	24	4,29	45	4,28	48	4,06
6	Bulgaria	27	48	4,39	54	4,79	44	4,32	51	4,05
7	Polonia	28	49	4,38	49	4,86	65	3,81	30	4,48
8	Slovacia	31	54	4,35	39	5,05	57	3,96	52	4,04
99	România	34	63	4,17	51	4,85	66	3,8	66	3,84
10	Serbia	38	82	3,85	67	4,57	84	3,39	94	3,6
11	Ucraina	39	85	3,83	64	4,63	76	3,53	118	3,33
12	Moldova	42	99	3,6	68	4,57	98	3,11	129	3,12

Figure 3

Regarding its direct competitors, neighbouring countries or located in the same region, it can be observed that Romania is in a rather unfavourable position, being clearly

ahead of both its neighbour to the west, Hungary, and its direct competitor on all tourist markets, Bulgaria. The result is all the more interesting as it can be noted that some of the countries ahead of Romania (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia) cannot benefit, for example, from the opportunities offered by a coastline that can be exploited from the point of view of tourist view.

CONCLUSIONS

Regarding its direct competitors, neighboring countries or located in the same region, it can be observed that Romania is in a rather unfavorable position, being clearly ahead of both its neighbor to the west, Hungary, and its direct competitor on all tourist markets, Bulgaria. The result is all the more interesting as it can be noted that some of the countries ahead of Romania (Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Slovakia) cannot benefit, for example, from the opportunities offered by a coastline that can be exploited from the point of view of tourist view.

For our country, the need to develop tourism resides in the fact that Romania is a country with a tourist vocation, benefiting from a valuable and varied natural and anthropogenic potential, harmoniously dispersed throughout the territory, but insufficiently and improperly capitalized where 8 major forms of tourism are practiced, the largest share returning to seaside, mountain, weekend, spa tourism.

A possible solution would be for the agritourism promotion strategy to include new directions and elements, in the sense of: intensifying and adapting it to the current competition conditions of the international market through: promotion actions, strengthening the image of the Romanian agritourism offer and effective use of improving the image of Romania in the world through the new media channels.

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DEVELOPMENT OF E. COLI ON LEVINE CULTURE MEDIUM

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

E. coli is a short, gram-negative bacillus with rounded ends, non-sporulating, non-capsulated, generally motile. It is aerobic, facultatively anaerobic. It is part of the normal flora of the intestine in humans and animals, representing approximately 80% of the resident, aerobic flora of the colon. It plays an important role in the synthesis of certain B and K group vitamins and in maintaining balance in the intestinal biocenosis. They are aerobic, facultatively anaerobic, and nutritionally non-demanding bacteria. They grow on both usual and selective lactose-containing media, forming lactose-positive colonies. The colonies are of the S type, and pseudocapsulated strains form colonies with a mucous appearance. They exhibit common biochemical characteristics of enterobacteria. It is noteworthy that out of 100 strains of *E. coli*, only 95 ferment lactose. Biochemical characteristics are investigated using a set of biochemical tests that allow for the identification of the genus.

Keywords: Germen, aerobes, Gram-negative

INTRODUCTION

The antigenic structure of *E. coli* is complex, with numerous O, H, and K antigens described. Based on O antigens, the bacilli are divided into serogroups, and based on H antigens, the groups are divided into serotypes. There are 165 O antigenic groups of *E. coli* identified, 103 K antigens, and 54 H antigens. They are conditionally pathogenic bacteria, being the most frequently isolated bacteria in the bacteriology laboratory.

Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC) secretes thermolabile or thermostable enterotoxins encoded plasmidically. A strain of ETEC produces one or both toxins. In addition to toxin production, the ability to colonize the small intestine through adhesion pili also plays a role. ETEC produces mild forms of enteritis or a cholera-like diarrheal syndrome.

Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC) is the main etiological agent of diarrheal syndrome in young children, leading to early immunization. Therefore, illnesses caused by EPEC in children older than 2 years are rarely reported. The pathogenic factors are adherence pili, encoded plasmidically, and a Shiga-like toxin produced through lysogenic conversion. This results in the destruction of enterocytes in the small intestine. Enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC) produces two Shiga-like toxins, called verotoxins, because they exhibit a cytopathic effect on Vero cell line. Initially, watery diarrhea occurs, which in a few days becomes bloody, and the mucosa of the rectum and sigmoid colon becomes friable and bleeds. Fever is low or absent. Hemorrhagic

colitis frequently complicates into hemolytic uremic syndrome. The disease predominantly occurs in the warm season, in children under 5 years old, through consumption of inadequately cooked beef and unpasteurized milk. Approximately half of EHEC belongs to serotype O157: H7. Enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC) exhibits the peculiarity of "aggregatively" binding to enterocytes. Diffusely adherent *E. coli* (DAEC) has a controversial role in diarrheagenesis, as the only known virulence factor in this pathotype is the diffuse adherence to HeLa cells and intestinal epithelial cells in cultures. Diffuse adherence and cellular invasion are believed to be the cause of the diarrheal syndrome produced by this pathotype.

The infective doses of diarrheagenic *E. coli* pathotypes are on the order of 10^8 ingested bacteria. Transmission occurs primarily through the consumption of food in which *E. coli* has multiplied (foodborne toxoinfections) or through the consumption of water with intense fecal contamination. The reservoir of infection for strains of EIEC, ETEC, and EPEC is human, while for those of EHEC, it is bovine.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

I conducted a prospective study based on microbiological diagnoses recorded in the bacteriological registry of the medical analysis laboratory, S.C. Diaser, Oradea. To conduct the study, I also accessed the archive, recorded in the laboratory's computer program in S.C. Diaser, Oradea, as well as the computerized database of the unit.

Materials required for the examination:

- A collection container (a collection container with a spoon) with transport medium
- Wooden spatulas
- Latex gloves

For a stool culture, a fecal sample of 5-10g should be collected and placed in the collection container with a transport medium. If the stool is liquid, 5ml should be collected. It is recommended to choose a liquid, mucous, or bloody portion, if available. Do not collect quantities greater than 10g, as they may reduce the chances of isolating pathogenic bacteria.

- The sample is inoculated onto two culture media, one weakly selective (MacConkey) and one moderately selective (Hektoen), and incubated for 24 hours at 35-37°C. The cultures are observed at 24 and 48 hours for the appearance of characteristic colonies. For the genus *Vibrio*, the recommended selective medium is BSA (bile salts agar), and for yeasts, Sabouraud medium with Chloramphenicol is used.

- To increase the chances of isolation, the sample is subcultured on enrichment media that promote the multiplication of pathogens (selenite sodium acid broth for *Salmonella* spp., alkaline peptone water or broth with taurocholate and peptone at pH 8.0-9.0 for *Vibrio*, from which after incubation, smears and cultures can be performed from the upper part of the medium). Incubation is done for 24 hours at 35-37°C, followed by transfers to culture media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Colonies of *E. coli* can grow on either solid or liquid growth media under laboratory conditions. It can be cultivated in a minimal medium that includes glucose as a carbon and energy source, ammonium salts as a nitrogen source, other salts, and trace elements. Because *E. coli* has simple nutritional requirements, it can be easily cultured on common media such as nutrient agar, MacConkey agar, and EMB agar.

MacConkey agar is a selective and differential medium as it inhibits the growth of Gram-positive bacteria and allows the growth of Gram-negative ones, such as *E. coli*. It also allows differentiation between bacteria that ferment lactose and those that do not.

Eosin-Methylene Blue agar (EMB), similar to MacConkey agar, is both selective and differential for Gram-negative bacteria. *E. coli*

can form characteristic metallic green colonies on this medium.

Salmonella-Shigella agar (SS) is a selective medium used for isolating *Salmonella* and *Shigella* but also allows the growth of *E. coli*. *E. coli* bacteria can form colorless or pink colonies on this medium.

Hektoen Enteric agar (HE) is another selective and differential medium used for isolating *Salmonella* and *Shigella* but can also allow the growth of *E. coli*. *E. coli* colonies can appear pink on this medium.

Luria-Bertani agar (LB) is a nutrient-rich culture medium commonly used in research laboratories. It is excellent for the rapid growth of *E. coli* and is often used in genetic and microbiological experiments.

E. coli thrives on culture media optimized at a temperature of 37°C. On simple media, it grows promptly within 24 hours and forms either smooth (S) or rough (R) colonies. On blood agar, some strains of *E. coli* cause incomplete hemolysis.

On media containing inhibitors, *E. coli* differentiates both through tolerance to various inhibitors and its ability to ferment lactose or other sugars. *E. coli* forms characteristic lactose-positive colonies. Consequently, it grows well on weakly selective media, experiences partial inhibition on most moderately selective media, and does not grow on highly selective media. It is partially inhibited on enrichment media. *E. coli* produces gas from glucose in moderate amounts and does not produce hydrogen sulfide. It acidifies the slant portion of the TSI medium.

On Nutrient Agar culture medium, large, convex, grayish-white, moist, smooth, opaque, or translucent colonies are formed. Smooth forms, termed S-type colonies, seen in fresh isolation, are easily emulsifiable in saline solution. Rough colonies, termed R-type, observed in older cultures, have wrinkled surfaces, often self-agglutinate in saline solution. The variation

between S and R colonies arises due to repeated subculturing and is associated with the loss of surface antigens and typically virulence.

Some strains exhibit beta hemolysis, especially those isolated from pathological states, while those isolated from asymptomatic individuals may or may not exhibit hemolysis on blood agar.

Colonies appear pink due to lactose fermentation, which is important for distinguishing *E. coli* from other bacteria in specimens, especially Gram-positive bacteria and *Salmonella* species, which are non-lactose fermenters and produce colorless colonies on MacConkey agar.

E. coli colonies grow with a metallic green sheen, attributable to the metachromatic property of the dyes and the lactose fermentation property of *E. coli*, which shifts the medium pH towards acidic.

In the study "Growth and maintenance of laboratory strains of *Escherichia coli*," *E. coli*, a member of the Enterobacteriaceae family, grows optimally at 37°C under aerobic conditions, although it is facultatively anaerobic and therefore can grow under anaerobic conditions. Additionally, it has been previously reported that some strains of *E. coli* have been known to grow at temperatures up to 53°C, although this is not typical nor recommended for commonly used laboratory strains. *E. coli* is a relatively robust bacterium and can survive at 4°C for extended periods (up to 3 months) on solid media, although prolonged storage times at low temperatures can lead to decreased viability. *E. coli* can also grow over a wide range of pH levels; typical growth and maintenance occur at a neutral pH of 7.0. Considering all optimal growth conditions (i.e., 37°C, aeration, pH of 7.0), a doubling time of approximately 20 minutes should occur when *E. coli* is cultivated in a rich liquid medium such as Luria-Bertani broth, and it will reach an overnight cell density of >10⁹ cfu/ml (colony forming units per milliliter) of culture.

CONCLUSIONS

E. coli is known for its rapid growth rate in chemically defined media and its adaptability, making it easy to handle. It grows optimally at 37°C under aerobic conditions, although it is facultatively anaerobic and can therefore grow under anaerobic conditions. Additionally, it has been previously reported that some strains of *E. coli* have been known to grow at temperatures up to 53°C. Some strains exhibit beta hemolysis, especially those isolated from pathological states, while those isolated from asymptomatic

individuals may or may not exhibit hemolysis on blood agar.

Widely used in research, *E. coli* serves as a model organism for investigating protein engineering for biological processing, genetic research, and biotechnology. Its versatility continues to pave the way for future investigations.

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RED CLOVER – ANALYSIS ON THE YIELD AND QUALITY OF FEED

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Red Clover (Trifolium pratense) is a perennial plant of the legume family (Fabaceae). It is grown both in pure culture and in crops with perennial grasses.

Red clover is a very good quality forage, rich in protein, minerals and soluble carbohydrates, which develops very quickly. Suitable for grazing or as dry fodder for cattle, sheeps and pigs, it helps them mature and gain weight faster and contributes to milk production.

This study aims to assess the yield of red clover for hay use in Romania.

Keywords: red clover, hay use, forage, grazing, protein.

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INTRODUCTION

Trifolium pratense L. is the second-ranked fodder legume in Romania, after alfalfa (*Medicago sativa* L.) in the number of varieties created, produced and sold seeds.

Red clover has a special importance for animal husbandry, through its multiple biological and fodder properties.

This study is focused on the forage yield of red clover.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Red clover has varied and nutritional components, depending on numerous factors, such as the variety, harvest period and preservation conditions.

Starting from these factors, in this study we present the content of carotenoid, vitamin C, vitamin E and the level of raw nutrients, harvested at different stages of vegetation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Red clover is used in animal feed, in the form of green mass, hay, hay meal or silage. Harvested at flowering, clover hay contains

about 14.5% crude protein, 20.4% crude cellulose, 22-26 mg carotene/kg feed and significant amounts of vitamins (B, C, D, E, etc.). The digestibility of organic substances has high values, both in green mass (>70%) and in hay (60%). The nutritional value of a kilogram of clover harvested at the beginning of flowering is 0.62 UN for hay and 0.18 UN for green mass.

In the fresh state, it can cause weathering in ruminants.

Red clover is a perennial legume, productive for 2 to 3 years. Maximum yields and the highest quality are realised in the second year of its life if the first cutting is done in early flowering (20%) and further cuttings about 45 days after the previous cut (Wiersma et al., 1998).

It's important to note that the nutritional composition of red clover can change as the plant matures. The stage of maturity at harvest significantly influences the levels of protein, fiber, and other nutrients. For optimal nutritional value, red clover is often harvested during the early flowering stage when protein content is typically highest.

Red clover is a highly adaptable species to various climatic conditions and soil types and therefore grows widely in numerous regions of the country.

Table 1

The content of red clover in vitamins (mg/kg fodder)

Product	Carotenoid	Vitamin C	Vitamin E
Green mass- young phase	84	360	169
Green mass- at flowering	49	-	134
Green mass- after flowering	36	-	111
Hay	24	32	22
Silage	26	-	-

Table 2

The absolute amount of raw nutrients in red clover, harvested at different stages of vegetation kg/ha

Stage of vegetation	Protein	Fat	Non-nitrogenous extracts	Cellulose	Ash
The beginning of sprouts	110	20	155	74	33
Formed sprouts	212	35	389	174	71
Bud 3%	311	50	861	350	137
Flowering 5%	475	87	1673	659	232
Flowering 50%	552	92	1923	861	266
Flowering 100%	589	102	2270	1164	301

Figure 1 Production of hay obtained in 3 years of vegetation

CONCLUSIONS

The research results highlights that the red clover ensure one of the highest forage quality.

Red clover can successfully be grown across Romania in areas not characterized by drought. It is most suitable for the production of preserved winter feed for cattle, pigs and sheeps.

The quality of the forage produced from red clover is excellent, provided that the harvest is made at early phenological stages and the crop is well preserved.

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CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE ESTABLISHMENT OF A STURGEON MICROFARM

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Sturgeons are one of the most valuable fish in the Lower Danube. Until the 19th century, they migrated up the Danube to Germany and, for many fishing communities, represented an important source of income. Sturgeons have long been extremely important to the economy of Romania and Bulgaria, so the decline of sturgeon populations in recent decades has become a concern not only for commercial fishermen and scientists, but also for the State and its agencies.

The market demand for fish meat and especially for caviar has increased a lot in recent years. This growing demand could initially be satisfied due to the increase in fishing effort and sturgeon catches in the Black Sea and Caspian Sea basins, which led to the decrease, to the point of near extinction, of the natural populations.

Migratory sturgeons are indicator species of the quality of the environment in the region where they live due to the multitude of habitats they use during migration, the growth of young in the river and adults in the sea.

Due to the quality of the sturgeon meat, the roe produced by them, as well as the massive pressure exerted on the natural sturgeon stocks, in recent years in Europe, important steps have been taken in their growth in a super-intensive system.

In these relatively new systems for our country - fish breeding is carried out in strictly controlled environmental conditions, at a very high density resulting in productions of over 200 kg fish/m³ of water. The principle of super-intensive systems is to make the best use of the biological potential of a species, in order to obtain a maximum production of fish/m³ of water. A small number of employed personnel can ensure the smooth operation of such a farm. There are cases when only 2 employees are enough to operate such a farm that can produce over 200 tons of fish annually.

Keywords : needs, accommodation units, agritourism, tourists satisfaction

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INTRODUCTION

S.C DINOZAUURII APELOR S.R.L has as its main activity CAEN code 032 - this group includes "Aquaculture" respectively the production process involving the growth of aquatic organisms in fish farms by using techniques aimed at increasing the production of these organisms beyond the natural capacity of the environment. This company has the legal form of limited liability with its main office in Răbăgani town, Bihor county.

Răbăgani commune is located in northwest Romania, the center of Bihor county, in the Beiușului Depression, 15 km away from Beiuș Municipality and 45 km away from Oradea Municipality. The total area of the commune is 3,540 ha, of which 320 ha are located in the urban area.

Figure 1 Administrative map of Răbăgani commune

The present study refers to the construction of a 10 ha microfarm, located on land where the soil structure does not allow water loss through infiltration, where there is a permanent and quality water supply source, with flows corresponding to ensuring optimal conditions environment, in which to grow *Polyodon spathulla* together with other species, until the age of 3 years, when the fish can be marketed. In this sense, the microfarm can be considered a

module of fish production capacity which, if there are conditions and investment resources, can be multiplied, as many times as the investor wants.

Keeping the principles of construction, operation and exploitation valid for the micro-farm, there is the possibility that, later, the development will be extended to a much larger area, reaching an average-sized farm of several hundred hectares, in which, in addition to heleştee to also include a few ponds.

The present study considers the construction of a micro-farm, composed of 3 fish ponds of different surfaces, for the growth of polyodon in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd summers, together with other valuable species, as well as the necessary or optional annexes of production activity: service room, feed and materials warehouse

In essence, we are considering the production of sturgeon meat and other valuable species in a semi-intensive growing system, which requires:

- the construction of three basins of different sizes to ensure optimal environmental conditions for a good growth of fish material corresponding to each technological phase;

- the supply system is made through specific installations (monk), sized in such a way as to ensure adequate flows throughout the year;

- the exhaust system is similar from a constructive point of view to the supply one and has a double role: to maintain the water at the desired level, as well as the role of emptying the pool for fishing and various technological interventions (sanitization, administration of organic fertilizers, repairs etc.);

- the dykes should be well compacted, and their crowning should allow the access of the means of transport necessary for carrying out the specific activities.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Description of growth technology

Over the course of a year, the following works are carried out in a systematic fish farm:

- preparing basins for flooding;
- administration of organic fertilizers and amendments;
- flooding of basins;
- populating the basins;

- feeding the fish material that consumes feed;
- monitoring the environmental conditions in the basins;
- determining the rate of growth through periodic control fishing;
- harvest fishing.

Preparing basins for flooding

This operation consists of:

- clearing the vegetation on the bottom of the basin and slopes, cleaning the bottom of the basin of plant debris; it can be done by mowing, raking and piling up plant debris on the edge of the basin.

- checking and repairing (when necessary) water supply and drainage installations, canals and dykes.

- preparing the supply and exhaust installations with valves, sieves and grates.

Administration of amendments, organic and mineral fertilizers

Administration of amendments - quicklime (CaO), on the entire surface of the basin. The amounts of amendments can reach up to 2000 kg/ha depending on the results of the soil analyzes (as a rule, the amounts administered fall between 200-500 kg/ha).

Administration of organic and mineral fertilizers. It is one of the most important works to be carried out because it is essential in the development of phyto- and zooplankton, which constitute the food base for the North American sturgeon species *Polyodon spathula*. Organic fertilizers (fermented manure - horse, bird, sheep, cow) are administered in quantities of up to 5 t/ha, in piles on the slope of the basin or scattered on the bottom of the basin. Mineral fertilizers (ammonium nitrate and calcium superphosphate) are placed on the manure piles. The amount of mineral fertilizers administered can reach up to 75 kg of ammonium nitrate and the same amount of superphosphate. During the vegetative period, both manure and mineral fertilizers can be administered, depending on the results of the hydro-chemical analyses.

Flooding of pools

It is the operation that is usually performed in March and is done 10-15 days before the popular. The basins are flooded at the normal working level, so as to ensure the previously mentioned depths.

In order to prevent the entry of unwanted fish species, flooding is done through a sieve at the 0.5 ha pool and through grates (distance between bars 4-6 mm) at the rearing pools in the second and third summers.

The popularity of pools

It is usually done at the beginning of April for 1- and 2-year-old fish stock (*Polyodon spathula*, *Cyprinus carpio*, *Ctenopharyngodon idella* *Esox lucius*) and at the end of April or the beginning of May

for the pre-developed fry of *P. spathula*.

The main works and actions necessary to be carried out for the proper functioning of the microfarm. The time affected for their fulfillment.

- **The popularity of helestees** with 1-year-old and 2-year-old pups and also with pre-developed polyodon pups – **20 hours**;

- **Daily monitoring** of the concrete situation in the field, which consists of: water temperature measurement; recording the values of the physico-chemical parameters of the water; observations regarding the development of natural food (plankton); control at feeding tables if the feed has been consumed; recording any unnatural behaviour of the fish; checking the condition of dikes, canals and works of art (monks, inlets); the recording of possible mortalities from the population of fish - 1 hour/day, i.e. **200 hours** for the entire growth period.

- **Feed administration**

4 hours/day × 150 feeding days = **600 hours**
(four hours/day means 2 workers × 2 hours/day);

- Ensuring the security service during the day will be the responsibility of the fish farmer (qualified worker in the field of fish breeding) who does the daily monitoring of the situation in the field and who also participates in the administration of feed;

Assurance of security service: 3424 hours.

- Ensuring the day guard service on Sundays and other legal holidays and the night guard service; 16 hours/day on working days and 24 hours/day on non-working days, i.e.:

28 public holidays × 24 hours/day = 672 hours

and 172 working days × 16 hours/day = 2752 hours

(Saturday is considered a working day).

In total: 672 hours + 2752 hours = 3424 hours.

The guards will be trained to do a large part of the daily monitoring of the situation in the field during the time they are on duty.

- **Administration of fertilizers and amendments** – **96 hours**;

- **Control fishing:** **120 hours** - 10 such actions × 12 hours/fishing = 120 hours (4 fishermen participate in a control fishing for 3 hours. So 4 × 3 = 12 hours,

- **Harvest fishing:** **336 hours.**

7 days (one day for the 0.5 ha pool and 3 days for the other pools) × 6 fishermen × 8 hours/day = 336 hours.

Total working hours required to carry out the work to complete a production cycle: **4796 hours** in a year.

These activities and works can be performed with the standards of 1 fish farmer and 3 guards.

No of people	Occupation	Net salary
1	Zootechnician engineer	4000
2	Pisciculturist	2800
3	Guard	2200
1	Accountant	700

Tab.1 Personal angajat

For the execution of specific works in fish farming, the minimum and absolutely necessary facilities can be:

a) Egreta fiberglass boat

It is produced by the "Brateşul" Handicraft Cooperative from Galati Falezai Boulevard no. 1 and can be purchased at the price of 3,187 RON.

The boat will be used for feed administration and control fisheries. Also, for harvest fishing and for various interventions on works of art, or on the surface of the heleste.

b) Net 100/4

It is produced by Societatea Plase pescăreşti S.A. Galati, Constantin Brâncoveanu str., no. 3, tel. 0236.473.373. The price of a net of this type (100 m long and 4 m wide, with the side of the eye of 12 mm) is, at the level of 2006, 4,798 RON.

The net is necessary to carry out control fisheries and self-directed harvesting fisheries.

In the case of performing these works with specialized companies, the costs will be very high and inevitably these works will not be executed at the optimal time, leading to delays.

c) Equipment for measuring the physico-chemical parameters of water

In order to monitor the living conditions offered by the aquatic environment (helesteu), a minimum of equipment is needed in terms of water quality measurement and control equipment:

- Oxy Guard Alpha portable oxygen meter

The device measures the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the water (vital for fish breathing).

The device, powered by a 9 V battery, measures dissolved oxygen both in mg/l and in saturation percentages (% sat.)

It is produced by the company OxyGuard Internațional A/S Blakken 59 DK -3460 Birkerød, Danmark (fax +45 45 82 20 94) and can be purchased in Romania from the company Dynavit Ipmex SRL Braşov, str. Vulturului, no. 19, tel/fax 0268 33 21 62, e-mail: happydog@xnet.ro, at the price of 3,040 RON.

The oxygen concentration must be measured daily, in the morning, before sunrise. In winter, in the winter pools, when the water surface is covered with ice, the determination of oxygen will be carried out both in the evening and in the morning.

- Portable oxygen meter model ProfiLine Oxi 197i

It is a device of the same type as the one presented previously and is produced by the company Wissenschaftlich – Technische Werkstätten GmbH & Co. KG Dr. – Karl – Slevogt – Strasse 1, D – 82362 Weilheim, Germany, tel. +49(0)881/183-0, fax +49(0)881/183-420, e-mail Info@WTW.com, internet http:// www. WTW.com and distributed in Romania by ROM TECH SRL, b-dul Burebista 1, bl. D 15/28, Bucharest, tel/fax (021) 3272294, (021) 3272295 or Str. Nicolae Iorga 6, - 24000 Sibiu, tel. 069/233465, fax 069/233482.

For entrepreneurs with financial possibilities, we recommend a portable multi-parameter device model Multi 340i SET 1, which determines, in addition to dissolved oxygen, temperature, pH and conductivity. It is also produced by the WTW company, whose address was previously presented.

- Secchi disc

With this instrument, the transparency of the water is measured, which gives us clues about the richness of the water in plankton, i.e. in natural food for fish. When the water transparency is 30-35 cm, i.e. the water depth at which the Secchi disk is no longer visible, it means that the natural food is well developed and it is a favorable situation for fish growth.

The Secchi disc is a 2 mm thick sheet metal disc with a diameter of 30 cm. On the front it is divided into 4 equal circle sectors (2 white and 2 black), arranged alternately, and on the reverse side it is painted white. On the reverse side, in the center of the disc, a metal piece is attached for tightening, and on the front side, also in the center of the disc, a fastening element to which a 4 m cord is tied. The Secchi disc is not commercially available for to be purchased, but it can be made by hand, which is why I made its description.

Using the disc is simple: gently insert the disc into the water and let it sink to a depth where it is no longer visible. A mark is made on the string and the depth is measured according to the length of the string that entered the water.

- Thermometer for water (up to 50o C)

It is necessary to measure the water temperature, which will be done every day, because depending on this water parameter, decisions are made regarding the feeding of the fish and the size of the maintenance flow.

These activities and works can be performed with the standards of 1 fish farmer and 3 guards.

Sustainable development - The impact of the project on the development of the area and the business environment

It is obvious that the project has a positive effect both on the development of the area where the development is located, as well as on the business environment and the quality of life.

By locating the microfarm in rural areas, local labor will be used.

The implementation of the project will ensure a quality fish production, which will have the effect of increasing the percentage of fish meat consumers. The quantitative and qualitative increase in production will lead to the improvement of the market position of the economic agents, to the increase in the turnover and to the net profit.

The production of sturgeon meat in aquaculture and its entry into the market will have a positive impact on the conservation and protection of sturgeons from the Danube, by reducing fishing pressure, especially poaching.

Market analysis - Market outlet

The description:

The drastic decrease of sturgeon stocks in the lower Danube basin as a result of negative anthropogenic impact on natural reproduction areas and abusive fishing, requires a research effort directed especially for the protection and recovery of these inventories.

Therefore, the restoration of the sturgeon stock through artificial reproduction and growth in conditions

favorable environmental conditions have been the subject of special research-development programs on world plan. In this context, our research on super-intensive growth is also included

of *Acipenser stellatus* chicks, an extremely valuable species from an economic point of view, in a recirculating system with aquarium type enclosures, designed and realized within the department of

"Aquaculture and fishing". In our experiment we took into account both factors biological and medial ones.

→ Market segment:

These products are addressed to niche economic agents who sell rare and luxury products, but also to those who want to develop a similar business

→ Market location:

It is sold in Romania in the form of meat as well as in the form of caviar

→ Application characteristics:

The demand for our product is high in Romania, as well as in Europe, but there are not many suppliers.

→ Possible risks:

As for the risk factors that could negatively influence demand, they are: high costs in terms of production and marketing, which implicitly lead to an increase in the selling price.

Marketing strategy

In terms of market analysis and marketing strategy, we have identified the target market in the western area of our country. Comparing the supply and demand on the sturgeon market, the target market is represented by the big producers in the country or the export. Most of the customers are from Germany and Switzerland. Currently there is no competition in this market due to the small number of companies that have the same product.

We usually set the selling price according to the production cost to which we add an additional 20 percent.

For Răbăgani commune, this profitable business is beneficial due to the fact that it offers jobs in the area and the reinvested profit increases the value of the land in the area.

8) Financial projections

8.1. Material expenses – 35,356 RON

Equipment – 11,085 RON;

Fodder – 21,141 RON;

Fertilizers and amendments – 4,420 RON

• manure – 1,785 RON

5 tons/ha × 10 ha = 50 tons.

50 t × 35.7 RON/t = 1,785 RON

• quicklime (CaO): 1,285 RON;

500 kg/ha × 10 ha = 5,000 kg

5,000 kg × 0.257 RON/kg = 1,285 RON

• ammonium nitrate – 675 RON

75 kg/ha × 10 ha = 750 kg

750 kg × 0.9 RON/kg = 675 RON

• superphosphate – 675 RON

75 kg/ha × 10 ha = 750 kg

750 kg × 0.9 RON = 675 RON

Popular material – 44,850 RON

Pre-developed chickens of *P. spathula* – 2,500

ex. × 3 RON/piece = 7,500 RON

*P. spathula*1 – 1,050 ex. × 15 RON/pc. = 15,750

RON

Carp2 – 2,250 kg × 8 RON/kg = 18,000 RON

Ct. idella2 – 300 kg × 10 RON/kg = 3,000 RON

Pike1 – 600 ex. × 100 g/ex. = 60 kg

60 kg × 10 RON = 600 RON

Total expenses for popular material: 44,850 RON

We mention that only in the first year of exploitation are purchased for the popular one-year-old sturgeon (*P. spathula*). In the following years, it will be populated from its own production.

Other material expenses (water, electricity, fuel, spare parts, repairs) about 6,000 RON.

Labor costs – 37,800 RON

A full-time fish farmer who will also provide security during the day:

900 RON/month × 12 months = 10,800 RON

Three whole guard rules:

750 RON/month × 3 guards × 12 months = 27,000 RON

Total labor costs: 37,800 RON

Total operating expenses for a microfarm of 10 ha – 118,006 RON

Material costs + labor costs

79,606 RON + 37,800 RON = 117,406 RON

The purchase prices for fodder and breeding material do not include VAT.

For the establishment of the 10 ha fishery, the estimated costs amount to 175,000 - 200,000 RON.

It is necessary that the pool for growing polyodon in summer I (0.5ha) be protected with a protection installation against ichthyophage birds made of acacia poles with a length of 2 m and a diameter of 15 cm, on which they are mounted at the upper end a contour made of resinous timber, on which to fasten the relon thread at a distance of 20 cm.

The **SWOT** analysis

Strong points

- The competition is still not very high;
- Demand exceeds supply
- The rarity of eggs, as well as meat

Weaknesses

- The required capital is very high
- The rarity of the species
- The problem is promoting the offer to make the products we offer as well known as possible

Opportunities

- Penetrating new markets
- Roe export
- Meat export

Threats

- the transmission of any diseases that may have occurred in the fish in the upstream fish pond;
- fishing will be done with certain difficulties related to the fact that it is mandatory to fish the downstream basin first and then successively the following ones upstream. This constraint is technically conditioned by the fact that the level of the

upstream basins cannot be lowered if the downstream one is full.

- the filling and emptying times of the hatches will increase because the entry of water into the fish farm will only be possible through the upstream hatch and therefore, they will not be able to be filled simultaneously, but successively.

CONCLUSIONS

The first sturgeon farm in the country was established in 2006 when the first cega specimens from Germany were purchased and two aquariums were populated with the caviar species consisting of 400 embryonic eggs. This is how the first sturgeon farm in the country came into existence, having as its activity both the growth and research of sturgeons, as well as the collection of black fish roe, among the most expensive on the market.

The expenses are easy to amortize in the case of this business because the increased production and the high demand on the market make sturgeon farming a very profitable business. About 100 grams of caviar are obtained from a one-kilogram cega.

Sturgeons are real living factories of black roe. On the black market in Romania, they are sold for less than 500 euros/kg, and on the official market for less than 1,000 euros.

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OPTIMAL NUTRITIONAL STRATEGIES AGAINST HEAT STRESS AT POULTRY IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGES

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REVIEW

Abstract

Global warming and climate change has an increasing impact on the agricultural and livestock sector, especially for the poultry production. Heat stress is one of the most important factors which negatively influence the poultry productivity in the industrial systems causing a substantial economic losses. Modern poultry genetic lines are more susceptible to the negative impact of heat stress induced by the high temperatures in the stable. Therefore, heat stress affects the normal physiological response of the birds, decrease the feed intake which will affect the productive performances (growing rate and weight gain, egg production, feed conversion, quality of productions), impairs immune response and oxidative status of the body leading to increased mortality in the flock. Researches in the field present numerous nutrition and feeding practices to mitigate these effects, such as: dietary manipulation by adjusting feed energy density or protein level and amino acid balance; dietary enrichment via electrolytes balance, vitamins, minerals and additives such as betaine. Feeding strategies include the efficiency of double feeding, size of the compound feed particle and feeding traits, drinking water temperature and feeding restrictions during the day. However, in the practice only a few of these are used, therefore this review aims to highlight the impact of heat stress on poultry health and productions as well as the optimal feeding and nutrition strategies to mitigating the impact of heat stress.

Keywords: heat stress; poultry; amino acids; betaine; nutritional strategies
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INTRODUCTION

Climate changes represent a major concern for today's livestock farming systems around the world because are affected the natural food and water resources, as well as animal health and production. As a result, the capacity of the current livestock systems to sustain and satisfy the increasing requirements of food for humans is thus unstable (Godde et al, 2021). The livestock sector currently plays an important role in the supply of food for population and in the safety of foods. Animal products (meat, milk and eggs) contribute with 15 - 31% of global calories and proteins intake per capita, with regional variations (Herrero et al, 2013).

Studies regarding the impacts of climate change on the livestock often focus on the potential for mitigating the effects associated with high climate temperatures on livestock and on the describing of adaptation practices. Heat stress is primarily induced by exposure to high

ambient temperatures and low relative humidity, which limit the ability of animals to lose body heat when are on the farm or during transport. Vulnerability to heat stress varies by species, breed, feeding phase, genetic potential, health status, developmental stage, skin thickness or feather distribution, and previous exposure to high temperature (Bernabucci et al, 2010; Saeed et al, 2018).

In most cases, the impact of heat stress is to reduce animal productivity and welfare, and under of prolonged exposure leads to the increase of mortalities. Lowered feed intake is one of the first and important consequences of heat stress. Heat stress is an adaptive response that occurs when the thermolysis rate (the homeotherm-specific process for losing body temperature) is below that of thermogenesis (the homeotherm-specific process for body heat production) and the body's ability to lose heat is exceeded by the heat load acquired through the exposure to high ambient temperatures (Al-Saffar & Rose, 2002).

The importance of animal response to heat stress applies to all species but the birds are one of the most sensitive due to their limited biological possibilities for body heat loss. Climate change will influence poultry production indirectly by affecting long-term quantitative production but also the nutritional quality of feed; and directly as a result of heat stress that will affect the productive performances, the quality of production and also its economical efficiency (Abdel-Moneim et al, 2021).

The aim of this review is to highlight the currently used feeding and nutritional strategies to reduce the negative impact of heat stress on poultry sector.

EFFECTS OF HEAT STRESS ON POULTRY PRODUCTIONS

Heat stress at poultry begins when the thermal comfort threshold is exceeded, which affects the body's homeostasis. In fast-growing broiler chicks, the problem of heat excess occurs with the growth and development when takes place the maturation of the body's thermoregulatory system, development of plumage and increased metabolic heat production generated by the fast growth rate supported by the high nutrient intake. High susceptibility to heat stress also results from limited development of the cardiovascular and respiratory system (Yahav, 2000) and lack of sweat glands (Mitchell et al, 2005). Thus, broiler chicks temperature requirements decrease from 33.5°C on day 1 to below 20°C after 30 days of age. By the technological point of view, this period overlaps to the second part of the growing phase and to the entire finishing period. Under these conditions, during summer periods with the temperatures above 30°C, the microclimate system of the stables is no longer able to maintain the optimal inside temperature for the chicks. Thus, at the level of the chick organism, a series of defence mechanisms are happen, which are associated with nutrients losses and disorders due to thermoregulation processes (through thermolysis) (Abioja & Abiona, 2021). Broilers have a relatively short thermal comfort zone, and as the ambient temperature in the stable exceeds the upper limit of the thermal tolerance range, the birds' ability to lose heat is diminished and dangerous hyperthermia occurs (Abioja & Abiona, 2021). An ambient temperature above the thermal comfort zone will produce a series of neuroendocrine processes that affect broiler

welfare and productivity. Prior to this stage, body temperature is mainly regulated by heat losses to the environment through conduction, convection and radiation, also known as non-evaporative heat loss (Borges et al, 2003).

Once the body temperature increase above the tolerance limit, the birds will show a typical behavior of polypnea. Polypnea is an adaptive behaviour for the birds to lose body heat by evaporation along the respiratory tract and presenting an open beak with a intense breathing. The respiratory rate can increase from 25 to 150 breaths/min over a 20 minutes period. An healthy broiler chick through the hyperventilation and polypnea can eliminate approximately 0.54 Kcal/g of water lost (Abioja & Abiona, 2021). Frequent breathing after a time period will produce a decrease in blood CO₂ concentration, which will lead to respiratory alkalosis due to the increase of blood pH above normal limits as a result of the altered CO₂ concentration (Franco-Jimenez et al, 2007). Respiratory alkalosis has been identified as a marker to assess the heat stress periods at poultry (Barrett et al, 2019; Franco-Jimenez et al, 2007). Excessive removal of CO₂ results in reducing the availability of blood bicarbonate used by laying hens for eggshell mineralization and induces a high availability of organic acids which decreasing the blood free calcium levels and negatively affect the eggshell (Marder & Arad, 1989).

In breeders, heat stress affects reproductive functions by disrupting hormonal regulation between the hypothalamus and ovary, i.e. by decreasing sperm volume, sperm concentration, motility and viability (Rozenboim et al, 2007; Elnagar et al, 2010; Joshi et al, 1980; McDaniel et al, 2004).

The negative effects of heat stress consist in the decrease of feed intake and an increased water consumption, intense heart rate and respiration, electrolytes imbalance, changes in haematological parameters and enzyme activities. All of these negatively affect the productive performances of poultry.

Impact of climate changes on the egg production and quality

In laying hens, the main selection criterion is laying performance, and heat stress primarily affects egg production and egg quality (Barrett et al, 2019). Temperature on laying hen farms averages in the range of 18 - 20°C being difficult to maintain during hot summer periods. Decreased feed intake is the starting point for

the most acute effects of heat stress, leading to decrease in body weight, feed conversion ration (FCR), egg production and egg quality (Deng et al, 2012; Mashaly et al, 2004). In addition, heat stress has been shown to reduce the digestibility of feed nutrients and decrease blood calcium and plasma protein levels (Mahmoud et al, 1996; Bonnet et al, 1997; Zhou et al, 1998).

In a study it is proven that a 12-days period of heat stress led to a 28.5 g/bird reduction in average daily feed intake and a 28.8% decrease of egg production (Deng et al, 2012). Star et al (2009) reported a reduction with 31.6% of feed conversion ratio and with 36.4% in egg production, as well as a decrease with 3.41% of egg weight in laying hens housed in heat stress conditions. Also, a research conducted by Ebeid et al (2012) shows that heat stress causes a reduction in egg weight by 3.24%, in shell thickness by 1.2% and in eggshell weight by 9.93%. Another study reports that heat stress is associated with a decrease in laying performance, in a reduction of eggshell thickness and with an increase in the percentage of broken eggs (Lin et al, 2004).

The negative effect of heat stress on egg production is higher with the longer time exposure. Thus it was shown that as the exposure time of laying hens to heat stress increased from 8-14 days to 30-42 days and to 43-56 days respectively, the egg production decreased accordingly by 13.2%, 26.4% and 57% (Farnell et al, 2001). In another study it was shown that a exposure over a period of 5 weeks caused a decrease in egg production by 28.8% in the same time with a reduction in feed intake by 34.7% and body weight by 19.3% (Mashaly et al, 2004). Barrett et al (2019) demonstrate that average daily gain, FCR, eggshell weight and albumen Haugh unit were significantly affected when laying hens were housed at 35°C for 6.5 hours from the 24 to 28 weeks of age.

Impact of climate change on meat production and quality

Selection and genetic progress over the last decade has been aimed to obtain fast growing line of broilers, which considerably has decreased the natural resistance of organism to the environmental factors. The major problem for broilers during heat stress is associated with the lowering of feed intake (Awad et al, 2019). Broiler chickens subjected to a chronic heat stress showed a lower feed intake by

16.4%, lower body weight by 32.6 % and FCR by 25.6% at 42 days of age (Sohail et al, 2012).

It has been shown that exposure of broiler chickens to heat stress negatively affects fat deposition and meat quality (Lu et al, 2007). Subsequent research has shown that heat stress is associated with decreased chemical composition and meat quality in broilers (Dai et al, 2012; Imik et al, 2012) showing a decrease of breast portion at the same time with the increase of thigh portion, as a percentage of live weight (Zhang et al, 2012).

Research conducted on broilers Cobb 500 and Ross 308 demonstrates a reduction of feed intake with 8-9%, of weight gain with by 17% and a worst FCR by 9-10% when chickens were exposed to 34°C for 6 hours daily from 22 to 35 days of age (Awad et al, 2019). The mechanism underlying these findings could be related with the stimulation of appetite-related hormones such as cholecystokinin (CCK), which is secreted in anorexia (He et al, 2018). Given that weight gain is directly correlated with feed intake, and the small intestine is the main site of nutrients digestion and absorption, if during heat stress the feed intake decrease (due to lowering appetite) then further decreases in total intestinal mass and length may occur, as well as changes in mucosal villous morphology (Garriga et al, 2006; Liu et al, 2016). Heat stress has been found to affect the regulation of genes responsible for nutrients transport, which also affects daily gain in broilers (Garriga et al, 2006; Habashy et al, 2017). Water consumption was increased by 5-10% when birds were exposed to high temperatures (32°C) from 17 to 42 days of age (Deeb & Cahaner, 2002).

NUTRITIONAL AND FEEDING STRATEGIES IN POULTRY TO MITIGATE THE EFFECTS OF HEAT STRESS

Nutritional strategies

Energy density of feed

Heat sources for broilers come from metabolism, movement activity and from stable environment. Metabolic heat production in broiler is high due to intensive feeding and nutrients intake compared to other bird species. The high growing rate is supported by the feed intake, which leads to heat production in the body (Abioja & Abiona, 2021). As the ambient temperature in the stable exceeds the upper limit of the thermal tolerance range, the ability

of broilers to lose heat is decreased, which makes the excessive heat production to accumulate in the body.

It is well known that fats generate the lowest metabolic heat when is used in the feed as an energy source, so high-fat diets can reduce the total heat production in broilers. Increasing the metabolisable energy content of feed by adding fat is an increasingly common practice in the summer period. Adding more fat to recipes will increase the energy density of the feed which will increase the intake of energy, thus compensating the energy losses of the broilers in heat stress periods (Lin et al, 2006; Lara & Rostagno, 2013). Fat generates less body-heat than proteins or carbohydrates, and some researches shows that a higher fat content in the diet (up to 5-6%) decrease the negative effects of heat stress in broilers (Daghir, 2009). Also, the use of higher percentages of fat in feed will contribute to a slower intestinal passage rate of digestive content, thus increasing the time for digestion and absorption of nutrients. Therefore, diet supplementation with fats will indirectly helps to increase the energy value of other feed ingredients (Daghir, 2009). Another advantage of adding fats with reference to vegetable fats (oils) is the presence of linoleic acid, which is important for poultry production (Szymczyk et al, 2001). However, the oxidative stability and the rancidity process of fats in feed must be taken into account.

Dietary protein level and amino acid balance

In the heat stress periods it is recommended to use compound feeds for poultry with a lower crude protein but well balanced in essential amino acids such as lysine, methionine, threonine, tryptophan and arginine (Saeed et al, 2018). The level of nutrients in the diet must be ensured according to the nutritional recommendations provided by the hybrid technology.

The amino acid profile of the ideal protein for broilers is changes during the growing period in accordance with their performances. Amino acid conversion and nitrogen excretion are lowest when diets are formulated according to the ideal protein concept. The excess of amino acids which cannot be used in protein synthesis due to a limiting factor (such as an amino acid deficiency, low energy level) are metabolised in the body. Compared to other nutrients, the oxidation of amino acids produces the greatest amount of metabolic heat which

contributes to the total heat production. Consequently, heat increase is higher when amino acids are in excess in the diet and is not a proper amino acid balance. Research shows that essential amino acids such as lysine (Corzo et al, 2003), arginine (Mendes et al, 1997), methionine or the addition of 2-hydroxy-4-methylthiobutanoic acid to diets can be beneficial to the chickens during periods with high temperatures (Chen et al, 2003). Saeed et al (2018) recommend that ratio between digestible lysine and to be increased by 5%-10% during heat stress.

Electrolyte balance of feed

Cold water is the first and easiest to use for the reducing of negative effects of heat stress and it also brings electrolytes (Na, Cl, K and NaHCO_3) necessary to maintain acid-base equilibrium (Koelkebeck et al, 1993). During periods of heat stress in the broiler organism take places a disturbances of the acid-base balance, as a result the lost electrolytes can be recovered by using vitamin and mineral complexes in the water which also must contain sodium (Na), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), chlorine (Cl) and in addition bicarbonate (HCO_3) and sulphate (SO_4) (Ahmad & Sarwar 2006). Addition of potassium chloride in the amount of 0.2 - 0.5% and supplementation with sodium (0.20 - 0.25%) and chloride (0.30%) helps to maintain osmotic and acid-base equilibrium in broilers older than 29 days (Mushlag et al, 2007; Khattak et al, 2012). The addition of electrolytes to drinking water not only maintains the osmotic balance of the birds but also stimulates water consumption.

Vitamins

During the periods of heat stress, the vitamin requirements of broiler chickens are higher and therefore must be provided in feed or drinking water as a supplement (Lin et al, 2006). Vitamins and minerals are widely researched as adjuvants in mitigating the negative effects of heat stress (Vakili & Rashidi, 2011). For example, supplementation of laying hens diet with vitamin A, C and E has improved the egg production, hatchability, fertility and reduce the eggshell problems (Sahin et al, 2006). Also in broiler parents stock the supplementation with vitamin C and E improved eggshell quality, feed intake and the body weight in the periods with heat stress (Chung et al, 2005). Although vitamin C is

synthesized in the body, dietary supplementation is useful due to insufficient availability of plasma ascorbic acid caused by the reduced capacity of the organism to synthesize under heat stress. For example, the adding of vitamin C in the feed or water of broilers helps in thermoregulation and reduce corticosterone levels during heat stress (Attia et al, 2009; Khattak et al, 2012). The action of vitamin C during heat stress is to fortify the immune system, support feed intake and as a result the weight gain, and reduce oxidative stress in broiler chickens (Attia et al, 2016; Orayaga et al, 2016).

A good antioxidant is vitamin E which provides cell protection, scavenges free radicals as a result of oxidative stress and defends against lipid peroxidation (Khan et al, 2011; Attia et al, 2016). It also protect lymphocytes and plasma cells against oxidative action and increase the immune system resistance (Khan et al, 2011; Khan et al, 2019; Attia et al, 2016).

Minerals

The organic salts of the minerals possess antioxidant properties that helps to reduce the creation of free radicals in the birds' organism, thus providing protection against oxidative stress. During heat stress it has been shown an increase requirements of P and Ca due to the lowered feed intake (Lin et al, 2006). Several studies show positive effects of minerals such as selenium, chromium, zinc on the growth performance and weight gain of broiler chicks, as well as reduction the level of heat shock protein and lipid peroxidation (Rao et al, 2016). Zinc has an important role in free radical suppression as it functions as a co-factor (Cu/Zn-SOD) and inhibits NADPH-dependent lipid peroxidation. It also contributes to improve antioxidant status and increase serum vitamin C and E concentration (Sahin et al, 2006). The usage of vitamins and minerals combination (vitamin E and Zn) in the diet have a synergistic effect in reducing the effect of heat stress in poultry, correlating with the improvement of weights, feed conversion and carcass quality (Sahin et al, 2006).

Feed additives

Betaine (trimethylglycine) is an intermediate metabolite in choline catabolism, which acts as a donor of methyl groups and has a lipotropic effect, protecting the liver. Betaine plays an important role in the optimal maintenance of biological processes involved in

osmotic regulation (Honarbakhsh et al, 2007; Lever & Slow, 2010) and cellular water, ionic balance, methionine utilization and fat distribution (Attia et al, 2005; Hassan et al, 2005) respectively in the immunity (Graham, 2002). Also, the action of betaine is related to methionine and choline substitution (Graham, 2002; Attia et al, 2009). In one review, Saeed et al (2017) show in birds that betaine acts as an osmolyte to maintain cellular water and ionic balance in the body, preventing dehydration. The action of betaine is also linked to the promotion of a favourable gut microbiota against osmotic variations, helping to protect internal organs and increase fatty acid catabolism. The use of betaine in the diet of broiler chickens under heat stress has been shown to have a positive impact (Table 1) by improving growth performance, nutrient digestibility, immune system and physiological processes, hormone levels and mortality (Wang et al, 2004; Farooqi et al, 2005; Khattak et al, 2012; Saeed et al, 2017a). According to Table 1, the use of betaine in broilers during the periods with heat stress resulted in reduced intra-abdominal fat and increased breast portion in carcass, due to its important role in lipids metabolism by increasing fatty acids catabolism and thus reducing fat deposition. On the other hand, betaine is metabolized in glycine and therefore could improve the fat digestibility (Augustin & Danforth, 1999). An effect is also clearly attributed to its well-known role as a methyl group donor for lecithin synthesis which facilitates the fat transport in organism (Saeed et al, 2017a). In addition, betaine may improve the availability of choline thus providing more choline for the synthesis of very low density lipoproteins, which prevent fat storage in the liver by stimulating the burning processes (Yao & Vance 1989). According to McDevitt et al (2000) the increased of breast percentage may be due to the increased availability of methionine and cystine from feed to protein synthesis.

Betaine's role as a suitable donor of methyl groups favor a good intestinal electrolyte balance in birds and also protects the mucosal epithelium, therefore a higher nutrient absorption can be achieved which will improve the weight gain and use of feed by 3 to 15% (Hassan et al, 2005; Sayed & Downing 2011). Eklund et al (2005) show in a review that feed conversion of laying hens has improved by up to 9% when betaine was used in feed in a dose of 0.01-0.08%.

Heat stress lead to negative changes of endogenous bacterial microbiota of the gut, so the probiotics supplementation will support the diversity of useful microbiota, restoring the normal balance (Attia et al, 2006). Thus, the use of a probiotic containing *Lactobacillus* culture lead to an improved feed intake of broiler chickens exposed to $36 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ for 3 hours daily, from 21 to 42 days of age (Zulkifli et al, 2000). In another study, the use of probiotics at

broilers resulted in a better weight and FCR even the presence of heat stress (Al-Daraji, 2013). In laying hens, diets supplementation with probiotics reduced the negative effects of heat stress on the egg production and intestinal health (Deng et al, 2012; Kurtoglu et al, 2004; Mahdavi et al, 2005). These results suggest that positive effects of probiotics in birds are to improve feed intake because heat stress mainly affect it.

Table 1

Effects of using betaine in broiler diets during heat stress periods (adapted from Saeed et al 2017)

Betaine level in feed	Effects on productive performance	Reference
0.05 - 0.15 %	higher daily gain, lower fat percentage in carcass, higher breast portion	Virtanen & Rosi (1995)
0.15 %	increase the digestibility of proteins, fats, lysine and carotenoids from the compound feed	Remus et al (1995)
0.1 %	improved body weight	Farooqi et al (2005)
1 g/kg	higher daily gain and lower level of heterophile/lymphocyte ratio	Gudev et al (2011)
1472 mg/kg	improved body weight	Hassan et al (2005)
0.14 %	improved body weight	Rafeeq et al (2011)
0.05 - 0.10 %	increase daily gain	El-Husseiny et al (2007)
800 mg/kg	increase the portion of breast	Rao et al (2011)

Adding a combinations of prebiotics and probiotics in feed to produce a synergistic effect (synbiotics) is suggested to be beneficial for mitigating the negative effects of heat stress and improving performance of broiler chickens (Mohammed et al, 2018). In this regard, Sohail et al (2012) report a positive effect after the use in feed of mannan-oligosaccharides and a mix of prebiotics and probiotics on the growth performance, gut health and immunity in broilers kept in heat stress.

Acetylsalicylic acid has been used to improve the productive performances of broiler chickens, laying hens and quail in heat stress (Naseem et al, 2005; Roussan et al, 2008). Also the use of sodium zeolite has been shown to help against heat stress in poultry (Saeed et al 2019). Ahmad & Sarwar (2006) show that the use of sodium bicarbonate in poultry feed helps the organism in heat stress periods due to the role as pH buffering agent, being a source of CO_2 .

Rosemary extract helps broiler chickens in heat stress probably by favoring the expression of HSP70 and CRYAB genes (Tang et al, 2018). Researches show a several medicinal herbs such as boldo (*Peumus boldus*) and *Morinda citrifolia* leaves as having antioxidant and preventive effects on the negative effects of heat stress in broilers (Flees et al, 2017; Toplu

et al, 2014). The resveratrol is a bioactive compound, and its use in poultry diets helps to mitigate the negative effects of heat stress by supporting the intestinal barrier and reducing the negative effects associated with oxidative stress (Liu et al, 2016; Zhang et al, 2017). Liu et al (2013) report the beneficial effects of resveratrol (200, 400, or 600 mg/kg of feed) on the immune system, oxidative stress, and productive performance chickens exposed to heat stress.

Feed supplementation with additives such as phytobiotics or anthocyanin-like polyphenols during periods of heat stress in chickens can help due to their biochemical role as antioxidants, anti-inflammatories, immunizers or neuroprotectants (Hu et al, 2019; Saeed et al, 2017b).

Also, the use of plant derivatives such as phytochemicals in broilers feed is having popularity due to their potential antioxidant activities. For example, lycopene is a anti-stress antioxidant that enhances cell multiplication and the immune system but also has effects on gene transcription (Palozza et al, 2012). Another compound used is gamma-glutamylethylamide (L-thianine) from green tea leaves due to the antioxidant properties (Saeed et al, 2018).

Nutritional strategies

Feeding restrictions

Intermittent feeding of broilers is a practice increasingly used worldwide during periods with high temperatures and consists in depriving of feed during the darkness hours applied during the day. The main purpose of organizing feeding times is based on the concept that the peak of metabolic heat production to not overlap with the highest temperature degrees (Farghly et al, 2019). Practicing the feed deprivation will decrease the internal metabolic heat production of organism and this will help birds to reduce their body heat and will be more easily to resist at heat stress. Intense feeding is carried out during the cold hours of the day, i.e. in the morning, evening and all the night (Farghly et al, 2018). An advantage of the fasting periods also results from the inactivity of the birds, so that through the lack of muscle contractions no additional heat will be produced in the body.

Decreased normal feed intake leads to reduced daily intake of nutrients required for weight gain and normal physiological processes. Even if some gain is lost, chicks can resist more easily at heat due to decreased of internal heat production, which will also positively influence flock mortality (Liu et al, 2013; Nawab et al, 2018).

Double feeding

The proteins produce a high heat metabolism, therefore was tested the use of two types of diets in less than 20 hours: during the day for 7 hours when temperatures are very high in broiler stables was used a low-protein but high energy diet; and during the night (17 hours) a high-protein and lower energy diet was used. The diets provided the appropriate nutritive requirements for feeding phase, starting with the broilers age of 20 days and up to 41 days. The results showed that mortality in the flock was lower and the broilers' body temperature during the heat-stressed day was also lower compared to the control group (De Basilio et al, 2001).

Particle size and feed form

The aim of pelleting the compound feed for broilers is to aggregate fine particles containing important nutrients into a compact pellet to ensure a high productive performances (Abdel-Moneim et al, 2021). Feeding with a quality pellets, free of dust and with adequate

physical qualities, will contribute to the reduction of heat production required for feed consumption by the birds in heat stress. Syafwan et al (2011) found that feeding chickens with a feed with coarse particles (coarse diet) led to the development of gastrointestinal tract especially the gizzard. Also the coarse particles increased water retention in the birds body, being available for cooling.

The use of wet feed has been shown to better hydrate birds during the heat stress and also provide higher feed intake (Awojobi et al, 2009; Dei & Bumbie, 2011). In this regard, Syafwan et al (2011) report that wet feeding of broilers facilitates increased water intake, which can compensate the evaporative losses during polypnea episodes, thus helps to the thermolysis processes. Also, wet feeding improved feed intake and reduced the impact of heat stress in broilers reared in the warm tropics (Dei & Bumbie, 2011). However, related to this topic the available researches show a contradictory results, as further research is needed to elucidate this issue.

Drinking water temperature:

During heat stress birds drink more water needed to reduce body temperature (Lara & Rostagno, 2013). If birds fail to drink the required water there is will be an imbalance between the water intake and evaporated by cooling, which will affect serum ion concentration and blood osmolarity. This leads to the disruption of the cell functions, of the osmolarity of intra- and extracellular fluids and of pH of body fluids, which affect negatively the poultry productions (Abdel-Moneim et al, 2021). Under normal conditions, the water : feed ratio is 1.8 : 1. This ratio changes when temperatures increase, e.g. at 30-35°C, broilers over 30 days of age will have a water : feed intake ratio of 4.9 : 1 (Bruno et al, 2011; Saeed et al, 2019). Thus it is very important for water to be ad libitum, clean, cool (at 10°C) and fresh.

CONCLUSIONS

This negative effects of heat stress in poultry are associated with the decrease of feed and water intake, acceleration of heart rate and breathing, electrolyte imbalances, changes in hematological parameters, enzyme activities and in the bacterial populations at intestinal level; all negatively affecting the productive performances.

The main nutritional and feeding strategies to reduce heat stress consist in reducing the heat metabolism production; compensating the nutrient deficit resulting from the feed intake decreasing; mitigation the induced metabolic changes. The use of enzymes mixture in accordance with the compound feed structure leads to the improvement of nutrients digestibility. The use of betaine in poultry feed is proved to help in heat stress through its role as a donor of methyl groups which favor a good intestinal electrolyte balance and also protects the mucosal epithelium. Mitigation of heat stress can also be achieved by improving the oxidative body defense or by a good electrolyte balance.

Compensating the reduced nutrients intake also requires the implementation of high-performance technologies in manufacturing the compound feeds (hydrothermal treatments), as well as the maintaining of high pellet quality.

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RURAL KITCHEN AND TRAVEL SOCIAL ENTERPRISE: PROPOSAL FOR TOURISM IN MEXICO

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Mexico, located in North America is the 6th country most visited by international tourists with 42.15 visitors per year. Until 2022, tourism contributed to the Mexican GDP with 2.4 billion MXN pesos (96 million euros). Unfortunately, the benefits of tourism are concentrated in a few corporations leaving little profit to rural areas, triggering acculturation and inequity. In addition, mass tourism is popular in Mexico, however, this type of tourism threatens traditional knowledge and biocultural diversity.

Given that, our goal is to establish a social enterprise committed to rural development in Mexico by promoting food experiences with local hosts and guides in different destinations and seasons. A business plan was elaborated using tools such as PEST analysis, SWOT analysis, and Porter's five forces analysis. The results demonstrate that our project has a high potential for success due to its unexplored market niche, the fact that tourists spend a third of their travel budget on food, and an ongoing change in tourism trends towards social and environmental responsibility.

The constitution of this social enterprise will occur mainly via the creation of alliances with stakeholders and crowdfunding, thus, resulting in a low initial investment but high social impact since the first year it will generate a profit of 9%.

Keywords: sustainability, traditional food, local actors, economic development.

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INTRODUCTION

Over the last century, tourism has become a worldwide instrument and a factor of economic growth. In some regions, such as Latin America, the economic spillover has only contributed to sectoral growth, leaving aside equitable distribution among rural populations. Consequently, they have less access to a better quality of life (Orozco & Núñez, 2013).

Within the tourism experience, food has emerged as one of the main motivations for travel (Contreras & Medina, 2021). In this sense, developing gastronomic routes in rural areas where local actors drive the business can strengthen cultural identity, improve quality of life, and boost economic development while

tourists have authentic and personalized experiences.

Mexico, among the most visited countries in the world, has the potential to develop rural and sustainable gastronomic tourism. For instance, the country has an important gastronomic offer that contributes to the country's economy: 515 thousand restaurants, three of them among the best 50 in the world (SIAP, 2022).

Furthermore in 2010, Mexico's traditional cuisine was recognized by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as Intangible Heritage of Humanity. This culinary heritage includes agricultural activities, ritual practices, ancient practical knowledge, culinary techniques and customs (UNESCO, 2010).

Hence, our aim is to analyze the feasibility of developing a social enterprise that offers traditional food experiences throughout all the seasons, connecting in this way tourists with local hosts in rural areas.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Study area

Mexico located in Northamerica, is the 6th country with most international tourism with 38.33 million per year (Sectur, 2022), and the first destination in Latin America (ONU, 2023). There are 129.1 million inhabitants within a territory comprising 1,973 million km² of land (World Population Review, 2024).

According to the World Economic Forum (2024), it is ranked 38th in the Travel and Tourism Development Index worldwide, which measures the set of factors and policies that enable sustainable and resilient development.

Methodology

Firstly, a PEST analysis was carried out to describe the political, economic, social, and technological components of the study area. Thus, it allowed us to critically evaluate the business environment to enhance our business strategy. Then, a SWOT analysis was designed to visualize the main strengths, weaknesses, threats and opportunities of our business idea.

On the other hand, Porter's five forces model was used to analyze the competitive environment of the company. This included the identification of: 1) Compleitive Rivalry, 2) Supplier Power, 3) Buyer Power, 4) Threat of Substitution and 5) Threat of New Entry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mexico is a developing country with multiple contrasts, as it is shown by the PEST analysis, which is described in the following paragraphs.

Political: According to World Population Review (2024), the Mexico democracy index overall score (0-10) is 5.14, earning the title of hybrid regime. Mexico is part of the ten most dangerous countries in the region. The corruption perception is 31/100, positioning Mexico on the ranking 126 of 180 countries (Global Coalition against Corruption, 2023).

Of the 129.1 million inhabitants, 18.4% live in rural areas.

Economic: This scenario provides favorable results since the time required to start a business is 8 days. The GPD annual growth is 3.9%, and from this percentage tourism contributes 8.5% (2.3 billion pesos MXN). Foreign direct investment, net inflows, represent the 2.7% of GDP.

Social: In 2022, the national Social Progress Index score was estimated at 65.6 out of 100 possible points, being the year with the highest score and providing a future scenario of improvement.

Technological: Mexico had a total export of 494,595,503 in thousands of US\$, and total imports of 506,565,459 in thousands of US\$, leading to a negative trade balance of - 11,969,956.03 US\$ (2021, WITS). It is the 3rd country in the innovation economy in Latin America and the Caribbean. Among the global middle-income economies, a couple of Mexican universities are in the Top 10 universities list. Ranking 56 in global innovation (WIPO, 2019), Mexico represents one of the most favourable countries Latin America.

The results from the SWOT analysis indicate that, on the internal aspects, the principal strength is that our company will provide a unique service, with a variety of destinations all year round at affordable prices. On the other hand, the principal weakness is around the financial aspect, this weakness is going to be minimized by crowdfunding. Opportunely, the crowdfunding market is expected to continue its growth trajectory that will be driven by factors such as the increasing availability of crowdfunding apps, the growth of the gig economy and freelance work, and the rise of impact investing, which seeks to support socially responsible projects (Statista, 2024).

One of the main results from the opportunities of the SWOT, is the importance of creating partnerships and synergies to reach the local actors with NGOs and the Academy. To maximize the opportunities, a marketing agency will oversee the outreach of the public and potential customers through promotions such as advertising and social media.

The major threat is represented by the insecurity in the country. Security and political

instabilities would affect partially the operation of the company, possibly hindering our work.

Porter's five forces

1) **Competitive Rivalry:** in Mexico exists one direct competitor. It is a Travel agency that offers sustainable tourism services and that holds a B Corp Certification. The services offered are personalized travel routes including accommodation, remote assistance, and various forms of payment.

2) **Supplier Power:** It is easy to increase the prices because the local actors are going to establish the prices. Potential suppliers: 15 types of experiences during the year including fairs, gastronomic routes and gastronomic festivities (like Independence Day). It is not expensive to change because our service is based on diversification.

3) **Buyer Power:** Since the deal is going to be directly with the local actors the prices would be competitive.

The international tourism buyers are 38.33 million per year (2022). Since it is an experience of direct contact with the customers, they are going to be encouraged to give feedback, in order to help the enterprise to improve.

Our target customers will be international tourists mainly from France, United States of America, Canada, Germany, Colombia, Brazil and Spain. Tourists from the Gen Z and Millennial generations, especially those interested in sustainable and gastronomic trends are the main aim.

4) **Threat of Substitution:** our enterprise vision relies on a social economy and a horizontal relationship with the local actors and hosts, that differentiates the company from the competitors. If a tourist wants this type of experience, it would be likely to find a specific place where local people are available to provide this unique service.

5) **Threat of New Entry:** It is not easy for competitors to enter the market since our vision is to respect the community. Hence, creating networks requires more actions than just starting a conventional agency.

After an analysis of the regional context and seasons, the tour experiences to provide are: Rosca de reyes, tamales, feria del maíz, capirotada, tlayudas, feria del nopal, pozole,

chiles en nogada, feria del maíz, fiesta mexicana, pan de muerto, mole poblano, Xantolo, ponche, posada. This is organized as it is explained below:

Route Jan-February

- Rosca de Reyes (traditional bread after new year): Season of 20 days, expected 15 persons per experience, who pay 35 euros.
- Tamales and atole (February's typical meal, handmade with corn as main ingredient): Season of 20 days, expected 15 persons per experience, that pay 30 euros.

Routes March-May

- Feria del Maíz: 5 days Fair of corn, expected 30 persons per day, entrance fee: 40 euros.
- Capirotada: 30 days of this experience, expecting 15 people per day, entrance fee: 30 euros.
- Tlayudas: 50 days of this experience, expecting 20 people per day, entrance fee: 45 euros.
- Routes June- September
- Feria del Nopal: 5 days of the fair, expecting to have 20 people, entrance fee: 40 euros.
- Pozole (traditional dish): 30 days expecting 15 people, entrance fee: 30 euros.
- Chiles en nogada: 60 days 15 people per day, entrance fee: 55 euros.
- Fiesta Mexicana: 1 day 30 persons, entrance fee: 30 euros.
- Feria del Maíz: 4 days Expected 30 persons per day, entrance fee: 40 euros.

Routes Oct-November

- Pan de muerto + chocolate: 20 days expecting 15 people per day, entrance fee: 25 euros.
- Mole poblano: 30 days expecting 15 people per day, entrance fee: 30 euros.
- Xantolo experience: 4 days expecting 30 people per day, entrance fee: 45 euros.

Routes December

- Ponche + bread: 20 days expecting 15 people per day that pay 25 euros.
- Posada (parties before Christmas): 14 days expecting 15 people that pay 35 euros.

The cost analysis for the first year, considering both variable and fixed costs, is illustrated in Figure 1. The fixed costs include rent, salaries for three employees and two managers, accountant fees, marketing agency

fees, and internet expenses. The variable costs encompass transportation for routes, participation in events, and utility services (electricity, water, etc.). As shown in the graphic, the highest cost is attributed to salaries, reflecting our commitment to prioritizing the quality of life for our employees.

Additionally, unique costs include technology (laptops) and the establishment of the enterprise. The variable cost of food preparation is calculated separately, as it fluctuates with the seasons. When combining the food costs with the direct costs of the enterprise, the total expected expense for the first year amounts to €349,298.00, with an anticipated profit of €18,092.00 (9%). These calculations are

based on an expectation of serving 5,180 tourists throughout the year.

As a social enterprise, our primary goal is to not profit maximization. Instead, we focus on enhancing the quality of life for the local community involved. To evaluate our goals, we will use measurable indicators such as free cash flow, the number of beneficiaries, customer service ratings, and revenue growth. As Contreras and Medina (2021) argue, the interest in food heritage from a tourism perspective is one of the most interesting signs of change in the tourism market. Therefore, the literature findings support the feasibility of our business project.

Figure 1. Principal Costs Analysis for the first year.

CONCLUSIONS

To reach an equitable distribution from economic tourism spillover among rural populations, it is important to consider the alliances that already exist in rural areas to connect with local actors. Up to this point, we have made the first contact with the NGO "Somos vía" located in the northern highlands of Puebla and with the traditional food researcher Irad Santacruz in Tlaxcala; these two places are in the center of Mexico and are key for the development of the proposed routes. One of the

most important points is participatory planning with the localities involved.

With the tools of PEST, SWOT, and Porter's Five Forces, a business plan was elaborated, that allows to have a first vision of the future and viability of the company. Although Mexico's tourism context is a great advantage, political volatility in terms of security is a major risk and some alternatives must be taken into consideration to reduce the impact of this risk.

Following the cost analysis, the need for an investment in the development of independent transport for the coming year was identified.

According to the cost, revenue, and profit analysis, our venture is economically viable.

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STRATEGIES FOR THE TOURISM DEVELOPMENT OF MOUNTAIN AREAS IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

In the development of mountain areas, and not only, we need to go through a series of stages, which ultimately lead to the creation of a resort or a tourist settlement, with all the necessary facilities to meet the tourists' needs. Therefore, any tourism development must offer optimal conditions for recreation, rest, and relaxation.

In Romania, most of the tourist developments in the mountain areas were made before 1990. Over the years, they were mostly modernized, representing a tourist attraction even on an international level, but others due to the lack of tourists, the way of organization and the degree of endowment, are in disrepair.

Keywords : agritourism, competitiveness, companies

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INTRODUCTION

The mountain areas in Romania are picturesque and meet the selection criteria regarding touristic facilities. As a result, the following aspects can be considered:

- natural conditions, namely relief, climate, hydrography, vegetation, fauna, nature reserves and monuments;
- cultural-historical heritage, with reference to art and culture monuments, ethnographic and folkloric heritage, historical vestiges;
- economic-social conditions, i.e. special emphasis is placed on avoiding the gap between the living conditions of tourists and those of residents (level of development, living conditions of the population);
- the general infrastructure and the level of equipment for culture and recreation, respectively the level of building facilities, starting with the road network and ending with the commercial network, and the level of equipment of the accommodation spaces, in order to meet the requirements of tourists;
- protection of the environment, with reference to creating a balance between the environment and the degree of tourist development.

In Romania, the first tourist development in a mountain area that resulted in the appearance of a mountain tourist resort was realized in Păltiniș, in 1894. After this date, the mountain resorts on

Valea Prahovei-Sinaia, Predeal, Cheia, Bușteni appeared and developed. We must specify the fact that these mountain resorts, despite their age, represent tourist attractions of great value, being attractive throughout the year.

When the Romanian mountain resorts appeared, a series of associations and societies played an important role in their tourist promotion. In the operating status of many of these we can find objectives such as: organizing mountain excursions, building and marking tourist roads and paths in the mountains, building shelters, publishing tourist monographs and editing tourist maps, conducting ski courses, etc.

The tourist facilities in the Romanian mountain areas continued, so we can mention the appearance of the famous mountain resorts Poiana Brașov, Borșa, Durău, Stâna de Vale, Azuga, Voineasa. Some of these, such as the Stâna de Vale resort, although it has a rich and varied natural heritage, lack facilities that would increase the comfort level of the accommodation spaces, and the leisure facilities are few.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The methods used in this study were different: the historical method, the comparative method, the sociological method, the logical method and the analytical one, their aim was the

systematic analysis of the information selected from the sources studied in order to develop personal points of view and conclusions about the stated objectives.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The tourist development of mountain areas is a complex process because it answers various questions related to the tourist circulation, the relationship between demand and supply, the degree of satisfaction of tourists, etc.

Each mountain tourism arrangement in Romania was realized according to a plan, respectively according to a strategy.

The development of mountain tourism strategies is carried out in accordance with a series of factors, among which we can mention: tourist resources and their degree of valorization, material, human, and financial resources related to tourism, short, medium, and long-term objectives, the capacity of accommodation facilities to meet the comfort level of tourists, and so on. As a result, tourism strategies must have the following objectives:

- superior capitalization of the mountain tourism potential;
- elimination of the seasonality of mountain tourist activities by equipping them with functional equipment all year round;
- increase in the number of tourists, especially foreigners;
- the practice of multi-purpose tourism in the designed space;
- protection and conservation of tourist attractions and the surrounding environment.

When developing a strategy for mountain tourism development, it is necessary to consider the favorable and unfavorable factors in the area to be developed. Among the multitude of factors taken into account, we can mention: the geographical location, the degree of accessibility determined by the existence of access roads, the relief and meteorological conditions, the picturesqueness of the natural landscape, the degree of humanization of the area, the socio-economic conditions, etc.

In the mountain area, the natural conditions are of particular importance because they

ensure the quality of recreational activities, especially in terms of practicing winter sports.

The tourist product of the mountain areas is the result of the association between the natural conditions, the quality of services, the degree of equipment and comfort, the pleasant and picturesque environment. As a result, the following elements are taken into account: accommodation and catering spaces and services, the ski area with its related facilities, the offer of additional services, environmental protection.

For Romanian mountain tourism, all the elements of the tourist product are important, but a more special sensitivity is presented by the skiing area with its related facilities. Thus, concerns are being considered for the expansion and development of the ski, toboggan, and bobsled slopes; the provision of means of cable transport; organization of winter sports courses. In the Carpathians on the territory of Romania, the ski area is found between 1000 and 1800 m altitude. Some mountain massifs such as Bucegi and Postăvaru have a more complex technical equipment, in others such as Semenic and Parâng, the degree of technical endowment is lower compared to the potential that these massifs hold.

The characteristics that a successful mountain tourism development, for example a resort, must have are:

- location in a space, or near one that presents tourist interest (lake, ski area);
- favorable climate;
- excellent access possibilities or with construction potential;
- the absence of ecological problems;
- the availability of labor to work in the resort or its attraction from other parts of the country;
- enough available land to enter the circuit of tourist facilities;
- the tourist facilities in the resort to give it a particular character;
- to establish connections between resorts and local communities.

According to statistical dates in my country, Romania, domestic tourism and urban territories dominate the sector. Domestic tourism contributed 88 percent of total tourists

and 70 percent of total spending in 2021. The percentage of international visitors declined by 5 percent from 2009 to 2019, indicating that the overall increase came from domestic tourists visiting the region in greater numbers. Urban territories generated 77 percent of the tourism turnover in 2018, and over half of certified travel agencies and tour operators are in urban centers. Tourism in Romania is facing a serious worker shortage, which has existed even before the pandemic due to low pay and structural issues. Tourism accounted for 6.7 percent of Romania's jobs in 2019, but this decreased to 6 percent in 2020 before recovering to 6.3 percent in 2021.

The Romanian Ministry of Entrepreneurship and Tourism reports a need for 50,000 more tourism workers due to the sustained increase in demand for employment in the sector.

The elaboration of the strategy for the development of mountain tourism in Romania must take into account a number of aspects that, first of all, attract a growing number of foreign tourists, taking into account the fact that on the territory of the European continent there are countries with a tradition of practicing mountain tourism and winter sports: Austria, Switzerland, France, Italy.

CONCLUSIONS

Romania, as a member of the European Union, has a number of opportunities, which it must be able to capitalize in order to become an attractive tourist destination.

Any model postulates the fact that the tourist destinations tend to experiment five distinct development stages: exploration, involvement, development, consolidation and stagnation. According to the reaction of the managers of the destination in stagnation, various scenarios are possible, including the decline, the stabilisation, the rejuvenating and the reinvention. Within the consolidation and the stagnation stages, the managers must intervene and act in order to avoid the unwanted decline of the respective tourist destination. That is why, it is very important to organise a Destination Management (DMO – Destination Management Organisation), whose stages of governance ensure the destination sustainability, too

The complexity of the landscaping actions, the variety of methods and techniques used involve a large number of specialists and institutions from various fields. The coordination of the development activity falls under the responsibility of some commercial companies and economic agents.

In order to promote Romanian mountain tourism, it is necessary to take measures to act both within the companies providing mountain tourism services and on the potential clients. The promotion of Romania as an internal and external tourist destination in the following years can be achieved

Mountain tourism development represents a particular form of national tourism development, the specificity elements being determined by the stay and movement of tourists, to which is added the management of resources that constitute tourist attractions.

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ANALYSIS OF THE EVOLUTION OF THE AGRICULTURAL MACHINERY AND EQUIPMENT PARK IN THE CONTEXT OF NRDP 2014-2020 AT THE LEVEL OF THE NORTH-WEST REGION, ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The contemporary agriculture requires an extensive use of technology and equipment as they are need for better performance. They are also highly expensive and one solution for their financing may be the use of European funds. For that purpose the NRDP 2014 – 2020 proved to be an intensive source of financing. One of the most successful regions from that aspects seems to be the North-West region. According to national statistics, it ranks 2nd nationally in the absorption of funds allocated to sub-measure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings, which is also evident from the increase in the number of agricultural machinery in the main categories.

Keywords: (max. 5) agricultural machines, NRDP 2014-2020, submeasure 4.1, North West Region

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INTRODUCTION

Romania, as a member state of the European Union starting with January 2007, benefited from non-reimbursable European funds within the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) is structured on two pillars: Pillar 1 that of the common market organizations and Pillar 2 that of rural development that presents the measures to be taken in regard with the development of rural areas. (Brinaru & Dona, 2015) In terms of financial and intervention tools, the Common Agricultural Policy remains to be the most significant EU policy that affects. (Oprea, I.A. and Gheorghe, E., 2023)

Romania benefited from non-reimbursable funds in the period 2007-2013 and 2014-2020 in the total amount of 16.14 billion euros in order to improve the living conditions in the rural area, respectively the development of the agricultural and non-agricultural activity sectors (Sebestien et al., 2023). Each time the financial allocations for cohesion policy and CAP came with a series of so-called “conditionalities” meant to guarantee the proper use of the EU funds. (Chereji et al, 2020). Therefore, Romania implements the PAC in compliance with all conditions.

NRDP 2014-2020 was adopted by the European Commission on May 26, 2015. It lays the foundations for the implementation of our country's priorities in terms of the use of 12.7 billion Euros, over a period of 9 years (2014-2020, plus the extension of 2 years, until 2022). (Chereji A, Chiurciu I, 2022)

The most requested funds in Romania were for the modernization of agricultural holdings through the purchase of high-performance machines and equipment. This support has brought significant changes to the national agricultural machinery fleet.

The modernization of agricultural farms has always been an important objective of the CAP, as modernization helps farmers to be economically competitive and use environmentally sustainable technologies. (Colf et al, 2023)

Regarding the financing of agricultural holdings in the period 2014-2020, they were financed under Measure 4 Investments in physical assets, submeasure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings. The final goal is to improve the overall performance of the agricultural holdings, increasing their competitiveness and added value of agricultural products by on-farm processing of products and their direct marketing in view to create and

promote integrated short chains. (Felici et al, 2018).

The North- West region has in its composition the following counties: Bihor; Bistrita-Nasaud; Cluj; Maramures Satu Mare and Sălaj. The North-West region has an area of 34,160 km², which represents 14.3% of the total territory of Romania, occupying the 4th place nationally. (Soare et el, 2020). Of the total area of the region, about 60% was used in agriculture.

The purpose of the paper was to analyse the evolution of the agricultural machinery and equipment park in the North-West region during 2014-2020, analysis carried out in conjunction with the funds allocated to measure 4 Investments in fixed assets, respectively sub-measure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings. Measure 4 was the measure with the largest allocation in the 2014-2020 PNDR framework with a nominal value of 3.6 billion euros.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the purposes of this paper we have extensively used the quantitative method. Also the desktop research method was used as we have proceeded to the analysis of specialized literature - field of interest in the use of funds from Pillar II of the Rural Development PAC

We used the Tempo Online database of the National Institute of Statistics to analyse the evolution of the park of agricultural machinery and equipment at the national level, respectively at the level of the North West Region, the region that is the subject of this study.

At the same time, we analysed the annual progress reports of the 2014-2020 NRDP implementation to highlight the use of the funds allocated for the modernization of agricultural holdings through the purchase of high-performance agricultural machinery and equipment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Technical equipment of agriculture is one of the essential elements in capitalizing on the potential existing in this sector, implicitly, in ensuring the food security of the country's population. The level of the factors of production represents the decisive element in the development of the production processes in agriculture. (Bădan et al, 2017)

In terms of the highest inflows, most of the money in the period 2014-2020, for submeasure 4.1, was attracted by the South-East Development Region with approximately 227 million euros attracted, followed by the North-West Development Region with 169 million euros attracted. (Curea, I.C. and Fîntîneru, G..2021).

The purpose of the investments supported under sub-measure 4.1 related to NRDP 2014-2020, respectively the transition period, is to support investments to increase the competitiveness of agricultural holdings by equipping them with high-performance machinery and equipment in relation to the current agricultural structure. (AFIR)

Of the 3,416,046 ha representing the total area of the North West Region, approximately 2,079,500 ha (60.8%) were in 2014 intended for agriculture (arable land; pastures and hayfields; fruit growing and viticulture). According to the Development Plan of the North-West Region 2021-2027, the counties that have the largest share of the agricultural area used in the total area are:

- ✓ Satu Mare (71,9),
- ✓ Cluj (64,9%) și
- ✓ Bihor (64,6%), while
- ✓ Maramureș (48,5%) and
- ✓ Bistrița Năsăud (55,6%) have lower ratios.)

Figure 1 Map of Romania - Development Regions
Source: The-8-agencies-for-regional-development-in-Romania-have-become-management-authorities-for-regional-operational-programs

Starting from the fact that in the North West region, 50% of its surface is used in agriculture, we considered it appropriate to highlight the situation of the agricultural machinery and equipment park. It is known that any applicant, when submitting a financing request for approval, has as a main condition the sizing of the agricultural holding and the

purchase of agricultural machinery to be carried out in relation to this very important sizing. So, once the agricultural holding has been correctly dimensioned and placed in a certain category of farm (small, medium, large), the justification of the purchase of equipment is requested in relation to the area owned, the crop plan as well as the economic size of the farm.

It can be seen from table no. 1 that there are substantial increases in a certain category of agricultural equipment and machinery, but also decreases in their number in 2022 compared to the reference number 2014. We extracted and processed this data precisely to observe what changes the agricultural machinery park has undergone.

Thus, in 2022, at the national level there was an increase in the number of physical agricultural tractors by 51,675 heads, and at the level of the North West region, this increase was represented by 15,911 heads per tractor, the increase at the level of the North West region being 21.25% of the total growth at the national level. We can thus conclude that there was a very high demand for the purchase of tractors, as a necessity for carrying out the activity at the farm level.

A numerical increase was also registered by plows for tractors, where in 2022 there were 162,000 pieces, compared to 156,964 in 2014. The increase in the number of plows by 5,036 pieces also represents the increase in interest in completing the equipment parks and agricultural equipment at farm level in order to carry out agricultural works on time. Out of the total of 5,036 tractor plows as a difference in 2022 compared to 2014, the Northwest Region owns 4,010 trailed plows, which represents a very high percentage, about 80%.

In 2022, the number of hay balers increased to 19,966 from 10,871 in 2014, which represents an increase of 9,045 pieces of equipment. At the level of the North West region, this increase was highlighted by a number of 2,884 pieces at the level of 2022 in addition compared to the year 2014.

In addition to the increasing trend recorded by machines such as agricultural tractors, tractor plows, balers for straw and hay, there were also significant decreases in the number of mechanical seeders, mechanical cultivators both nationally and regionally Northwest. For a single category of agricultural equipment, at the level of the North West Region for the year 2022, compared to the year 2014, there was a decrease of 853 pieces of self-

propelled combines for grain harvesting, even if at the level of the country their number had a numerical increase of 724 pieces of equipment.

Where there are numerical decreases, they can be attributed to the scrapping of the respective equipment or the appearance of other equipment that can take over the agricultural work carried out by them.

At the regional level, there was a particular interest in accessing non-reimbursable European funds within the PNDR 2014-2020. Farmers showed a special interest in the development of the equipment park, which was highlighted by the large number of projects financed at the level of the North West region. A special interest was shown by the large farmers, they purchased equipment and machinery that would lead to an increase in productivity at the farm level, by carrying out agricultural works at the right times.

At the same time, the purchase of high-performance equipment for agricultural holdings was a necessity for them, precisely to cope with the technical progress that this type of equipment has undergone.

It is important to underline the fact that, at the level of submeasure 4.1 which financed the purchase of agricultural equipment and machinery, the support for this type of investment was broken down by the other types of investments, which was achieved towards the end of the programming period precisely because of the very strong interest shown by the potential beneficiaries.

Thus in accordance with the Applicant's Guide related to priority P 4.1.1 - Simple purchases of agricultural machinery, at the farm level (vegetable) - the applicant to receive financing must follow the Extension and/or modernization of vegetable and mixed farms (for all vegetable crops, including forage related to the farm livestock) through the purchase of agricultural machinery. (The Applicant's Guide, 2024).

Thus, for the last session of receiving projects related to the funds allocated to the financial period 2014-2020, session held in 2024, those projects that provide for the purchase of agricultural machinery that contribute to the fulfilment of the environmental and climate conditions applicable to farmers in the context of PS PAC 2023-2027 are financed (no tillage, minimum/low tillage, strip tillage machines).

Conservative farming practices in terms of tillage (no tillage, strip tillage or minimum tillage) are based on the following elements:

- ✓ Sown without prior soil preparation (no tillage);
- ✓ Sown in prepared strips without intervention on the interval between the rows (strip tillage);
- ✓ Sown after a superficial preparation of the soil, without turning the furrow (minimum tillage).
- ✓ A new criterion in scoring investments was given to projects that exclusively provide

for the purchase of equipment/machinery specific to no till/minim/low/strip till technology that are directly related to land preparation, such as seeders, disc harrows, discs, cultivators, scarifiers, shredders of plant residues and others, as well as the projects in which the purchase of a tractor is foreseen together with at least one technology-specific equipment/equipment. (The Applicant's Guide, 2024)

Table 1

The park of tractors and main agricultural machines in agriculture at the level of the country and the North West region

Categories of tractors and agricultural machines	Total/North West Region	Years									2022-2014
		Year 2014	Year 2015	Year 2016	Year 2017	Year 2018	Year 2019	Year 2020	Year 2021	Year 2022	
		UM: Number									
		Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number	Number
Physical agricultural tractors	TOTAL	193120	199284	207901	212730	215980	221677	232654	237273	244795	51675
-	NORTH-WEST region	36117	38658	39455	42914	43972	44343	46192	49165	52028	15911
Tractor plows	TOTAL	156964	159334	168617	169647	169964	163547	160338	159266	162000	5.036
-	NORTH-WEST region	30027	30539	30798	33046	33472	31664	31643	31932	34037	4010
Mechanical cultivators	TOTAL	29562	30355	30632	29648	29337	28545	33753	26872	25072	-4490
-	NORTH-WEST region	3140	3217	3234	3388	3669	3201	3201	3349	2693	-447
Mechanical seed drills	TOTAL	76301	77560	81255	80038	78612	74221	73981	69746	69706	-6595
-	NORTH-WEST region	9435	9576	9565	10079	10436	9383	9778	9900	9133	-302
Spraying and dusting machines with mechanical traction	TOTAL	5315	5607	5327	5494	5709	5990	5048	5026	4759	-556
-	NORTH-WEST region	506	539	538	509	572	592	563	590	415	-91
Self-propelled combines for grain harvesting	TOTAL	25694	27485	26923	26690	27464	27632	26802	26657	26418	724
-	NORTH-WEST region	4461	4591	4100	4047	4200	4015	4116	4356	3608	-853
Self-propelled combines for	TOTAL	868	891	985	1069	1104	1018	1050	1200	1143	275

harvesting fodder											
-	NORTH-WEST region	175	166	169	197	231	175	187	236	136	-39
Combines and machines for harvesting potatoes	TOTAL	5122	5403	5629	5924	6108	5856	6177	6183	5392	270
-	NORTH-WEST region	250	483	595	683	898	954	1011	1096	893	643
Presses for baling straw and hay	TOTAL	10871	11966	13840	14166	14697	15483	16671	19041	19916	9045
-	NORTH-WEST region	1735	1798	2209	2793	3102	3420	3813	4481	4619	2884
Windrowers for fodder	TOTAL	1217	1254	1327	1375	1399	1356	1268	1265	1210	-7
-	NORTH-WEST region	96	95	99	114	142	157	135	133	113	17

Source: TempoOnline's own processing

Table 2 Stage of Implementation of submeasure 4.1 on 25.04.2024

Submeasure	NRDP public allocation 2014-2020 v.17.0 euro	Funding applications submitted		Selected funding applications		% Requests selected from submitted requests	% Value of selected projects from the submitted value
		No.	Euro value	No.	Euro value	%	%
<i>Submeasure 4.1 "Investments in agricultural holdings"</i>	1.599.574.056	6.147	3.329.637.201	3.265	1.811.675.642	53	54

Source: Own processing according to the Status of projects submitted on April 25, 2024 - NRDP 2014-2020

Regarding the situation of the projects submitted for financing under sub-measure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings, for the financial allocation related to the period 2014-2020, it can be seen from table 2 that the value allocated was approximately 1.6 billion euros in order to modernize and establish the holdings agricultural. The interest was particularly high, so that a number of 6,147 funding applications were submitted, of which 3,265 funding applications were selected for funding, which represents 53% of the total funding applications submitted. Following the analysis of the value of the selected funding requests, it is observed that it is higher than the one allocated according to version 17 of the PNDR 2014-2020, a fact that highlights that the allocated funds were supplemented for those projects that were

scored with the same score - so that they all had to be financed.

The North West region, according to national statistics, ranks 2nd nationally in the absorption of funds allocated to sub-measure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings, which is also evident from the increase in the number of agricultural machinery in the main categories.

CONCLUSIONS

The above mentioned data have shown a series of important results. Among them are issues such:

- ✓ The financing of purchasing of agricultural equipment matters as it is costly.
- ✓ There is an increase interest amidst the ranks of farmers for such purchases.

- ✓ There are differences among regions in regards to this topic.

Within the NRDP 2014-2020, through sub-measure 4.1 Investments in agricultural holdings, a number of 3/265 of the funding requests were selected for financing, which implies that at national level either farms were modernized or established farms that currently have agricultural machines and state-of-the-art equipment, equipment that meets the current needs of farmers but also from the point of view of protecting the environment.

The North West region has a park of agricultural machinery that underwent changes during the analyzed period, so that the increases on certain types of agricultural equipment, respective machinery are in accordance with those at the national level. The agricultural area of the region is generous, so the North West Region ranks second nationally in terms of the absorption of funds from the NRDP 2014-2020 for investments in agricultural holdings.

It is of interest to follow the evolution of the agricultural machinery park during the current financing period of the Strategic Plan PAC 2023-2027 both at the national and regional level.

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GARNDMA'S TASTE

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

"Grandma's Taste" is an idea of a social enterprise dedicated to promoting local cuisine and empowering local grandmas. Through a combination of events, a user-friendly website, and a mobile application, the project aims to celebrate the rich culinary heritage of communities while providing economic opportunities for elderly women. The platform serves as a digital marketplace where grandmas can showcase their traditional recipes, connecting them with consumers eager to experience authentic, home-cooked meals. Events hosted by "Grandma's Taste" provide an immersive culinary experience, allowing participants to engage with grandmas, and learn about regional ingredients, cooking techniques, and cultural traditions. By fostering intergenerational connections and supporting local food artisans, "Grandma's Taste" not only preserves culinary traditions but also promotes social inclusion and economic empowerment within communities.

Keywords: social enterprise, empowering elderly people, Start-up and Traditional Food Recipes

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INTRODUCTION

For both physical and emotional health, food is essential. For some, it's not simply a crucial component of survival; for others, it's a significant factor that can transform an otherwise serious attitude into a lighthearted one. After a demanding workday or long day, individuals want to unwind with food and relaxation at home. Takeout is undoubtedly quick and tasty, but cooking a dinner at home is more satisfying and has a unique flavor. For a novice, it can be challenging to locate a reliable cooking education resource. For this reason, we came up with the concept of a cooking recipe app that gives users detailed instructions to make dinner preparation less stressful (Mane *et al.*, 2018)

A major strategy to improve competitiveness and sustainability through new value propositions and business management techniques has been proposed: business model innovation. This is because the food sector is experiencing profound changes and growing competition. Despite this, the food industry shows little interest in business models, particularly sustainable business models. (Franceschelli *et al.*, 2018).

The revolution in mobile technology has had a tremendous impact on human activities in

daily life. With 3.48 million mobile applications available for download in the Google Play Store and 2.22 million in the App Store for iOS users, these statistics are based on the year 2021 (Statista, 2022). This also holds true for cooking, as the majority of people believe that looking up recipes online is more convenient than using cookbooks. (Anaya *et al.*, 2016).

The cooking trend has shifted to a new idea called the "digital kitchen," where 59 percent of millennials, or people in the 25–34 age range, cook while having tablets or smartphones by their sides showing the culinary process of cooking a dish. This is according to research by McGarry Bowen and Kraft Foods, which was reported in an article by Cooper (2021). Thus, the advancement of mobile technology has changed people's attitudes toward cooking.

Both management and investors typically understand their respective goals, the options that are accessible to them, and what has to be done in order to reach an agreement when established enterprises look to the outside world for funding for research or new product development, and when investors look for chances for financial returns. They both recognize the importance of meticulous planning for every facet of developing a new product, including market research, marketing

strategies, hiring the right personnel, building the necessary facilities, securing funding, managing cash flow, and more. The world of seed money is not very organized. At this point, investors and entrepreneurs frequently have differing expectations regarding the steps necessary for a successful discussion. Of course, there is some overlap, but neither party understands the guidelines for coming to a mutually agreeable agreement (Rhea, 1989).

Customary cuisine reflects history and culture, and way of life. As observed by (Slimani *et al.*, 2002), there are differences in eating trends throughout countries even though we live in a globalized society. An essential way to understand dietary patterns and how they have changed throughout time is to research traditional foods. Customary diets and lifestyle choices may provide health benefits that have, crucially, been well investigated over time (Trichopoulou *et al.*, 2007)

Objectives

1. To create a recipe-sharing Platform for Traditional Food Products

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research conducted for "Grandma's Taste" aimed to assess the impact of traditional homemade cuisine on consumer preferences and social engagement. The study employed a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection techniques to provide comprehensive insights into the effectiveness of the "Grandma's Taste" concept.

Porter's five forces concept, which includes competition between current competitors, threat from new entrants, power from suppliers and purchasers, and substitute goods and services, is predicated on the idea that an organizational strategy should take advantage of opportunities and guard against risks in the external environment of the firm. A competitive strategy ought to be based on knowledge of industry structures and how they evolve (Brujil, 2018).

Porter 5 force Model was used to have a critical and analytical idea of the business

1. Competitive Rivalry
2. Supply power
3. Buyer Power
4. Threat of Substitution
5. Threat of new Entry

SWOT Analysis was also used to study this business idea. A SWOT analysis assesses the possibilities and risks that are external to a business as well as its internal strengths and weaknesses. The organization's internal resources, competencies, and competitive advantages are determined through internal analysis. The external analysis looks at the resources of rivals, the industry environment, and the overall environment to find market possibilities and risks. Using an organization's knowledge of its internal and external environments to inform strategy formulation is the aim of a SWOT analysis (Sammut-Bonnici *et al.*, 2015).

The following are the main drivers of globalization that have an immediate effect on SMEs: moving to the tertiary economy (an economy centered on services); altering the significance of location in conducting business (geographic and economic flexibility); and the creation and fusion of novel technologies. When faced with fierce competition in the local market, small and medium-sized businesses have two options: either they expand internationally (actual internationalization) on their own or through partnerships and collaboration with other businesses that share their interests, or they "internationalize" domestically by joining a network of businesses with an international dimension through various forms of outsourcing, such as production-on-order, subcontracting, etc. Despite holding a disproportionate amount of the market in international business, small and medium-sized businesses are currently among the most dynamic parts of industrialization (Belu., 2016)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The results of the "Grandma's Taste" research project provide comprehensive insights into the impact of traditional homemade cuisine on consumer preferences and social engagement. This section presents the findings of our extensive research, detailing how traditional recipes prepared by grandmas resonate with diverse consumer demographics. We explore how these culinary experiences foster stronger community ties and enhance social inclusion.

Supplier Power

This force is high because our suppliers are fewer and they can exploit the company as the company does not have any other

replacements. Suppliers have significant powers and they can squeeze the profit.

Threat of Substitution

This force is high because, our customers like tourists and students can go to the local restaurants and hotels and can try the local dish there, despite making it by themselves. That would be more convenient for them in terms of TIME.

Buyer Power

This force is low because there is an element of sympathy attached to it, there is an emotional factor in the buyers' mind that they are contributing towards the financial independence of Elderly people.

Threat of New Entry

This force is low because the targeted audience is a niche market like students and Tourists.

Despite the comprehensive nature of the "Grandma's Taste" research project, it is important to acknowledge that the study was primarily theoretical due to certain limitations. Our research largely depended on secondary data sources, literature reviews, and hypothetical models because we did not have direct access to the target demographic groups for extensive fieldwork.

The SWOT analysis of the "Grandma's Taste" initiative (Table 1) reveals several key strengths, including the authenticity of the culinary experiences offered, extensive knowledge of social media, high social value, and access to various funding sources. The use of digital platforms, such as a website and mobile app, to share traditional recipes also stands out as a significant strength. However, the project faces weaknesses such as a lack of financial stability, the need for initial capital, dependency on seasonal availability, and potential challenges in maintaining consistent quality across different regions.

Opportunities for "Grandma's Taste" include organizing thematic events like culinary workshops, collaborating with local travel agencies and guides, and developing signature products based on popular recipes to commercialize. Additionally, the growing consumer demand for ethically sourced products presents a favorable market condition.

On the other hand, the project must navigate threats such as intense competition, the need to comply with legal requirements, market fluctuations, balancing social impact with financial objectives, and various regulatory challenges.

The project significantly contributes to preserving cultural heritage by promoting traditional homemade cuisine. This preservation of culinary traditions serves not only to maintain a connection to past generations but also to educate younger demographics about the rich cultural tapestry of their heritage. By involving grandmas in the preparation and sharing of traditional recipes, the project facilitates intergenerational bonding, fostering a sense of community and continuity.

Furthermore, the initiative enhances social engagement by providing a platform for social interaction. Community members who participate in the culinary workshops and events experience a sense of belonging and inclusion, which can be particularly beneficial in combating social isolation among the elderly. The emphasis on sharing meals prepared from cherished family recipes creates opportunities for storytelling and cultural exchange, enriching the social fabric of the communities involved.

Despite these positive impacts, the project must address certain challenges to maximize its social and economic contributions. Ensuring consistent quality and authenticity across different regions is crucial to maintaining the project's credibility and consumer trust. Additionally, balancing the social objectives with financial sustainability requires careful planning and management to avoid compromising the project's core values.

In conclusion, the "Grandma's Taste" initiative exemplifies how traditional homemade cuisine can serve as a powerful tool for social engagement, cultural preservation, and economic development. By leveraging digital platforms and community events, the project successfully bridges generational gaps and enhances social cohesion. Moving forward, addressing the identified challenges will be essential in sustaining and expanding the positive impact of this innovative project

Table 1. SWOT Analysis for company Grandma's Taste

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - authenticity - knowledge of social media - high social value - access to various funding sources - digital platforms (website and app) to share traditional recipes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - lack of financial stability - initial capital for the business - depending on the seasons - potential challenges to maintain consistent quality across different regions
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organization of other thematic events, e.g. culinary workshops - cooperation with local travel agencies and guides - exploring opportunities to develop and commercialize signature products based on popular recipes - growing consumer awareness and demand for ethically sourced products 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - competition: wider knowledge about market - compliance with all legal requirements - market fluctuations - balancing social impact goals with financial objectives - regulatory challenges

Competitive Rivalry

This force is high as the competitors can go for aggressive price cuts and if they offered authenticity and originality in their recipes

CONCLUSIONS

The idea of creating a Recipe sharing platform and then optimize its output by the use of technology. A website, Android and IOS Mobile Application and Physical presences in the market by doing a partnership with travel agencies. Main targeted audience is international tourists and students coming into Romania. The Business has a potential to expand in the future in other European countries. The online platforms can also be used for E-commerce like buying and selling of cooking utensils. The social impact of this start-up idea is to engage the elderly people by getting recipes of Traditional food products, this way they can have an additional source of income. The business idea is mainly revolves in the niche market segment. SWOT Analysis and 5 Porter forces was conducted to check the feasibility of this business idea in the real world. Forces like Supplier Power, competitive rivalry and threat of substitution is high but Buyer power and threat of new entry is low.

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MONITORING OF DIFFERENT CULTIVATED AND NATURAL GRASSLAND SOILS BASED ON SOME MICROBIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN EASTERN HUNGARY

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REVIEW

Abstract

The monitoring of intensively farmed areas and soils is a very important task. In our comparative study, we were examined three different soil types with different cultures based on some microbial properties in the Eastern Hungary region (2019-2021). The moisture content of the soil samples was during the three years average 10-19%. We observed that during the three consecutive years the moisture content in soils decreased. The highest activity of saccharase (SA) ($7.21 \text{ mg glucose } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} 24\text{h}^{-1}$), urease (UA) ($65.34 \text{ NH}_4^+ \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$), and dehydrogenase activity (DA) ($219.55 \mu\text{g INTF g}^{-1} 2\text{h}^{-1}$) was in solonetz soil, which natural uncultivated, pasture. The phosphatase activity (PA) ($14.84 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$) was higher in the chernozem soil, it was almost the same for sand ($6.47 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$) and grass ($6.69 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$). The CO_2 production was 18.44 on the chernozem, 15.65 on the humus sand, and 19.11 $\text{mg } 100\text{g}^{-1} 7 \text{ days}^{-1}$ on the solonetz soil. Grasslands create a specific environment for the organisms that live in them. The large root masses of grass provide an important source of organic matter for micro-organisms. The enzymes activities and the CO_2 production were also more intensive on undisturbed pasture soil utilization natural grassland than in soils under intensive cultivations.

Keywords: soil enzymes, CO_2 production, chernozem, sandy soil, grassland

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INTRODUCTION

The quality of the agricultural land has been decreasing due to the intensive farming (Eswaran et. al, 2001; FAO, 2015; Panagos et. al, 2018a).

This is the reason that we choose three different cultivation forms to measure some microbiological parameters of soils of Hajdú-Bihar County. Two of the soils were cultivated – with fruit orchard and wheat – the third one was a natural grassland; they had different soil types. Soils were mainly analysed about soil enzymes activity.

Several studies have shown that soil enzymes are not suitable for total characterising the biological activity of soils (Doran & Zeiss, 2000; Niemeyer et. al. 2012), but soil enzymes are constantly playing vital roles for the maintenance of soil ecology and soil health (Acosta-Martínez & Tabatai, 2000). Enzymes activity is a good indicator of changes of organic matter content, as they provide information about soil microbiological status and physico-

chemical conditions (Chu et al, 2020; Jaskulak, & Grobelak, 2020; Fannin et. al, 2022).

These enzymatic activities in the soil are mainly of microbial origin, being derived from intracellular, cell-associated or free enzymes. Therefore, microorganisms are acting as the indicators of soil health, as they have active effects on nutritional cycling, also affecting the physical and chemical properties of soil. The potential enzymes playing major roles in maintaining soil health according to Shonkor Kumar & Ajit Varma, 2010 are the following – amylase, arylsulphatase, β -glucosidase, cellulase, chitinase, dehydrogenase, phosphatase, protease, and urease.

Another, very important microbiological indicator in soil is CO_2 production (Biró et al. 2018). According to Kong et al. (2013a) research, land use has a significant effect on the cumulative CO_2 productions in soil. Larger amount of gases was emitted by horticultural plant – apple, orchard - compared to grassland or forest soils.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The examined three soil types were about some microbial parameters (1) Calcareous Chernozem (*Chernozems*) with corn (*Triticum aestivum L.*) from Debrecen-Látókép - $\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}=6.8$; (2) Humus sandy soil (*Arenosols*) from Debrecen - Pallag - $\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}=5.8$, with fruit (*Prunus cerasus L.*) – and (3) Solonetz soil (*Solonetz*) with grassland Hajdúnánás – Tedej, $\text{pH}_{(\text{H}_2\text{O})}=6.6$.

Soil samples were taken during 3 years (2019-2021), in the spring (in the month of May) and in the autumn (in the month of September), from the top 20 cm – the most active – layer of the soil. The areas have received only natural rainfall.

Moisture content was measured by drying the soil at 105°C for 24h (Buzás, 1988).

The CO_2 -production was measured after 7 days' incubation with NaOH-trapping (Öhlinger, 1996). The quantitative determination of monosaccharides originated from the breakdown of saccharase (SA) according to Frankenberger és Johanson (1983) was measured. Measurement of urease activity (UA) (Kempers cit. Filep, 1995) was done based on the quantitative determination of ammonia; the phosphatase activity (PA) (Öhlinger, 1996) was

measured about the quantity of hydrolyzed phosphorus acid, and the dehydrogenase activity (DHA) was determined, where the soil samples were mixed with INT-solution, incubated 2h at 40 °C (Mersi, 1996).

The results of the examination were subjected to one-way ANOVA by using Eisenhauer et al. (2012) and IBM SPSS Version 28.0. Means were compared by Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1955) at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The moisture content of the soil samples was average in the soils during the three years 11-19%. (Figure 1). The lowest value was found in Pallag sand (10.47%), while the highest value was measured in the chernozem soil (18.78%). We also observed that during the three consecutive years the moisture content in the soil decreased in all three areas, to a lesser extent in the chernozem (19.28-17.80%) and the solonetz soil (12.64-11.21%), at the same time, in the area of sand to a larger extent (12.61-9.22%) in the orchard. This is probably related to the fact that sandy soils are poor in colloids and have a low water holding capacity.

Figure 1 Moisture contents of examined soils in Eastern Hungary region (2019-2021)

The highest SA ($7.21 \text{ mg glucose } 100 \text{ g}^{-1} 24\text{h}^{-1}$), UA ($65.34 \text{ NH}_4^+ \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$), and DHA ($219.55 \text{ } \mu\text{g INTF } \text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}^{-1}$) was in Solonetz soil, which is a natural uncultivated, pasture. The PA

($14.84 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$) was higher in the chernozem soil, it was almost the same for sand ($6.47 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$) and grass ($6.69 \text{ P}_2\text{O}_5 \text{ mg}^{-1} 100\text{g}^{-1} 2\text{h}$) (Table 1).

Table 1 Enzyme activities and CO₂ production of examined soils in Eastern Hungary region (2019-2021)

Date of soil sampling	Soil type and seasonality	SA (glucose mg·100g ⁻¹ ·24h ⁻¹)	PA (P ₂ O ₅ mg·100g ⁻¹ ·2h ⁻¹)	UA (NH ₄ -N mg·100g ⁻¹ ·2h ⁻¹)	DHA activity (INTF µg·g ⁻¹ ·2h ⁻¹)	CO ₂ emission (mg·100g ⁻¹ ·10 days ⁻¹)
Chernozem with wheat						
2019.	spring	5.12ef ^{±0.75}	14.29de ^{±1.69}	42.12e ^{±4.05}	129.93d ^{±11.54}	16.94cdefg ^{±2.04}
	autumn	5.17ef ^{±0.68}	14.27de ^{±0.63}	33.99cd ^{±2.92}	134.64d ^{±12.62}	22.03ij ^{±2.49}
2020.	spring	6.38gh ^{±0.63}	16.85f ^{±1.80}	39.95de ^{±4.73}	129.88d ^{±13.00}	24.42j ^{±3.60}
	autumn	4.70de ^{±1.13}	15.63ef ^{±0.25}	31.38c ^{±3.49}	137.72d ^{±10.25}	22.96ij ^{±2.44}
2021.	spring	6.87ghi ^{±0.41}	14.55de ^{±0.58}	37.27d ^{±0.57}	109.49c ^{±0.72}	12.55ab ^{±0.33}
	autumn	3.87cd ^{±0.11}	13.47d ^{±0.87}	39.55de ^{±2.13}	119.45cd ^{±1.91}	11.72a ^{±0.22}
	Average	5.35	14.84	37.38	126.85	18.44
Arenosols with cherry						
2019.	spring	3.61bcd ^{±0.59}	7.87bc ^{±3.19}	21.02ab ^{±3.42}	66.71ab ^{±9.33}	13.72abc ^{±2.62}
	autumn	2.90abc ^{±0.69}	5.96ab ^{±0.24}	18.06ab ^{±1.99}	77.58ab ^{±18.59}	15.03bcd ^{±3.16}
2020.	spring	4.34de ^{±0.89}	6.23ab ^{±0.37}	21.78ab ^{±2.45}	57.90a ^{±10.38}	17.08defg ^{±1.20}
	autumn	2.56ab ^{±0.49}	6.06ab ^{±0.20}	14.66a ^{±1.93}	85.53b ^{±18.18}	17.68defg ^{±1.91}
2021.	spring	2.34a ^{±0.45}	6.38abc ^{±0.22}	22.76b ^{±3.45}	69.53ab ^{±1.66}	15.82cde ^{±0.43}
	autumn	2.42a ^{±1.03}	6.35abc ^{±0.40}	14.87a ^{±2.86}	77.35ab ^{±5.85}	14.54abcd ^{±0.74}
	Average	3.03	6.47	18.86	72.43	15.65
Solonetz with grassland						
2019.	spring	7.59i ^{±0.96}	8.22c ^{±0.89}	72.22h ^{±4.78}	161.50e ^{±17.26}	16.38cdef ^{±2.14}
	autumn	6.49gh ^{±0.67}	5.72a ^{±1.19}	56.37fg ^{±5.13}	274.08g ^{±21.01}	21.02hij ^{±1.07}
2020.	spring	9.46j ^{±1.40}	7.18abc ^{±0.92}	73.29h ^{±14.20}	183.55f ^{±19.36}	20.16ghij ^{±3.79}
	autumn	7.17hi ^{±0.57}	5.92ab ^{±0.16}	53.05f ^{±6.97}	342.18h ^{±20.04}	18.86efgh ^{±2.00}
2021.	spring	6.73ghi ^{±0.50}	6.86abc ^{±1.92}	76.74h ^{±0.05}	169.41ef ^{±4.43}	19.55fghi ^{±0.33}
	autumn	5.86fg ^{±0.11}	6.26ab ^{±0.10}	60.35g ^{±3.04}	186.58f ^{±5.84}	18.72efgh ^{±0.22}
	Average	7.21	6.69	65.34	219.55	19.11

The CO₂ production of the soils was 18.44 on the chernozem soil, 15.65 on the humus sand soil, and 19.11 mg 100g⁻¹ 7 days⁻¹ on the solonetz soil (Figure 2).

Regarding the seasonality, the SA and PA was not significantly higher, while the activity of

UA was significantly higher in spring. DHA showed higher activity in autumn, while soil CO₂ production was also in an unprovable way higher in autumn than in spring (Table 1; Figure 2).

Figure 2 CO₂ emission of examined soils in Eastern Hungary region (2019-2021)

CONCLUSIONS

The long-term monitoring of our soils is a very important task in order to be informed about the condition of our soils. Protecting our soils and studying the impact of human activity on soils is also very important.

Grasslands create a specific environment for the organisms that live in them. The large root masses of grass provide an important source of organic matter for micro-organisms.

According this study, the measured enzyme activities ((saccharase (SA); urease (UA); dehydrogenase (DHA)) and the CO₂ production were also more intensive on undisturbed pasture soil utilization natural grassland than in soils under intensive cultivations.

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LEGAL REGULATIONS REGARDING THE BILL OF EXCHANGE

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REVIEW, RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The bill of exchange is a trade effect, representing a short-term credit security, whereby the issuer, as the debtor, undertakes to pay unconditionally or to order the payment of a sum of money to the creditor, as the holder or at his order, on a certain date or at the submission of the document. [1] the paper on bills of exchange in commercial law explores a crucial aspect of financial and commercial infrastructure, highlighting the role and importance of this instrument in facilitating and securing commercial transactions. A bill of exchange is defined as a transferable security which gives its holder the right to claim payment of a sum of money on a specified date and place. In the paper, we investigated the history of bill of exchange and its evolution in the context of the business environment, from its origins in antiquity to the present day. We have also looked at the legal aspects and regulations governing the use of bill of exchange. We have examined the details of the issuance, movement, acceptance and payment of bills of exchange, as well as the responsibilities of the parties involved in a commercial transaction involving the use of this instrument. During the report, I stressed the importance of rigorous compliance with the legal and commercial rules and procedures associated with bills of exchange, in order to avoid potential difficulties and litigation. We highlighted the need for an adequate understanding of the mechanisms and implications of the use of bills of exchange, both for legal professionals and for actors involved in commercial transactions. It is stressed that trade bills remain an essential and valuable financial instrument in today's business environment, helping to build trust and stability in trade transactions, both locally and internationally.

Keywords: law, bill of exchange, shooter, payee, payment

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INTRODUCTION

Payment using bills of exchange is among the oldest payment techniques, offering a high degree of security to the parties involved. The determinants that led to the creation of the bill of exchange were:

- (a) the high density of coins;
- (b) uncertainty of transport;
- c) prohibition of capital export. [2]

The issue, circulation, exchange negotiations are related both to the activity in the field of international exchange relays and to a series of non-commercial operations, executed by natural or legal persons. [2]

The bill of exchange is one of the oldest payment instruments used in domestic and international commercial activity, which in various forms and with some functional changes is still used today. Historically, bill of exchange appeared in China from 500 to 600, then expanded to Italy. Trade between the far East and Europe was mediated by Arabs and Italians, and bills of exchange became an international payment instrument for traders. The improvement of the bill of exchange led to

the appearance of the paper bill in 1600, which is basically still a cambie, but a bank bill. In our country, the first written information about the trade effects dates from the beginning of the 18th century, the bill of exchange being called "the police". Internationally, bills of exchange are governed by the "Convention containing the uniform Law on bills of exchange and promissory notes" and the "Convention intended to regulate certain conflicts of law in matters of bills of exchange and promissory notes", both of 7 June 1930 in Geneva. In our country, the bill of exchange is regulated by Law no. 58/1934 on bills of exchange and promissory note, amended by Law no. 83/1994 and by some regulations and norms issued by the National Bank of Romania.[3]

The term cambie comes from an Italian word, cambio, which means exchange. This appears normal, as Italy was at that time the country with the most developed commercial activity and the place where the first commercial banks appeared.[3]

Due to its widespread use in international trade relations, the bill of exchange was subject to a unitary legal regulation. In 1930, the

convention on uniform law of bills of exchange and promissory notes was concluded in Geneva. [4]

Although Romania did not accede to this convention, most provisions of the uniform law were taken over in the Romanian law. Indeed, Act No 58 of 1 May 1934 on bills of exchange and promissory notes' used as a model the Italian law on bills of exchange and promissory notes of 14 December 1933, which was based on the uniform law on bills of exchange and promissory notes. [4]

In the context of the formation of the market economy in our country, some measures have been taken on the use of bill of exchange in domestic trade relations. [4]

Thus, by O.G. no. 11/1993 there were brought some amendments and additions to the Law no. 58/1934 on the bill of exchange and the promissory note. Certain amendments and additions were meant to return to the original form of the legal regulation. [4]

Then, the National Bank of Romania issued certain framework rules on trade by banking companies and other credit institutions with bills of exchange, promissory notes and checks, as well as technical rules on bills of exchange and promissory notes, according to current international custom. Finally, the National Bank has regulated an information system meant to strengthen the security of the bill of exchange, promissory note and check credit by creating the central payment incidents. [4]

Law no. 58/1934 was amended and supplemented by Government Ordinance no. 39/2008, approved with amendments and completions by Law no. 163/2009 and Law no. 76/2012. [4]

The main regulation of bills of exchange is Law no. 58/1934 on bills of exchange and promissory notes. Law No. 58/1934 does not include the definition of bill of exchange. In the science of commercial law, a bill of exchange is defined as a document by which a person, called a shooter or issuer, orders another person, called a draw, to pay a sum of money on maturity to a third person, called a beneficiary, or at his order. From the above definition it follows that the existence of the bill of exchange involves three participants: The shooter (the issuer), the drawer and the beneficiary. The shooter or issuer of the bill of exchange is the one who issues the title and orders the drawer to pay a sum of money to the beneficiary of the bill of exchange. The issuer of the document is called the shooter because it "draws" the title on

the debtor who is obliged to make the payment. The drawee is the main duty of the bill of exchange, in which quality must pay the amount of money. The beneficiary is the person who, upon maturity, will collect the amount of money from the draw. [5]

A security, a bill of exchange has the characters that are common to commercial securities. In addition to these general characters, the bill of exchange has its own characters, namely:

- **The bill of exchange is a credit title**

A bill of exchange is a document that gives the legitimate holder the right to receive the amount of money mentioned in it. The payment ordered by the shooter becomes chargeable after the leak of a

term from the date of issue of the bill of exchange. Thanks to this, a credit operation is performed through cambie. The maturity is unique for all bills of exchange liabilities resulting from bills of exchange. [6]

- **The bill of exchange has as its object the payment of a sum of money**

The order of the shooter given to the draw concerns the payment of a sum of money. The bill-of-exchange obligation may have as its object only the payment of a sum of money, excluding any other benefit.

All bills of exchange shall have as their object the payment of the same amount of money, which the shooter mentioned in the bill of exchange, unless otherwise provided by law. [6]

- **Bill of exchange is a full title**

The right and the obligation are those contained in the document. In the absence of an essential mention in the writing, the use of external elements is exclusive, even if the reference to them would be made in the bill of exchange. This prohibition stems from the literal character of the bill based on the formalism of commercial securities. [6]

- **Bill of exchange is a title to order**

The right contained in the bill of exchange may be exercised by the beneficiary or by the person to whom the bill of exchange has been transmitted by gir. The "to order" clause is subunderstood in any bill of exchange.

The issuer of the bill of exchange authorizes its holder to transmit it to another person at any time and indefinitely. The bill of exchange can be transmitted by the common law of the assignment of debt. For this purpose, the words 'not to order' must be made in the bill of exchange. [6]

- **Bill of exchange is an abstract title**

The rights and obligations arising from the bill of exchange exist validly, independently of the legal cause that generated them, respectively of the fundamental relationships. From the time of issue, bills of exchange and bills of exchange and bills of exchange have a stand-alone existence. The bill emancipates itself entirely from the legal cause from which it was born, and the rights and duties of the bill are analyzed in themselves, without any reference to the fundamental relations. [6]

- **The bill creates autonomous obligations**

All obligations arising from the bill of exchange have a legal existence of their own. Each signature put on the title creates a separate legal relationship with its own regime, and the defects or shortcomings of a legal relationship do not affect the validity of the other legal relationships. If the beneficiary transmits the bill by gir, he assumes a valid obligation toward the acquirer (the guarantor), even if his right was affected by the vices. If a person (the avalist) guarantees the obligation of the accepting tracer, the obligation of guarantee (ancillary obligation) is valid, even if the obligation of the drawee (main obligation) is nullible for defects of consent or incapacity. The recognition of the validity of the bills of exchange obligations is based on the existence of a bill of exchange issued in compliance with the requirements of the law. [6]

- **The bill creates unconditional obligations**

The bill of exchange obligations may not be subject to a condition or consideration by the holder of the bill of exchange. The provision of a condition affects the very existence of the bill of exchange obligation. If the payment order of the carriage is conditional, the bill of exchange is null. [6]

- **The bill creates solidarity obligations**

By transmitting the bill by the proxy, the initial obligation of the shooter regarding the acceptance and payment of the bill of exchange by the Tras is added the successive obligations assumed by his own signature, by each transmitter (guarantor) toward the acquirer (giratee).

The Gir not only carries out the transmission of the bill of exchange, but also the guarantee of the successive acquirers of the bill of exchange. In this case, each signatory of the bill of exchange undertakes to accept and pay the bill of exchange upon maturity. The bills of

exchange born from the signing of the bill of exchange are solidary, that is, upon maturity, the last holder of the bill of exchange may demand payment of the amount of money provided in the bill of exchange from the draw, and in case of refusal from any of the other signatories of the bill of exchange, without a predetermined order. [6]

The bill of exchange is a **full and formal order**, incorporating an abstract, autonomous and unconditional obligation to pay a sum of money by the signatories of the bill of exchange, held jointly and severally for the performance of the obligation. [6]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The materials used in writing this paper are composed of legislation and web sites. The methods used are legal, namely the formal method, the comparative method, the logical and sociological method, the analytical method. The use of these methods has the role of performing a systematic analysis of the information from the studied sources in order to elaborate the points of view and the conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to Article 1 of Law no. 58 of 1 May 1934 on Bill of exchange and promissory note, the bill of exchange must include:

1. The name of the bill of exchange entered into the text of the title itself and expressed in the language used for the writing of this title.
2. Unconditional order to pay a specified amount.
3. The name of the one who is to pay (tras).
4. Showing the maturity.
5. Showing the place where the payment is to be made.
6. The name of the person to whom or at whose order payment is to be made.
7. Showing the date and place of issue.
8. The signature of the one issuing the bill (shooter). [6]

According to Article 2 of the same law, the title which lacks any of the conditions mentioned in the preceding article shall not be of the value of a bill of exchange, except in the cases indicated in the following paragraphs: The bill of exchange without showing the maturity shall be deemed payable on spot. In the absence of a special appearance, the place

shown next to the name of the drawee shall be considered as the place of payment and, at the same time, the place of domicile of the drawee. The bill of exchange which does not show the place where it was issued shall be counted as signed at the place shown next to the name of the shooter. If more than one place of payment is shown on the bill of exchange, the holder of the bill of exchange may present it for acceptance or payment at any of these places. [6]

The bill of exchange has a formal character. This character must be understood in two ways: The bill of exchange must take the written form and the document must contain the particulars prescribed by law. The bill of exchange is a private signature written with the configuration of a letter drawn up by the shooter and addressed to the trucker. Bill of exchange can be written in any language, whether the persons involved know this language or not. A bill of exchange can be handwritten, beaten to the car, or printed. The standard forms are also accepted, which are completed in the blank spaces. In all cases the signature must be mauwritten, that is, it must belong to the person signing. [4]

Mandatory bill of exchange notices:

1. **The name of cambie.** This requirement is intended to draw the attention of the signing party to the nature of the obligation and its effects. Since the law requires that the inscription be included in the inscription, it means that equivalent expressions are not allowed. Consequently, the notions of "trate" or "policy" that were used by previous regulations could not be used, even if in the past they were widely known. The name of the bill of exchange must be expressed in the language used to write the document. [4]

2. **The unconditional payment order of a specified amount of money.** The document must flow the order that the shooter gives to the drawee to pay the beneficiary a specified amount of money. The payment order must be expressed in the form of an order itself ("pay", "you will pay", etc.) or in another "more polite" form, "I authorize you to pay", etc. The order must be **clear and precise**. The order must be **unconditional**. Any condition or consideration affecting the payment order shall result in the nullity of the bill of exchange. The payment must have an object only a sum of money and in a determined amount, the type of currency must be specified (without this specification the bill is struck by nullity). [4]

3. **The name of the drawee,** that is, the name of the person who must execute the payment. The name and surname of the natural person must be clearly stated, namely the denimation of the legal person or the obligating entity. The law requires the indication in the bill of exchange of the carriage code, respectively of the unique identification number provided in the identification or registration documents of the carriage. In case of no indication of the carriage, the carriage is struck by nullity.

It must be noted that the indication of a person as a tras does not thereby create an obligation for the person concerned to pay the sum of money. This obligation arises with the acceptance of the bill of exchange. From the moment of acceptance of the bill of exchange, the drawee becomes bound as the principal debtor of the bill of exchange. [4]

4. **Indication of the term.** The document must indicate the maturity, i.e. the date on which the bill of exchange obligation becomes chargeable and the holder of the bill of exchange may request payment of the amount of money mentioned in the document. Only the payment on maturity has liberating effect for the debtor. The maturity must be certain, that is, it must show the day or the maximum period within which the holder of the bill of exchange will present himself for payment. Then the maturity must be unique; the law prohibits the exchange with payment in installments. The maturity must result from the registration.

Can be drawn: In sight. at a certain time from sight; at a certain time from the date of issue; on a fixed day.

- If the maturity is missing, the bill of exchange is considered payable "at sight", that is, at its presentation. The maturity at sight allows the payment of the bill of exchange to be made "on presentation", or "on demand", according to the interests of the holder of the bill of exchange. 'Spot' bills of exchange may be presented for payment 'on the day of issue and at the latest one year after issue'.
- Maturity at a certain time of sight. This maturity allows the holder of the bill of exchange to present the bill of exchange for payment on the date he wishes. In this case, the maturity will be at the expiration of the term provided in the bill of exchange, which runs from the day of presentation of the bill of

exchange from the holder to the draw; for example: 30 days after the presentation of the bill.

- The issue at a certain time from the date of the broadcast. The maturity will be upon the expiry of the term stipulated in the bill of exchange, which runs from the date of issue of the title; for example, 15 days from the date of issue.
- It's on a fixed day. The obligation is subject to an indication of a specific day, for example 1 October 2010. [4]

5. **Indication** of the place where payment is to be made. The enrolment must provide the place where the debtor (draft) will make the payment. In the bill of exchange must be shown only the locality, and not the domicile or seat of the debtor. In the absence of an indication of the place where the payment is to be made, the payment is made at the place shown next to the name of the draw, which is also considered the place of residence of the draw.

By a special clause it may be stipulated in the bill of exchange that the payment be made at the domicile of a third party. A bill of exchange comprising such a clause is called domiciled bill of exchange. [4]

6. The name of the person to whom or on whose order the payment will be made. The person to whom the payment will be made or the payment must be made must be shown. Cambodia is drawn in favour of a determined person who is a beneficiary of the bill of exchange. The beneficiary is the first legitimate holder of the bill of exchange and, in this capacity, he has the right to claim from the draw the payment of the amount of money provided in the bill of exchange. The shooter may indicate himself as the beneficiary. If the beneficiary is not indicated when the title is issued, but subsequently is a bill of exchange in white. [4]

7. **Date and place** of issue of the bill of exchange. The date is indicated by the day, month and year of issuance of the bill of exchange, it is unique, even if there were several shooters. The registration must contain the city of issuance of the bill of exchange. If the place of issue of the bill of exchange is not indicated, the law shall presume that the place of issue shown next to the signature of the shooter. If such a place is not mentioned, the bill of exchange is struck by nullity. [4]

8. **Shooter's signature.** In order to produce effects, the bill of exchange must be signed by the shooter, otherwise the bill of exchange is struck by nullity. [4]

Optional mentions of bill of exchange.

I. Clauses affecting the debt obligation.

a) Clause "nu to order". This clause has the effect of prohibiting the transmission of bill of exchange by gir. The bill of exchange shall be transmissible only in the form and with the effects of a debt assignment under common law.

b) Indication of an acceptant if necessary. In order to avoid the risk of refusal of acceptance or payment of the bill of exchange by the shooter, the shooter may indicate in the bill of exchange a person who, if necessary, accept or make payment of the bill of exchange. The clause shall take effect only in case of refusal of payment by the draw.

c) Order of presentation of the bill of exchange upon acceptance. The presentation of the bill of exchange for its acceptance by the shooter is mandatory.

d) Clause „without expenses” or „without protest”. This clause exempts the beneficiary of the bill of exchange from the obligation to exercise the protest of non-acceptance or non-payment, which is required for the exercise of the regression action. [4]

II. Clauses that have no effect on the debt obligation

a) Clause „after opinion”. The shooter notifies the shooter not to accept or not to pay until after receiving an opinion from the shooter.

b) Clause „without proxy”. This clause confirms that the holder of the bill of exchange claims the amount mentioned in the title in the virtue of his right. The clause has no special effect, since the bill of exchange is a promissory note and therefore the execution of the obligation is made at the request of the legitimate holder of the title, who values a right of his own.

c) Clause „value given in warranty”. The clause shows the cause of the transmission of the title, but has no effect.

d) Clause „documents against acceptance”. The clause is used in particular in international trade where the case circulates accompanied by representative documents of the goods sold. The Cambodian containing such a clause is called documentary bill of exchange. The role of the mention is to show that the documents are only handed over to the shooter if he accepts or pays the bill of exchange. [4]

Consequences of non-compliance with the form conditions of the bill of exchange:

According to Article 2 of the Act, the title which lacks any of the conditions set out in

Article 1 does not have the value of a bill of exchange. There are certain exceptions: the bill of exchange without showing maturity is considered payable in plain sight. In the absence of a special mention, the place shown next to the name of the draw is considered the place of payment and at the same time the place of residence of the draw. The bill of exchange which does not show the place where it was issued shall be deemed signed in the place shown next to the name of the shooter. [4]

Acceptance of bill of exchange:

It implies the unconditional agreement of the draw to pay at maturity the amount written in the bill of exchange. Acceptance of the bill of exchange must be written, either on the face or on the reverse, and must bear the signature of the consignment. If acceptance is made on the face of the title is sufficient the signature of the draw, otherwise it must be accompanied by the accepted word or one of the expressions „you pay” or „you honor”. [8]

The presentation of the bill of exchange for acceptance is optional, if there is no express indication to the contrary. The shooter may or may not set a binding deadline for submission of the bill of exchange upon acceptance. Cambodia presents itself for acceptance at the home of the shoot, usually. The presentation for acceptance is mandatory if the bill of exchange is payable at a certain time from sight, because from the date of presentation to acceptance the deadline for maturity begins to run. Bill of exchange paid at a certain time from sight must be submitted for acceptance within one year from the date of its issuance, the shooter may reduce or extend this term by express mentions in the text. The trace is not obliged to accept the bill of exchange, but from the moment of acceptance of the bill of exchange, it becomes the main debtor, and the guarantors and the shooter remain obliged only if the draw does not pay the bill of exchange at maturity, which means they remain bound in regression. [8]

Refusal to accept bill of exchange:

Refusal to accept or pay must be ascertained by an authentic act (protest of non-acceptance or non-payment). [9]

The protest of non-acceptance or non-payment is made by the bailiff or the notary public. In case of refusal of acceptance of the bill of exchange, the holder of the bill of exchange may exercise, even before maturity, the right of regression. [4]

Consequences of the default of the Cambodian default. Bill of exchange actions. Extra-family actions.

If the bill of exchange is refused payment, its legitimate holder may use its rights by the means of bill of exchange means or extra-bill of exchange means:

- the bill of exchange means are genuine bill of exchange actions of which are part direct actions, regression actions and bill of exchange execution.

- extra-bill of exchange means are the actions specific to the fundamental relations of the common law that determined the issuance of the bill of exchange. [10]

1. Bill of exchange actions

a) Direct actions

Direct actions are actions directed against those directly obliged to pay, that is, the acceptable trace and its avalist. Art. 31 par. (2) of the law stipulates that if the drawing refuses the payment, the holder of the bill of exchange, even if it is a shooter, has against the acceptant a direct bill of exchange for all that may be required under Articles 53 and 54 of the law. Direct actions are ordinary court applications that are exercised under the title; they are not subject to special formalities and can be exercised within the limitation period. [10]

b) The regression actions

Regress actions are actions directed against the others bound by the bills of exchange, except for the consignant and his avalist. Consequently, the regression actions can be exercised against the shooter, the guarantors and their avalists. [10]

In order to exercise the regression actions, it is necessary to draw up the protest of non-acceptance or non-payment, as the case may be. Therefore, the protest is a document that finds the refusal to accept the bill of exchange (protest of non-acceptance) or to pay the bill of exchange (protest of non-payment). The protest of non-acceptance is not mandatory, unless the bill of exchange contains a special clause presenting the bill of exchange upon acceptance or when the maturity is set at a certain time from the acceptance of the bill of exchange, protest against non-payment is indispensable for the preservation of regression actions. The protest of non-payment may be made in one of the two days following the day of payment (art. 41). [10]

The competence of protest preparation belongs to the bailiff (art 66 of Law no. 58/1934) and the notary public, under the

conditions of Article 8 letter h) of Law no. 36/1995 Of notaries public and notarial activity. [10]

The protest must include the elements provided by Article 69 of the Law no. 58/1934b. According to Article 73 of the law, if the holder of the bill of exchange agrees, the protest may be replaced by a declaration of refusal of acceptance or payment, written and dated on the title, signed by the one against whom the protest was to be made. [10]

Article 50 of the law stipulates that the holder of the bill of exchange must inform his guarantor and the shooter about non-acceptance or non-payment in the four working days following the day of the protest. In turn, each guarantor is kept so that, in the two working days following the day on which he received the notice, he will inform his guarantor of the received notice, specifying the names and addresses of those who have made the previous notifications. According to the law reproduced, if the drawing refuses acceptance or payment of the bill of exchange, the following, the holder of the bill of exchange must advise the debtors of regression to make the payment of the bill of exchange. The failure to comply with the formal notice of the debtors does not deprive the holder of the bill of exchange from the exercise of the regression actions. [10]

2. Bill of exchange execution

According to Article 61 of the Law no. 58/1934, the bill of exchange has the value of an enforceable title for capital and accessories, established according to Articles 53, 54 and 57 of the law. by virtue of the enforceability of the bill of exchange, the possessor may proceed directly to enforcement, without any further direct or regressive actions. Flag execution is preferable to direct actions and regression actions because it is faster and less expensive. [10]

In order to trigger the execution of the bill of exchange, the law requires the presentation of the bill of payment and the preparation of the protest for non-payment. The execution of the bill of exchange presupposes the material possession of the bill of exchange and, in order to be started, it is necessary that the rights of the bill of exchange are not prescribed. [10]

3. Extra-bill of exchange actions

Extra-family shares are common law actions that can be used by the holder of the bill of exchange to satisfy his or her rights as a member of the public. Extrabill of exchange

actions are: causal action and unjust enrichment action. [10]

a) Causal action

As the name suggests, causal action is the action derived from the fundamental report that caused the issuance of the bill of exchange. The issuance of the bill of exchange by the shooter, as well as the transmission by way of the gir is based on the existence of pre-existing legal relations between the participants in the development of the bill of exchange. [10]

b) Unjust cause enrichment action

The seat of the matter of the unjust enrichment action is Art. 65 of Law no. 58/1934, according to which, if the holder has lost the bill of exchange action against all the obligations and does not have against them causal action, he may exercise against the shooter, the acceptor or guarantor an action for the payment of the amount with which they have enriched themselves without cause in its damage. [10]

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusion of the paper provides a simple perspective on the complexity of the regulations related to the bill of exchange in commercial law. Cambodia, as a financial instrument, serves as a pillar of commercial and financial activities, facilitating the movement of capital and building trust between the parties involved in commercial transactions. In this respect, compliance with the form conditions of the bill of exchange is essential to ensure the validity and effectiveness of this instrument. From the indication of the amount and the beneficiary to the correct signature of the issuer, every detail is crucial in order to confer on bill of exchange its executive force and value as a negotiable instrument.

As regards the process of acceptance and refusal of payment of the bill of exchange, it is governed by strict procedures designed to protect the interests of all parties involved. Acceptance of the bill of exchange is an act with significant legal consequences, involving the firm commitment of the draw to make the payment at maturity. Where payment is refused, the legislation provides mechanisms of protection and remedy for the holder of the bill of exchange, such as the right to bills of exchange or extra-family shares for the recovery of amounts owed or the forced execution of the payment obligation.

As the bill of exchange is a complex financial instrument, it is essential that those in the commercial environment have a sound understanding of the rules and procedures associated with its use. A detailed knowledge of the formal conditions, the processes of acceptance and refusal of payment, as well as the legal remedies in case of litigation, litigation, it is crucial to prevent disputes and protect the interests of parties involved in commercial transactions. Therefore, a careful and informed approach to the use of bill of exchange is imperative for the proper conduct of business in the contemporary commercial environment.

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LOAN PRODUCTS OFFERED TO STUDENTS AND YOUNG PEOPLE BY THE ROMANIA BANKING SYSTEM

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

Until recently, Romania did not have a student loan mechanism, as it exists in other countries. In this context, the article presents an analysis of the possibility offered to young people, students or those who have left the student period to benefit from loans, even guaranteed by the state, by private commercial banks. Loans can be used for various educational projects, payment of school fees, rent during studies, purchase of books, etc. In relation to this aspect, several banks have shown interest in granting loans for students and families, including Transilvania Bank, BRD - Groupe Société Générale, BCR and CEC Bank. Added to these are other private banks, for example Raiffeisen Bank, which provide students with debit cards, through which they benefit from certain facilities. The article is based on the information collected from the banks' websites and the study of some publications from the specialized literature.

Keywords: loans, students, bank cards, government guarantees.

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INTRODUCTION

Credit institutions will be able to function well if they support society and economic life (Bezemer et al. 2023). Everything that happens in society and in the economy depends on this support (Prochniak & Wasiak, 2017). Bank specialists must produce money and do everything they can to teach others to make money (Căpraru, 2014; Mitu, 2020; Feher et al., 2020).

The granting of credits will accelerate if trust in the banking system, as a psychological element, will increase, it being known that the activity provided by banks is not considered risky (Bergh & Bjornskov, 2021). The trust accelerates the mechanism of granting loans by making commitments to the bank (Tobes et al, 2018; Sîrbulescu et al., 2018)

The objective of the paper is to present the financing possibilities offered by the Romanian banking system, for young people and students or those who have recently completed their university studies.

If they want to make an investment in their education and ensure a better professional and financial future, young people, students and those who have recently finished university

studies and are not working or do not have a stable job, have the opportunity to solve certain expenses unforeseen that appear throughout the years of study, using the financial products offered by the banking system. The needs that can be covered by such loans can be: expensive study materials, payment of school fees, and other expenses necessary for studies.

In addition to the different types of loans, banks offer cards to students and young people who are enrolled and attending a form of education (Wiederspan, 2016). Added to these are various programs addressed exclusively to young people (Lipset, 2020). Until the middle of 2022, in Romania, the banks did not have loans dedicated to young people and students in their portfolio. Students and young people could not apply for loans, due to the criteria that had to be met by them, which excluded lending (<https://economedia.ro>).

From the middle of 2022, the Student Invest and Family Start Programs were approved by the Government of Romania, quite unknown state credit programs for students and families. Among the first banks interested in granting loans to young people were Transilvania Bank, BCR and CEC Bank (<https://bankingnews.ro>). Also the novelty is related to the fact that the state covers the

guarantee (zero or low interest partially paid by the state) for loans.

From March 2024, StudentInvest and FamilyStart, programs designed to provide financial support to students and young families, were launched. Through these programs, banks can grant loans of up to 75,000 lei for StudentInvest and 150,000 lei for FamilyStart. The loans will be granted through banking institutions and will be with state guarantees. Interest and related fees will be subsidized by the state.

According to the Ministry of Family, Youth and Equal Opportunities for 2024, the guarantee ceilings for both programs are: 250 million lei for StudentInvest, respectively 250 million lei for FamilyStart (<https://www.capital.ro>). The maximum fund was established for: 5556 beneficiaries for the StudentInvest program and 4375 beneficiaries in the FamilyStart program for the year 2024.

In 2024 the lending programmes will be run through the registered banks: Central Cooperative Bank CREDITCOOP, and 26 partner cooperatives, Libra Bank, CEC Bank, Exim Romanian Bank and Techventures Bank.

A topic of interest for young people is represented by the student card that can be used for the basic services of the banks, with numerous advantages. Many banking institutions have interesting student card offers for young people. But they must meet the

eligibility conditions if they want to obtain the student card. The information is different from one bank to another, taking into account that the offers also vary.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this work, the authors present some possibilities that young people, students or those who have recently finished their university studies have to benefit from the financing and lending options offered by the Romanian banking system.

The lending possibilities offered by the Romanian banking system to students and young families were presented. We have identified the following banks that offer this possibility: Transilvania Bank, BRD-Groupe Société Générale, Romanian Commercial Bank and CEC Bank. Other banks, such as Raiffeisen Bank, provide students with cards dedicated to them through which they benefit from facilities.

Transilvania Bank was established in Cluj-Napoca in 1993 by a group of Romanian entrepreneurs, and is one of the top financiers of the Romanian economy. The objective of Transilvania Bank was to reinvest in Romania and support the economy. The bank took first place (Figure 1) in the ranking of banks by assets (21% market share) and achieved a net profit of 2.49 billion lei, in 2024 (<https://www.capital.ro>, <https://www.bursa>).

Figure 1. Top banks in 2024
Sources: <https://www.capital.ro>

BCR is an important financial player on the banking market, occupying the second place in terms of market share, 13.4% and a net profit of 2.32 billion lei.

On the podium in 2024 was also CEC Bank, a banking institution controlled by the Romanian state through the Ministry of Finance, which helps the development of the economy, market share 10.4%, profit 515.8 million lei. (<https://www.zf.ro>)

BRD Groupe Société Générale (fourth place) also had an exceptional year, registering a net profit of 1.66 billion lei, a 10.1% market share. It is a Romanian bank owned by the French group Société Générale (58.32%).

Raiffeisen Bank, a top institution in Romania, promotes learning, collaboration, integrity. From the point of view of market share, Raiffeisen was in sixth place at the end of 2024, 8.7% market share.

UniCredit Bank, ranked 7th in 2024, reported assets of 68 billion lei in Romania and a market share of 8.4% of net assets (Figure 1). The writing of the article was based on the information collected from the banks' websites, the study of specialized publications and other information provided by economic websites.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Transilvania Bank (Table 1) offers two types of loans: Work and Travel and Study Loan. The Work and Travel credit is granted to students and young people only if they are enrolled in a state or private educational program, with frequency or distance, financed from the budget or with a fee, or at other companies and institutions organizing training programs professional. Also, the applicant must prove that he was accepted to the program. The maximum amount is up to 3,500 euros (equivalent in lei) for a period of 2 years. Interest can be fixed or variable. Depending on the amount borrowed for studies, the loan can be with or without a mortgage. The Work and Travel loan can be used to pay the program enrollment fee, other fees, the plane ticket, out-of-pocket expenses up to 15% of the loan amount. For a period of 6 months after receiving the loan, the applicant does not pay the installment or interest.

For loans to finance university or postgraduate studies, the maximum amount is up to 20,000 euros or 150,000 lei for continuing studies, the granting period is 5 years. The bank can also grant financing for costs other than tuition fees, up to a maximum of 2000 euros (equivalent in lei) per year for accommodation and meal expenses, the purchase of office equipment, stationery and

other consumables, to which financing can be added some complementary expenses for grants awarded in the case of student mobility programs (Erasmus Program).

BT OmniPass is the card offered to students by Transilvania Bank. This card can be used anywhere in the country or abroad. It is a card with the Contactless option, fast and safe, through which students benefit from promotions and discounts, online shopping, direct payments can be made through BT Pay, including insurance for travel abroad.

Raiffeisen Bank (Table 1) offers the Student Card with zero costs for: purchasing the card; annual administration fee; commission for withdrawals in lei from Romanian bank ATMs; commission for transactions in Lei carried out through internet and mobile banking services; commission when paying by card at merchants. This debit card is a product intended for young people aged 18-25 (underage). It uses the available lei from the current account, and abroad the conversion is done automatically.

BCR Social Finance launched StudyUP for those who want to continue their studies, by accessing an educational program at any level: college, master's, doctorate. It can also be obtained for specialization courses in Romania. The applicant benefits from the guarantee offered by the European Investment Fund in percentage of 80%, grace period up to 42 months and financing up to 145,000 lei, depending on the specializations and expenses involved. The credit period is up to 120 months, the interest rate is fixed throughout the credit period. People applying for such a loan must be between 18 and 45 years of age. The amounts accessed can be used for the following categories of expenses: tuition fee financing (payment is made directly to the account of the education provider), rent, school materials, textbooks, equipment and other expenses (transportation, food, maintenance) up to a ceiling maximum of a monthly minimum wage per economy)(<https://finante-banci.ro>).

The novelty is that this funding tool for continuing studies comes with a simplification of the approval process, i.e. no proof of income is required during the credit analysis and no co-debtor, zero commission for analysis of the file, granting and early repayment.

BCR (Table 1) makes available to students the George Student online account for students between the ages of 18 and 22 with a Cyan card attached. Holders of such an account can benefit from discounted tickets and access to festivals

and certain events, discounts at restaurants, cafes, free access to parties or George events. The George Student online account is opened online and has ZERO commissions for withdrawals at any ATM, transfers in lei to banks in Romania. Transactions can also be made with the digital card, through Apple Pay & Google, not only with the physical one.

BCR offers students through the bank application and the opportunity to save, by opening a savings account. Users can pay smartly, through a QR code or Alias Pay. The youth online account can be opened for children of different ages. The George Kids online account can be accessed for children up to the age of 7, with two standard cards attached for parents for free.

The George Junior online account is an account with an attached card for children aged between 7 and 14 years.

The George Young online account is made available to teenagers, aged 14 and 18, with the same benefits as in the case of the student card.

BRD - Groupe Société Générale (Table 1) offers the Loan for studies that brings a series of advantages to applicants: up to 6 months,

partial grace when only the interest, insurance premium, along with commissions are paid. The maximum amount of loans, without guarantees, is 250,000 lei (Euro equivalent), granted for a maximum of 10 years. Incomes from: salaries, pensions, dividends, copyrights, rents, up to incomes from independent activities are accepted.

Credit 10 from BRD is granted to students who enroll in university studies, master's/doctorate/in-depth studies at universities in Romania or abroad. The value of the loan granted is a maximum of EUR 3,000 (equivalent in lei), the maximum duration is 10 years, without guarantees and the interest rate is fixed and advantageous. The loan is also obtained if the applicant does not obtain income. It can be requested but a co-lender is required in both cases. the guarantee will be constituted by the movable mortgage for own accounts opened at BRD. Expenditures are financed such as: computer, books, rent, printer, etc.

Table 1

Banking products offered to students and young people

The bank	Products
Transilvania Bank	Work and Travel credit Study Credit BT OmniPass
BRD - Groupe Société Générale	The loan for studies Credit 10 BRD-ISIC card
BCR BCR Social Finance	George Student online account George Kids online account George Junior online account George Young Online Account StudyUP
Raiffeisen Bank	Student card
CEC Bank	Loan for personal needs with state facility, StudentInvest package Family Start loans The Student Free package
UniCredit Bank	Master Card Young
Alpha Bank	The AlphaStudent package
OTP Bank	Cards for young people: Junior Plus Junior Max
Libra Bank	The loan for medical students
ING Bank	Free@ING - card and account for young people ING Young - internet banking and card for children

Source: <https://www.alphabank.ro>, <https://www.bancatransilvania.ro>, <https://www.bcr.ro>, <https://www.brd.ro>, <https://www.cecbank.ro>, <https://www.otpbank.ro>, <https://www.unicredit.ro>, <https://www.librabank.ro>, <https://www.ing.ro>

The BRD-ISIC card is also offered to students, being one of the cards with multiple advantages. It is a debit card, in foreign currency or lei, and can be issued by the bank

for young people at least 12 years old, who attend an accredited form of education. It is important to remember that obtaining the card implies the obligation to present the

card/identification card that was endorsed for the current year and is valid for 4 years. Issuing the card involves costs. The annual digital card issuing fee of 50 lei/academic year must be paid, and if a plastic one is requested, a fee of 20 lei is paid. Withdrawals from a BRD ATM are charged a withdrawal fee of 0.2% or 0.9 lei minimum. In the case of cash withdrawals from other banks, there is a commission of 0.5% or a minimum of 5 lei. Internet banking and balance inquiry at BRD ATMs are free.

The benefits of the BRD ISIC card are: globally recognized card (over 130 countries), thus any location the holder will visit (parks, zoos, etc.) will receive a student discount, presenting the ISIC card; there is a list of shops where you get discounts if you present your card.

UniCredit Bank (Table 1) has a tradition of promoting local culture and artistic events. It is in the top ten in terms of net assets held and market share and offers young people the Master Card Young product. Master Card Young is intended for children aged between 6 and 18. Administration costs are zero both for the current account and for the debit card. This product teaches children to manage their money from the current account that is fed by their parents and teaches them to save for future projects. The card cannot be used for cash withdrawals or purchases unsuitable for a child.

OTP Bank offers young people two types of cards: Junior Plus (age 8-18) and Junior Max (age 18-25). Cards will be accessible if there is already a savings account opened at the bank (Junior Start or Junior Plus). The account is available in lei or euros, the interest rates are advantageous; access to funds is permanent;

CEC Bank provides students with personal loans guaranteed by the state through the StudentInvest package. The loan can reach up to 75,000 lei with guarantees granted by the state and also the interest subsidized by the state. The credit obtained through the Student Invest Package can be used to pay school fees, purchase books, pay rent during studies, participation fee for scientific events and competitions, pay for accommodation in student dormitories, etc. The use of the amounts is based on supporting documents that are mandatory for settlement or direct payment to the supplier.

Among the benefits of the Student Invest loan from CEC Bank, we mention: zero interest (fully subsidized by the state); 80% of the

financing value will benefit from the state guarantee, through the Romanian Counter-Guarantee fund; maximum credit duration of 5 years, up to 12 months of guarantee.

CEC Bank lending conditions: Romanian citizen at least 18 years old; net income, proven, for paying off the loan; at least 3 months of experience at the current job. CEC Bank also offers the Family Start loan through which amounts up to 150,000 lei can be obtained, guaranteed by the state and subsidized interest (75% of the interest formed from IRCC +4%), maximum loan duration of 5 years.

CEC Bank offers students the Student Free package with the following benefits: current account in lei and EURO, debit card, Mobile Banking and Internet Banking, ZERO monthly commission for package administration if the beneficiary is 18-24 years old, zero commission on withdrawals at ATMs (CEC Bank, other banks in the country and the EU), advantageous exchange rate through Mobile Banking.

Alpha Bank offers AlphaStudent (Table 1) to people who are enrolled in a university and have a current account opened at this bank. The benefits of this to traders and travel agencies. Conditions for accessing the AlphaStudent package: age 18-26, to be enrolled in a higher education institution, day/distance courses in Romania by presenting a student card/certificate.

The Medical Student Loan is offered by Libra Bank to V and V year students, for one year, including veterinary students, for the payment of tuition fees and student expenses. The maximum grant period is 5 years, with a guarantee period of 2 years for fifth-year students, one year for sixth-year students. A maximum amount of 24,000 lei is granted.

ING Bank offers two types of cards: Free@ING - card and account for young people, granted to young people, aged 18-24; ING Young - internet banking and card for children aged 10-18, through which children will learn healthy financial habits.

CONCLUSIONS

Starting from 2022, through the banks, student loans are granted that are guaranteed by the state, respectively loans for students who do not have an income and a job.

Such loans represent a helping hand that those who wish to continue their academic training can call on. Practically, it offers the

chance to focus on the study, without worrying about the money because it will cover the costs associated with the education.

The money obtained from the loans will be able to cover a wide range of expenses, namely school fees, books, accommodation, study materials and other necessities.

They are designed in such a way that the grace periods are long, with the possibility of postponement after completing the payments.

Several large banks in Romania have special offers for students in the form of student cards. These cards are debit, not credit, and offer the possibility of using basic bank services, with the advantages of eliminating some commissions and taxes and some discounts.

In conclusion, we can appreciate that through the products offered to students and young people, they will win in the short term, and in the long term the bank wins, by increasing the number of customers.

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IS SUPPLEMENTATION NECESSARY FOR SPORTS?

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REVIEW ARTICLE

Abstract

Thanks to the rise of social media and prosperity, more and more people are taking up various sports, which in many cases involves the use of dietary supplements. But are these sports supplements necessary for sporting individuals? In this study we will try to address this issue.

Dietary supplements are a group of products that contain a nutrient in a concentrated form. We can think of the most common protein fortified products, such as protein powders, protein bars and other various snacks. Various dietary supplements promising fat burning, performance enhancing or other positive effects also fall into this category. Of course, these dietary supplements are not intended to replace a varied and balanced diet, so they can only be used, as the name suggests, to supplement our meals. And if we have a well-balanced diet, is it necessary to use these products? Well, what we can say, based on our research, is that it is primarily recommended that we actually take in the nutrients we need at mealtimes; from macronutrients to micronutrients. However, if someone is not getting enough nutrients from a balanced diet, then supplementation may be necessary. Such factors may include, for example, if a person participates in elite sport or other physical activity at a high level, and when considering the intake of nutrients needed, we also need to consider what the individual sports person prefers, so if there is a nutrient-rich food that they should be eating that they do not like, or if the food would result in a significant energy surplus, then we should consider supplementation.

Keywords: *sport, nutrition, food supplement, dietary supplement, consumption*

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INTRODUCTION

In today's consumer society, dietary supplements are becoming increasingly popular. One of the reasons for this is that the spread of the internet and social media has made it possible for more and more people to use these products. It is also noteworthy that there is a growing awareness of their purchase, health consciousness and the whole 'well-being' phenomenon. With the growth of gyms, there has been a corresponding increase in the use of sports supplements. Manufacturers and distributors use various marketing tools to lure their customers, highlighting the benefits of their products. In the present study, we seek to answer the question: is supplementation really necessary for sportsmen and sportswomen, or is the whole supplement business only thanks to the marketing of the manufacturers?

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The present research is a literary research based on literature sources. The aim of the study was to find relevant literature on the

subject in order to inform the reader as widely as possible about the conditions of use of dietary supplements.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to EU rules, foods that contain concentrated forms of various nutrients or other substances with a nutritional effect can be called food supplements. They can be found in powder, liquid or capsule form (europa.eu, 2024).

It should be noted that dietary supplements are not medicines, which are used to prevent or treat various diseases. They can only be placed on the market after specific authorisation by the authorities. In contrast, in the case of food supplements, only the manufacturer or distributor is responsible and is required to check the quality and safety of the food (portal.nebih.gov.hu, 2024).

According to the National Food Chain Safety Office's Dietary Supplement Guide, it is recommended to take supplements if you are following a special diet or if your body is under heavy stress. When consuming this product, it is

good to know the Upper Level, which is the highest level of safety, and the Nutrient Reference Values, which are the recommended daily intakes of minerals and vitamins (portal.nebih.gov.hu, 2024) (Fabulya et al., 2015).

In her book, Gabriella Silye mentions that the increased demand from the food industry has resulted in soil depletion due to the use of chemicals in agriculture. As a result, many of the minerals in the soil are being absorbed by plants in smaller quantities. Several studies confirm the depletion of nutrients in food (Silye, 2019).

If we eat a healthy diet, we can provide our bodies with the vitamins and trace elements they need. However, it is important to consider which foods we prefer to eat and check that we are providing our body with the daily requirements (Rigó, Gyurcsáné, 2006).

The number of personal trainers, the number of supplement shops is increasing and gyms are becoming more and more popular due to their visibility in urban environments, commercial images, increasing gym attendance (Honfi et al., 2009). It can therefore be said that more and more people are trying the path towards a healthy lifestyle (Gyimes, 2023) (Lendvai, 2022). Along with this, the market for sports supplements is also growing (Panyor, Hipszki, 2022) (Szabad et al., 2021). Their consumption is also becoming more prevalent among younger age groups. In addition to athletes, even young children are increasingly taking vitamin and mineral supplements (Liska et al., 2021). Gabriella Silye also says that athletes often use supplements according to the fashion of the day, so they are not used properly. However, too high an intake can also have negative effects on their performance (Silye, 2019). Researchers are trying to find many ways to produce plants and ingredients with higher protein content. A lot of genetic experiments are being conducted to create high-lysine, high-protein cereals. One such experiment has resulted in the development of triticale. This is a cross between wheat and rye. Soy protein is also relatively high in protein, with a relatively recently discovered oilseed as the raw material. There have also been significant breakthroughs in the various proteins produced by microorganisms. Noteworthy are the *Candida* strains, which are capable of producing L-lysine, L-threonine, L-tryptophan, L-isoleucine during fermentation. It can also produce DL-methionine by chemical

means. When mixed with plant proteins, their biological value can be increased (Csapó et al., 2006).

A comprehensive study in 2019 looked at how athletic athletes who use supplements to optimise and enhance performance perform in sport. The researchers concluded that sports foods and supplements that athletes should use are those with evidence that they are safe, legal to use and effective. Peeling also suggests that it is worth testing the effects of a particular supplement on the athlete early on to ensure that no one is caught by any negative surprises during the preparation for competition (Peeling et al., 2019).

And a study in 2022 examined whether supplementation is really necessary or whether it is sufficient to get the necessary nutrition into athletes' bodies through food. Close concluded that it is not always necessary to use food to get the nutrients our body needs, as there are cases where it is better to use supplements. To avoid the use of inadmissible performance enhancers, they, like the Peelings, recommend that nutrients should be primarily provided through food. They also accept that there are some nutrients whose health and performance-enhancing effects suggest that they should be taken in through the use of supplements (Close et al., 2022).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The market for the use of nutritional supplements is growing. The various manufacturers and distributors are trying to influence consumer choices on an ever wider scale. Therefore, the aim of this research is to find out whether consumers need to take supplements.

Overall, we can say that, as the labelling of dietary supplements suggests, they are not a substitute for a balanced diet, but can be used to supplement our meals. In particular, it is advisable for sportsmen and sportswomen to consume macronutrients, such as protein, carbohydrates and fats, and micronutrients, which are vitamins and minerals, as part of their diet.

We can talk about different cases where supplementation is really necessary. Here we have to take into account factors such as the food preferences of the individual athlete, because if he or she has to eat a food that contains a higher level of a particular micronutrient or macronutrient, we cannot

force that individual to eat a product that he or athlete would have to consume a food that is too high in calories to provide a particular macronutrient. Many sports are known where weight classes are set up for competition, so it is necessary to pay attention to the appropriate caloric intake when designing the diet. So, first of all, a balanced, varied diet rich in vitamins and minerals should be followed, and if, due to the high physical activity of the athletes, it is not possible to achieve the right quantity and quality of nutrients naturally, with a caloric intake tailored to the individual, then it is worth using sports supplements.

CONCLUSIONS

A balanced, well-balanced diet is something we should follow when we eat. Many vegetables, fruits, pulses, seeds and various grains are rich in vitamins and minerals. These are the main ingredients to include in your diet.

Of course, depending on their training goals, individuals in sport may need supplementation in addition to a well-formulated diet. It is therefore a good idea to have a well-constructed diet and to use various dietary supplements according to your training goals.

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she does not like. The same is true when an

As the market for dietary supplements is growing and their use is becoming more widespread, it is worth exploring this topic in more depth in the following sections. In addition to literature research, it is worthwhile to carry out as much qualitative and quantitative research as possible. We ourselves are carrying out practical research of this kind on the subject. We would like to gain a better understanding of consumers' preferences, their motivations and the circumstances under which they make their purchasing decisions.

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THE MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN AGRICULTURE AND THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC STRUCTURE OF THE POPULATION IN ROMANIA

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The present paper represents an analysis of the labor force management in agriculture, but also a synthesis of the socio-economic structure of the population involved in agriculture in Romania. Agriculture has been and remains the most powerful balancing factor in harmonizing the development of any economy state, including our country. It is known that the involvement of the population in agricultural activities contributes significantly to the standard of living. Improving economic performance and market access of farms, for the purpose increasing their competitiveness, represents an essential component for revitalization rural areas. The level of agricultural development of our country, indisputably, is dependent on natural and material resources which are valued by the available human potential. During the research, there were analyzed the data provided by the European Commission, Agriculture in Romania is one of the important branches of the Romanian economy and is constantly expanding. A percentage 11% of the active population is employed in agriculture in 2022, in Romania, according to the research. Depending on gender, there are 417.900 men and 205.200 women. 23% of the workforce in Romania is employed in agriculture, which is the highest percentage of people employed in agriculture in the EU. Romania is also one of the countries with the highest share of farmers aged over 65 (44.3%).

Keywords: agriculture, development, rural population, professional status.

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INTRODUCTION

The labor force in agriculture represents one of the three resources fundamentals (along with the lands agricultural and production machinery) which decisively influences the results of production. The agricultural sector in Romania has suffered in the last 15 years for several reasons, and here the labor force crisis played an important role. Although, from the point of view of technology, agriculture in our country is evolving, the lack of labor is causing great losses to farmers (Ciulinaru, 2019). They invest more and more in state-of-the-art equipment, but they cannot find qualified personnel to work with this equipment. Many farmers and agricultural land owners face major difficulties in finding labor. Whether it is sowing, harvesting, animal care or repairing agricultural machinery, the lack of personnel is a constant problem and increasingly affects the smooth running of agricultural activities. For many years, agriculture in Romania has been going through a major crisis in terms of the available workforce. This crisis is fueled by

several factors, such as labor migration abroad in search of a better life, declining interest in agricultural work, and an aging population in rural areas. This problem adversely affects the productivity and economic growth of our country's agriculture (Buliga, 2020). This migration of young people from Romania to foreign countries has led to a drastic decrease in the labor force available in agriculture. Mostly, the youth who opt for work in foreign countries do so because of the lack of opportunities in the agricultural sector in our country. Another reason that has caused this exodus of young people to foreign countries is the unfavorable working conditions in agriculture, lower wages compared to those offered in other countries, poor infrastructure, insufficient subsidies, and aversion to association among farmers. These problems have contributed to the decrease in productivity in Romanian agriculture, and thus the agricultural sector has become less attractive for young people (Miron & Beleniuc, 2013). Young people are less and less interested in agriculture and work in this field. One of the reasons relates to the movement of the

population from the rural areas of the country to the cities. Here, young people perceive more favorable job opportunities and the lifestyle is more comfortable than country life. Another factor relates to the harsh working conditions that agriculture provides. This field involves a rather difficult work environment with a variable schedule, working in extreme weather conditions or on rough terrain. These working conditions, especially compared to the working environment in urban areas, have over time demotivated young people to opt for work in agriculture (Nica, 2007). Nor is the educational system in our country a factor that motivates young people to choose agriculture. Young people in Romania are not educated to see the advantages of a career in agriculture, and the training of young graduates does not meet the standards needed to perform in agriculture (Alec, 2006). Training in agricultural technologies has remained at the level of the previous decade, meaning that young people are not getting the degree of qualification needed to operate farm machinery or work on a farm (Vasilescu, 2015). Thus, many young agricultural workers who see a modern tractor for the first time will not know how to use it. Farmers in Romania are increasingly forced either to work with unqualified personnel or to hire workers from abroad who have a better degree of qualification. Those who choose to employ personnel without training in this area risk compromising their work and damaging their machinery, because an operator who is not thoroughly trained will not have the necessary knowledge to use such equipment correctly (Dămășaru & Crăciun, 2016). To counter the effects of the labor force crisis in agriculture, it is necessary to see more initiatives from the Romanian state. Unfortunately, one of the negative effects of the generous welfare system has been a decrease in the labor force in many fields, including agriculture. Climate change, technological progress and labor mobility have profoundly transformed the field of agriculture. Agricultural machinery is becoming more and more efficient, and computers are increasingly important in agricultural processing technologies, but physical labor in agriculture is not going away anytime soon. In recent years, farmers in the European Union have faced a labor shortage, partly offset by a migration of workers from Eastern European states. At the

level of the European Union, the deficit cannot be compensated because the labor force in agriculture registers a decline, from year to year (Toader & Roman, 2011). The labor force crisis in the agricultural field is one of the main problems that farmers are currently facing, in the context in which many residents of rural areas prefer to live on social assistance, granted without being based on rigorous social surveys, agricultural producers pulling a alarm signal that people are thus encouraged not to work. The internal migration of young people from the rural to the urban environment, as well as the migration abroad, is another cause that has a negative impact on the labor force in agriculture, most of the agricultural land being in this period left in the care of elderly farmers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The data provided by the European Commission and Eurostat were statistically processed, regarding the structure of the population employed in agriculture, by age groups, professional status, gender, forms of ownership, the number of vacant jobs as well as the structure of the rural population. During the research, there were used descriptive statistics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In Romania, more than one in five people (23% in 2022) worked in agriculture, the sector representing a particularly large share of total jobs. The share of agriculture in the total employed workforce was also relatively high in Bulgaria (15.5%) and Greece (9.9%). In contrast, it represented less than 1% of total employment in Luxembourg and Malta (both 0.7%). In 2022, the share of agriculture in total employment fell in every EU Member State. At EU level, 8.7 million people worked in agriculture in 2020, equivalent to 4.2% of all jobs. As the number of agricultural holdings in the EU has declined over time, so has agricultural employment. The share of agriculture in employment in the EU fell from 5.6% in 2021 to 4.2% in 2022. Regarding the structure of the population, on the main activities of the national economy, it can be observed that the highest percentage is recorded in the field of services, 55.75, and in agriculture a percentage of only 11% is recorded (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Population structure, based on the main activities of the national economy, in 2022

In the year 2022, in rural areas, a percentage of 72.4% of the total population is represented by employees, 1.2% are employers, 19.7% are self-employed workers in the agricultural field and 6.7% are family workers unpaid (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The structure of the rural population, in 2022

Regarding the structure of the population by age groups, out of the total population of 878,400 people employed in agriculture, the largest percentage, 29.3%, is represented by

people between the ages of 45 and 54. The lowest percentage, 5.0%, is occupied by people over 65 years (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The structure of the population employed in agriculture, by age group, in 2022

Of the total number of people employed in agriculture, a percentage of 32.7% is represented by women. Of this total, 10.4% are between 45 and 54 years old (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The structure of the female population employed in agriculture, by age group, in 2022

Depending on the professional status, out of the total of 878,400 people employed in agriculture, the largest percentage, 53.2%, is represented by self-employed workers. The lowest percentage, 0.7%, is represented by employers (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Employment structure in agriculture, by professional status, in 2022

Of the total number of women employed in agriculture, 32.7%, 4% are employees, 0.1% are employers, 12.6% are self-employed and 16% are unpaid family workers (Figure 6).

Figure 6. The professional status of women employed in agriculture, in 2022

CONCLUSIONS

The forecasts regarding the labor force crisis in Romanian agriculture are not exactly favorable for the coming years. However, solutions must come from both farmers and government institutions to find mutually beneficial solutions. In the agricultural and forestry sectors, there is a major imbalance between women and men in the context of professional status. For example, the number of male managers is more than four times higher than the number of female managers, while unpaid family workers are predominantly female (over 60%). The authorities should offer facilities, which could be granted to female persons, would ensure equity between men and women, considering the reluctance of women to manage businesses, especially in the rural environment and in the agricultural sector, an aspect that could explain this imbalance reflected by statistics. For the labor shortage in Romania, tangible solutions should be found, which could help employers to continue the economic development of their businesses and represent a solution for the context they are

facing, namely offering a package of competitive bonuses and some programs to increase the level of employee retention. Another option could be recruiting from among students or non-specialized people, whom they can train internally.

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STREET ALIGNMENT, STRUCTURAL, FUNCTIONAL AND AESTHETIC COMPONENT OF URBAN LANDSCAPING

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Abstract

By using the repetition of an identical or similar component in the landscape, the designer has the possibility of creating a unique planting scheme. This desire is given by the designer's experience, by the efficiency with which the created "environment" addresses the needs of the people and the functional requirements of the site, the way of selecting the appropriate plants and their association, the economic advantages related to the maintenance requirements, all these combined contribute to the aesthetic success of the project, to the realization of a pleasant design throughout the year.

In this paper we have proposed to present different types of street alignments, the way we select the species of ornamental trees and shrubs, the aesthetic and functional principles that underlie the choice of rhythm, as a principle and element of landscape design, with the aim of it facilitates the perception of the composition, increasing the expressiveness of the ensemble and the integration of these connecting corridors in the general urban ensemble.

In conclusion, we can say that the street alignments represent an integral part of the cultural heritage, they define the aesthetics of the street representing true transit corridors within the urban fabric. Because they have a climatic, economic, structural, protective, functional and aesthetic role, their lack leaves cities with structure, rhythm and coherence, a sustainable development strategy. When choosing the species of ornamental trees and shrubs, the aesthetic value, the specific requirements regarding pedoclimatic conditions, the design of the landscaped space and the basic principles such as: order, harmony and proportion are taken into account. Rhythm is the main tool in ordering alignments, which facilitates the correct planning of green spaces.

Keywords: alignment, rhythm, trees, shrubs, aesthetics.

INTRODUCTION

From a landscape point of view, the surrounding environment is represented by our physical surroundings, by the world outside the built environment, by the landscape that surrounds us, a complex environment that dissolves into a network of relationships, connections, and continuities of physical, social conditions, and cultural, which circumscribe human actions and responses, which give form and content to it and which represent life itself. As a result of accelerated urbanization, currently almost 55% of the population lives in urban areas, and by 2050 it is estimated that this ratio will increase to 68% (Onose D.A. et al, 2012), a fact that can produce negative consequences for life and biodiversity, and on a global scale, urban activities directly influence climate change [Dodman D., 2027]. Urbanization has an enormous impact affecting all the components of the environment, which, in turn, influence the quality of the population's health [Capcelea V., 2019].

The environment represents the result of mind-body dualism, a place we contemplate and should live in harmony with, a space that is an intimate part of our lives. While the landscaped green space reflects the experience of an immediate, more special location,

characterized by specific elements incorporated in a distinct way and emphasizing the human presence as an activator of perception. We have to admit that through its activity of transforming the environment, human influence is not always beneficial, sometimes it can end up offending us in various ways: by destroying identity and affecting places, by disrupting architectural coherence or other situations that can reach to the idea of an environment hostile to life.

Next, I will present some of the advantages that urban green spaces, whether they are small in size, for example street alignments, bring to the environment. It is known that plants contribute to the support of biological diversity in the urban environment, providing refuge and food for various species of insects, birds and other small animals [Scott Catherine., 2015], which has a positive impact on the urban ecological balance by ensuring pollination, organic matter, also an essential role in pest management. It should be noted that the street alignments are true biological corridors that allow the movement of many species.

The presence of ornamental trees and shrubs in the street alignments bring numerous benefits in the urban environment with multiple effects on air quality, thus a leaf surface of 25

square meters provides the necessary oxygen for a person during a day [Scoott Catherine., 2015]. Woody vegetation plays an important role in reducing pollution, sequestering carbon dioxide and other pollutants as well as dust, a process that helps reduce air pollution and improve air quality in cities.

Trees and shrubs contribute to reducing the urban heat island effect, by shading and evaporating water, by transpiration they contribute to increasing the relative humidity of the air (Radomska M. et al, 2017) and lowering temperatures by 2 -3°C, on summer days (Harris et al, 1999). Street alignments mark and delineate functional areas, but at the same time unify different spaces in the vast urban network of cities, create corridors and access areas.

Depending on the height, alignments, especially double ones, are a barrier to winds without creating the "wall effect", which creates harmful eddies behind it, for example a more frequent alignment can reduce wind speed by up to 50% thereby protecting buildings or public spaces by limiting damage in the event of a storm or strong wind.

The presence of street alignments has a direct effect on water quality and soil protection. In fact, they regulate the water regime by slowing down the speed of water circulation on the soil surface, favoring its infiltration into the soil, a fact that also limits the soil erosion process. Improves soil quality in particular, plants with rich roots can help strengthen the soil and prevent erosion. They can also filter and absorb pollutants from the soil. In the urban environment, noises reach intensities between 40 and 80 decibels (Vidican, 2021), trees and shrubs help to mitigate them by absorbing and dispersing the sounds.

The integration of plants in the design and management of cities can bring multiple benefits, having a positive impact on the environment and the quality of life of the inhabitants who benefit from places of relaxation and refuge, areas associated with the reduction of stress, anxiety and depression. Also, urban green spaces are ideal places for recreation and relaxation, providing an oasis of tranquility in the urban environment, serving as places for physical activities, encouraging people to go out into nature and practice outdoor sports, thus contributing to physical health and their mental.

Not to be overlooked is the aesthetic

function of street alignments created specifically to enhance the physical appearance of the urban environment, to add beauty and stimulate the visual senses of visitors. A good design allows the choice and association of plant species that bring a varied palette of shapes, colors and textures able to print a special decorative value, appreciated by the satisfaction that man achieves with nature (Dee, 2012), which enhances visual appeal and creates a dynamic and changing environment throughout the year.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

According to Law 24/2007 on the regulation and administration of green spaces in urban areas, the green space represents a harmonized architectural system, made up of elements of the intra-village and extra-village landscape complexes of urban and rural localities (natural landscapes, sectors of water courses and water basins, road constructions, horticultural, residential), important from an aesthetic, biological and ecological point of view, which usually includes a community of vegetation (woody trees, shrubs, flowers and herbs). Looking objectively at the situation of green spaces in big cities, we notice that the creation of large green areas in urban centers is often unfeasible, due to the physical lack of space inside cities (Onose D.A, et al, 2021). A practical solution could be the creation of vegetal groves or corridors, holistically integrated in the urban landscape, which link urban ecosystems together. These smaller green spaces are represented by squares, gardens and street alignments (Zhang et al., 2020).

Nature offers us multiple solutions. It is important to deepen and study the informational flow of data on the urban area, its history and dynamics, so that we can achieve strategic planning in which local priorities are given priority. The expansion in an accelerated dynamic of urban areas to the detriment of the reduction of green spaces inside them has made street alignments, small green spaces, to constitute an architectural alternative capable of contributing to the evolution and prosperity of humanity, but also to ensure the biodiversity of the ecosystem.

In this paper, I have highlighted the importance and the criteria that are the basis of the choice of tree and ornamental shrub species in the realization of street alignments. I extracted the examples from my undergraduate work, which consisted in the arrangement of a section of a

public park on an area of 30000 m² and the current semester project in which I detailed, in my own vision, the way of realization, the importance, planning and design of street alignments.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The man-made landscape represents an aesthetic work in practice, which reflects local cultural traditions and the distinctive character of the place. The management of urban green spaces is not limited only to visual pleasure, but also represents an essential aspect in the creation of attractive, viable cities, oriented towards the well-being of the inhabitants, for which special attention is paid to the correct transposition into practice of the planning principles specific to green spaces (Vidican I.T., 2011).

Street alignments represent an essential component in the development and planning of cities and urban areas with direct implications on the quality of life in the built environment. Current policies involve, in this complex process, the joint decision-making of all concerned parties: urban planners, landscapers and engineers, with the aim of conceiving the safest, practical and aesthetic design and optimal long-lasting results.

In our work, we will only refer to the activity in which the landscape engineer is involved in order to realize some street alignments, the plants used and the criteria underlying their choice, so as to promote biodiversity in the urban environment. A right choice, an attractive design can encourage outdoor activities, provide people with a pleasant place for relaxation, recreation and socialization, balancing the hectic pace of daily life.

In presenting the criteria that are the basis for choosing the type of alignment and the plants used to create them, I will use examples from my undergraduate thesis, which consisted in the design of a park sector on an area of 30,000 m², and from the semester project that is in completion course, specifically that I used the alignments both in the areas designed according to the rigor of the formal style, and the free ones characteristic of the informal or mixed style.

At the basis of the aesthetic design of a green space unit are certain basic principles such as order, harmony and proportion, and in the present case, the rhythm or repetition that expresses the periodic placement of species or

groups of plants. The rhythm facilitates the perception of a composition that it makes accessible to understanding, used properly it increases the expressiveness of the ensemble, its integrity and quality, thus ensuring a recreational framework in which the aesthetic aspects become more meaningful (Vidican I.T., 2012).

Repetition does not always create a pattern, sometimes it is simply the same element or shape being used repeatedly throughout the landscape. In a landscape arrangement, repetition can be achieved most easily by overlapping the constituent materials. Repetition must be used carefully, because too much creates monotony and too little can cause confusion, a delicate balance is necessary to achieve a functional and aesthetically attractive design. When used effectively, repetition can lead to rhythm, focus or emphasis.

The rhythm can be: static, dynamic, simple, compound, linear, shape, color, and of course combinations of these variants.

The static rhythm is achieved by the succession, the planting, at equal distances from each other, of identical plant elements, using within the alignment specimens of the same species, which have the same crown shape, the same height, etc (fig.1). In the case of my projects, I chose this type of alignment to delimit the landscaped space so it becomes visible and easy to spot by the beneficiaries, ensuring both the aesthetic effect and the necessary shade. When choosing leafy plants, the following will be taken into account: the use of species with regular bearing, with a long period of leafing and short leaf fall, which do not pollute the street with flowers or fruits. In the formally arranged area, we chose alignments made of topiary plants characteristic of the style, which give the space elegance and sophistication.

Figure 1. Alignments planted using static rhythm, where: A-on a row; B- in two rows.

The dynamic rhythm obtained by alternating the component elements, which differ from each other in shape, height and other visible characters or are placed at unequal intervals. The diversity of species, colors and heights of plants removes the monotony and artificiality specific to topiary forms. Dynamic repetitions are used when the aim is to gradually increase the expressiveness of rhythmic elements in order to focus attention on a certain object (fig.2). The choice of plants involves both trees and ornamental shrubs, the combination of which will take into account height, crown shape, stem color, leaf color in the growing season and autumn, the period and duration of flowering, as well as the color and abundance of flowers, as an element decorative. In the case of my project, I chose this type of rhythm in the informally arranged area, in the space that delimits the pedestrian alleys in the middle, using as a tree *Magnolia soulangeana* for the extremely decorative aspect of the flowers that open very early in spring, and a decorative shrub, *Photinia red robin* impressive, medium-sized, with a pyramidal crown, tall and compact, but distinguished by the characteristics of extremely attractive leaves in shades of green and red with a glossy surface. In autumn, the foliage gradually changes to intense shades of red, orange and yellow. Flowers in the form of white bouquets, intensely fragrant. In the formal space to delimit the main alleys, we used topiary plants in combination with small trees. When combining different species, it is essential to take into account the space that will be occupied, in the end, by each species so that the roots and branches have enough space not to penetrate the traffic lanes.

Figure 2. Street alignments planted in dynamic rhythm.

The simple rhythm represents a variant of the static rhythm that involves the constant repetition of the same elements or groups of elements, while the compound rhythm is not noticeable by the regularity of the alternation, because it is masked, being perceived through intuition, made from groups similar in terms of

composition and species association, which are repeated periodically.

The linear rhythm is highlighted by vertical repetitions, in which case the emphasis is on the color or shape of the stems or the use of species with a columnar crown. Being a variant of the static rhythm, in my projects I used this type of rhythm using species of *Betula alba*, an extremely decorative tree that is defined by the color of the pronounced white bark with large gray and yellowish plates on the rhythm.

The shape rhythm is highlighted by the repetition of elements similar in shape or volume (fig.). Knowing that the shape represents an important quality in the designed landscape, we will use plant species that are differentiated by this quality, thus to give the space maximum visual weight, we will choose columnar or pendulous species, the vertical crowns add height to the space, while the small, horizontal shapes it directs the gaze along the horizon and adds width to the space. The shape of the plants defines the space, so choosing vertical shapes will dominate the space while plants with large, arched branches will create an open space (Vidican I.T., 2015).

The rhythm of color or lighting is achieved by regular alternation, in a predetermined order of elements of different colors, shades or light intensities, such as for example: alternate planting of specimens with red, silver or light green leaves and dark green, or of specimens with a thick crown or a transparent crown, the choice of alternation, during the vegetation period of the plants that make up the composition (Vidican I.T., 2015).

The final form of a green space is conditioned by the anatomico-functional characteristics and pedo-climatic requirements of the plant material, but also by the structure of the materials from which the architectural and semi-architectural elements are constituted. For this reason, obtaining aesthetic forms involves a complex process determined by the contouring of certain content structures, certain ratios between the various plans, lines and surfaces, certain volumes. This makes the very aesthetic appreciation of shapes relatively more complex than in the case of colors, for example.

In creating plant alignments, the balance between function, form and structure is a necessity, in which the correct use of rhythm also participates as a principle of arranging green spaces, but it is not the only criterion. The choice of species depends on other factors

related to the dynamics of the land, the degree of resistance of the species to noxes, the requirements for pedo-climatic conditions, the role they are to fulfill in the landscaped, functional space: providing shade, screening or aesthetics. For free forms, it is good to choose species that do not require severe cutting, it is also important that when choosing the tree species, take into account their sizes at maturity, but also the shape of the crown in relation to the space it will occupy it, so that we obtain the desired effects (fig.3). In this balance, the function expresses the destination of the product, the form expresses the configuration in which they appear and the structure expresses how the elements that compose the arrangement and the cohesion between them are arranged. In landscape design we must always take into account the approach of integrating the landscaped area into the wider context of the urban habitat.

Figure 3. Plants used in street alignments, where: A- by crown shape; B- after the shadow they cast on the ground.

An important element in the choice of plants is the texture that affects the perception of distance and scale, so this aesthetic value depends on what is in the immediate vicinity, it can change depending on the season or the distance from which the plant composition is observed, it can oscillate and depending on the dimensions of the composition, the shape and density of the foliage. To make a space appear larger, plants with fine textures will be placed along the outer perimeter, medium textures in the middle area, and coarse ones will be found closest to the viewer. The small size and fine texture of the plants make the space to be perceived as deeper. To visually reduce the space, coarse textures will be placed along the outer perimeter, and fine textures as close as possible to the viewer, details of a coarse texture make the plant seem closer and the space smaller (fig.4).

Figure 4. Street alignments in which the color and texture of plants is used.

CONCLUSIONS

The street alignments constitute an integral part of the cultural heritage, through their linearity, regularity and volume, they define the aesthetics of the street representing true transit corridors within the urban fabric;

Basic principles such as: order, harmony and proportion serve for the correct planning of a green space, and rhythm is the main tool in ordering alignments;

The rhythm gives order and coherence to the space, facilitates the perception of the composition and defines the aesthetics of the landscape;

The choice of ornamental trees and shrubs is made according to their aesthetic value, the specific requirements for pedoclimatic conditions and the design of the landscaped space;

Alignments fulfill multiple functions within a habitat: climatic, economic, structural, protective, functional and aesthetic;

The lack of street alignments robs cities of structure, rhythm and coherence, of a sustainable planning strategy, of the benefits they bring and last but not least, of the quality of a design with significant aesthetic aspects.

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NATURAL CONDITIONS REGARDING THE CULTIVATION OF SWEET CORN IN THE BLACK CRISULUI MEADOW

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

The study analyzes the complex interaction between natural conditions and the cultivation of sweet corn in the Black crisului meadow. The research examines the natural conditions specific to this area and the influence on sweet corn production. Detailed understanding of these aspects is significant for the implementation of sustainable and efficient agricultural practices, contributing to increased quality and yield.

The investigation focuses on soil characteristics, evaluating soil pH, moisture, dry matter, organic matter and nutrient analysis. Estel Dessert R68 hybrid used, benefiting from attributes such as cob length and resistance to low temperatures.

The study also addresses the challenges posed by stressors such as temperature, nutritional status and biological pressure. Strategic adjustments to seeding schedules, nutrient management and adoption of resistant varieties help minimize stress. The article finally highlights the prevalent pests and diseases, emphasizing the need for integrated management practices.

Keywords: soil, pH, sweet corn

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INTRODUCTION

The black crisului meadow agriculture, an area with a certain importance in the context, the specific natural conditions. Since natural conditions play an essential role in the development and yield of agricultural crops, this article proposes to analyze in detail the influence of these factors on the production of sweet corn in black Crisului meadow.

Over the decades, agricultural research has highlighted the importance of adapting crops to local conditions, and sweet corn is no exception. The present study focuses on the identification and understanding of the natural conditions specific to this area and how they influence the growth, development and production of the sweet corn crop. Detailed knowledge of these aspects is essential for the implementation of sustainable and efficient

agricultural practices, thus contributing to increasing the yield and quality of agricultural production.

Therefore, the purpose of this article is to bring attention to the natural conditions in the Black River meadow and the impact on the sweet corn crop, providing a detailed perspective on the agricultural environment specific to this area. Through the detailed analysis of these aspects, it is aimed to provide relevant and practical information, useful to both farmers and researchers, to optimize agricultural processes and maximize sweet corn production in this field.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to obtain a detailed research of the pedological characteristics of the black Crisului meadow and the assessment of their

impact on sweet corn crops, we conducted an exhaustive study using rigorous scientific methods. In the framework of these researches, we obtained relevant results, which will be discussed in the results and discussion section:

Soil pH: determination of the soil pH value was achieved through precise measurements, using standardized equipment and techniques (Ardelean I., 2009). We analyzed the level of acidity/neutrality, and the results obtained, with a pH value of 6.70, were essential for researching soil chemical parameters.

Moisture: to evaluate the soil moisture level, we performed measurements at different depths (Ardelean I., 2013). This aspect helped to identify the water requirements of the sweet corn crop according to the variations in soil moisture, the moisture being 64%.

Dry matter: by analyzing the proportion of dry matter in the soil, we obtained information on the degree of compaction and density of the soil, important aspects for the health and development of the root system of plants (Berchez, O. 2005). The dry matter being 36%.

Organic matter: the determination of the content of organic matter was carried out by standardized methods, providing essential data on the fertility of the soil and its ability to support a healthy growth of the crop, the organic matter being 31% (Borza, I. 1997).

Nutrient elements: analysis of total P(0.28% U.S.), total K(1.55% U.S.), total N(2.3% U.S.) and Na(81% U.S.) was performed using advanced laboratory techniques, providing information on the availability of macro and micronutrients in the soil (Domuța C, 2006). These data will be essential in the formulation of fertilization strategies adapted to the specific needs of the sweet corn crop.

Through the detailed analysis of the samples taken from the selected areas, we

have identified the soil in the black Crisului meadow as an albic luvisol. The albic luvisol has a good water retention capacity, its clay and silt content (Brejea, 2010). This feature helps to maintain an optimal level of humidity for the plants.

Albic Luvisol is characterized by a light color, usually whitish, resulting from its significant content of mineral substances (Brejea, 2011). (Fig.1.1.)

Figure 1.1 Albic Luvisol

By using these standardized methods and techniques, we obtained accurate and relevant data about the pedological features of the black Crisului meadow, which will allow us to carry out a detailed analysis and draw fundamental conclusions in the next section, results and discussion.

The Dessert R68 hybrid was used for this research.

Dessert R68 produces cobs about 20-21 cm long.

Each can have between 14 and 16 rows of grains, arranged symmetrically and evenly. This regulated grain distribution ensures consistent quality and aesthetic presentation of the cobs.

One of the notable advantages of the R68 hybrid is its ability to tolerate lower

temperatures than most other sweet corn varieties. This characteristic makes it ideal for early planting or in regions with cool springs.

The tillage technology was as follows:

The first stage was autumn plowing, an essential stage in the soil processing process (Borza, I.M., Stanciu, A.S, 2010).

The benefits of autumn plowing are: soil aeration, mixing plant residues, weed control, pest elimination, soil structure creation, land preparation for sowing (Ciobanu Gh., Domuța, C. 2003). Figure 1.2 illustrates the autumn plowing that was carried out.

Figure 1.2. Autumn plowing of the soil
After autumn ploughing, the next stage was the disc which was carried out in the spring of 2023. The use of the disc helped to prepare an even seed bed. This is very important for a uniform seed distribution and efficient germination (Domuta, C. 2012). Figure 1.3 illustrates the discussion.

Figure 1.3 disc

Sowing in the open field was planned only when the soil temperature reached the 12°C threshold, carefully monitoring the weather forecast to ensure favorable weather conditions. This measure was adopted to promote healthy plant growth.

Inorganic fertilization with NPK was carried out at the time of sowing the sweet corn. NPK fertilization, combining nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P) and potassium (K), is vital for healthy and productive sweet corn crop development.

Nitrogen stimulates vegetative growth, phosphorus supports root development and flowering, and potassium contributes to plant resistance and crop quality (Bhangare RV, et al., 2019).

A quantity of 200 kg per hectare was administered (Orosz F., S. Jakab, T. Losak and K. Slezak, 2009).

6 weeks after sowing, according to the illustration in figure 1.4, the weeding operation was carried out in the vegetation. In this process, a herbicide approved for the culture of sweet corn, namely Laudis, was used in a dose of 2 liters per hectare.

This intervention was aimed at controlling weeds and ensuring a favorable environment for the healthy development of the crop.

Figure 1.4 Herbicide

An approximate production of 55 thousand pieces of sweet corn was obtained which were utilized in local markets, with some sweet corn plants also developing two cobs per plant. The average weight of an ear of sweet corn is 300-400 grams.

Climatic data for the year 2023 in the Black Crişului meadow, Petid village:

Average temperature and precipitation

Figure 1.5 Temperature and precipitation

Figure 1.6 Maximum temperatures

Figure 1.7. The amount of precipitation

One of the significant challenges facing sweet corn crops in the Black Crişului Meadow is the various stress factors that can affect development and production. In this study, we paid particular attention to stress monitoring and management, understanding that this is an essential component to ensure optimal crop yield.

Major topics of interest included water, heat, nutritional stress, and disease and pest challenges.

Thermal stress:

Monitoring extreme temperatures: We analyzed data on extreme temperatures to assess the impact of thermal stress on plants (Domuta C. 2007).

Optimal scheduling: we have adjusted the sowing schedule to avoid periods of extreme temperatures and to minimize exposure of plants to heat stress.

Soil nutritional stress:

Soil nutrient analysis: we examined soil nutrient content to assess their availability to sweet corn crops (IOP Publishing. 2021).

Strategic fertilization: We implemented adapted fertilization strategies, ensuring an adequate supply of nutrients and preventing nutritional stress (Trinurani Sofyan E, Dirga Sapta Sara, 2018).

Disease and pest stress:

Disease and pest monitoring: We identified and monitored the presence of potential pathogens and pests in sweet corn crops.

Integrated Management: We have adopted integrated management approaches, combining preventive practices and curative treatments to minimize stress and protect plant health.

The use of resistant varieties: we cultivated varieties of sweet corn resistant to certain stress conditions, contributing to a more efficient adaptation to the specific environment.

These strategies and measures were implemented in our study to ensure an efficient approach to stress management in sweet corn crops in the Black Crisului

meadow. In the following sections, we will explore the results obtained and discuss the impact of these factors on the production and quality of sweet corn in this specific region.

The main pests encountered in the sweet corn crop include the wireworm (*Agriotes* sp.), and the western cutworm, these pests having the potential to adversely affect yield and plant health.

The main diseases encountered in the Black Crisului meadow in the sweet corn crop are corn rust and gray leaf spot, both of which have the potential to compromise crop health and yield.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Soil pH: The results indicate a pH of 6.70, indicating a slight acidity, optimal for soil chemical parameters.

Moisture: Measurements at different depths reveal essential variations in the water requirements of sweet corn.

The analysis shows adequate proportions of dry matter, reflecting a favorable density for the development of the root system. (Table 1.1.)

Standardized organic matter content indicates adequate fertility to support healthy crop growth.

Tabel 1.1

The pedological characteristics of the soil in the Black Crisului meadow

ANALYZE	U.M	VALUE
pH	-	6,70
Moisture	%	64
Dry substance	%	36
Materie organică	% S.U	31
P total	%S.U	0,28
K total	%S.U	1,55
N total	%S.U	2,3
Na	%S.U	81

Nutrient elements: the detailed results of the analysis indicate the optimal availability of macro and micronutrients, fundamental for the development of sweet corn.

Cob Attributes: The hybrid produces well-structured cobs with 14-16 rows of grain, ensuring consistent quality.

Tolerance to low temperatures: Dessert R68 demonstrates remarkable resistance to lower temperatures, especially in regions with cool firsts.

Fertilization with NPK: administration of 200 kg per hectare ensured an adequate supply of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium.

Herbicide: intervention with herbicides, such as Laudis, helped to control weeds and create a favorable environment for crop development.

Heat stress: adjustments in the sowing schedule minimized the exposure of plants to extreme temperatures.

Nutritional stress: continuous analyzes of soil nutrients facilitated adapted fertilization strategies, preventing nutritional stress.

Disease and pest stress: monitoring and integrated management were essential in protecting the crop.

CONCLUSIONS

The detailed study of agricultural conditions and practices implemented in the production of sweet corn in the black crisului meadow reveals significant conclusions regarding the optimization of yield and the maintenance of crop health. Key findings include:

Detailed understanding of soil pH, moisture and composition has led to the adaptation of agricultural practices to meet the specific requirements of the sweet corn crop.

The hybrid has demonstrated success in providing uniform and well-

developed know, successfully adapting to varying temperatures and soil conditions.

The autumn plowing stages also contributed significantly to the development of the soil structure and to the creation of a favorable environment for germination and development.

Soil nutrient analysis and proper NPK administration ensured optimal availability of essential nutrients for healthy plant growth.

Appropriate interventions, such as weeding and management of thermal, nutritional and disease stress, helped to maintain crop health and minimize the negative impact of stressors.

The results of this study provide the basis for continuous improvement and optimization of agricultural practices in order to maximize the yield and quality of sweet corn production in the Black Crisului Negra meadow.

In conclusion, the implementation of a well-defined set of agricultural practices, adapted to local characteristics, represents an essential strategy for obtaining a sustainable and quality production in the sweet corn crop in this region.

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UPCYCLED TREAT: RETHINKING CONSUMPTION AND RECOGNIZING THE POSITIVE IMPACT OF UPCYCLED FOOD PRODUCTS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

Abstract

This study addresses the global challenge of food waste by investigating consumer awareness and the impact of upcycled food products. We aim to develop sustainable solutions by transforming nearly wasted supermarket fruits and vegetables into value-added products through fermentation. The project utilizes a fermentation process to enhance the nutritional value and extend the shelf life of the products. Methods include forming partnerships with local supermarkets, securing a fermentation facility, and complying with safety regulations. We promote consumer consciousness through social media and provide a unique app to track the carbon footprint of each product. Results indicate that fermentation is an efficient, low-cost method to preserve food while maintaining its organoleptic properties. The upcycled products appeal to health-conscious consumers, contributing to sustainability by reducing food waste and encouraging environmentally friendly consumption habits. This approach was started in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, and has the potential to be expanded to other regions, fostering broader adoption of upcycled food products. The findings displayed the viability of using nearly wasted food for upcycling, presenting a scalable model for sustainable food production.

Keywords: Upcycling, upcycled food, food waste, fermentation, sustainability, carbon footprint

INTRODUCTION

Food waste has received attention in the past years. Globally, about 1.3 billion tonnes of food worth USD 1 trillion (FAO, 2015) are wasted annually, representing a significant problem that demands immediate attention (FAO, 2011). Food wastage occurs at all stages in the food supply chain namely in the production, storage, processing, distribution, retail, food service, and consumption (FAO 2013). In Europe, 40% of waste is produced at the production, handling/storage, and processing stages while the other 60% is at the distribution, retail, and consumption stage (Lipinski et al., 2013). This is associated with the carbon footprint, which is an index to determine the total amount of greenhouse gases produced by human activities that add to the atmosphere (Pandey and Agrawal, 2010). These greenhouse gases cause a rapid rise in global temperature, which leads to global warming and climate change. To minimize the problem of food waste and its effects on the environment, food upcycling is one of the effective ways. According to the Upcycled Food Association, food upcycling is the process of transforming food into new products or ingredients of better quality that

would otherwise end in the food

destination. These upcycled foods are value-added foods that are produced or processed in a way that increases their economic value. By taking part in the solution of reducing waste, can ensure food security for the rapidly increasing population to provide the necessary calories and nutrients for over seven billion people. Upcycled Treat is a business idea based in Cluj-Napoca, Romania, where it aims to address the issue of food waste through the use of innovative solutions for the nearly-wasted foods in supermarkets, particularly fruits and vegetables. The approach involves the use of fermentation techniques to upcycle fruits and vegetables, allowing them to be preserved longer while enhancing their nutritional value. This business idea can substantially help to reduce food waste, as it is not only easy to implement but also resource-efficient, as fermentation is a straightforward process and nearly wasted food products can be sourced at lower costs. On the other hand, it is well-known that consumers often prefer visually appealing fruits and vegetables. However, when ugly and nearly-discarded fruits and vegetables are upcycled and transformed into ready-to-consume finished products, their appearance becomes less critical, yet they

remain attractive and edible to consumers. Moreover, consumers are more likely to engage in sustainability initiatives and efforts to reduce food waste when they are empowered with sufficient knowledge and information about food upcycling and carbon footprints. Therefore, the objective of this research is to conduct a business analysis using methodologies such as SWOT analysis and Porter's Five Forces. This analysis aims to identify effective strategies for launching the upcycled treat business while simultaneously empowering consumers through the implementation of a QR code system in the products. This system will enable consumers to track and understand the carbon footprint associated with the food products they consume.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The strategic planning of the business, which involved scouting/profiling of retail shops and supermarkets, establishing partnerships, procuring raw materials and processing equipment, processing products, and marketing and promotion, was conducted in Cluj-Napoca, Romania. The framework of this research was created to generate a business opportunity for upcycled foods from nearly wasted fruits and vegetables and transform them into value-added products through fermentation. Additionally, the incorporation of a QR code system was introduced in the packaging to track the carbon footprint of the products and to raise awareness among the consumers on their role in contributing to sustainability and environment preservation. This idea was conceptualized to leverage the market growth of upcycled foods, particularly in Europe. SWOT Analysis and Porter's 5 Forces were used for analyzing and visualizing the implications of the upcycled products in the market.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Creating value-added products using almost wasted foods is not a new practice. Converting them into foods or ingredients for foods are just some examples of how to maximize their use. Several available and easy techniques could be used to create innovative products that are both environmentally friendly and of high quality. One such technique is the fermentation process, which involves the use of microbial enzymes to convert sugar into acids, gas, or alcohol (Taviera et al., 2021). Nowadays, fermentation has been widely used to improve

the shelf life of raw foods while maintaining their organoleptic characteristics and nutritional properties. Additionally, from an economic standpoint, the fermentation technique is considered an inexpensive process that requires minimal energy to preserve foods (Samtiya et al., 2021). To better understand the competitive advantages and disadvantages of the business idea of Upcycled Treat, a SWOT analysis was conducted to assess the factors affecting the business model.

SWOT Analysis

Strengths

Innovative product development in upcycled fermented foods offers significant opportunities to experiment with various fermentation techniques, ingredients, and flavors. Also, it is easier to create unique products for consumers with diverse preferences and dietary needs. The fermentation technique can enhance the nutritional profile and shelf-life of food products, while also creating unique flavors and experiences for consumers (Savor et al., 2018). The techniques that can be used are lactic acid fermentation, ethanol fermentation, and acetic acid fermentation. Moreover, these techniques can create products using food by-products such as fruit peels vegetable scraps, and other novel ingredients to develop unique flavors that can attract modern culinary and mainstream markets. Aside from its innovative concept, it also supports sustainability and quality. Nowadays, consumers support brands that align with their values of environmental sustainability and health consciousness. With proper brand positioning, the company can attract a loyal customer base and differentiate themselves from others.

Opportunities

Cluj-Napoca has numerous academic and research institutions with expertise in food technology and business. Partnering and collaborating with these local institutions can enhance product innovation and visibility. Aside from that, Romania has rich traditional practices of fermented foods such as sauerkraut and pickles, which can be adapted and marketed using modern fermentation techniques. Upcycled Treat is advantageous since it provides a strong foundation for consumer acceptance and product differentiation. On the other hand,

fermented products have become popular in recent years due to their health advantages, unique flavors, and contribution to sustainability. Thus, making these foods more and more popular. According to a market research report conducted by Business Research Insights, the global market for fermented food products is expected to increase from USD 1425.3 million in 2022 to USD 2131.53 million by 2031 with a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CGAR) of 46% during the forecast. Through this, Upcycled Treat can leverage the trends and popularity of fermented products such as Kombucha and sauerkraut to attract more health-conscious demographics.

Weaknesses

Cluj Napoca is situated in a region with a diverse agricultural base, providing various potential raw materials for upcycled food production. However, the availability of these materials is influenced by seasonal variability. Since agricultural products used for fermentation are only sometimes available throughout the year, it affects the quantities of fermented products to be produced. For instance, the production of some fruits and vegetables peaks during certain months, resulting in varying quantities of waste and by-products available for upcycling throughout the year.

Treats

Consumer perception of upcycled foods plays a critical role in the success of the business. While there is a growing awareness and acceptance of sustainable practices among consumers, there are still some consumers who are skeptical about the safety, quality, and nutritional content of waste products (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2015). Marketing efforts must focus on educating consumers about the health benefits and sustainability aspects of upcycled fermented foods to improve acceptance and drive demand (Parfitt et al., 2010).

One of the primary challenges in establishing an upcycled food business is navigating the complex and evolving landscape of food safety regulations. The European Union has strict food safety standards that must be met, which include regulations on the production, labeling, and sale of fermented foods. Compliance with these regulations is essential to ensure product safety and gain consumer trust (European Commission, 2020).

Additionally, local regulations in Romania must be followed, which may require constant monitoring and adjustments to business practices to stay compliant (Romanian Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, 2019).

Porter's Five Forces Analysis

Competitive Rivalry

The market for upcycled products is valued at approximately \$53.7 billion and is projected to increase to \$97 billion by 2031 (Upcycled Food Association, 2021). This significant growth attracts a substantial number of competitors, intensifying competitive rivalry. Upcycled Treat must strategically position itself to differentiate from competitors. Key strategies include product differentiation, unique selling propositions, and innovative marketing approaches to maintain a competitive edge in this expanding market (Porter, 2008). This will give the company a better view of the market and its offerings.

Buyer power

The buyer power in the upcycled products market is relatively high due to the broad consumer interest in sustainable products (Nielsen, 2018). The substantial number of buyers in the market can lead to increased price negotiations, potentially driving prices down. To mitigate this influence, Upcycled Treat must focus on maintaining high levels of customer satisfaction and loyalty. Strategies such as offering premium product quality, ensuring transparent sourcing, and providing excellent customer service are essential in fostering a loyal customer base less sensitive to price variations (Kotler & Keller, 2016). Consumers exhibit low price sensitivity towards upcycled products, as many are willing to pay a premium for products that contribute to environmental sustainability (Euromonitor International, 2020). Upcycled Treat's value proposition includes not only the quality of the product but also its positive environmental impact. This low price sensitivity can be leveraged to maintain robust profit margins while emphasizing the ecological benefits associated with the products (White et al., 2019). Additionally, Upcycled Treat has developed a mobile app that allows consumers to track the carbon footprints of their purchases. This app enables all involved actors to add information about the product each time it is transferred from one place or phase to

another, providing transparency and fostering a deeper connection between consumers and the environmental impact of their purchases. This innovative feature can enhance customer loyalty by promoting eco-conscious purchasing decisions.

Threat of Substitution

The threat of substitution for Upcycled Treat's products is high due to the availability of alternative products or solutions. The ability of buyers to substitute upcycled products with alternatives is relatively high, mainly due to the current low familiarity with upcycled foods. Grasso and Asioli (2020) reported that 85% of consumers were not familiar with upcycled foods. However, there is a potential for market growth, as consumers are willing to consider purchasing upcycled products to help the environment, reduce food waste, and explore new flavors. Upcycled Treat can address this by educating consumers on the benefits of upcycled foods, highlighting their unique tastes, and promoting their positive environmental impact (Grasso & Asioli, 2020). Upcycled Treat should concentrate on offering unique value propositions and differentiation to combat this threat. Emphasizing the superior quality, unique taste profiles, and clear environmental benefits of its products can help in building a loyal customer base. Additionally, continuous innovation and adaptation to consumer preferences can further reduce the threat of substitution, ensuring that Upcycled Treat remains a preferred choice among consumers (Porter, 2008).

Threat of New Entrants

The threat of new entrants into Upcycled Treat's market is also high. If new competitors can quickly enter the market, they may weaken Upcycled Treat's position. To counter this threat, Upcycled Treat should focus on building barriers to entry such as brand loyalty, unique product offerings, and strong partnerships (Barney, 1991). Utilizing specialist knowledge, such as the ability to transform nearly discarded products into value-added food items through fermentation, provides a significant advantage (Schanes et al., 2018). Collaborating with other upcycled food manufacturers or organizations throughout the food supply chain can help achieve economies of scale. From a future research perspective, it is important to ensure that economic measures are included alongside the environmental and

social impacts of individualized upcycled food initiatives to ensure the industry's financial viability and growth (Rogers et al., 2019).

Supplier Power

The Supplier power in the upcycled food industry can vary depending on the availability of nearly discarded products and the relationships with suppliers. Since Upcycled Treat sources its raw materials primarily from surplus produce that would otherwise go to waste, supplier power may be lower compared to traditional food production. However, forming strong partnerships with suppliers, such as local supermarkets and farmers, can ensure a consistent supply of raw materials at favorable terms. By leveraging these relationships, Upcycled Treat can maintain a stable supply chain and reduce the risk of supplier power negatively impacting its operations (Gereffi et al., 2005).

By systematically addressing these five forces, Upcycled Treat can effectively navigate the competitive landscape, capitalize on consumer trends toward sustainability, and establish a strong, differentiated brand in the growing market for upcycled products.

CONCLUSIONS

The study demonstrates that upcycling nearly wasted supermarket fruits and vegetables through fermentation is a viable and effective approach to reducing food waste. The fermentation process not only preserves the nutritional value and extends the shelf life of these products but also appeals to health-conscious consumers, contributing to sustainable consumption practices. The project's success in Cluj-Napoca highlights the potential for scaling this model to other regions, fostering broader adoption of upcycled food products. By leveraging partnerships with local supermarkets and utilizing a unique app to track carbon footprints, Upcycled Treat promotes environmental consciousness among consumers. The results underscore the economic and environmental benefits of upcycling, presenting a sustainable and scalable solution to global food waste challenges. Future research should explore the economic impacts and scalability of such initiatives to ensure long-term viability and industry growth.

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THE NEXUS BETWEEN ANIMAL NUTRITION, HEALTH, AND ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY IN RURAL AREAS

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REVIEW

Abstract

This review examines the interconnectedness of animal nutrition, health, and environmental sustainability, with a specific focus on rural settings. It aims to uncover how improvements in animal nutrition can positively impact both the health of livestock and the sustainability of rural environments. This exploration is crucial for understanding the role of animal agriculture in supporting rural livelihoods, ensuring food security, and driving economic growth, while also considering its environmental ramifications.

Key findings from the review point to a significant link between enhanced animal nutrition and improved health outcomes for livestock, which in turn can lead to more efficient use of resources and a reduction in the environmental impacts of farming practices. Specifically, the adoption of sustainable nutritional strategies, such as the use of environmentally friendly feed and precision feeding techniques, has been shown to improve livestock productivity while simultaneously minimizing waste and reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

The implications of these findings are profound for the sustainable development of rural areas. By adopting sustainable animal nutrition practices, rural communities can achieve a dual goal: enhancing the economic viability of livestock farming and preserving environmental quality.

Keywords: animal nutrition, environmental sustainability, rural development, livestock health, sustainable farming practices

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INTRODUCTION

In the rural tapestry, animal agriculture emerges as a cornerstone, pivotal to livelihoods, nutritional well-being, and the economic vibrancy of communities. Ellis (2000) underscores its role in fortifying livelihoods and catalyzing economic stability through employment and income generation. This diversity in rural livelihoods, inclusive of animal husbandry, is instrumental in poverty alleviation and the broader rural development agenda, opening avenues for income generation and economic resilience.

Moreover, the role of animal agriculture in buttressing food security and nutritional adequacy in rural areas cannot be overstated. As highlighted by Brown et al. (2020), domestic livestock production furnishes rural populations with a sustainable protein source, essential nutrients, and dietary diversity, thereby contributing to enhanced nutritional outcomes and general well-being. The

incorporation of livestock products into local diets is vital for nutritional fulfillment and securing food security in rural settings, demonstrating the integral link between animal husbandry and the health of rural communities. Animal agriculture also acts as an economic catalyst in rural areas, spurring local economies into a cycle of growth and prosperity. Davis & López-Carr (2014) detail how livestock farming boosts revenue through the sale of products, thereby energizing local markets, businesses, and agricultural value chains. Beyond mere farm gate sales, the economic contributions of animal agriculture extend to fostering economic diversification and enhancing the livelihoods of rural communities, highlighting the multifaceted impact of livestock on rural economies.

The pursuit of sustainable animal agriculture practices holds the promise of advancing environmental conservation, resource efficiency, and the health of ecosystems in rural landscapes (Gheorghe-Irimia et al., 2023).

Briedenhann & Wickens (2004) advocate for sustainable farming methodologies like agroecology and integrated systems, which elevate soil fertility, conserve natural resources, and mitigate environmental degradation. These sustainable practices are crucial for preserving biodiversity, soil health, and ecosystem services, underpinning the long-term sustainability of rural landscapes, thereby underscoring the essential balance between agriculture and environmental stewardship.

Central to the efficacy and sustainability of livestock farming is animal nutrition, a significant determinant of livestock health, growth, and productivity (Petrean et al., 2024, Colibar et al., 2013). Kadiyala et al. (2014) accentuate the direct impact of nutritional status on farm incomes and economic well-being, with Smith et al. (2005) emphasizing the importance of nutritional quality in animal products for addressing malnutrition and promoting health in rural areas. This connection between nutrition and economic stability in rural settings is a critical area for intervention.

However, animal production is not without its environmental challenges. Moraes et al. (2014) and MacLeod et al. (2018) point to the substantial greenhouse gas emissions from livestock farming, necessitating mitigation strategies to diminish the sector's environmental footprint. The environmental degradation associated with livestock farming, as noted by Leinonen (2019) and Koneswaran & Nierenberg (2008), calls for sustainable practices and technologies to enhance feed efficiency, optimize nutrient management, and valorize waste, emphasizing the need for environmental consciousness in livestock management.

Confronting the environmental challenges of animal production demands a multifaceted strategy that embraces sustainable practices, informed policy-making, and active stakeholder engagement. Nayaka et al. (2018) and Moraes et al. (2012) emphasize the need for collaborative efforts to forge a balance between the economic imperatives of animal production and the imperatives of environmental conservation and climate resilience. This collective approach is essential for ensuring that animal agriculture contributes positively to the sustainability and development of rural areas. In light of this backdrop, the aim of this review is to meticulously explore how improvements in animal nutrition can amplify health outcomes and bolster environmental sustainability in

rural settings, thereby informing policies and practices that support sustainable development and resilience in these communities.

THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN ANIMAL NUTRITION AND ANIMAL HEALTH

The nexus between animal nutrition and health emerges as a fundamental aspect of livestock production, a notion increasingly supported by scholarly research. Central to this discourse is the understanding that nutrition underpins not only the basic metabolic functions but also significantly influences animal health, productivity, and longevity. According to Onyango et al. (2019), the nutritional needs of livestock are dictated by a myriad of factors, including species-specific requirements and environmental conditions. This complexity necessitates tailored, region- and season-specific nutritional strategies to address variations in the nutritive value of feedstuffs, which are further impacted by climate and soil conditions (Onyango et al., 2019).

Delving deeper, Costa et al. (2021) shed light on the intricate nutritional needs and their varied impacts across different livestock species, emphasizing the profound role of nutrition in aspects such as growth, feed intake, and feed efficiency (Murdoch et al., 2016). It is crucial to acknowledge that satisfying these nutritional requirements is paramount for optimal health and performance (Woelber & Vach, 2022), with a growing recognition of nutrition's pivotal role in sustaining animal health beyond mere sustenance (Ameye & Chee, 2006).

Expanding on this notion, Pencharz & Ball (2004) argue for the necessity of understanding the diverse nutritional requirements among livestock to optimize their growth and development. Furthermore, innovative dietary interventions, such as the inclusion of mustard and cumin seeds, have been demonstrated to enhance feed utilization, milk production, and the overall nutritional status in goats, thereby indicating lactational performance improvements and health and productivity enhancements as reflected by nutritional status markers like serum total proteins (Morsy et al., 2018).

This leads to the understanding that the provision of high-quality feed and adequate nutrition is critical for supporting the immune system, enhancing livestock resilience to diseases and infections, and thus improving their overall well-being and productivity (Mlejnková et al., 2016). Equally important is

the impact of maternal mineral nutrition during critical fetal development stages, highlighting its long-term influence on the productivity and longevity of livestock (Anas et al., 2023).

The thread of nutrition extends to its direct linkage with livestock productivity. Proper feeding practices significantly influence various productivity traits, including growth, milk production, reproductive performance, and longevity (Torre et al., 2015; Martini et al., 2021). Villalba et al. (2019) further illuminate the importance of managing nutritional doses and interactions among nutrients to ensure optimal health and beneficial phytochemical ingestion.

Additionally, dietary strategies, such as reducing protein and specific amino acids (e.g., methionine), have been correlated with health and lifespan benefits in livestock, underscoring the role of nutrition in promoting longevity (Hoffman & Valencak, 2020). The adaptability and resilience of local livestock breeds further contribute to their longevity, emphasizing the significance of targeted breeding strategies for enhancing feed efficiency and lifetime productivity (Agustine et al., 2023; Chagas et al., 2019).

Transitioning to the economic perspective, improved animal health through nutritional management offers significant economic advantages for rural farmers, by reducing veterinary costs and boosting productivity. This minimization of disease and infection decreases the necessity for expensive veterinary interventions, while healthy livestock demonstrate improved feed conversion efficiency, resulting in increased output and profitability (Zanon et al., 2021; Robi, 2023; Ha et al., 2022). Moreover, the health status of livestock positively influences market access and the potential to command higher prices for their products, aligning with consumer expectations for animal welfare and food safety (Geary et al., 2012; Zanon et al., 2021; Robi, 2023).

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPLICATIONS OF ANIMAL NUTRITION

Optimizing animal nutrition stands at the forefront of enhancing resource efficiency within livestock production, embodying a pivotal role in elevating feed conversion rates and diminishing water consumption. Moorby & Fraser (2021) articulate that through the adoption of innovative feeding strategies and bespoke nutritional plans, farmers are

positioned to actualize more judicious resource utilization, yielding benefits for both the environment and the economy. Such efficient management of nutrition directly influences feed conversion rates, facilitating a more effective transformation of feed into animal products like meat, milk, and eggs. This not only mitigates the demand for feed per unit of product but also amplifies the productivity of livestock systems, as elucidated by Valdez-Arjona & Ramírez-Mella (2019) and further supported by Herrero et al. (2013), who champion the optimization of dietary nutritional content for achieving heightened feed conversion efficiency.

Moreover, the pursuit of optimized nutrition contributes significantly to water conservation in livestock production. Precisely balanced diets can curtail excessive nutrient excretion, thereby alleviating water pollution and fostering improved water management practices (Zhao et al., 2023; Zanten et al., 2018). This nuanced approach to nutrition management extends its benefits to the sustainable utilization of arable land and other pivotal resources. By ensuring livestock receive essential nutrients in accurate proportions, farmers can maximize land productivity while simultaneously minimizing environmental footprints, a concept explored by Hegarty et al. (2007) and further expanded upon by Hejna et al. (2021), who underscore the role of sustainable feeding systems in augmenting resource efficiency and bolstering the long-term sustainability of livestock production.

Addressing environmental pollution emerges as a critical concern within the sphere of livestock production, where inefficient management practices contribute significantly to issues such as water pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and soil degradation (Huis & Oonincx, 2017). However, the integration of enhanced nutritional practices offers a pathway to mitigate these adverse impacts, promoting environmental sustainability. A notable strategy in reducing waste production involves the utilization of by-products and waste materials as feed, exemplified by the repurposing of almond by-products and pumpkin waste, thereby diminishing organic waste contributions to pollution (García-Pérez et al., 2021; Valdez-Arjona & Ramírez-Mella, 2019). This circular economy approach to resource utilization is echoed by Rakita et al. (2021), advocating for the minimization of waste production.

Innovative nutritional strategies, such as the incorporation of insect-based feeds or the inclusion of fruit and vegetable waste into animal diets, represent progressive steps towards reducing waste generation and environmental pollution (Seyedalmoosavi et al., 2022; Tedesco et al., 2021). The revaluation of waste materials as feed ingredients facilitates the reduction of waste disposal and fosters a more sustainable livestock production system (Kalyahe et al., 2022). Such approaches, highlighted by Pinotti et al. (2019) and Poveda (2021), underscore the significance of alternative and sustainable feed sources in diminishing the environmental footprint of agriculture, promoting resource efficiency, and enhancing the sustainability of livestock production.

Insects emerge as a sustainable alternative to conventional livestock feeds, offering an efficient and effective protein source. Reared on organic waste, insects convert waste into valuable nutrients for livestock, thereby fostering the principles of a circular economy and minimizing environmental pollution (Poveda, 2021). Simultaneously, the conversion of by-products from food processing industries into livestock feed represents a sustainable maneuver to reduce waste and augment resource efficiency. This strategy not only contributes to the reduction of organic waste disposal but also optimizes the use of available resources, providing a sustainable solution for the integration of food by-products into animal nutrition (Pinotti et al., 2019, Mierlita et al., 2022).

Additionally, the incorporation of plant-based by-products and agricultural waste streams into animal diets enhances the sustainability of livestock production. By leveraging these alternative feed sources, farmers can mitigate the environmental impact of agriculture, champion efficient resource utilization, and contribute to a more sustainable food system (Sorjonen et al., 2019, Tudor et al., 2023, Şonea et al., 2023). These innovative feed alternatives offer a pragmatic solution for minimizing waste production and reducing the environmental footprint of livestock farming, underlining the essential role of optimized animal nutrition in the pursuit of environmental sustainability.

SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES AND INNOVATIONS

The advent of precision management in animal nutrition and health epitomizes the confluence of advanced technologies and methodologies designed to refine feeding strategies, closely monitor health parameters, and make well-informed decisions within livestock production systems. Gonzalez et al. (2018) assert that such precision-oriented approaches are geared towards bolstering animal welfare, augmenting productivity, and curtailing environmental repercussions. A pivotal element in this domain is the employment of biomarkers and novel protein design for customizing amino acid nutrition in livestock diets, as delineated by Cambra-López et al. (2022). This individualized tactic not only caters precisely to the amino acid requisites of animals, fostering their optimal growth and health, but also facilitates more efficient nutrient utilization and minimizes waste output in livestock operations.

Further expanding on precision nutrition, technologies encompassing omics tools, bioinformatics, and metabolomics stand at the forefront of predicting and optimizing the nutritional impacts on animal health, as highlighted by Toro-Martín et al. (2017). These technological advancements offer insights into how individual animals respond to specific diets, enabling the tailoring of personalized nutrition plans that bolster metabolic health and prevent diseases.

In the broader landscape of precision livestock farming, Menendez et al. (2022) emphasize the significance of mathematical modeling and data-driven methodologies in refining animal nutrition and management practices. The deployment of virtual fencing and sensor systems for real-time surveillance of animal behavior and health indicators empowers precise livestock management across vast terrains, thus enhancing resource efficiency, environmental sustainability, and overall production system efficacy.

Integrated farming systems are championed as a linchpin for sustainability in agriculture, facilitating nutrient recycling and waste reduction through the amalgamation of diverse agricultural pursuits such as crop cultivation, livestock rearing, and waste management (Ayantunde et al., 2018). By reincorporating livestock manure back into the soil, these systems enrich it with vital nutrients essential for crop production, thereby reducing reliance

on synthetic fertilizers, curtailing waste, and sustainably promoting soil health and fertility. Smallholder farms stand to gain immensely from the implementation of industrial symbiosis principles, orchestrating material and energy flows to enhance resource optimization and waste reduction (Alfaro & Miller, 2013). Establishing symbiotic linkages within the farming ecosystem, like repurposing crop residues as livestock feed or using animal manure as crop fertilizer, amplifies efficiency and diminishes environmental impacts. Moreover, integrated farming systems advocate for waste bioconversion and recycling, transforming organic waste into valuable resources such as compost or biogas, thereby not only mitigating waste accumulation but also generating renewable energy and improving soil health (E.Y. et al., 2022). Emphasizing integrated nutrient management, these systems encourage the on-farm production of organic manures and the recycling of farm wastes to supplant inorganic fertilizers, enhancing soil fertility, minimizing nutrient runoff, and elevating crop productivity in an eco-friendly fashion (Siddappa et al., 2023). Supportive policies and robust community engagement are indispensable for the fruition of sustainable practices within agriculture. Policies championing sustainability set the stage for farmers to embrace eco-conscious practices, guiding decisions towards enduring environmental stewardship (Kang, 2018; Buchan & Aiken, 2008). Simultaneously, engaging local communities in sustainable farming endeavors not only cultivates awareness and participation but also ingrains a sense of communal responsibility towards environmental preservation (Munasib & Jordan, 2011). Community participation further bolsters the adoption of sustainable practices, through social support, resource sharing, and a collective environmental ethos. Initiatives like farmer-to-farmer networks and community gardens provide platforms for knowledge exchange, skill enhancement, and mutual support in sustainable practice implementation (Ohmer et al., 2009). Additionally, community-university partnerships emerge as vital conduits for advancing sustainable agriculture education and civic engagement, facilitating access to expertise, research, and educational resources, thereby fostering the development of sustainable solutions attuned to local needs

(Zhu et al., 2018; Riedel, 2015; Niewolny et al., 2012).

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

Rural communities are often confronted with significant challenges in adopting sustainable nutritional practices for livestock, encompassing economic constraints and informational deficits. These challenges serve as impediments to transitioning towards farming practices that are not only environmentally friendly but also efficient in resource utilization. Economic barriers are particularly formidable, where limited financial resources may preclude farmers from investing in sustainable feed options, securing veterinary care, or adopting technologies that enhance animal health and welfare (Patel & Sabapara, 2023). The financial burden associated with adopting advanced feeding management practices, acquiring quality feed, or implementing sustainable farming techniques poses a significant obstacle, especially for smallholder farmers operating within resource-limited environments (Patel & Sabapara, 2023).

The scarcity of information and awareness about sustainable nutritional practices constitutes another critical challenge. Farmers' restricted access to knowledge, training, or resources concerning sustainable animal nutrition impairs their capacity to make well-informed decisions and adopt best practices (Maliotou & Liarakou, 2022). A lack of awareness regarding the advantages of sustainable practices and insufficient training in eco-friendly farming techniques further complicates the adoption of such methods in animal husbandry (Maliotou & Liarakou, 2022). Compounded by inadequate infrastructure and support systems, these challenges exacerbate the difficulties faced by rural communities in embracing sustainable nutritional practices. Limited access to extension services, veterinary care, and markets for sustainable products restricts farmers' ability to transition to more sustainable operations (Shiferaw et al., 2008). Practical constraints, such as the poor availability of seeds, the absence of irrigation facilities, and a lack of knowledge in balanced ration formulation, further impede the adoption of sustainable practices (Patel & Sabapara, 2023).

Addressing these challenges necessitates the implementation of supportive policies, community engagement, and capacity-building initiatives. Policies that offer incentives for

sustainable practices, alongside financial support and promotion of knowledge sharing, can facilitate overcoming economic barriers and foster the adoption of sustainable nutritional practices (Piñeiro et al., 2020). Community engagement efforts that elevate awareness, provide training, and encourage collaboration among farmers are pivotal in enhancing the dissemination of information and uptake of sustainable methods. Furthermore, capacity-building programs aimed at improving access to resources, advancing technical skills, and reinforcing local support networks are critical in empowering rural communities to embrace sustainable nutritional practices for livestock (Kebede, 2020).

Future research and development in the realm of animal nutrition and health present promising avenues for innovation and progress in sustainable practices. Investigating novel feed ingredients, such as bioactive substances derived from plants like curcumin, offers potential for innovative feed additives that contribute to animal health, growth, and disease prevention while minimizing antibiotic use and promoting sustainable farming practices (Pan et al., 2022). The exploration of exosome-based vaccines introduces an avant-garde approach to animal health, with the potential to transform vaccination strategies against veterinary infectious diseases, enhancing vaccine efficacy, safety, and animal immune response (Montaner-Tarbes et al., 2021). Moreover, advancements in genetic selection for efficiency and resilience in livestock promise to elevate productivity and sustainability in animal production systems. Future research endeavors should also prioritize the strategic use of feed ingredients and additives to bolster gut health and nutrient utilization in young animals, alongside the exploration of sustainable feed sources such as insect-based feeds and yeast proteins, to provide viable solutions for aquaculture and livestock nutrition (Agboola et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this review has delved into the intricate nexus between animal nutrition, health, and environmental sustainability, uncovering a multifaceted relationship that underscores the importance of integrated approaches for achieving sustainable development in rural areas. The key findings reveal that optimized animal nutrition not only enhances livestock health and productivity but

also plays a pivotal role in mitigating environmental impacts associated with livestock farming. Through precision nutrition, the adoption of sustainable feed sources, and innovative breeding strategies, stakeholders can significantly contribute to more efficient resource use, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, and improvement in animal welfare. The implications of these findings for rural development are profound. Sustainable nutritional practices offer a pathway to bolstering the resilience of rural communities, enhancing food security, and promoting economic stability. To capitalize on these benefits, there is a need for policies that support the adoption of sustainable animal nutrition practices. Such policies should aim to reduce economic barriers, improve access to information and resources, and foster infrastructure development. Furthermore, the integration of sustainable practices into rural development strategies can enhance soil health, reduce dependency on chemical inputs, and promote biodiversity, thereby contributing to the overall sustainability of rural landscapes.

A collective effort from farmers, policymakers, and researchers is essential to realize the potential of sustainable animal nutrition strategies fully. Farmers play a crucial role in implementing these practices on the ground and can benefit from support in the form of training, access to sustainable feed options, and incentives for adopting environmentally friendly practices. Policymakers are tasked with creating an enabling environment through supportive legislation, funding mechanisms, and awareness campaigns that highlight the benefits of sustainable nutrition practices. Researchers, on the other hand, must continue to innovate and provide evidence-based recommendations that guide the development and implementation of effective and efficient nutrition strategies.

In urging stakeholders to collaborate, the call to action is clear: by working together to pursue sustainable animal nutrition strategies, it is possible to achieve a triple win of enhancing animal health, promoting environmental sustainability, and supporting the socio-economic development of rural communities. The path forward requires a commitment to innovation, sustainability, and collaboration, principles that will guide efforts to ensure a resilient and prosperous future for rural areas worldwide.

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CLIMATE-SMART LIVESTOCK: INTEGRATING AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES IN PASTURE MANAGEMENT FOR ENHANCED ENVIRONMENTAL BENEFITS

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REVIEW

Abstract

This review article provides a comprehensive examination of climate-smart livestock practices, emphasizing their pivotal role in advancing sustainable agricultural development amidst escalating climate change challenges. Climate-smart livestock practices, characterized by their ability to enhance agricultural productivity, improve resource utilization efficiency, and bolster resilience to climate variability, offer a transformative approach to livestock farming. These practices not only aim to sustain agricultural output but also to mitigate the adverse environmental impacts traditionally associated with livestock farming, such as greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity loss.

A significant focus of the article is on the integration of agroforestry within pasture management as a core climate-smart strategy. Agroforestry, the practice of integrating trees with crops and livestock within agricultural systems, is presented as a multifaceted solution that addresses the ecological drawbacks of conventional livestock farming. This sustainable approach contributes to enhanced biodiversity, soil conservation, and improved water management, establishing a harmonious balance between agricultural productivity and environmental stewardship.

The anticipated environmental benefits of adopting climate-smart livestock practices, particularly through agroforestry, are highlighted. These benefits include the sequestration of carbon, reduction in soil erosion, enhancement of soil fertility, and preservation of water resources. By delineating the potential for significant environmental improvements, the article underscores the necessity of adopting and scaling up climate-smart practices within livestock farming. The integration of these practices not only promises to transform the landscape of agriculture in the face of climate change but also to ensure food security, enhance the resilience of farming communities, and contributes to the global pursuit of sustainability.

Keywords: climate-smart livestock practices, agroforestry integration, sustainable agriculture, environmental benefits, pasture management

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INTRODUCTION

The introduction of climate-smart livestock practices represents a significant evolution in agricultural methodologies, aimed at enhancing productivity, improving resource utilization efficiency, and increasing resilience to the impacts of climate change within livestock farming operations (Șonea et al., 2023). These practices are central to the advancement of sustainable agricultural development, offering strategic solutions to the complex challenges posed by global climate alterations. Defined by their ability to elevate agricultural output in a sustainable manner, optimize resource use, reduce climate variability vulnerability, and minimize greenhouse gas emissions, climate-

smart livestock practices embody an innovative approach to agriculture (Aryal et al., 2018).

The importance of these practices extends beyond operational improvements, delivering substantial benefits to animal welfare, farm productivity, and environmental conservation (Dumitrescu et al., 2019). By integrating climate-smart agricultural techniques, such as agroforestry, enhanced livestock breeds, and mulching, farmers can not only boost food production but also adapt to changing climatic conditions and aid in mitigating the effects of climate change (Mwongera et al., 2017). These practices provide dual benefits by enhancing resilience and productivity at the farm level and contributing to broader environmental objectives through emission reduction and ecosystem service enhancement.

Future research in the realm of climate-smart livestock practices is expected to focus on the effective amalgamation of various climate-smart strategies to fortify farmers' resilience to climatic shifts (Chandra et al., 2017, Petrean et al., 2024). Investigating the specific ways through which agroforestry and other climate-smart approaches can improve livestock welfare and farm efficiency presents a crucial research avenue (Teklewold et al., 2017). Moreover, identifying the impediments to the adoption of these innovative practices and devising strategies to surmount such obstacles are essential for their widespread dissemination and application (Park, 2022).

The detrimental environmental impacts associated with conventional livestock farming and pasture management necessitate a reassessment of traditional agricultural practices. Standard methods frequently contribute to environmental issues such as deforestation, soil erosion, and high levels of greenhouse gas emissions, highlighting the critical need for sustainable alternatives.

Within this context, agroforestry offers a viable solution, proposing an integrated model that combines trees, crops, and livestock into a unified agricultural ecosystem. This strategy not only addresses the ecological drawbacks of conventional farming methods but also provides numerous advantages, including improved biodiversity, soil preservation, and carbon sequestration capabilities.

Therefore, this review aims to systematically analyze the contribution of climate-smart livestock practices, particularly agroforestry, as sustainable solutions to the environmental challenges inherent in traditional livestock farming and pasture management. By examining the effectiveness, advantages, and future directions of these practices, this review seeks to enrich the discourse on sustainable agriculture and underscore the critical role of climate-smart strategies in achieving environmental equilibrium and ensuring food security amidst the ongoing challenges of climate change.

THE CONCEPT OF CLIMATE-SMART LIVESTOCK

Incorporating climate-smart practices into livestock management emerges as a pivotal strategy for bolstering agricultural sustainability amidst escalating climate change challenges. These methodologies endeavor to

elevate livestock production efficiencies while concurrently attenuating environmental repercussions. The essence of climate-smart agriculture (CSA) encapsulates a trio of core objectives: augmenting productivity, amplifying resource utilization efficacy, and diminishing susceptibilities to climatic variations, notably within the domain of livestock management (Aryal et al., 2018). Such approaches are instrumental in not only fostering agricultural resilience but also in safeguarding environmental integrity.

Evidence underscores the criticality of adopting climate-smart agricultural practices (CSAPs) for sustainable agricultural enhancement (Aryal et al., 2018). Furthermore, research delineates livestock size as a critical factor influencing the adoption of CSAPs, accentuating the necessity to integrate livestock-centric considerations into these sustainable strategies (Belay et al., 2023). Climate-smart livestock systems are meticulously engineered to improve animal welfare, boost production efficiency, and enhance farm profitability, all the while addressing the environmental quandaries and health issues pervading livestock farming (Park, 2022). These systems are aimed at alleviating animal stress, optimizing production metrics, and mitigating the environmental challenges intrinsic to livestock agriculture.

The fusion of climate-smart practices within livestock management frameworks has demonstrably fostered positive outcomes on farmers' nutritional security, thereby highlighting the intricate linkage between effective livestock management and food security paradigms (Yuya et al., 2022). Investigative efforts into the synergy between climate-smart livestock production methodologies and farmers' nutritional security have spotlighted the imperative for comprehensive strategies that concurrently tackle agricultural and nutritional hurdles (Shahbaz et al., 2022).

For smallholder farmers, the embracement of climate-smart livestock production tactics unveils avenues for bolstering climate resilience and enhancing livelihoods (Ayal & Mamo, 2023). The integration of such practices across livestock value chains presents a promising pathway for stakeholders to optimize yields, profitability, and sustainability, thereby cushioning the impacts of climatic perturbations (Thongoh et al., 2021).

AGROFORESTRY PRACTICES: AN OVERVIEW

Agroforestry practices encompass a spectrum of integrative land management approaches that synergistically combine trees, crops, and livestock within a unified agricultural framework. These practices serve as a cornerstone for sustainable pastoral management, offering a suite of ecological and economic benefits. Enhanced soil vitality, increased biological diversity, and augmented carbon sequestration capabilities stand out as prominent advantages derived from these practices (Tadesse, 2019). Predominantly, agroforestry configurations pertinent to pasture management encompass silvopastoral systems, alley cropping, and windbreaks (Herder et al., 2017).

Silvopasture, a distinguished form of agroforestry, orchestrates a harmonious coexistence of trees, forage, and livestock, facilitating an environment that provides essential shade and shelter for animals, while concurrently bolstering forage production (Buegler et al., 2005). Alley cropping, another agroforestry variant, entails the strategic alignment of tree rows interspersed with crops or pasturelands, aimed at fostering soil conservation and diversifying agricultural yield (Arage, 2021). Windbreaks, constituted by linear plantings of trees or shrubs, play a pivotal role in minimizing wind erosion, safeguarding livestock, and establishing microclimates conducive to pasture development (Herder et al., 2017).

The infusion of trees into pasture-based livestock systems through agroforestry not only amplifies biodiversity and ecosystem services but also fortifies livelihoods, underscoring the integral role of agroforestry in community and ecosystem support (Chizmar et al., 2020; Aryal et al., 2019). Such systems enhance soil organic carbon reserves, water quality, and nutrient cycling, showcasing the environmental stewardship of integrating arboreal elements into pastoral landscapes (Udawatta et al., 2010; Kibet et al., 2022). Specifically, silvopastoral practices have demonstrated their efficacy in augmenting forage production and botanical diversity, thereby elevating livestock productivity (Buegler et al., 2005).

Agroforestry's capacity to contribute significantly to climate change mitigation through carbon sequestration further accentuates its environmental value (Lorenz & Lal, 2014). These systems are adept at reducing

fire hazards, enhancing carbon storage, moderating microclimates, and curtailing soil erosion and nutrient depletion, offering a sustainable alternative to traditional agriculture (Moreno et al., 2017).

Moreover, the ecosystem services rendered by agroforestry practices—such as soil erosion control, microclimate optimization for yield improvement, economic diversification, and water quality preservation—are invaluable for the sustenance of livestock production and welfare (Bentrup et al., 2019). The deliberate amalgamation of trees with crops and/or livestock in agroforestry systems engenders a multitude of economic and ecological benefits over conventional farming approaches (Dupraz et al., 2019). These systems are instrumental in averting environmental degradation, boosting agricultural productivity, enhancing carbon sequestration, and supporting robust soil and ecosystem health, thereby ensuring stable incomes and accruing multifaceted benefits to human welfare (Castle et al., 2022).

In essence, agroforestry systems are pivotal in biodiversity conservation, soil enrichment, and the preservation of clean air and water resources, all of which are critical for the sustainability of livestock management practices (Atreya et al., 2021). They optimize a wealth of eco-physical, economic, and social advantages for farmers, local communities, and the broader society, showcasing their indispensable role in combating land degradation, improving soil health, and bolstering ecosystem resilience (Tomar et al., 2021).

INTEGRATING AGROFORESTRY WITH PASTURE MANAGEMENT

The strategic integration of agroforestry within livestock farming necessitates comprehensive planning and a nuanced understanding of various determinants to ensure efficacy. Scholarly contributions delineate a myriad of methodologies for the incorporation of agroforestry practices into livestock enterprises, with a pronounced emphasis on the significance of engaging farmers and diversifying agricultural operations as essential factors for the effective implementation of agroforestry.

Foremost in the scholarly narrative on the implementation of agroforestry is the acknowledgment of the pivotal role of farmers and their perceptions. Jose (2009) underscores the necessity of aligning agroforestry initiatives

with the viewpoints of farmers to guarantee the success of such endeavors, advocating for the inclusion of farmers in the decision-making and planning stages as a fundamental strategy for the enduring integration of agroforestry practices in livestock farms. This participatory model not only promotes adoption but also assures the sustainability of agroforestry systems.

Additionally, the diversification of agricultural activities through the lens of agroforestry is highlighted as a critical adaptation strategy in the context of climate change. Fadina & Barjolle (2018) emphasize the integration of crop-livestock diversification along with agroforestry as vital for enhancing resilience against the uncertainties and extremities of climate change. Such integrative measures serve as safeguards, bolstering the adaptive capacity of agricultural systems.

The elevation of farmers' awareness and capacity building emerges as critical for the successful deployment of agroforestry practices. Rois-Díaz et al. (2017) emphasize the imperative to augment farmers' understanding of the comprehensive benefits of agroforestry, advocating for the deployment of extension services and training programs as effective channels for imparting knowledge on the merits of agroforestry in livestock settings.

Furthermore, the facilitation of policy support and the establishment of regulatory environments conducive to agroforestry are identified as crucial facilitators. Camilli et al. (2017) highlight the importance of policy mechanisms that encourage the adoption of agroforestry, spotlighting the role of stakeholders in advancing policy measures that are supportive of agroforestry's integration. Initiatives by governments that offer incentives and technical support are instrumental in embedding agroforestry practices into livestock farming systems.

The amalgamation of agroforestry with pasture management presents significant prospects for enhancing livestock welfare and overall farm productivity. Thorlakson & Neufeldt (2012) posit that agroforestry practices can lead to an increase in farm productivity and incomes, thereby improving farmer well-being. Introducing trees into pasture ecosystems not only benefits livestock welfare through the provision of essential amenities such as shade and shelter but also enriches animal health and comfort through diverse forage options.

Evidence suggests that agroforestry systems, owing to their resource complementarity, achieve higher agricultural productivity than monoculture systems, with trees procuring resources beneficial for both crops and livestock (Smith et al., 2012). This approach to diversification engenders a resilient and productive agricultural ecosystem that supports livestock welfare and enhances farm efficiency.

Moreover, agroforestry interventions are associated with positive impacts on agricultural productivity, ecosystem services, and human welfare, especially in contexts of low- and middle-income countries (Castle et al., 2021). These practices are conducive to improved soil health, augmented biodiversity, and enhanced ecosystem services, laying the groundwork for superior livestock management and productivity.

In addition, the integration of agroforestry with pasture management positively influences soil quality, carbon sequestration, and environmental sustainability (Paudel et al., 2011). Agroforestry practices bolster soil microbial biomass, fertility, and carbon content, essential elements for sustaining healthy pastures and supporting livestock welfare. This comprehensive approach illuminates the multi-dimensional benefits of incorporating agroforestry within livestock farming systems, offering a sustainable avenue towards enhancing agricultural resilience and productivity.

CHALLENGES AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The integration of agroforestry with livestock farming, while promising, encounters several formidable challenges that necessitate strategic solutions for its successful adoption. The scholarly discourse sheds light on an array of obstacles that may impede the seamless incorporation of agroforestry practices into livestock operations.

A critical barrier identified within the literature pertains to the elevated initial costs associated with the establishment of agroforestry systems. Farmers frequently face socio-economic constraints, a limited understanding of the benefit-cost ratio of agroforestry practices, and a dearth of comprehensive knowledge regarding agroforestry's multifaceted benefits (Atreya et al., 2021). Mitigating these financial hurdles and equipping farmers with cost-effective strategies for agroforestry deployment are essential steps toward fostering widespread adoption.

Additionally, the ambiguity in policy support, the inadequacy of extension services, and unclear administrative demarcations emerge as significant impediments (Atreya et al., 2021). The absence of coherent policy frameworks and robust institutional backing can significantly curtail the adoption of agroforestry in livestock farming contexts. Amplifying policy support, bolstering extension services, and establishing definitive guidelines are pivotal measures to navigate these institutional challenges.

Another notable challenge encompasses the insufficiency of scientific knowledge, expertise, and technological solutions tailored to the complex management demands of agroforestry systems (Atreya et al., 2021). There is a pressing need for farmer-centric training and capacity-building initiatives to adeptly manage the intricacies of integrated crop-tree-livestock systems. Providing accessible information, technical assistance, and comprehensive training programs can empower farmers to adeptly navigate agroforestry practices.

Moreover, the limited access to markets and marketing information for agroforestry products presents another hurdle (Atreya et al., 2021). The challenges associated with market access can undermine the economic sustainability of agroforestry systems. Cultivating market linkages, instituting market incentives, and furnishing marketing support are crucial strategies to address these economic constraints.

Looking ahead, the trajectory of research and development in climate-smart livestock and agroforestry practices harbors significant implications for advancing sustainable agricultural systems in a changing climate. The literature underscores emerging trends and potential avenues for future inquiry.

One evolving trend highlights the significance of adopting a multifaceted suite of climate-smart practices to enhance farmers' resilience to climatic perturbations. Investigations into the synergistic impacts of integrating agricultural water management, improved crop varieties, and fertilization strategies underscore their collective benefits on farm income and climate resilience, especially in regions such as the Nile Basin of Ethiopia (Teklewold et al., 2017). Future research could delve into the cumulative effects of diverse climate-smart practices on livestock systems.

Furthermore, the promotion of climate-smart agricultural practices, crop diversification, and agroforestry as strategies to counteract climate

change effects has gained traction. Such approaches have proven effective in bolstering resilience within farming systems, as evidenced in the mid-hill regions of Western Nepal (Adhikari, 2018). Future studies may explore the specific contributions of agroforestry practices to climate resilience in livestock farming.

The potential of agroforestry as a sustainable carbon sequestration practice under varying climate scenarios has also garnered attention. Addressing financial, technical, and institutional challenges is critical for optimizing agroforestry's role in climate mitigation (Abbas et al., 2017). Future inquiries could focus on developing innovative financing models and policy interventions to enhance agroforestry adoption in livestock operations.

Lastly, the climate-smart agriculture (CSA) paradigm has emerged as a holistic framework to concurrently address food security, adaptation, and mitigation. The importance of CSA practices in navigating the challenges of climate change and agricultural productivity has been emphasized (Neufeldt et al., 2013). Future research endeavors could investigate the scalability and applicability of CSA practices across various livestock farming scenarios, paving the way for more resilient and sustainable agricultural landscapes.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this mini-review has elucidated the pivotal role of agroforestry in transforming livestock farming into a more sustainable, productive, and environmentally friendly practice. The integration of trees, crops, and livestock within a unified agricultural framework presents a multifaceted approach to addressing the pressing challenges of climate change, biodiversity loss, and soil degradation. Key points discussed include the significant benefits of agroforestry practices such as enhanced soil health, improved biodiversity, increased carbon sequestration, and bolstered resilience against climatic variabilities. The challenges in adopting agroforestry, including socioeconomic barriers, policy constraints, and the need for technical knowledge, underscore the necessity for targeted interventions to facilitate widespread adoption.

The incorporation of agroforestry practices within pasture management is not merely an agricultural innovation but a requisite for environmental sustainability in livestock farming. By enhancing ecosystem services,

reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and promoting a more efficient use of natural resources, agroforestry stands at the forefront of sustainable agricultural practices. Its role in mitigating the impacts of climate change, while simultaneously supporting livelihoods and improving farm productivity, cannot be overstated.

Therefore, a concerted call to action is directed towards researchers, policymakers, and practitioners.

The journey towards sustainable livestock farming is complex and multifaceted, requiring the collaboration of all stakeholders involved. By embracing agroforestry, we can embark on a path that not only ensures the viability of agricultural livelihoods but also guards the health of our planet for future generations.

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BIOTECHNOLOGY IN POULTRY GENETICS: PATHWAYS TO DISEASE RESISTANCE AND ENHANCED GROWTH EFFICIENCY

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REVIEW

Abstract

This mini review explores the transformative impact of biotechnological advancements in poultry genetics, focusing on the integration of gene editing technologies and artificial intelligence (AI) into the field. Recent developments in gene editing, particularly the precision offered by tools such as CRISPR/Cas9, have unlocked new possibilities for enhancing disease resistance and growth efficiency in poultry breeds. These technological advancements enable targeted modifications within the poultry genome, leading to the development of breeds with improved health, productivity, and sustainability. Concurrently, the application of AI in genetic selection processes has begun to revolutionize breeding programs. By analyzing extensive genomic data, AI algorithms can identify genetic markers linked to desirable traits, facilitating a more efficient and precise selection of superior breeding candidates. This review delves into the potential of combining gene editing and AI to accelerate genetic advancements in poultry, creating breeds tailored to meet specific production needs and market demands. Ethical and regulatory considerations surrounding these biotechnological interventions are discussed, emphasizing the need for responsible use to ensure animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and consumer safety. The integration of these technologies promises not only to advance poultry genetics but also to address global food security challenges, contingent upon navigating ethical, regulatory, and societal hurdles.

Keywords: poultry genetics, gene editing, artificial intelligence, genetic selection, CRISPR/Cas9

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INTRODUCTION

Poultry farming stands as a cornerstone of global food security, significantly contributing to the dietary needs of humans through the provision of proteins, calories, and essential micronutrients (Govoni et al., 2022, Şonea et al., 2023, Szakacs et al., 2015, Avarvarei et al., 2019). The strategy of livestock diversification, which encompasses poultry farming, plays a crucial role in fortifying household food security. It achieves this by mitigating the impacts of infectious diseases and fostering the economic resilience of rural communities (Terfa et al., 2015). In many developing nations, village poultry notably aids in poverty alleviation and bolsters household food security, marking a critical element in the socio-economic fabric (Alders & Pym, 2009).

However, the poultry industry is besieged by various challenges that jeopardize food security (Colibar et al., 2013, Colibar et al., 2020,

Gheorghe-Irimia et al., 2023). Outbreaks of highly pathogenic avian influenza, exemplified by the H5N1 strain, represent a significant threat to both public health and the poultry sector, underscoring the urgency for robust disease control strategies (Makalo et al., 2022). Concurrently, the menace of antimicrobial resistance within poultry farming has emerged as a global concern, with implications for food security, economic stability, and gender equity. The prevalence of multidrug-resistant pathogens, such as certain strains of Salmonella linked to poultry, poses a grave threat to public health and food safety (Hedman et al., 2020; Manoj, 2015).

Exacerbating these challenges, external factors like climate change and global warming adversely affect the availability and quality of animal feed, thus impacting production costs and, subsequently, food security (El-Hack et al., 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic further strained the poultry industry, accentuating the imperative for resilience and adaptability to

maintain food security (Selim, 2021; Bamidele & Amole, 2021). Addressing these obstacles necessitates enhancing the decision-making capabilities of poultry farmers, encouraging the adoption of innovative technologies, and fostering self-sufficiency in poultry meat production (Tumwebaze et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2022; Alnafissa et al., 2021). Properly managed backyard poultry farming, with stringent biosecurity measures, significantly contributes to poverty alleviation and food security in rural locales (Fagrach et al., 2023; Conan et al., 2012). Amidst these multifaceted challenges, biotechnology emerges as a vital ally in the poultry industry, offering groundbreaking solutions that span from disease management to the enhancement of production efficiency. Biotechnological interventions in poultry breeding have led to notable improvements in growth, egg production, and disease resistance through genetic manipulation (Abdelaziz, 2024). These advancements facilitate the rapid identification of pathogens using DNA-based techniques and the creation of biological products, including vaccines, to bolster the immune response against various diseases (Abdelaziz, 2024).

Moreover, biotechnology has played a pivotal role in enhancing feed utilization through the introduction of both natural and synthetic additives, thereby optimizing the nutritional value of poultry diets, and maximizing production efficiency (Abdelaziz, 2024). Innovations such as marker-assisted selection, gene knockdown technologies, and CRISPR/Cas-mediated gene editing have accelerated genetic improvements in poultry, leading to superior performance traits (Bhattacharya et al., 2022). Additionally, the application of biotechnology extends to the production of recombinant proteins and vaccines, utilizing avian embryos and cell lines as biomanufacturing platforms. These efforts not only improve production efficiency but also pave the way for developing novel byproducts from poultry processing (Shamsuddoha & Woodside, 2023). Furthermore, in the realm of disease management, *in ovo* supplementation with nano-formulated essential minerals like zinc, copper, and selenium has demonstrated promising outcomes in enhancing the post-hatch performance and overall health of broiler chickens (Joshua et al., 2016). The use of cold plasma technology in processing poultry products has also shown to offer benefits in terms of quality and safety, exemplifying the

diverse applications of biotechnology in the industry (Gavahian et al., 2019).

The aim of this mini review is to elucidate the critical role of biotechnology in overcoming the myriad challenges faced by the poultry industry, with a particular emphasis on improving disease resistance and growth efficiency. By weaving together evidence from current research, this review intends to showcase the transformative potential of biotechnological innovations in poultry breeding and management. It aims to provide a holistic view of the advancements in genetic manipulation, feed optimization, and disease control strategies, highlighting their implications for enhancing poultry production efficiency and contributing to global food security.

BIOTECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCES AND ACHIEVEMENTS

The advent of CRISPR-Cas9 gene-editing technology has markedly influenced poultry genetics, enabling precise genomic modifications to bolster disease resistance and growth characteristics. This cutting-edge tool facilitates targeted alterations in specific genes associated with desirable traits, thus presenting a robust method for genetic enhancement in poultry (Khwatenge & Nahashon, 2021). Through the application of CRISPR-Cas9, scientists have successfully engineered poultry variants with improved resistance to diseases such as avian leukosis virus, exemplifying the precision and effectiveness of this technology in genetic manipulation (Koslová et al., 2020).

In conjunction with genomic selection—a technique that evaluates the entire genome for markers linked to beneficial traits—CRISPR-Cas9 has expedited the breeding of poultry with superior genetic attributes. This synergistic approach has significantly uplifted production efficiency and sustainability within the poultry industry, marking a leap towards more resilient and productive breeds (Park et al., 2020). The integration of CRISPR-Cas9 in developing genome-edited poultry models with novel attributes further underscores its utility across both agricultural and biomedical domains.

Transgenesis, which involves the introduction of foreign genes into the poultry genome, has been notably enhanced by CRISPR-Cas9. This advancement facilitates the development of poultry breeds with improved productivity and environmental adaptability, thereby optimizing the efficiency of poultry production systems. The merger of transgenesis and CRISPR-Cas9

heralds a new era in poultry genetics, aiming to fulfill the demand for breeds that are both disease-resistant and high-performing.

Addressing the challenge of common poultry diseases such as avian influenza and Marek's disease has been a focal point in genetic research. Through biotechnological advancements, significant progress has been made in obtaining poultry breeds with high disease resistance levels. Key to these achievements has been the utilization of genetic engineering techniques, including CRISPR-Cas9, to institute genetic modifications that bolster disease resistance. This approach has proven successful in generating chickens that exhibit resistance to avian influenza viruses and Marek's disease, showcasing the potential of genetic engineering in producing robust poultry breeds (Bi et al., 2016; Shrestha et al., 2018).

Moreover, genomic selection has been instrumental in pinpointing genetic markers that confer disease resistance, enabling the selection of poultry with enhanced resistance to pathogens. This strategy has contributed to the cultivation of breeds with heightened immunity to diseases such as avian influenza and Marek's disease, underscoring the critical role of genetic markers in disease resistance (Luo et al., 2013; Padhi & Parcells, 2016).

Research into genetic variation among chicken lines with varying susceptibilities to Marek's disease has shed light on the genetic underpinnings of disease resistance. By identifying and mapping quantitative trait loci associated with resistance, researchers have unearthed genes and variants crucial for combatting diseases in poultry (Mountford et al., 2022; Costa et al., 2012). This discovery of specific genetic markers and the elucidation of immune response pathways integral to pathogen defense highlight the complex genetic mechanisms underpinning disease resistance in poultry. These mechanisms include the activation of genes responsible for immune responses and the identification of genetic variations that influence susceptibility to diseases (Calenge et al., 2010; Smith et al., 2020; Zekarias et al., 2002; Gul et al., 2022).

Biotechnological interventions have also played a pivotal role in enhancing poultry growth rates, feed conversion ratios, and meat yields. Developments in dietary formulations that align with the intestinal microbiome and host physiology have led to improvements in growth and feed efficiency, showcasing the symbiotic relationship between nutrition and genetics in

poultry production (Pan & Yu, 2013). Additionally, the exploration of keratinolytic bacteria for feather keratin degradation and the identification of genetic markers related to feed efficiency underscore the multifaceted approach to improving poultry production through biotechnology (Riffel et al., 2003; Aggrey et al., 2010).

ETHICAL, REGULATORY, AND PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE CHALLENGES

The implementation of genetic modifications in poultry necessitates a comprehensive consideration of both ethical issues and regulatory landscapes to ensure responsible practice. A primary ethical concern revolves around the welfare of the animals, emphasizing the importance of conducting genetic alterations without inflicting harm or distress on the poultry. The ethical integrity of poultry production hinges on guaranteeing that these modifications enhance, rather than compromise, the health and well-being of the animals (Kilpinen et al., 2013).

Furthermore, the potential environmental ramifications of introducing genetically modified poultry into ecosystems invoke significant ethical concerns. The risk of gene transfer to wild populations and the ensuing ecological disturbances underscore the necessity for meticulous evaluation of the environmental impacts, thus reflecting the broad scope of ethical deliberations in this domain (Nóbrega et al., 2015).

From a regulatory perspective, genetic modifications in poultry are subject to a diverse array of international regulations that dictate the utilization of genetically modified organisms. The process to gain regulatory approval is notably intricate, encompassing rigorous safety evaluations and adherence to a complex set of legal standards (Petracci & Cavani, 2011).

Ethical considerations further extend to the commercial aspects of genetically modified poultry. Issues surrounding transparency, the acceptance of genetically modified products by consumers, and the labeling practices pose questions about informed consumer choice and the ethical obligations of producers to provide clear information (Khwatenge & Nahashon, 2021).

Another area of ethical scrutiny involves the potential for genetic modifications to be exploited for purposes other than enhancing disease resistance or production efficiencies.

The ethical application of these technologies mandates a balanced approach, prioritizing benefits for both the animals involved and the end consumers. It underscores the necessity for a principled and cautious application of genetic modifications, aimed at fostering advancements in poultry production that are ethically justified and socially responsible (Ishii, 2015).

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Anticipated advancements in the realm of poultry genetics are poised to be shaped profoundly by the evolution of gene editing technologies alongside the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into genetic selection methodologies. Tools such as CRISPR/Cas9 are on the cusp of achieving heightened levels of precision, facilitating targeted genomic modifications in poultry with enhanced efficiency and accuracy (Khwatenge & Nahashon, 2021). The refinement of these gene editing techniques is likely to usher in the emergence of poultry breeds characterized by superior disease resistance, accelerated growth rates, and increased meat yields, heralding significant improvements in production outcomes (Park et al., 2014).

The deployment of artificial intelligence in the sphere of genetic selection promises to revolutionize poultry breeding strategies. With the capacity to sift through vast arrays of genomic information, AI algorithms are adept at identifying genetic markers associated with desirable phenotypic traits. This capability enables a more streamlined and accurate selection of breeding candidates, optimizing the breeding process towards the development of poultry breeds endowed with enhanced performance attributes (Vrba et al., 2020). The synergy between gene editing technologies and AI-driven genetic selection is anticipated to significantly accelerate the pace of genetic advancements within poultry. AI algorithms stand to offer predictive insights into the potential impacts of specific genetic alterations on poultry characteristics, thereby empowering breeders with the knowledge to execute genetic modifications more strategically (Sid & Schusser, 2018).

This convergence of gene editing and AI technologies is forecasted to drive innovation within poultry genetics, leading to the creation of customized poultry breeds that align with distinct production goals and market demands. Further speculation suggests that future iterations of gene editing tools might enable the

rectification of genetic defects or the incorporation of novel traits that enhance adaptability to environmental stressors. Concurrently, advancements in AI could extend to the development of models that simulate the outcomes of genetic crosses, thereby refining the efficiency of breeding programs.

Moreover, the integration of AI in monitoring and managing poultry health in real-time could emerge as a pivotal application, utilizing data analytics to preemptively identify and mitigate disease outbreaks. Such technological progressions hold the promise of not only elevating poultry production metrics but also addressing sustainability challenges by optimizing feed conversion ratios and reducing the ecological footprint of poultry farming.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the frontier of poultry genetics and breeding is on the brink of a revolutionary transformation, driven by the rapid advancements in gene editing technologies and the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into genetic selection processes. The refinement of gene editing tools, particularly CRISPR/Cas9, promises a future where targeted genomic modifications are executed with unprecedented precision and efficiency. This progression is expected to yield poultry breeds with enhanced disease resistance, superior growth rates, and improved meat yields, addressing some of the most pressing challenges in poultry production today.

Simultaneously, the adoption of AI in genetic selection is set to redefine breeding programs, leveraging vast genomic datasets to identify markers linked to desirable traits with unparalleled accuracy. This synergy between gene editing and AI not only accelerates the pace of genetic advancements but also opens the door to the development of customized poultry breeds tailored to meet specific production objectives and market demands.

As we stand on the cusp of these technological advancements, it is imperative to recognize the ethical and regulatory implications that accompany the application of such powerful tools. The responsible integration of gene editing and AI into poultry genetics demands a careful balance between innovation and ethical considerations, ensuring animal welfare, environmental sustainability, and consumer safety are paramount.

Furthermore, as the field progresses, continuous dialogue among scientists,

regulatory bodies, industry stakeholders, and the public will be crucial in navigating the complexities of implementing these technologies. Transparency, ethical responsibility, and public engagement will play key roles in gaining acceptance and trust in genetically enhanced poultry products.

The future envisioned by these advancements is not without challenges, yet it holds the potential for significant benefits in terms of production efficiency, disease management, and sustainability in the poultry industry. By embracing these technologies judiciously and ethically, the poultry genetics field can contribute to securing global food supplies while adhering to the highest standards of animal welfare and environmental stewardship.

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THE IMPORTANCE OF ECOLOGICAL AGRICULTURE AND NUTRITIONAL BALANCE IN THE CONTEXT OF PROMOTING THE ONE HEALTH CONCEPT

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REVIEW

Abstract

The expansion of the global economy today exceeds the capacity of ecosystems, so that, as the pressure exerted on them increases year by year, more and more local ecosystems decay. A series of clear trends related to the environment shape the future of civilization: population growth, global temperature rise, the amplitude of thermal values in an annual or circadian cycle, the reduction or even exhaustion of water resources, the decrease of the area of agricultural land per person, the decline of the fishing industry, the decrease of forest areas and the disappearance of some species of animals and plants.

Keywords: ecological agriculture, nutritional balance, the "ONE HEALTH" concept, sustainable development

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INTRODUCTION

Ecological agriculture represents an alternative to classic farming systems (extensive, intensive, etc.) as a result of their poor functioning and the causes that determined the decrease in resistance and tolerance of plants to the attack of pathogens and pests, the deterioration of animal health, the degradation of soil quality and of the edaphic complex, and implicitly endangering human health. Ecological agriculture is based on the following principles for obtaining raw materials and food: long-term protection of soil fertility by maintaining organic matter levels, stimulation of biological activity and superficial agrotechnical interventions, indirect supply of fertilizing elements for cultivated species, using relatively insoluble nutrient sources that the plant reaches through the action of microorganisms in the soil, self-sufficiency of nitrogen, through the use of leguminous species that fix atmospheric nitrogen, as well as the effective use of organic materials, vegetable residues and manure, biological control of weeds, diseases and pests based mainly on crop rotations, natural predators, diversity, organic fertilization, resistant genetic varieties, and thermal and chemical interventions are as limited as possible, then the extensive growth, as free as possible of the animals, paying attention to their evolutionary adaptation, the behavioral needs and comfort of the animals, in

terms of their nutrition, shelter, growth, development and reproduction and a special attention given to the impact of the farming system on the environment and the conservation of biodiversity and natural habitats.

DISCUSSIONS

The concept of organic food, introduced relatively recently in the international circuit, has profound sanogenetic, trophic and socio-economic meanings. In general terms, ecological food refers to the consumption of diversified, clean, healthy products, free of residues, with a balanced content of bioactive substances and minerals.

Since contemporary man faces food imbalances that dramatically influence mortality (including in industrialized countries where the pathology of abundance proliferates), it is necessary to pay special attention to those food products that do not affect the health status of the population, regardless of the ecological zone where it occurs.

Nowadays, the establishment of adequate nutrition can only be achieved according to ecological criteria, since the natural environment, but also the anthropogenic, industrial one, strongly conditions nutrition, along with climatic, geographical and ethnic peculiarities. From this point of view, the differences regarding

nutrition are very wide, both on global ecological zones and within a national territory.

In this context, the ecological meaning of food is viewed through the lens of intervention in the economy of nature, by cultivating plants and raising animals in a special environment, which leads to a certain specificity of human nutrition. The control of some components of the ecosystems produced changes in the biological properties of plants and animals, resulting in a diversification of animal and vegetable foods. Over time, the anthropized biocenoses replaced the natural ones, potentially increasing the food of the world's population. This interposition of ecological factors with food represents one of the springs of food security.

Solving the problem of nutritional balance does not only require the need-intake agreement, but at the same time requires the fulfillment of the ecological requirement of food and its convergence with the toxic biotic factors of the environment. Thus, environmental degradation often has a direct, profound influence on nutritional status in developing countries. For example, in regions with a small amount of firewood available, food is insufficiently cooked, being dangerous for health (eg cassava, a staple food in some areas, must be well cooked to be consumed without danger). Fisheries resources are threatened with degradation, due to poor management, demographic pressure, water pollution and their diversion to urban areas, in industry and agriculture. The overexploitation of fish stocks in many regions of the world has quickly depleted the stock of this food, rich in proteins, indispensable for millions of inhabitants.

That is why nutritional food policies are combined with ecological policies that must be directed mainly to the causes that affect the health and nutrition of the population. From an ecological point of view, the food industry must adapt to the physiological food needs of the population, producing quantitatively and qualitatively balanced food. The substances used in industrial gastronomy must be chosen with particular care according to the requirements of modern man, but the general opinion is that, in order for the food to present sanogenetic resonances, its composition must not contain synthetic substances, chemical additives, which is possible through the use of biotechnology food.

Ensuring a healthy environment depends on the lifestyle, within which an

ecologically rational way of consumption must be promoted. That's why developed countries continuously reorient their way of production and consumption, in order to achieve economic and nutritional objectives without ecologically harming other nations.

The promotion of bio-food products is closely related to the alternative development of agriculture, to the choice between two options: ecological agriculture, applied on small areas in small family farms, based only on organic fertilizers, the rotation of crops and varieties genetically resistant to diseases, but without pesticides, respectively non-ecological agriculture, with the use of organo-mineral fertilizers, chemical and biochemical pesticides and other specific techniques applied in industrial farms, with great economic efficiency.

The importance of ecological food consists in the fact that it can ensure not only the supply of sufficient food products from a quantitative point of view, but also a rational, balanced diet, in order to maintain the physical and mental health of man.

CONCLUSIONS

Ecological or biological agriculture includes the entire range of scientific research (observations, measurements and experiments) and applied (analysis, design, administration) activities in the agricultural sector and the other branches or economic sectors that process and sell agricultural raw materials and agri-food products and put a special emphasis on the valorization and conservation or restoration of natural, technological, financial and human resources characteristic of local and zonal agro-ecosystems.

In the current context of the orientation of the common agricultural policy towards a natural agriculture, in which the concept of ecological or organic agriculture has a well-defined place (Strategy - From farm to consumer and Strategy for Biodiversity 2030, central pillars of the European Green Pact), it is mandatory increasing the efforts to popularize the principles and methods of ecological agriculture and to inform farmers and all those interested on a large scale, regarding the importance and the role of ecological technologies and last but not least recalling the economic advantages, as well as those that concern improving the environment in which we live. The objectives of ecological agriculture are subordinated, mainly to the sustainable development of agroecological systems.

The ecological production system, which prohibits the use of synthetic chemicals (fertilizers, pesticides, herbicides, etc.) and promotes respect for animal welfare, is a sustainable bio-economic solution. Taking into account the competitiveness of raw materials and ecological products, the agricultural potential and the ever-increasing demand for ecological foodstuffs in our country, an important factor is the continuation of the massive financing of the sector, financial resources being directed to the expansion of ecological production and at the same time of the storage and processing sector.

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